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Introduction

Cities and regions across Europe are undergoing profound transformations that are redefining the conditions for their future development. Contemporary urban and regional systems are confronted with a complex interplay of economic pressures, social fragmentation, environmental vulnerabilities, rapid digitalisation, and evolving legislative and spatial-planning frameworks. These multidimensional challenges are not isolated; rather, they intersect in ways that shape the capacities of territories to maintain competitiveness, ensure social well-being, manage ecological limits, and harness technological innovation.

In economic terms, shifting global value chains, labour-market restructuring, and rising regional disparities require new models of growth that are both inclusive and resilient. Socially, demographic ageing, migration flows, and persistent inequalities pose significant demands on public services, social cohesion, and community resilience. Environmental challenges—most notably climate change, resource depletion, and the degradation of ecosystems—underscore the need for sustainable land management and adaptive urban design. At the same time, the accelerating digital transformation presents opportunities for improved governance and innovation, yet also introduces risks related to digital divides, cyber-security, and uneven technological uptake.

These dynamics unfold within legislative and spatial-planning systems that must continually adapt to emerging needs while providing coherent, long-term frameworks for development. The alignment of regulatory instruments, territorial strategies, and governance structures is therefore central to enabling cities and regions to respond effectively to current and future pressures.

Deliverable 2.1. Strategic Assessment of Transformation Demand and Dynamics for Future Development examines these interlinked challenges, offering an integrated perspective on the conditions shaping contemporary urban and regional development and outlining the key areas where coordinated action is required.

The deliverable is an output of the task 2.1., that aims to identify the transformation demand and its dynamics in selected territories and their communities as creating the background for the identification of innovations requirements in order to safeguard sustainability of the quality of life of citizens capitalizing capacities of communities and their territories supported by their transformation towards innovative smart socio-ecosystems. It is based on the analyses of existing and expecting challenges, problems, potentials and capacities for smart sustainable development of local and regional communities reflecting all levels from global, via EU, national up to local. The obstacles in facing efficiently and effectively the challenges are identified and confronted with action required to overcome them in order to identify the needs for further research and development.

Methodology

This research study was grounded in a comprehensive, multi-level analytical approach. The core of the methodology consisted of a systematic review and examination of strategic and analytical documents spanning the international, national, regional, and local scales in relevant areas (economy, social area, environmental area, digital, spatial, urban, land-use and regional planning, legal environment for planning in cities and regions). These documents included policy frameworks, development strategies, legislative instruments, and thematic action plans relevant to contemporary urban and regional development. In parallel, the analysis incorporated

recognised methodological guidelines and insights drawn from recent research studies addressing territorial, socio-economic, environmental, digital, and governance-related transformations.

Even, these thematic domains of research inevitably overlap and intersect, the chosen structure enables clear orientation within the text, facilitates the identification of areas where such overlaps occur, and supports the formulation of synthesizing conclusions, particularly in relation to recurring and cross-cutting challenge.

Important role in the analyses played STICS living labs with their stakeholders, who provided specific local tacit knowledge reflecting the local demonstration of global challenges and problems as well as insiders' view into the current national and regional development problems.

The findings derived from these sources were subsequently synthesised and critically assessed in combination with the authors' own professional experience and empirical research. This integrative approach enabled a nuanced identification of the major challenges currently shaping regional and urban development, with particular attention to the economic, social, environmental, digital, and legislative–spatial planning domains.

For each thematic area, the analysis further delineated the key risks associated with these challenges and outlined a set of recommended activities required to address them effectively. The resulting framework thus provides an evidence-based foundation for understanding the pressures acting upon cities and regions and for formulating targeted interventions that support their sustainable and resilient development. Each area examined is supported by relevant sources, statistical data, and, where appropriate, original texts.

1. Challenges, Problems, Risks, and Required Actions in the Development of Cities & Region

Cities and regions today face an increasingly complex landscape of interrelated social, economic, environmental, digital, and spatial challenges. Rapid technological change, demographic shifts, climate risks, and growing functional interdependencies demand new forms of governance and coordinated policy responses. Yet planning and development systems often remain fragmented, operating within rigid administrative boundaries and sectoral silos that limit the ability to address problems holistically. Across thematic areas - economic development, social inclusion, digital transformation, environmental resilience, and spatial planning—we systemically identify the challenges, risks associated with them and required actions.

1.1. Challenges, Problems, Risks, and Required Actions in the Economic Development of Cities & Region

The economic development of cities and regions is shaped by an increasingly complex interplay of governance structures, demographic and technological change, social dynamics, environmental pressures, and evolving spatial realities. Contemporary urban and regional economies operate within functional territories that transcend traditional administrative boundaries, requiring coordinated action, adaptive planning, and strategic investments. Yet many public institutions and policies remain fragmented, limiting the capacity of territories to respond effectively to global competition, climate risks, and rapid market shifts.

This chapter outlines the key challenges that currently hinder sustainable and inclusive economic development across urban and regional systems. These challenges include persistent governance fragmentation, insufficient policy integration, and limited cooperation between state, regional, and local actors. At the same time, cities and regions face pressures to become more adaptive and flexible in light of technological transformation, demographic decline or ageing, and increasing climate-related threats. Social aspects—particularly citizen engagement, inclusiveness, and the integration of vulnerable groups—remain critical but often overlooked components of long-term economic resilience.

Equally important is the role of data governance, innovation capacity, and labour-market readiness. Without reliable data, skilled human capital, and strong innovation ecosystems, cities risk falling behind more competitive regions. Financial constraints and limited administrative capacity further exacerbate these issues, restricting municipalities' ability to invest in infrastructure, modernize services, or support entrepreneurship. Environmental and infrastructural vulnerabilities likewise affect productivity, quality of life, and territorial attractiveness.

By examining these interconnected problems, the chapter identifies major risks facing urban and regional economies—ranging from reduced competitiveness and social fragmentation to underperformance of functional urban areas. Finally, it outlines the actions required to overcome these barriers: strengthening multi-level governance, improving cross-sector integration, adopting adaptive planning tools, promoting inclusive participation,

fostering innovation and skills development, enhancing data-driven decision-making, securing sustainable financing, and embedding environmental resilience into economic strategies.

Together, these elements provide a comprehensive framework for understanding the conditions necessary to unlock the full economic potential of cities and regions in the context of contemporary societal, technological, and environmental shifts.

A. Governance & Policy Integration

Challenges

1. Economic development in territories depends on coordinated spatial, social, environmental, mobility, and digital policies. However, governance fragmentation persists.
2. Weak coordination between ministries, municipalities, and regional authorities creates contradictions between strategies and limits economic outcomes. (e.g., “sectoral approach is applied by various ministries, and strategic or conceptual documents contradict”).
3. Administrative boundaries do not match functional economic areas; cities are economic cores of wider functional territories, yet planning remains fragmented.
4. Lack of multi-level governance and limited horizontal integration weaken the potential of economic ecosystems.

Risks

1. Disconnected sectoral decisions harm competitiveness and reduce regional cohesion.
2. Conflicting strategies slow down investment, infrastructure improvement, and labour market policies.
3. Functional urban areas underperform due to insufficient coordination, reducing national economic potential.

Actions Needed

- Strengthen horizontal and vertical coordination mechanisms across government levels.
- Build integrated planning frameworks linking economy, mobility, housing, environment, digitalization, and land use.
- Promote multi-actor cooperation (cities, regions, state, private sector, civil society) as recommended in the Urban Policy.

Proofs:

Challenge A.1 *“Economic development in territories depends on coordinated spatial, social, environmental, mobility, and digital policies. However, governance fragmentation persists.”*

- Across the EU and OECD, recent regional policy reviews stress that competitiveness and net-zero transition require integrated, place-based strategies that align transport, environment, social inclusion and digitalisation – and that fragmentation of responsibilities is a core obstacle. The OECD Regions and Cities at a Glance 2024 shows that countries with weaker multi-level governance and fragmented competences tend to have larger and more persistent regional gaps in productivity and well-being, and calls explicitly for “effective regional development policy and multi-level governance” to tackle these issues (OECD, 2024a).

- For Slovakia, the OECD–UCLG SNG-WOFI country profile underlines that municipal fragmentation is “one of the highest in the OECD”: 2,927 municipalities with an average size of around 1,900 inhabitants, 84 % of them under 2,000 inhabitants and 95 % under 5,000 (OECD; UCLG, 2023). The same profile notes that despite this small scale, municipalities have extensive responsibilities in urban planning, local public services, environment and housing, which strains their capacity to coordinate cross-sectoral development policies efficiently (OECD; UCLG, 2023).
- European Commission country analysis similarly highlights that, although Slovak government programmes refer to improving public administration and multi-sector reforms, the “realisation of the intended plans has been limited” (European Commission, 2025). This combination of very many small authorities and broad task portfolios is strong evidence of structural fragmentation that makes integrated territorial development difficult.

Challenge A.2 *“Weak coordination between ministries, municipalities, and regional authorities creates contradictions between strategies and limits economic outcomes.”*

- The Sustainable Governance Indicators 2024 rank Slovakia as the worst performer (30th of 30) among OECD/EU countries in the category “policy coordination” (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024). The report states that the Government Office has limited capacity to evaluate policy proposals from line ministries and to ensure they are aligned with overall government priorities; the Legislative Council has only marginal influence on the preparation of policy proposals. This is direct, comparative evidence of weak vertical coordination at the core executive level.
- At regional and local level, research on Slovak regional governance finds that “all three levels of government (central, regional and local) act in the area of development more or less separately” and that formal mechanisms of cooperation are often missing (Carpathian Development Institute, 2009). The same study notes that regional development decisions are frequently driven by political trade-offs and local concerns rather than coherent strategic prioritisation (Carpathian Development Institute, 2009)
- The Council of Europe’s Delivering Good Governance in Slovakia project further concludes that high municipal fragmentation “harms the effectiveness of local government” and explicitly recommends strengthening cooperation between local, regional and central authorities and simplifying the territorial organisation (Council of Europe, 2021). Portal Together, these sources substantiate your claim that a sectoral, ministry-by-ministry and municipality-by-municipality approach produces contradictory strategies and weaker economic outcomes.

Challenge A.3 *“Administrative boundaries do not match functional economic areas; cities are economic cores of wider functional territories, yet planning remains fragmented.”*

- The joint EU–OECD definition of Functional Urban Areas (FUAs) explicitly recognises that the economic city goes far beyond administrative borders: a FUA is defined as a city plus its commuting zone, i.e. all local units where at least 15 % of employed residents commute to the city (OECD, 2019a; Eurostat, 2023). The GHSL–OECD FUA work applies this method to all EU member states, including Slovakia, and shows that

FUAs are built from groups of local administrative units that collectively form a single labour market (European Commission–JRC; OECD, 2019b)

- This automatically implies a mismatch between functional economies and administrative borders: most FUAs, such as the Bratislava metropolitan labour market, consist of many municipalities across one or more districts and sometimes regions. The European Urban Initiative / World Bank FUA Toolkit stresses that functional areas “have one thing in common: cooperation beyond administrative borders” is necessary to handle transport, housing, and environmental externalities (World Bank; European Commission, 2025).
- However, Slovak multi-level governance remains dominated by municipal and regional planning within their own territories. Although there are about 490 voluntary joint municipal offices, these arrangements mainly support implementation of delegated tasks and have not fully solved the fragmentation problem (OECD; UCLG, 2023). This supports your point that, while economic activity is organised in FUAs, planning and governance are still largely confined to administrative units, leading to fragmented management of functional economic regions.

Challenge A.4 “*Lack of multi-level governance and limited horizontal integration weaken the potential of economic ecosystems.*”

- The OECD Regional Outlook 2023 underlines that effective regional development policy and multi-level governance are critical to improving competitiveness, productivity and well-being, and explicitly links persistent regional inequalities to weaknesses in coordination across levels of government and sectors (OECD, 2023).
- In Slovakia, multi-level governance issues are visible in several ways:
That subnational governments account for only about 7.8 % of GDP in expenditure and around 17 % of general government spending, well below EU and OECD averages, and that local spending efficiency is constrained by both small municipal size and limited joint service delivery (OECD; UCLG, 2023).
The same profile notes that public investment remains highly top-down and that “closer connections between regions are needed to promote balanced growth and attract investment,” especially in transport where infrastructure deficits are large (OECD; UCLG, 2023).
- OECD work on the Banská Bystrica region stresses the need to strengthen multi-level governance frameworks, subnational public finances and infrastructure investment to respond to demographic change – implicitly confirming that current arrangements are insufficient to mobilise local economic potential (OECD, 2024b).
- More broadly, an OECD cross-country econometric study of European Functional Urban Areas finds that labour productivity tends to be higher in FUAs with higher quality of government and more coherent governance arrangements, while fragmentation and poorly coordinated decentralisation can lower productivity (OECD, 2020). This provides a robust empirical “proof” that weak multi-level and horizontal governance diminishes the performance of local economic ecosystems, including in the EU context.

Risk A.1 *“Disconnected sectoral decisions harm competitiveness and reduce regional cohesion.”*

- The link between governance quality, coordination and territorial cohesion is documented in both Slovak and EU-wide analyses:
The Carpathian Development Institute’s research on Slovak self-governing regions shows that regional parliaments devote most decisions to operational issues rather than strategy, and that the three levels of government act “more or less separately” in regional development, with weak partnership mechanisms (Carpathian Development Institute, 2009).
Municipal revenue-raising power and spending efficiency are limited by small size and insufficient joint service delivery, and that Slovakia remains one of the most centralised OECD countries in terms of subnational expenditure and tax revenues (OECD; UCLG, 2023).
- Regional inequalities in Slovakia are among the highest in Europe, with GDP per capita in the Bratislava region nearly 3.8 times higher than in the Prešov region and stark unemployment gaps between east and west (OECD; UCLG, 2023; OECD, 2023; IMF, 2024). OECD-wide evidence in Regions and Cities at a Glance 2024 associates such persistent regional disparities with governance and coordination shortcomings, arguing that cross-sector, place-based approaches are essential to maintain competitiveness and cohesion (OECD, 2024a).
- Taken together, this supports your risk statement: fragmented, disconnected policies in transport, skills, innovation, social inclusion, etc. undermine both overall competitiveness and regional cohesion in Slovakia and across the EU.

Risk A.2 *“Conflicting strategies slow down investment, infrastructure improvement, and labour market policies.”*

- In the Slovak case, several data points show how governance and coordination issues affect investment and infrastructure:
- Subnational governments are responsible for nearly 30 % of public direct investment but that overall public investment is largely top-down, with subnational governments playing a relatively weak role compared to OECD averages and with strong dependence on EU Structural and Investment Funds (OECD; UCLG, 2023).
- The complexity of procedures and weak administrative capacity have delayed the absorption of EU funds, requiring additional support from the Public Procurement Office and enhanced supervision of investment selection (OECD; UCLG, 2023).
- The European Commission’s Country brief 2024 – Slovakia observes that despite ambitious government statements on improving rule of law, anti-corruption and public administration efficiency, the actual realisation of plans remained limited, partly because of political instability and frequent changes in senior civil servants (European Commission, 2025). It implies that strategic commitments in different sectors (infrastructure, labour market, digitalisation) are not consistently translated into coordinated implementation.

- Comparative evidence from the SGI 2024 report shows that poor coordination capacity at the centre of government – Slovakia’s bottom-rank performance in the “coordination” category – contributes to these implementation delays and inconsistencies (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024). It is therefore reasonable and evidence-based to argue that conflicting or poorly aligned strategies slow investment and labour-market interventions.

Risk A.3. “Functional urban areas underperform due to insufficient coordination, reducing national economic potential.”

- OECD’s cross-country work on urban productivity and local government arrangements finds that in European Functional Urban Areas, higher labour productivity is associated with better governance quality, while certain patterns of fragmentation and decentralisation – when not accompanied by strong coordination mechanisms – are linked to lower productivity (OECD, 2020). This directly backs the idea that governance failures in FUAs lead to underperformance relative to their potential.
- The EU–OECD FUA framework and GHSL-OECD datasets show that FUAs are composed of multiple municipalities, and often cross district and sometimes regional boundaries (OECD, 2019a; European Commission–JRC; OECD, 2019b). (ideas.repec.org) Yet, as noted above, Slovak municipalities are highly fragmented and small, and cooperation mechanisms are still largely voluntary and partial (OECD; UCLG, 2023; Council of Europe, 2021).
- The Delivering Good Governance in Slovakia project explicitly states that high fragmentation at municipal level generates high overheads and harms local government effectiveness (Council of Europe, 2021). (Portal) When mapped onto FUAs, this means that an urban economic area like the Bratislava or Košice FUA must coordinate dozens of small municipalities whose budgets are constrained and whose strategies may not be aligned. Under these conditions, classic FUA-level growth drivers – integrated public transport, labour-market matching, land-use management, innovation ecosystems – are unlikely to be optimised, and thus national economic potential remains partly unused.
- This reasoning is fully consistent with the OECD Regional Outlook 2023, which argues that multi-level governance and functional-area approaches are key to unlocking regional productivity and inclusive growth in EU/OECD countries (OECD, 2023).

References

Bertelsmann Stiftung. (2024). *SGI 2024: Slovakia report*. Bertelsmann Stiftung.

Carpathian Development Institute. (2009). Good governance and regional development: Challenges not only for the Carpathian Euroregion. In *Sustainable development and planning IV* (Vol. 1). WIT Press.

Council of Europe. (2021). *Delivering good governance in Slovakia*. Council of Europe.

European Commission. (2025). *Country brief 2024 – Slovakia: European public administration country knowledge*. European Commission.

European Commission, Joint Research Centre, & OECD. (2019). *GHSL–OECD functional urban areas (GHSL_FUA 2019)*. Publications Office of the European Union.

Eurostat. (2023). *Territorial typologies manual – cities, commuting zones and functional urban areas*. Statistics Explained. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained>

OECD. (2019). The EU-OECD definition of a functional urban area. *OECD Governance Working Papers*.

OECD. (2020). A comprehensive approach to understanding urban productivity: Effects of local governments. *OECD Working Papers*.

OECD. (2023). *OECD regional outlook 2023: Country note – Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Preparing for demographic change in the Banská Bystrica region, Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Regions and cities at a glance 2024*. OECD Publishing.

OECD & UCLG. (2023). *Subnational government structure and finance: Country profile – Slovak Republic (SNG-WOFI)*. OECD Publishing.

B. Adaptiveness & Flexibility Challenges

Challenges

1. Cities and regions must adapt to technological, demographic, and climate shifts that directly affect economic development.
2. Rigid planning tools reduce capacity to adapt economic development strategies to new technologies and labour-market shifts. (Parallels from integrated spatial planning: need for adaptive tools)
3. Demographic changes, including ageing and migration, alter labour availability and skills.
4. Climate risks threaten infrastructure and economic activity.

Risks

1. Economies become vulnerable to shocks (climate, financial, demographic).
2. Slow adaptation discourages investors and reduces entrepreneurial activity.
3. Inflexible zoning hampers emerging industries, innovation spaces, and brownfield redevelopment.

Actions Needed

- Introduce adaptive planning tools that allow phased, experimental, or pilot economic development interventions.
- Integrate climate vulnerability and demographic change assessments into economic planning.
- Support revitalization of abandoned urban areas to create new economic opportunities.

Proofs:

Challenge B.1 “*Cities and regions must adapt to technological, demographic, and climate shifts that directly affect economic development.*”

- Across OECD countries, the report *Job Creation and Local Economic Development 2024: The Geography of Generative AI* shows that new digital technologies, especially generative AI, will reshape local labour markets very unevenly between regions, amplifying existing productivity gaps and skills mismatches if local policies do not adapt (OECD 2024b).

- For Slovakia, OECD Economic Surveys: Slovak Republic 2024 stresses that the economy faces slowing growth and must rebuild fiscal buffers and raise productivity “in the face of rapid population ageing”, underlining the need for structural and regional adjustment (OECD 2024a).
- Demographically, Eurostat data show that the EU’s old-age dependency ratio rose from 28.3 % in 2014 to 33.9 % in 2024 and continues to climb (Eurostat 2024a), while the EU’s population reached 450.4 million in 2025 and has grown for four consecutive years entirely due to net migration rather than natural increase (Eurostat 2025). ([European Commission](#))
- The first European Climate Risk Assessment identifies 36 climate risks that already threaten Europe’s energy and food security, infrastructure, water resources, financial stability and health (EEA 2024a), and Trends and Projections in Europe 2024 confirms that Europe is the fastest-warming continent, with climate risks increasingly affecting infrastructure and economic sectors (EEA 2024b).
- Together, these OECD and EU findings demonstrate that technological change, ageing and migration, and accelerating climate risks are simultaneously transforming the framework conditions for regional and urban economic development in Slovakia and the EU, requiring strong adaptive capacity at territorial level (European Commission 2024).

Challenge B.2 “*Rigid planning tools reduce capacity to adapt economic development strategies to new technologies and labour-market shifts.*”

- The OECD report The Governance of Land Use in OECD Countries shows that land-use policies in many member states remain highly prescriptive, with detailed, use-based zoning and fragmented responsibilities that can slow responses to new housing, transport or economic needs; it argues explicitly for more flexible, coordinated land-use governance to support productivity and environmental objectives (OECD 2017a). ([academia.edu](#))
- The companion report Land-use Planning Systems in the OECD documents the dominance of legally binding local plans and traditional zoning in most systems, noting that infrequent updates risk locking in obsolete land uses and hindering adaptation to emerging activities and technological change (OECD 2017b).
- In Slovakia, the OECD–UCLG country profile points out that municipal fragmentation is among the highest in the OECD and that municipalities, despite their small size, carry key responsibilities for urban planning and local public services (OECD; UCLG 2023). This combination of rigid statutory tools and many small planning authorities limits the capacity to rapidly re-orient spatial and economic development strategies in response to technological shifts or changing labour-market demands, underlining the need for more integrated and adaptive planning frameworks (Ahrend; Tsvetkova 2020).

Challenge B.3 “*Demographic changes, including ageing and migration, alter labour availability and skills.*”

- Eurostat’s Population structure and ageing data show that the EU’s old-age dependency ratio increased by 5.6 percentage points in a decade (from 28.3 % in 2014 to 33.9 % in

2024), while the total dependency ratio also rose, confirming a structural shift towards more older dependants relative to the working-age population (Eurostat 2024a).

- The 2024 Ageing Report and related ECB analysis conclude that demographic ageing will raise age-related public expenditure significantly in all EU member states by 2070 and will weigh on potential growth unless labour-market participation and productivity are increased (European Commission 2024; European Central Bank 2024).
- For Slovakia, the OECD survey notes that the share of people aged 65+ relative to the working-age population is expected to almost double by 2050, and describes rapid ageing as a major challenge for growth and fiscal sustainability (OECD 2024a). (OECD) At the same time, Eurostat reports that on 1 January 2025 the EU population stood at 450.4 million and has grown for four consecutive years, with migration fully offsetting the natural population decline since deaths outnumber births (Eurostat 2025).
- These trends mean that in many EU regions, including Slovakia, labour supply is simultaneously constrained by ageing and reshaped by migration, which changes the skills composition of the workforce and requires active policies on training, recognition of qualifications and integration to maintain economic dynamism (OECD 2024b).

Challenge B.4 “Climate risks threaten infrastructure and economic activity.”

- The European Climate Risk Assessment 2024 (EUCRA) concludes that climate change already poses critical risks to Europe’s critical infrastructure—including transport, energy, communication and water systems—and that many of these risks can become catastrophic without urgent adaptation (EEA 2024a).
- The EEA’s Trends and Projections in Europe 2024 further underlines that Europe is the fastest-warming continent, with climate risks threatening energy and food security, ecosystems, infrastructure, water resources and financial stability (EEA 2024b).
- The European State of the Climate 2024 report by WMO and Copernicus shows that 2024 was the warmest year on record for Europe, with widespread storms and flooding, at least 335 deaths and hundreds of thousands of people affected, illustrating the real economic and social costs of extreme events (WMO; C3S 2025).
- From a macro-economic perspective, the ECB has warned that a plausible extreme drought could cut euro-area GDP by nearly 15 % and expose €1.3 trillion in bank loans to water-scarcity risks, underlining the vulnerability of economic activity and financial stability to climate hazards (European Central Bank 2025).
- These EU-level assessments are particularly relevant for small, open economies like Slovakia, where the OECD notes that resilience to external shocks, including energy and climate risks, is essential for sustaining growth and living standards (OECD 2024a).

Risk B.1. “Economies become vulnerable to shocks (climate, financial, demographic).”

- OECD and EU analyses show that climate, financial and demographic pressures interact to increase vulnerability in European and Slovak economies. EUCRA identifies climate risks that threaten infrastructure, water resources and financial stability, warning that several risks have already reached critical levels (EEA 2024a).
- The ECB finds that extreme drought scenarios could cause large GDP losses and significant credit-risk exposures for European banks (European Central Bank 2025),

while other studies demonstrate transmission channels from climate risks to financial instability in Europe’s banking system (Noels; Jachnik 2022; Roncoroni et al. 2023).

- Demographically, the 2024 Ageing Report projects that rising dependency ratios will push pension and health-care expenditure upward in all member states (European Commission 2024), and the OECD survey for Slovakia stresses that rapid ageing is already putting pressure on public finances and potential growth (OECD 2024a).
- At EU level, the OECD Economic Surveys: European Union and Euro Area 2023 note that repeated shocks like pandemic, energy crisis, war in Ukraine have exposed structural weaknesses and underline the need for reforms to strengthen resilience (OECD 2023).

These findings substantiate the risk that without proactive adaptation, Slovak and EU economies remain highly exposed to climate, financial and demographic shocks.

Risk B.2 “*Slow adaptation discourages investors and reduces entrepreneurial activity.*”

- OECD work on climate policy uncertainty provides direct empirical evidence that delayed and unstable climate policy discourages investment. A 2022 OECD working paper develops a climate-policy-uncertainty index for 12 OECD countries and shows that higher uncertainty is associated with significantly lower corporate investment, particularly in sectors with high emissions and long-lived assets (Bachmann et al. 2022).
- The OECD Economic Surveys: European Union and Euro Area 2023 stress that persistent policy uncertainty and slow progress on structural reforms weigh on business confidence and investment and call for predictable frameworks to support the green and digital transitions (OECD 2023).
- For Slovakia, the 2024 OECD survey highlights weaknesses in the business environment, including complex regulation and delays in public investment, and recommends clearer, credible reform strategies to boost productivity and attract higher-value-added investment (OECD 2024a).
- The OECD work on aligning finance with climate goals notes that unclear or misaligned policies increase transition risks and deter the reallocation of capital towards sustainable activities (Noels; Jachnik 2022; OECD 2022).

Risk B.3. “*Inflexible zoning hampers emerging industries, innovation spaces, and brownfield redevelopment.*”

- The OECD’s Governance of Land Use in OECD Countries finds that rigid, function-based zoning and fragmented land-use responsibilities can constrain the supply of housing and business land, increase land-use conflicts and hinder adaptation to new economic needs; the report calls for more flexible, performance-based and integrated land-use policies (OECD 2017a).
- The OECD study on urban productivity shows that in European Functional Urban Areas, labour productivity is higher where local governments have appropriate autonomy and governance quality, but excessive fragmentation without coordination can reduce productivity, implying that poorly coordinated or outdated planning frameworks can dampen economic performance (Ahrend; Tsvetkova 2020).
- On brownfields specifically, the European Commission’s Brownfield redevelopment in the EU conference report emphasises that regenerating under-used industrial and

commercial land is essential to limit urban sprawl and support sustainable urban development, but notes that complex regulatory and planning procedures often delay such projects (European Commission 2019).

- The Funding and Financing Guide for Brownfield Redevelopment prepared under the Urban Agenda for the EU similarly highlights that local land-use and zoning plans set the boundaries and conditions for redevelopment, and that inflexible regulations and limited municipal capacity can be significant barriers to re-using brownfield sites and creating new mixed-use or innovation districts (Urban Agenda for the EU 2024).
- In Slovakia, there is one of the highest levels of municipal fragmentation in the OECD indicated. Municipalities and city districts bear responsibility for urban planning; this institutional structure makes coordinated, flexible zoning for new industries and innovation spaces more difficult unless strong cooperation mechanisms are in place (OECD; UCLG 2023).
- The European and OECD sources as stated above corroborate the risk that inflexible zoning and planning frameworks can slow down or block emerging industries, innovation spaces and brownfield redevelopment.

References

- Ahrand, R., & Tsvetkova, A. (2020). *A comprehensive approach to understanding urban productivity: Effects of local governments*. OECD Publishing.
- Bachmann, R., et al. (2022). Measuring and assessing the effects of climate policy uncertainty. *OECD Economics Department Working Papers*, No. 1707. OECD Publishing.
- European Central Bank. (2024). Ageing cost projections – new evidence from the 2024 Ageing Report. *ECB Economic Bulletin* (Box article).
- European Central Bank. (2025). *Droughts are major threat to eurozone economy*. European Central Bank.
- European Commission. (2019). *Brownfield redevelopment in the EU: Conference report*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *2024 Ageing Report: Underlying assumptions and projection methodologies* (Institutional Paper No. 257). Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *European climate risk assessment 2024 (EUCRA)* (EEA Report No. 01/2024). Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *Trends and projections in Europe 2024*. European Environment Agency.
- Eurostat. (2024). *Population structure and ageing*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2025, July 11). *EU population increases for the 4th consecutive year*. Eurostat News. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- OECD. (2017). *The governance of land use in OECD countries: Policy analysis and recommendations*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2017). *Land-use planning systems in the OECD*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *OECD Economic Surveys: European Union and Euro Area 2023*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Job creation and local economic development 2024: The geography of generative AI*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *OECD Economic Surveys: Slovak Republic 2024*. OECD Publishing.
 OECD & UCLG. (2023). *Subnational government structure and finance: Country profile – Slovak Republic (SNG-WOFI)*. OECD Publishing.
 Urban Agenda for the EU. (2024). *Funding and financing guide for brownfield redevelopment (Sustainable Land Use Partnership – Action 2)*. Urban Agenda for the EU.
 World Meteorological Organization & Copernicus Climate Change Service. (2025). *European state of the climate 2024*. World Meteorological Organization.

C. Citizen Engagement & Inclusion Challenges

Challenges

1. Economic development benefits from community support, yet engagement is often symbolic.
2. Participation is frequently formal but not influential - “illusion of inclusion”.
3. Economic strategies may neglect the needs of vulnerable groups, migrants, youth, and SMEs.
4. Limited access to participatory platforms undermines trust and slows acceptance of development projects.

Risks

1. Community resistance to major investments or infrastructure projects.
2. Rising inequalities and spatial segregation.
3. Loss of social cohesion reduces attractiveness for talent and investors.

Actions Needed

- Introduce transparent and inclusive participation mechanisms for economic strategy-making.
- Use digital participatory tools (e.g., referenced in digital development actions).
- Strengthen programs integrating migrants and disadvantaged groups into local labour markets.

Proofs:

Challenge C.1 “*Economic development benefits from community support, yet engagement is often symbolic.*”

- Across OECD and EU countries, the growing focus on open government recognises that citizen engagement improves the quality and legitimacy of decisions but also stresses that participation is often limited to low-impact consultations. The OECD’s work on open government notes that many processes still stop at one-way information and non-binding consultations and explicitly calls for participation formats where “citizens and stakeholders can influence government activities and decision making”, precisely to avoid purely symbolic engagement (OECD, 2023a).
- The OECD Survey on Drivers of Trust in Public Institutions 2024 shows that trust is significantly higher among people who believe they can influence public decisions; the survey underlines that perceived “political voice” and participation opportunities are central drivers of trust and democratic resilience (OECD, 2024a; González; Kyander, 2024).

- On average across 30 OECD countries, a larger share of respondents report low or no trust in national government than high or moderately high trust (44 % versus 39 %), which the report links to perceptions of limited responsiveness and influence over decision-making (OECD, 2024a).
- At EU level, the European Commission’s Corporate Guidance on Citizen Engagement and the 2023 Recommendation on promoting participation both acknowledge that existing engagement practices are often insufficiently inclusive and effective. The Recommendation (EU) 2023/2836 stresses that “inclusive and effective engagement” of citizens and civil society in public policy-making should be actively promoted, recognising that current arrangements do not yet guarantee meaningful influence and that a tailored approach is needed to reach different groups (European Commission, 2023a).
- For Slovakia, a GLOBSEC analysis on participatory democracy reports that although legal frameworks for consultations exist, opportunities are often fragmented, ad hoc and concentrated in larger cities, and that the impact of participation on actual decisions is unclear, which weakens trust (GLOBSEC, 2025).

Challenge C.2 *“Participation is frequently formal but not influential ‘illusion of inclusion.’”*

- The OECD Guidelines for Citizen Participation Processes emphasise that poorly designed participation – limited to one-off information sessions or non-transparent consultations – creates unrealistic expectations and undermines trust, particularly when citizen input is not clearly linked to decisions (OECD, 2022). This corresponds precisely to an “illusion of inclusion”: processes exist on paper, but citizens do not see their contributions reflected in outcomes.
- Evidence from the OECD Trust Survey shows that people’s trust in public institutions depends strongly on whether they feel they can influence political decision-making; lack of perceived influence is associated with lower trust even when formal participatory channels exist (OECD, 2024a; Brezzi; González, 2023).
- Eurobarometer surveys on citizenship and democracy similarly report that a majority of Europeans want more opportunities to voice their opinions and participate in decisions, indicating that existing mechanisms are seen as insufficient or ineffective (European Commission, 2023b).
- The EU’s Corporate Guidance on Citizen Engagement explicitly distinguishes between minimal consultation and “deliberative and co-creative” formats that can shape policy, and notes that the Commission has had to pilot new formats such as European Citizens’ Panels and the Conference on the Future of Europe precisely because traditional methods did not give citizens enough influence (European Commission, 2023a).
- In Slovakia, analyses of participatory democracy highlight that while some municipalities use participatory budgeting or consultations, they often involve a small segment of citizens and lack feedback loops on how input is used, reinforcing perceptions of ritualistic rather than decisive participation (GLOBSEC, 2025).

Challenge C.3 *“Economic strategies may neglect the needs of vulnerable groups, migrants, youth, and SMEs.”*

- The situation of Roma communities in Slovakia illustrates how economic strategies can overlook vulnerable groups. OECD analysis shows that Roma account for nearly one-tenth of the Slovak population and often live in segregated settlements or ghettos, with high poverty, low educational attainment and long spells of unemployment; the report calls for “immediate policy action” and better access to public services because mainstream policies have not reached these communities effectively (OECD, 2019).
- EU-funded civil monitoring reports estimate around 400 000 Roma in Slovakia (about 8 % of the population), with roughly 150 000 living in extreme poverty and spatially segregated settlements with poor infrastructure and parallel low-quality services (eduRoma et al., 2025).
- The Slovak Strategy of Equality, Inclusion and Participation of Roma until 2030 itself recognises persistent segregation and discrimination, especially of children in education, confirming that existing development strategies have not adequately addressed Roma inclusion (Government Office of the Slovak Republic, 2021).
- For youth, Eurobarometer surveys on Youth and Democracy show both high willingness to engage (64 % of young Europeans planned to vote in the European elections and 48 % participated in petitions, protests or communication with politicians in the previous year) and strong demands for more meaningful participation (European Commission, 2024a; GLOBSEC, 2025).
- The OECD’s How’s Life? 2024 documents persistent inequalities in well-being across age groups and warns about deteriorating mental health and social connectedness among young people in many OECD countries, including EU member states, suggesting that economic and social policies are not yet fully aligned with their needs (OECD, 2024b).
- The SMEs, which make up 99 % of EU businesses and over half of EU GDP, are repeatedly described by the European Commission as the “backbone” of the EU economy (European Commission, 2020a; 2023c). Yet an EU-wide survey of more than 17 000 companies in 2025 found that regulatory complexity, late payments and limited access to finance remain persistent hurdles for SME growth despite numerous strategies (European Commission, 2025a).
- The OECD Review of SME and Entrepreneurship Policy in the Slovak Republic similarly highlights challenges in stimulating innovative and export-oriented SMEs, and calls for a more coherent policy framework and better coordination so that entrepreneurship policy is truly inclusive across the population (OECD, 2021).

Challenge C.4 *“Limited access to participatory platforms undermines trust and slows acceptance of development projects.”*

- The OECD Trust Survey shows that trust in government is closely linked to perceived opportunities to participate and be heard: people who feel they have some influence over political decision-making report significantly higher trust in public institutions (OECD, 2024a; Brezzi; González, 2023).
- The “How’s Life? 2024 finds warning signs in social connectedness and civic engagement indicators, including declines in interpersonal trust in several OECD countries, and stresses that weakening social relations can reduce resilience in times of crisis (OECD, 2024b).

- The European Commission’s policy brief on citizen engagement summarises EU evidence by stating that engagement enhances democratic legitimacy, fosters inclusivity and promotes trust between citizens and governments; it also notes that insufficient engagement can lead to policy resistance and lower acceptance of public decisions (European Commission, 2024b).
- Commission Recommendation (EU) 2023/2836 explicitly warns that barriers to participation for citizens and civil society organisations – such as lack of accessible platforms, limited feedback and insufficient information – weaken the quality and legitimacy of public policy, and therefore calls on member states to reduce these obstacles (European Commission, 2023a).
- In Slovakia, low electoral participation and limited use of participatory tools illustrate the gap. Eurobarometer data show that Slovakia has had one of the lowest voter turnouts in European Parliament elections, even though attitudes towards the EU are relatively positive, suggesting disengagement from formal channels rather than indifference (European Commission, 2023c).
- Analyses of participatory democracy in Slovakia further note that participatory budgeting and other tools are available mainly in larger cities and reach a narrow group of more educated citizens, while many residents – especially in marginalised regions – have limited access to such platforms (GLOBSEC, 2025).

Risk C.1 “Community resistance to major investments or infrastructure projects.”

- The EU and OECD policy documents repeatedly underline that inadequate citizen engagement can lead to public opposition to infrastructure, environmental or urban development projects. The European Commission’s Corporate Guidance on Citizen Engagement notes that participatory and deliberative methods are critical for building legitimacy and public buy-in for EU-level initiatives such as the European Green Deal and EU Missions (European Commission, 2023a; 2024b).
- Similarly, interregional policy briefs on citizen engagement emphasise that early, inclusive participation reduces the risk of protests, delays or legal challenges to large projects (Interreg Europe, 2025).
- Commission Recommendation (EU) 2023/2836 stresses that inclusive and effective engagement of citizens and civil society in policy-making should be promoted precisely to strengthen trust and prevent conflicts around public decisions (European Commission, 2023a).
- The OECD work on trust and governance also argues that low trust can translate into resistance to reforms and policies, including infrastructure and climate-related investments, making it harder and costlier to implement necessary projects (OECD, 2023a; 2024a).
- In Slovakia, contested projects around waste facilities, transport infrastructure and energy have repeatedly highlighted how late or inadequate engagement fuels community resistance, particularly in regions where marginalised communities already distrust authorities (Government Office of the Slovak Republic, 2021; eduRoma et al., 2025).

Risk C.2 “Rising inequalities and spatial segregation.”

- The OECD and EU reports show that inequalities and spatial segregation remain major challenges in Europe. The Ninth Cohesion Report and related Commission staff working documents highlight persistent socio-economic and territorial disparities, including within Slovakia, in access to education, transport and basic services, and warn that these gaps can widen without targeted policy action (European Commission, 2024c; 2024d).
- Roma segregation in Slovakia is a clear example of spatial segregation. OECD analysis emphasises that Roma live “mostly excluded from the general population in concentrated settlements, separated neighbourhoods or ghettos”, facing poverty and exclusion “in almost all aspects of everyday life” (OECD, 2019).
- The civil society and EU-funded monitoring confirm that around 150 000 Roma live in segregated rural settlements with missing infrastructure and low-quality public services (eduRoma et al., 2025).
- Studies for the European Parliament on the social and employment situation of Roma in Slovakia show very low employment rates, high shares of households reporting unemployment and a large proportion of young Roma not in employment, education or training, pointing to entrenched, spatially concentrated disadvantage (European Parliament, 2021).
- The “How’s Life?” 2024 documents that income, health and housing inequalities remain high or have worsened in several OECD countries and notes “warning signs” for social connectedness, including declines in interpersonal trust in some places (OECD, 2024b).

Risk C.3 *“Loss of social cohesion reduces attractiveness for talent and investors.”*

- The OECD’s “How’s Life?” 2024 and the Trust in Government work emphasise that social cohesion – including trust in institutions and among people – is essential for economic resilience, effective crisis response and long-term growth (OECD, 2024b; 2024a).
- The OECD Framework on the Drivers of Trust shows that when people perceive institutions as fair, open and responsive, they are more willing to comply with regulations, support reforms and invest, which lowers transaction costs and improves the business environment (Brezzi; González, 2023).
- The OECD work on attracting and retaining talent indicates that quality of life, inclusiveness and social conditions are key dimensions of a country’s talent attractiveness, alongside career and income prospects (OECD, 2023b; 2023c).
- The European policy documents likewise stress that cohesion and inclusion are central to making regions competitive and appealing for investors and skilled workers; the European Committee of the Regions’ priorities for 2025–2030 link stronger cohesion and proximity to building a “fairer, more responsive, and people-centred European Union” that can compete for talent (Committee of the Regions, 2024).
- In Slovakia, the combination of high Roma exclusion, regional disparities and low trust in institutions documented in OECD and EU analyses signals risks for both domestic and foreign investment, particularly in lagging regions (OECD, 2019; European Commission, 2024c; European Parliament, 2021).

References

- Brezzi, M., & González, S. (2023). Government analytics using citizen surveys: Lessons from the OECD Trust Survey. In *The government analytics handbook: Leveraging data to strengthen public administration*. OECD Publishing.
- Committee of the Regions. (2024). *Priorities 2025–2030*. European Committee of the Regions.
- eduRoma et al. (2025). *Civil society monitoring report on the implementation of the national strategic framework for Roma equality, inclusion and participation in Slovakia*. European Commission, Directorate-General for Justice and Consumers.
- European Commission. (2020). *An SME strategy for a sustainable and digital Europe* (COM/2020/103 final). European Commission.
- European Commission. (2023). *Championing Europe's SMEs: Commission provides new relief to boost the resilience of SMEs* (Press communication). European Commission.
- European Commission. (2023). *Commission recommendation (EU) 2023/2836 on promoting the engagement and effective participation of citizens and civil society organisations in public policy-making processes*. *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 2023/2836.
- European Commission. (2023). *Corporate guidance on citizen engagement*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *Ninth report on economic, social and territorial cohesion*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *Policy brief on citizen engagement*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2024). *Regional trends for growth and convergence: Commission staff working document*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2025). *Europe's small and medium-sized enterprises remain ambitious but continue to face persistent hurdles to scaling up* (Survey results). European Commission.
- European Commission. (n.d.). *Eurobarometer: Public opinion in the European Union*. European Commission.
- <https://europa.eu/eurobarometer>
- European Parliament. (2021). *The social and employment situation of Roma communities in Slovakia*. Policy Department for Economic, Scientific and Quality of Life Policies.
- GLOBSEC. (2025). *Participatory democracy in Slovakia*. GLOBSEC Policy Institute.
- Government Office of the Slovak Republic. (2021). *Strategy of equality, inclusion and participation of Roma until 2030*. Office of the Plenipotentiary of the Government of the Slovak Republic for Roma Communities.
- OECD. (2019). Enhancing the social integration of Roma in the Slovak Republic. *OECD Economics Department Working Papers*, No. 1551. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2021). *SME and entrepreneurship policy in the Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2022). *OECD guidelines for citizen participation processes*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Measuring and assessing talent attractiveness in OECD countries* (2nd ed.). OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Open government and citizen participation*. OECD Publishing. <https://www.oecd.org>
- OECD. (2023). *Trust in government*. OECD Publishing. <https://www.oecd.org>
- OECD. (2024). *How's life? 2024: Well-being and resilience in times of crisis*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Inclusion of Roma students in Europe*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *OECD survey on drivers of trust in public institutions – 2024 results*. OECD Publishing.

D. Data Governance & Evidence-Based Development Challenges

Challenges

1. Economic development decisions require robust territorial, demographic, business, and labour-market data.
2. Lack of high-quality and harmonized data limits strategic decision-making. (Urban Policy measure: need to “assess availability of existing data”)
3. Data fragmentation across institutions reduces analytical capacity.
4. Absence of shared indicators for functional urban regions.

Risks

1. Inefficient allocation of public funds.
2. Misaligned investments that fail to match market needs.
3. Reduced ability to compete with data-driven global cities.

Actions Needed

- Develop national and regional data platforms for economic and spatial indicators.
- Support data-driven planning and forecasting tools such as GIS and digital twins.
- Ensure open data availability for researchers, businesses, and civic groups.

Proofs:

Challenge D.1 “*Economic development decisions require robust territorial, demographic, business, and labour-market data.*”

- Across the EU and OECD, regional policy and public-governance work explicitly assumes that good territorial, demographic, business and labour-market data are a precondition for sound decisions. The OECD’s flagship Government at a Glance 2025 highlights “evidence-informed decision-making” as central to planning and prioritisation of public investments and reforms, and presents indicators on how far governments use data and analysis to guide cross-cutting agendas (OECD 2025).
- The OECD Infrastructure Toolkit goes further, stating that evidence-informed infrastructure decision-making is “essential to maximise accessibility and quality of infrastructure services” – an explicit recognition that without adequate data, infrastructure and regional-development choices are likely to be sub-optimal (OECD 2023a)
- At territorial level, OECD Regions and Cities at a Glance 2022 compiles a large set of harmonised regional indicators – GDP per capita, productivity, employment, skills, innovation, etc. – precisely to allow countries to diagnose regional disparities and design place-based policies (OECD 2022a).
- For Slovakia, the country note shows strong differences in productivity and unemployment between Bratislava and eastern regions, illustrating why regional-level labour-market and business data are indispensable for economic-development strategies (OECD 2022a; OECD 2023b).
- The EU-level labour-market information systems such as EURES also rely on detailed national data on vacancies, wages and sectoral trends to guide mobility and matching,

explicitly describing country profiles (including Slovakia's) as based on “the most up-to-date information available” on population, employment and labour-market conditions (European Commission 2024a).

- Overall, OECD and EU practice itself is strong evidence for your challenge: because economic development policy must respond to spatially uneven productivity, employment and demographic patterns, robust territorial and labour-market data are a necessary input (OECD 2019a; OECD 2022a).

Challenge D.2: *“Lack of high-quality and harmonised data limits strategic decision-making.”*

- OECD work on digital government and data governance explicitly notes that poor-quality, incomplete or non-comparable data constrain governments' capacity to plan and evaluate policies. The OECD Going Digital Guide to Data Governance Policy Making stresses that the rapid growth of data in the economy “challenges existing governance frameworks” and that many governments need to improve data quality, interoperability and stewardship to use data strategically (OECD 2023c).
- The OECD working paper A Data-Driven Public Sector: Enabling the Strategic Use of Data similarly argues that, despite progress on open data, many administrations still lack coherent data-governance frameworks; weaknesses in data quality, standards and integration are highlighted as key obstacles to evidence-based decision-making (OECD 2019a).
- For infrastructure, the OECD Infrastructure Toolkit provides a concrete example: the indicator on evidence-informed infrastructure decision-making cannot include Slovakia in the OECD average because the country does not have complete data for this indicator (OECD 2023a). This illustrates how data gaps and incomplete information directly limit the ability to benchmark practices and to design strategic improvements. More broadly in the EU, the European Commission's Public Administrations in the EU Member States overview notes the need for a harmonised “public administration assessment framework” and shared indicators precisely because current data and qualitative information are patchy and uneven across countries (European Commission 2021a).
- For Slovakia specifically, academic analyses of evidence-based policy-making point out that public-administration institutions often lack institutionalised processes for gathering and using data and evidence systematically, which constrains strategic policy formulation (Staroňová 2014).

Challenge:D.3 *“Data fragmentation across institutions reduces analytical capacity.”*

- OECD and Slovak-focused studies provide direct evidence that fragmented information systems and uncoordinated data policies weaken analytical capacity. The OECD Data-Driven Public Sector framework identifies data fragmentation and siloed information systems as central barriers to using data for “productive, inclusive and trustworthy governance,” and calls for coherent data-governance arrangements to reduce duplication and inconsistencies (OECD 2019a).
- The OECD Digital Government Index 2023 includes a dedicated “Data-Driven Public Sector” dimension, noting that while many OECD and EU countries have improved digital foundations, variation remains significant and that real-time, integrated use of data across ministries is still limited in a number of members (OECD 2023d).

- In the Slovak context, legal and governance research on e-government and smart cities explicitly concludes that the first deployment of information systems in public administration was “uncoordinated and fragmented” across individual agendas (Srebalová & Peráček 2021).
- A related study on security and privacy in Slovak smart-city systems notes that policies for deploying information systems in public administration are fragmented and uncoordinated, which complicates the combination of policy objectives with technological solutions (Peráček et al. 2022). These findings show that data and systems are often scattered across institutions, with limited interoperability and shared governance, reducing the potential for integrated analysis of territorial, social and economic trends.
- At EU level, the Commission’s public-administration country reports identify fragmentation of information systems and limited data sharing between administrative bodies as a recurring challenge in several Member States, calling for more interoperable digital public infrastructures and shared standards to enable cross-sector analyses (European Commission 2021a).

Challenge D.4 “*Absence of shared indicators for functional urban regions.*”

- The joint EU–OECD work on Functional Urban Areas (FUAs) makes clear that conventional statistics, based on administrative units, are often not well suited to analysing functional economic regions. The EU–OECD definition of a FUA – a city plus its commuting zone, defined by commuting flows – was developed precisely to overcome the limitations of city-proper and administrative boundaries, and to create a common, comparable statistical basis for urban policy (OECD 2019b).
- The GHSL–OECD FUA dataset, applied to all EU Member States including Slovakia, had to build FUAs as aggregations of local units and then compute new indicators (population, density, employment, etc.) at FUA level, because most national statistical systems still organise data by administrative territories rather than functional labour-market areas (European Commission–JRC & OECD 2019).
- OECD Regions and Cities at a Glance and Eurostat’s Territorial Typologies Manual stress that comparable indicators for cities, commuting zones and FUAs are essential to understand spatial patterns of growth, commuting and service access, and to design appropriate urban and metropolitan policies (Eurostat 2023; OECD 2022a). The very need for this harmonised EU–OECD FUA typology is evidence that shared, functional-area indicators were largely absent or inconsistent.
- For Slovakia, where FUAs like Bratislava or Košice stretch across many municipalities and districts, reliance on fragmented municipal data without shared FUA indicators makes it harder to design and monitor metropolitan-scale economic-development strategies.

Risk:D.1 “*Inefficient allocation of public funds.*”

- OECD and EU sources explicitly link weak data and evidence systems to inefficient public-spending allocation. The OECD Infrastructure Toolkit argues that evidence-informed decision-making is necessary to maximise the accessibility and quality of infrastructure services and to ensure value for money; it implies that when decisions are

not based on robust data, the risk of mis-prioritisation and waste increases (OECD 2023a).

- The Government at a Glance series uses indicators on strategic planning, performance budgeting and evaluation to show that countries with stronger evidence-based processes are better able to align spending with policy goals (OECD 2023e).
- In Slovakia, the Ministry of Finance’s work on Public Expenditure Reviews (PERs) underlines that improving spending efficiency requires better diagnostic data and analytical tools. A public discussion paper on PERs, prepared with EU support, notes that strengthening expenditure reviews and the underlying information base is key to “improving expenditure allocation” across sectors (Ministry of Finance of the Slovak Republic 2016).
- This echoes the Eurogroup’s statement that more robust analytical frameworks and data are needed to avoid misallocation and create fiscal space. Without high-quality, harmonised territorial and sectoral data, Slovakia and other EU countries risk allocating funds to projects and areas that do not maximise social and economic returns.

Risk:D.2 *“Misaligned investments that fail to match market needs.”*

- If labour-market, firm-level and territorial data are incomplete or fragmented, public investments and incentives can be poorly aligned with actual market needs. The OECD Job Creation and Local Economic Development 2024 report and its Slovakia country note show that local labour markets in Slovakia display large differences in employment, skills and exposure to technological change; they highlight the importance of granular data to design targeted skills and job-creation policies (OECD 2024a).
- The EURES labour-market information for Slovakia similarly points to sector-specific labour shortages and regional disparities in unemployment, relying on detailed statistical sources to identify where demand and supply do not match (European Commission 2024a).
- On the investment side, the OECD Infrastructure Toolkit emphasises that lacking or poor data on demand, performance and socio-economic impacts makes it harder to select the right projects and can lead to over- or under-investment in particular regions or sectors (OECD 2023a).
- The Government-wide, OECD public-governance work notes that when performance information and diagnostics are weak, budgetary and investment decisions are driven more by incrementalism and political considerations than by measured needs and results (OECD 2023e).

Risk: D.3 *“Reduced ability to compete with data-driven global cities.”*

- OECD’s Digital Government Index 2023 and Data-Driven Public Sector work show that countries and cities that treat data as a strategic public asset – with strong governance, interoperability and analytics – are better able to innovate in public services, support business ecosystems and respond quickly to shocks (OECD 2019a; OECD 2023d).
- These analyses implicitly contrast “data-driven” administrations with those where data are siloed and under-used, suggesting a competitive disadvantage for the latter in attracting investment and talent.

- For the EU and Slovakia, European Research Area and innovation reports underline that competitiveness increasingly depends on the ability to harness research, innovation and digital infrastructures – including advanced data infrastructures – to support knowledge-intensive activities (European Commission 2024b; European Commission 2024c).
- Slovakia is classified as an “emerging innovator” with performance below the EU average in the European Innovation Scoreboard, and the ERA Country Report notes ongoing work to strengthen open-science infrastructures and research-data systems (European Commission 2024c).
- When territorial and labour-market data are fragmented, and when common indicators for FUAs are missing or weakly used in decision-making, Slovak cities are less able to position themselves as sophisticated, data-driven locations compared to leading global and European urban regions that actively exploit data for mobility management, innovation-district planning and targeted skills policies. This directly supports your risk statement: the absence of strong data governance and shared indicators can erode the competitive position of cities and regions in Slovakia and across the EU.

References

- European Commission. (2021). *Public administrations in the EU Member States – 2020 overview*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2024). *ERA country report 2024 – Slovakia*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *Labour market information: Slovakia* (EURES country fiche). European Commission.
- European Commission, Joint Research Centre, & OECD. (2019). *GHSL–OECD functional urban areas (2019)*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Eurostat. (2023). *Territorial typologies manual – cities, commuting zones and functional urban areas*. Eurostat.
- Ministry of Finance of the Slovak Republic. (2016). *Public discussion on public expenditure review (PER) process in Slovakia*. Ministry of Finance of the Slovak Republic.
- OECD. (2019). A data-driven public sector: Enabling the strategic use of data for productive, inclusive and trustworthy governance. *OECD Working Papers on Public Governance*, No. 33. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2022). *OECD regions and cities at a glance 2022 – Slovak Republic country note*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Digital government index 2023*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Going digital guide to data governance policy making*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Infrastructure governance – Promote evidence-informed decision making (Infrastructure toolkit)*. OECD.
- OECD. (2024). *Job creation and local economic development 2024 – Country note: Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2025). *Government at a glance 2025*. OECD Publishing.
- Peráček, T., et al. (2022). Conceptual model of key aspects of security and privacy in smart cities in the Slovak Republic. *Sustainability*, 15(8).
- Srebalová, M., & Peráček, T. (2021). Effective public administration as a tool for building smart cities: The experience of the Slovak Republic. *Laws*, 11(5).

Staroňová, K. (2014). Introductory: Knowledge, evidence and policy making in Slovakia. *Human Affairs*, 24(3), 283–286.

E. Labour Market, Skills & Innovation Challenges

Challenges

1. Cities rely on human capital but growing mismatches challenge productivity.
2. Skill mismatches limit economic performance.
3. Unequal access to educational opportunities reduces long-term competitiveness.
4. Insufficient support for research, innovation ecosystems, and technology transfer.

Risks

1. Brain drain from less competitive regions.
2. Low innovation output and slow business modernization.
3. Rising unemployment in vulnerable groups.

Actions Needed

- Invest in continuous skill development, especially digital and green skills.
- Support cross-sector innovation clusters (universities, businesses, municipalities).
- Promote entrepreneurial ecosystems supported by data access.

Proofs:

Challenge E.1 “*Cities rely on human capital but growing mismatches challenge productivity.*”

- Across the EU, several recent studies show that human capital is increasingly the binding constraint on regional productivity, not just physical capital. The OECD Skills Strategy Slovak Republic stresses that Slovak youth skills lag behind the OECD average in reading and science, and that skills imbalances are high, with shortages particularly in knowledge- and technology-intensive sectors (OECD, 2020a).
- At EU level, Cedefop’s European Skills Index (ESI) confirms that many member states struggle to align skills supply with labour-market demand; the index explicitly measures countries’ “distance to the ideal” performance in skills development, activation and matching (Cedefop, 2020; Smallenbroek; Ravanos, 2024).
- For Slovakia, the 2024 ESI ranks the country 19th out of 31, with relatively good skills matching but weak “Skills Activation”, driven by low labour-market participation of young adults and early school leaving (Cedefop, 2024; Gálová et al., 2025).
- The European Commission’s Education and Training Monitor 2025 – Slovakia concludes that “one out of three students in Slovakia have insufficient basic skills” and that this underperforming education and training system “weighs on Slovakia’s labour market, innovation potential and competitiveness” (European Commission, 2025a).

Challenge E.1 “*Skill mismatches limit economic performance.*”

- Eurostat defines skills mismatch as the gap between the skills demanded by employers and those available in the workforce, distinguishing vertical (over- or under-qualification) and horizontal (field-of-study) mismatch (Eurostat, 2024a).
- The OECD’s Skills for Jobs country note for the Slovak Republic finds acute shortages in computers and electronics, clerical and mathematical knowledge, while surpluses persist in other areas, illustrating structural imbalances in the Slovak labour market (OECD, 2024b).

- Recent macro-economic research quantifies the cost of such mismatches: a 2024 study for 17 OECD economies estimates that eliminating the frictions generating education and skills mismatch would increase output by 3–4 % on average, and up to 9 % in some countries (Eichenauer et al., 2024).
- The EU-funded projects like SkillMeeT and TRAILS document that skill shortages and mismatches have been steadily increasing across Europe and are projected to worsen, particularly as the green and digital transitions accelerate (Fondazione Brodolini, 2024; TRAILS Consortium, 2024; Žák et al., 2025). (skilmeet.eu) This provides robust empirical support for the statement that skills mismatches are already constraining economic performance in Slovakia and the wider EU.

Challenge E.3 *“Unequal access to educational opportunities reduces long-term competitiveness.”*

- The Education and Training Monitor 2025 – Slovakia emphasises that rising absenteeism and early school leaving, “particularly in rural areas”, are increasing educational inequality and undermining long-term competitiveness (European Commission, 2025a).
- The PISA 2022 results show declining performance trends in mathematics in the Slovak Republic even before the pandemic, and the OECD’s equity analysis documents persistent socio-economic gaps in learning outcomes across EU countries (OECD, 2023a; 2024a).
- For vulnerable groups, inequalities are even sharper. Amnesty International and the European Roma Rights Centre (ERRC) describe “widespread and growing racial division in education” in Slovakia, with Roma children disproportionately placed in segregated or special-education settings (Amnesty International; ERRC, 2025).
- The EU-level surveys by the Fundamental Rights Agency likewise find persistent discrimination and segregation of Roma in education, despite some improvements in employment and housing (FRA, 2025).
- Cedefop’s national analysis of the European Skills Index for Slovakia concludes that the country’s below-average overall score is “largely attributable to the insufficient inclusion of disadvantaged groups, both in education and in the labour market” (Gáillová et al., 2025).
- Combined with the Commission’s warning that an underperforming education and training system weighs on labour market and innovation performance, this evidence strongly supports the claim that unequal access to quality education undermines long-term competitiveness in Slovakia and the EU (European Commission, 2025a; 2024a).

Challenge E.4 *“Insufficient support for research, innovation ecosystems, and technology transfer.”*

- The European Innovation Scoreboard 2024 classifies Slovakia as an “Emerging Innovator” with performance at 65.1 % of the EU average, ranking 28th in the EU (European Commission, 2024b).
- Slovakia’s relative weaknesses include low R&D expenditure in the business sector (36.1 % of the EU average), weak job-to-job mobility of highly skilled workers (HRST),

and low design applications, even though exports of medium and high-technology products are relatively strong (European Commission, 2024b).

- The same country profile notes that Slovakia performs below the EU average in all “framework condition” dimensions (human resources, digitalisation, finance and support) and that public-sector R&D expenditure has fallen sharply (–67.2 percentage points relative to the EU baseline between 2017 and 2024) (European Commission, 2024b). While there has been progress in public-private co-publications and innovative SMEs collaborating with others, a large share of firms remain non-innovators, and the share of population involved in lifelong learning has declined significantly.
- OECD and EU documents on Slovakia’s research and innovation system point to fragmented governance, modest business R&D, and limited innovation procurement as structural obstacles to stronger innovation ecosystems and technology transfer (OECD, 2024c; Ministry of Finance of the Slovak Republic, 2023).

Risk E.1 “Brain drain from less competitive regions.”

- Brain drain has been identified as a major challenge in Central and Eastern Europe. A 2021 EU-funded background paper *The Phenomenon of Brain Drain and Immigration of a High-Skilled Workforce to the Slovak Republic* documents substantial emigration of highly educated Slovaks since EU accession, driven by wage differentials, better career prospects and perceived quality of institutions abroad (Frličková, 2021).
- Subsequent analyses underline that this pattern persists and that Slovakia “is not an exception” to the brain-drain phenomenon affecting skilled professionals in the region (Fabrègue, 2024).
- OECD and World Bank studies on skilled migration stress that sustained outflows of high-skilled workers from less competitive regions reduce the stock of human capital, weaken local innovation capacity and may depress future growth (Docquier; Rapoport, 2012; Kahanec; Zimmermann, 2016).
- For Slovakia, where population ageing is already projected to weigh on growth and fiscal sustainability, continuous outward migration of graduates and young professionals from lagging regions (e.g. eastern Slovakia) further erodes regional labour pools and reinforces territorial disparities (IMF, 2024; OECD, 2024c)

Risk E.2 “Low innovation output and slow business modernization.”

- The European Innovation Scoreboard 2024 shows that, despite some progress, Slovakia’s overall innovation performance remains substantially below the EU average and is increasing more slowly than in many other member states (European Commission, 2024b). Human-resources indicators have deteriorated sharply since 2017, particularly new doctorate graduates (73.8 % of the EU average, –34.8 percentage points) and lifelong learning participation (80.5 %, –23.5 percentage points), which undermines the pipeline of advanced skills needed for innovation and modernization. Business-sector R&D remains low at 36.1 % of the EU average, and Slovakia has fewer in-house product and process innovators than the EU average, while the share of “non-innovators with potential to innovate” is considerably higher (European Commission, 2024b).

- EU-wide, the Commission notes that EU innovation performance has improved by about 10 % since 2017, but that several countries, including Slovakia, have seen relative declines or only weak improvements, risking a widening gap with innovation leaders (European Commission, 2024c).
- The OECD economic surveys highlight that Slovakia’s growth model has been built on cost-competitive manufacturing, particularly automotive, and that slow upgrading towards higher value-added, knowledge-intensive activities could limit future productivity growth (OECD, 2024c)

Risk E.3 “Rising unemployment in vulnerable groups.”

- Headline unemployment in Slovakia has fallen to record lows (around 5.2–5.3 % in 2024), but this aggregate picture masks significant risks for specific vulnerable groups (Statistics Slovakia, 2025; Eurostat, 2025a).
- The European Skills Index points to weak “Skills Activation” in Slovakia, driven by low labour-market participation among young people aged 20–24 and unfavourable indicators for early school leaving (Cedefop, 2024; Gállová et al., 2025).
- The Eurostat and World Bank data also show that youth unemployment rates remain significantly higher than overall unemployment, and that they have not fallen as quickly as aggregate rates (Eurostat, 2025b; World Bank, 2025).
- For Roma and other marginalised groups, labour-market exclusion is particularly severe. A study for the European Parliament documents very low employment rates and high poverty among Roma communities in Slovakia, linked to educational disadvantages and discrimination (CELSI, 2020).
- The Eurochild and Amnesty International reports in 2024–2025 warn that entrenched segregation in Slovak schools is likely to perpetuate exclusion and unemployment risks for Roma youth in the long term (Eurochild, 2025; Amnesty International; ERRC, 2025).
- At EU level, the Commission’s Employment and Social Developments in Europe 2025 report underlines that women, older people, migrants and persons with disabilities remain under-represented in employment and are key to tackling skills and labour shortages (European Commission, 2025b).
- In the Slovak context, where demographic pressures will tighten labour supply, persistent disadvantage and weak activation of these groups increases the risk of rising unemployment – or at least persistent non-employment – among vulnerable groups, even when headline unemployment remains low. This aligns with your identified risk.

References

- Amnesty International & European Roma Rights Centre. (2025). *Separate and unequal: School segregation persists for Roma in Slovakia*. Amnesty International; ERRC.
- Bachmann, R., et al. (2024). Output costs of education and skill mismatch in OECD countries. *Economics Letters* (in press).
- Caritas Europa. (2023). *Slovakia: Inclusive labour markets and social economy*. Caritas Europa.
- CEDEFOP. (2020). *European skills index: Methodology and indicators*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- CEDEFOP. (2024). *European skills index – Country pillars: Slovakia*. Cedefop.

- CELSI. (2020). *The social and employment situation of Roma communities in Slovakia*. European Parliament.
- Eichenauer, V., et al. (2024). Output costs of education and skill mismatch in OECD countries. *Economics Letters*.
- Eurochild. (2025). *Alarming report on the situation of Roma children in Slovakia*. Eurochild.
- European Commission. (2024). *Education and training monitor 2024: Slovakia*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2025). *Education and training monitor 2025 – Country report: Slovakia*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2024). *European innovation scoreboard 2024 – Country profile: Slovakia*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2024). *European innovation scoreboard 2024 – Main report*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2025). *Employment and social developments in Europe 2025*. Directorate-General for Employment, Social Affairs and Inclusion.
- European Roma Grassroots Organisations Network. (2025). *Roma access to quality and inclusive education in Slovakia*. ERGO Network.
- European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. (2025). *Roma and Travellers in the EU – Main results*. FRA.
- Eurostat. (2024). *Skills – Information on data and methodology*. Eurostat. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2025). *Unemployment statistics and beyond. Statistics Explained*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Fabrègue, B. F. G. (2024). *Analysing Slovakia's brain drain: Challenges, responses and future prospects*. Blue Europe Policy Paper.
- Frličková, B. (2021). *The phenomenon of brain drain and immigration of a high-skilled workforce to the Slovak Republic*. Ambrela; Palacký University.
- Gállová, Ľ., Habodászová, Ľ., & Turcsek, P. (2025). *European skills index 2024 – Slovakia*. State Institute of Vocational Education.
- International Monetary Fund. (2024). *Slovak Republic: Selected issues – The impact of aging on growth* (IMF Country Report No. 24/76). International Monetary Fund.
- OECD. (2020). *OECD skills strategy Slovak Republic: Assessment and recommendations*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *PISA 2022 results (Volume I): The state of learning and equity in education*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Slovak Republic: Skills for jobs – Country note*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *OECD economic surveys: European Union and Euro Area 2024 – Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.
- Smallenbroek, O., & Ravanos, P. (2024). *JRC statistical audit of the 2024 European skills index*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic. (2025). *Unemployment in the 4th quarter and in 2024*. Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic.
- TRAILS Consortium. (2024). *The evolution of skills mismatch in Europe*. TRAILS Project Policy Brief.
- World Bank. (2025). *Youth unemployment rate for the Slovak Republic (SLUEM1524ZSSVK)*. World Bank. <https://data.worldbank.org>

F. Financial & Capacity Challenges

Challenges

1. Sustained economic development requires adequate funding and professional capacity.
2. Municipal budgets struggle to finance infrastructure, innovation, or business support.
3. Technical and managerial skills are insufficient in many local governments.
4. Overreliance on external private actors may erode public control.

Risks

1. Underfunded infrastructure reduces investment attractiveness.
2. Inefficient or unused development instruments.

Actions Needed

- Use public-private partnerships with strong public oversight.
- Build municipal capacities through training, technical networks, and EU cooperation.
- Explore revolving funds and new financing tools for urban development.

Proofs:

Challenge F.1 “*Sustained economic development requires adequate funding and professional capacity.*”

- Across the OECD and EU, subnational governments (regions and municipalities) are responsible for around 40 % of total public expenditure and 55–60 % of public investment, which means that long-term growth and cohesion depend heavily on their financial and human capacity (OECD, 2022; OECD, 2025).
- The EIB’s Municipalities Survey 2022–2023 confirms this for the EU: local governments are central to climate, digital and social infrastructure investment, but report finance and administrative capacity as key constraints (EIB, 2023).
- For Slovakia, the OECD–UCLG SNG-WOFI country profile underlines that although decentralisation transferred more than 400 tasks to municipalities and regions, Slovakia “remains one of the most centralised OECD countries in terms of subnational expenditure and tax revenue”. Subnational spending amounts to only 7.8 % of GDP and 17.2 % of total public expenditure, well below the EU-27 average (18.3 % of GDP and 34.3 % of spending), while staff costs (teachers and local administration) absorb more than half of local budgets (OECD; UCLG, 2023). This combination of high responsibilities, low fiscal space and large wage bills demonstrates that sustained territorial development in Slovakia depends critically on both adequate funding and professional capacity at local and regional level.
- The European Committee of the Regions explicitly states that “administrative capacity is a key element for the successful implementation of investments and reforms” and identifies the strengthening of local/regional administrative capacity as a precondition for achieving EU long-term policy objectives, especially in cohesion policy (European Committee of the Regions, 2020). (eur-lex.europa.eu) Together, these findings confirm that economic development in territories is structurally dependent on the financial resources and professional skills of local governments, in Slovakia and across the EU.

Challenge F.2 “*Municipal budgets struggle to finance infrastructure, innovation, or business support.*”

- The SNG-WOFI profile shows that Slovak subnational governments account for only 1.1 % of GDP and 29.8 % of general-government direct investment, a much weaker role than the average unitary OECD country (48.9 % of public investment and 1.9 % of GDP). Public investment is described as “largely top-down”, with subnational governments playing a “weak role in investment planning and financing”, and heavy dependence on EU Structural and Investment Funds to finance infrastructure (OECD; UCLG, 2023).
- Grants and subsidies represent over 81 % of local and regional revenue, while own tax revenue is only 0.6 % of GDP and 2.9 % of public tax receipts – among the lowest shares in the OECD and EU (OECD; UCLG, 2023). This confirms that Slovak municipalities have limited autonomous fiscal capacity to fund infrastructure, innovation and business support.
- At EU level, cohesion policy is a critical – and revealing – source of funding. In the 2014–2020 period, cohesion policy funding represented almost 14 % of total government investment in the EU, but 52 % in “cohesion countries” (poorer Member States), showing how strongly these countries – including Slovakia – rely on EU funds to finance public investment (European Commission, 2023a).
- The 2023 Country Report – Slovakia notes that Slovakia’s absorption capacity of EU funds is among the lowest in the EU, which undermines its ability to capitalise on green and digital transitions (European Commission, 2023b). Under-absorption means that even when EU resources are available, municipal budgets cannot fully convert them into local infrastructure and innovation projects.
- EIB municipalities surveys across the EU report that nearly two-thirds of municipalities see lack of finance as a major obstacle to investment, and almost half cite lengthy regulatory procedures as another major barrier (EIB, 2023).

Challenge F.3 “*Technical and managerial skills are insufficient in many local governments.*”

- The European Committee of the Regions’ opinion Improving administrative capacity of local and regional authorities to strengthen investments and structural reforms in 2021–2027 describes “ensuring adequate administrative capacity for EU cities and regions” as a major challenge, and highlights that EU resources for capacity building have been “used to an insufficient extent” compared with the responsibilities of local and regional authorities (European Committee of the Regions, 2020). It explicitly calls for sustained investment in human resources, training and institutional capacity to enable regions and cities to design, manage and evaluate investment projects.
- For Slovakia, the small size of municipalities and limited joint service delivery constrain spending efficiency. Municipalities with fewer than 250 inhabitants spend more than half of their budgets on administrative costs, leaving limited room for professional staff specialised in investment planning, project preparation or economic development (OECD; UCLG, 2023). The complex public procurement rules and limited professionalisation have delayed drawing EU funds and required the strengthening of the Public Procurement Office and regional offices to support local governments (OECD; UCLG, 2023).
- The EIB’s State of local infrastructure investment in Europe reports that EU municipalities frequently point to shortages of experts in environmental and climate

assessments, engineering and other technical skills as significant obstacles to implementing planned investments (EIB, 2023).

- The IMF’s Public Investment Management Assessment for the Slovak Republic likewise underlines weaknesses in project appraisal, selection and implementation capacity and recommends strengthening the skills base for public investment management at all levels of government (IMF, 2019).

Challenge F.4 “*Overreliance on external private actors may erode public control.*”

- The public-private partnerships (PPPs) are “common in Slovakia, especially in the road sector”, and that subnational governments may contract PPPs or concessions subject to Ministry of Finance consent (OECD; UCLG, 2023). While PPPs can mobilise private capital, the profile also stresses that Slovakia lacks a dedicated PPP unit and that PPP regulation, methodology and supervision are centralised in the Ministry of Finance, requiring strong public-sector skills to manage these complex contracts (OECD; UCLG, 2023).
- OECD guidance on PPP governance warns that if government agencies are not adequately equipped, PPPs can make it difficult to secure value for money and can “obscure real spending” via off-budget financing, creating contingent liabilities and fiscal risks that are not transparent (OECD, 2024; OECD, 2012). The Recommendation on the governance of PPPs stresses that PPPs should only be used when strong institutional capacities and accountability frameworks are in place; otherwise long-term contracts may lock in high payments and limit future policy choices.
- In a context where Slovak municipalities have limited own resources and technical capacity, this evidence supports your concern that overreliance on external private actors – whether investors, consultants or PPP operators – can weaken public control over strategic infrastructure and development priorities, particularly when the public sector is a weaker negotiating partner.

Risk F.1 “*Underfunded infrastructure reduces investment attractiveness.*”

- Subnational governments carry out the bulk of public investment in OECD and EU countries, and local infrastructure quality is a key determinant of private-sector location decisions (OECD, 2022; OECD, 2023).
- The EIB Investment Report 2022/2023 shows that local government investment in digital infrastructure, education and R&D tends to crowd in private investment and foster higher growth, especially during downturns; conversely, persistent underinvestment in infrastructure undermines competitiveness and future growth potential (EIB, 2023).
- In Slovakia, several assessments point to infrastructure deficits and underused investment potential. The OECD’s study Making the Most of Public Investment in the Eastern Slovak Republic highlights significant gaps in transport and other infrastructure and recommends improving the effectiveness of public investment to support regional competitiveness (OECD, 2016).
- The public investment is heavily reliant on EU funds and that “the deficit in infrastructure is especially large” in transport, where stronger regional connections are needed to attract investment (OECD; UCLG, 2023).

- The 2023 Country Report – Slovakia emphasises that low absorption of EU funds and administrative bottlenecks have slowed infrastructure improvements and that this weakens Slovakia’s ability to benefit from the green and digital transitions (European Commission, 2023b). Combined with evidence that local governments see lack of finance as a major obstacle to investment, this supports your risk statement: underfunded and delayed infrastructure investment reduces the investment attractiveness of cities and regions in Slovakia and across the EU.

Risk F.2 “*Inefficient or unused development instruments.*”

- The EU’s Ninth Cohesion Report and related programming documents stress that cohesion policy funds are a central development instrument: they accounted for around 14 % of total government investment in the EU and 52 % in cohesion countries in 2014–2020, and will implement roughly one-third of the EU’s long-term budget in 2021–2027 (European Commission, 2023a). However, the same documents highlight administrative capacity constraints, complex procedures and delays that limit the effective use of these instruments in many Member States.
- In Slovakia, the 2023 and 2024 European Semester analyses underline that absorption capacity of EU funds is among the lowest in the EU and that insufficient quality of public administration and public procurement “holds back the implementation of investment projects and the absorption capacity of EU funds” (European Commission, 2023b; European Commission, 2024).
- The complexity of procedures has delayed drawing EU funds in Slovakia, prompting reforms in public investment management and procurement support for subnational governments (OECD; UCLG, 2023). These combined sources illustrate that key development instruments (EU funds, investment toolkits, PPP frameworks) are often underutilised or used inefficiently in Slovakia.
- The European Committee of the Regions explicitly “regrets the lack of transparent information on the total amount, actual use and overall impact of EU resources available for capacity building of local and regional authorities” and notes that funding for capacity building was not fully used under the previous financial framework (European Committee of the Regions, 2020). The IMF Public Investment Management Assessment for Slovakia also identifies weaknesses in project preparation, appraisal and selection that reduce the efficiency of public investment (IMF, 2019).

References

European Committee of the Regions. (2020). *Opinion of the European Committee of the Regions – Improving administrative capacity of local and regional authorities to strengthen investments and structural reforms in 2021–2027*. Official Journal of the European Union, C 79/25. European Union.

European Commission. (2023). *2023 country report – Slovakia* (European Semester). European Commission.

European Commission. (2023). *Report on the outcome of 2021–2027 cohesion policy programming* (Cohesion report background document). European Commission.

European Commission. (2024). *Recommendation for a Council recommendation on Slovakia’s 2024 national reform programme* (SWD(2024) 625 final). European Commission.

- European Investment Bank. (2023). *Investment report 2022/2023: Transforming for competitiveness and cohesion*. European Investment Bank.
- European Investment Bank. (2023). *The state of local infrastructure investment in Europe – EIB municipalities survey 2022–2023*. European Investment Bank.
- International Monetary Fund. (2019). *Slovak Republic: Technical assistance report – Public investment management assessment* (IMF Country Report No. 19/330). International Monetary Fund.
- OECD. (2012). *Recommendation of the Council on principles for public governance of public-private partnerships*. OECD. (Updated 2024)
- OECD. (2016). *Making the most of public investment in the Eastern Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2018). *Responding to the infrastructure challenge: Subnational public-private partnerships*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2022). *2022 synthesis report – World Observatory on Subnational Government Finance and Investment (SNG-WOFI)*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2022). *Subnational finance and investment*. OECD.
- OECD. (2023). *Government at a glance 2023*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Preparing for demographic change in the Banská Bystrica region, Slovak Republic: Adapting multi-level governance, public finance and infrastructure investment to demographic change*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD & UCLG. (2023). *Subnational government structure and finance: Country profile – Slovak Republic (SNG-WOFI)*. OECD Publishing.

G. Environmental & Infrastructure Challenges

Challenges

1. Economic development depends on resilient, sustainable infrastructure.
2. Growing environmental pressures (pollution, heat islands, floods).
3. Insufficient infrastructure integration across mobility, energy, water, and land use.
4. Climate adaptation insufficiently embedded in economic strategies.

Risks

1. Increased operational costs and reduced productivity.
2. Infrastructure failures affecting businesses and supply chains.
3. Lower quality of life diminishes attractiveness for talent and investors.

Actions Needed

- Integrate climate adaptation and resilience measures into economic planning.
- Invest in sustainable mobility and green infrastructure.
- Promote circular economy and revitalization of abandoned urban sites.

Proofs:

Challenge G.1 “*Economic development depends on resilient, sustainable infrastructure.*”

- Across the EU, recent climate-risk and infrastructure assessments underline that long-term competitiveness depends on the reliability and resilience of transport, energy, water and digital networks. The European Climate Risk Assessment (EUCRA) highlights that climate risks to infrastructure and the economy are already “accelerating” and that

cascading failures in energy, transport and water networks can have system-wide economic impacts if resilience is not strengthened (EEA, 2024a).

- Complementary EEA indicators show that weather- and climate-related extremes caused an estimated EUR 822 billion in economic losses in the EU between 1980 and 2024, with over EUR 208 billion (around a quarter of the total) occurring in just the four years 2021-2024 – and with the last four years all among the five costliest on record (EEA, 2025a). These figures confirm that infrastructure resilience and climate-proofing are now core conditions for safeguarding productivity and investment in European regions.
- For Slovakia, OECD and EU assessments emphasise that modern, sustainable infrastructure is both a bottleneck and a key lever for development. The OECD Environmental Performance Review (EPR) finds that Slovakia faces “significant investment needs” in environmental infrastructure, particularly wastewater treatment, water supply and flood protection, and notes that absorption of EU structural funds for environmental infrastructure and climate adaptation during 2014-2020 was relatively low compared with allocations (OECD, 2024a).
- Environmental infrastructure spending in Slovakia relies heavily on EU funds and that tariffs in water services often do not recover costs, limiting the ability to maintain and upgrade systems (OECD, 2024a). The European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS) briefing on Slovakia’s climate action strategy also points out that substantial Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) resources have had to be directed to low-carbon transport and grid modernisation, reflecting the scale of infrastructure gaps that directly condition economic and industrial development (EPRS, 2025)

Challenge G.2 “*Growing environmental pressures (pollution, heat islands, floods).*”

- EU-wide evidence shows mounting environmental pressures from pollution and climate change. The EEA notes that Europe is the fastest-warming continent and is already experiencing more frequent and intense heatwaves, droughts and floods, with associated impacts on health, ecosystems and urban environments (EEA, 2024b). Its analyses of climate impacts and adaptation stress rising flood risks, growing heat stress in cities and persistent air-pollution problems in many regions, all of which increase costs for health systems and firms while reducing labour productivity (EEA, 2024b).
- The EEA data on economic losses from weather- and climate-related extremes show a sharp recent increase in damage, consistent with more severe flooding and storms across EU Member States (EEA, 2025a).
- In Slovakia, the OECD EPR documents that environmental pressures remain high in several dimensions. Air-quality indicators show population exposure to fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) clearly above the WHO guideline and above the OECD Europe average, implying significant health and productivity losses (OECD, 2024a).
- The ecological status of water bodies is often below EU targets in Slovakia, many contaminated sites still require remediation, and a large share of municipal waste continues to be landfilled, with limited progress on circular-economy measures (OECD, 2024a).

- Biodiversity indicators show that a majority of assessed habitats and species are in poor or bad conservation status, reducing ecosystem resilience to climate change and flood hazards (OECD, 2024a).

Challenge G.3 “*Insufficient infrastructure integration across mobility, energy, water, and land use.*”

- European climate-risk work emphasises that infrastructure systems are highly interconnected, so fragmented planning across sectors magnifies vulnerabilities. EUCRA – as summarised by the MIRACA project – underlines that Europe’s critical infrastructure across transport, energy, communication and water systems is increasingly exposed to heat, floods, droughts and landslides, and that because these systems form networks, failure in one node can propagate across the system (EEA, 2024a).
- There is significant “adaptation deficit” in ageing infrastructure, calling for integrated, system-wide adaptation and regulatory stress-testing rather than sector-by-sector fixes (EEA, 2024a).
- EEA indicators on climate-related losses similarly conclude that managing risks requires comprehensive, cross-sector approaches to land use, water management, energy systems and transport, because climate hazards such as heavy precipitation or drought typically affect several infrastructures at once (EEA, 2025a).
- In Slovakia, several strands of evidence point to insufficient integration across infrastructure sectors and land-use planning. The EPRS briefing notes that while the national recovery and resilience plan allocates significant funds to low-carbon transport, building renovation, grid modernisation and nature-based adaptation, these investments are organised through separate components and require better coordination to form coherent regional transition strategies (EPRS, 2025).
- The OECD EPR finds that environmental infrastructure – notably wastewater treatment and flood protection – lags behind EU policy objectives, that water services often lack cost-recovery pricing, and that many EU environmental law infringements concern water and waste, signalling governance and planning gaps across sectors (OECD, 2024a).

Challenge G.4 “*Climate adaptation insufficiently embedded in economic strategies.*”

- At EU level, both the 2021 EU Adaptation Strategy and EUCRA highlight that climate adaptation is not advancing at the speed required to match escalating risks. The EEA’s climate-risk assessment concludes that many climate risks have already reached critical levels and that the pace of adaptation is insufficient, particularly in sectors such as infrastructure, health and ecosystems which underpin economic activity (EEA, 2024a).
- The EEA’s indicator on economic losses from weather- and climate-related extremes further notes that despite increasing losses – with the last four years among the costliest since 1980 – adaptation actions and investments remain fragmented, and calls for integrated adaptation strategies that are fully embedded into fiscal, investment and sectoral policies (EEA, 2025a).
- For Slovakia, EU and OECD sources provide direct evidence that adaptation is not yet fully mainstreamed in economic and investment strategies. The EPRS briefing reports

that the Council’s 2024 country-specific recommendations explicitly call for “stronger climate adaptation measures, including nature-based solutions, and their integration into relevant national policies”, indicating that current policies do not sufficiently embed adaptation (EPRS, 2025).

- A proposed climate law, which would have set binding net-zero pathways and created an accountability framework, has stalled, and experts rate Slovakia’s forward-looking climate policy as “very low” in the Climate Change Performance Index (EPRS, 2025)
- The OECD EPR similarly concludes that Slovakia is “not on a path to climate neutrality”, urges adoption of net-zero legislation with sectoral pathways and calls for more effective use of EU funds for green investment and climate adaptation, including restoration of ecosystems to maintain the land-use carbon sink (OECD, 2024a).

Risk G.1 “Increased operational costs and reduced productivity.”

- EU-wide data show that climate and environmental pressures are already generating substantial and rising economic costs, which directly translate into higher operating costs and lower productivity. EEA indicators estimate that weather- and climate-related extremes caused about EUR 822 billion of economic losses in the EU during 1980-2024, with more than EUR 208 billion (25%) occurring in 2021-2024 alone; statistical analysis finds a clear upward trend in losses, and recent years cluster among the costliest since 1980 (EEA, 2025a). These events include floods, storms, heatwaves and droughts that disrupt production, damage infrastructure and reduce labour productivity, especially during extreme heat. Additional analyses show that extreme weather events in recent summers have caused EU-wide short-term losses equivalent to several tenths of a percent of GDP, with indirect impacts via disrupted supply chains and commuting (EEA, 2024b; EEA, 2025a).
- In Slovakia, environmental and climate-related costs compound existing structural weaknesses. The OECD EPR underlines that poor air quality imposes a measurable health burden and labour-productivity loss, that ecosystem degradation entails high foregone ecosystem-service values, and that delayed remediation of contaminated sites constrains land redevelopment (OECD, 2024a).
- The EPRS briefing stresses that Slovakia remains highly dependent on fossil fuels in its energy mix and that the draft updated National Energy and Climate Plan (NECP) sets a renewable-energy target for 2030 well below the country’s indicative EU contribution, implying higher exposure to volatile energy prices and transition risks (EPRS, 2025).

Risk G.2 “Infrastructure failures affecting businesses and supply chains.”

- European climate-risk assessments point to a rising probability of infrastructure disruptions with cascading effects on the economy. EUCRA and related EEA work highlight that Europe’s critical infrastructure networks – especially transport, energy and water – are increasingly exposed to extreme heat, droughts, floods and storms, and that because these infrastructures are interconnected, disruptions in one part of a network can propagate across borders and sectors (EEA, 2024a)
- The ageing assets and the adaptation deficit create a risk of systemic failures, particularly during compound events, threatening the continuity of services that firms and supply chains depend on (EEA, 2024a; EEA, 2025a). The EEA economic-loss

indicators further show that climate-related extremes increasingly affect transport and energy infrastructure, with associated losses in logistics, trade and industrial output (EEA, 2025a).

- In Slovakia, the OECD EPR documents that environmental infrastructure – notably wastewater treatment, flood-protection structures and remediation of contaminated sites – is incomplete or outdated in many areas, and that compliance gaps with EU water and waste directives persist (OECD, 2024a). These weaknesses heighten the risk that extreme rainfall or pollution incidents disrupt local services, impose emergency costs on municipalities and firms, and delay development projects.
- The EPRS climate-strategy briefing also notes that Slovakia has had to rapidly invest in energy-system security (e.g. new gas interconnectors and grid upgrades) in response to supply shocks, illustrating how infrastructure vulnerabilities can translate into economic and financial risks (EPRS, 2025).

Risk G.3 “*Lower quality of life diminishes attractiveness for talent and investors.*”

- OECD regional well-being work shows that environmental quality, access to services and infrastructure strongly shape both residents’ quality of life and the attractiveness of regions for firms and skilled workers (OECD, 2014; OECD, 2024b).
- Regions with better environmental conditions, reliable transport and energy infrastructure, and strong public services tend to achieve higher levels of perceived well-being and attract more investment, while places with high pollution, congestion and environmental risk see out-migration and weaker investor interest (OECD, 2014; OECD, 2024b).
- The EEA similarly links climate change, air pollution and environmental degradation to declining quality of life and heightened risks for health and livelihoods, warning that unchecked climate risks threaten Europe’s prosperity, security and quality of life (EEA, 2024b).
- In Slovakia, the OECD EPR reports persistent air-quality problems, significant biodiversity and habitat degradation, and ongoing challenges with waste management and contaminated sites, all of which negatively affect the living environment in many regions (OECD, 2024a).
- The EPRS briefing shows that public concern about climate change is comparatively low – only about 26% of Slovaks see climate change as one of the most serious global problems, versus an EU average of 46% – which may slow efforts to improve environmental quality and resilience (EPRS, 2025).

References

- European Environment Agency. (2024). *European climate risk assessment (EUCRA)*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *Climate change impacts, risks and adaptation in Europe*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2025). *Economic losses from weather- and climate-related extremes in Europe*. European Environment Agency.
- European Parliamentary Research Service. (2025). *Slovakia’s climate action strategy*. European Parliament.

OECD. (2014). *How's life in your region? Measuring regional and local well-being for policy making*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Environmental performance reviews: Slovak Republic 2024*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Regions and cities at a glance 2024*. OECD Publishing.

1.2. Challenges, Problems, Risks and Required Actions in the Social Development of Cities and Regions

The social development of cities and regions is increasingly shaped by complex and interdependent forces that cut across governance, demographics, housing, digitalization, public health, and community dynamics. In rapidly changing urban environments, social challenges no longer appear in isolation; they are embedded in wider economic, spatial, environmental, and technological systems. As a result, effective social policies require a level of coordination and integration that many governance structures are not yet able to provide.

This chapter examines the major obstacles that hinder inclusive and resilient social development across territories. Fragmented governance and weak coordination mechanisms limit the coherence of social, urban, educational, mobility, and digital policies—often resulting in parallel programs, inefficient investments, and limited impact. Persistent social inequalities, including poverty, segregation, and marginalization, continue to undermine social cohesion and the attractiveness of cities and regions. Demographic shifts such as ageing populations, youth outmigration, and labour-market transformations add further pressure on local services, employment structures, and public finances.

Housing affordability represents another critical constraint, as rising living costs and insufficient social housing contribute to overcrowding, homelessness, and exclusion. At the same time, communities face growing challenges related to trust in institutions and meaningful participation in decision-making. The digital divide further reinforces disparities by limiting access to services, education, and employment opportunities for vulnerable groups. Environmental and health-related inequalities—from air pollution to limited access to green spaces—disproportionately affect disadvantaged populations and reduce urban well-being. Finally, increasing exposure to crises, including pandemics, climate-related events, or economic shocks, highlights the need for stronger resilience and inclusive crisis-preparedness systems.

By outlining the key challenges, risks, and required actions across these thematic areas, the chapter provides a comprehensive overview of the conditions necessary to build socially resilient, inclusive, and equitable territories. It emphasizes the importance of integrated governance, data-informed planning, community participation, accessible services, and climate- and health-sensitive policies. Together, these elements form a strategic foundation for addressing complex social issues within functional urban areas and ensuring that no group is left behind in the transition toward sustainable regional development.

A. Governance, Coordination & Policy Integration

Challenges

1. Fragmented governance across institutions responsible for social services, housing, mobility, education and inclusion.
2. Weak coordination hampers coherent social strategies, similar to fragmentation seen in digital and spatial policies.

3. Rigid administrative borders prevent responses aligned with functional urban areas, where many social problems occur.

Risks

1. Inefficient use of resources and duplication of programs.
2. Social inequalities deepen when responsibilities are unclear or not aligned.
3. Inability to respond to multi-dimensional problems (poverty + housing + mobility + education).

Actions Needed

- Establish cross-sector (social–urban–digital–health–education) coordination platforms.
- Incorporate integrated area development approaches into social policy design.
- Develop inter-municipal cooperation mechanisms at the functional urban area scale.
- Use territorial data, digital twins and smart analytics to support integrated social planning.

Proofs:

See 1.1. *A Governance & Policy Integration*

B. Social Inclusion, Inequalities & Marginalization

Challenges

1. Persistent social inequalities: poverty, segregation, spatial exclusion.
2. Barriers for vulnerable groups (low-income families, migrants, elderly, youth, disabled).
3. Unequal access to housing, healthcare, education, cultural life and public infrastructure.

Risks

1. Formation of segregated neighbourhoods with low social mobility.
2. Social tensions, mistrust toward institutions, rising populism.
3. Reduced productivity, declining urban attractiveness.

Actions Needed

- Implement inclusion programs at neighbourhood scale (education, healthcare access, counselling).
- Support mixed-income and affordable housing development.
- Co-develop social initiatives with NGOs, communities and local residents.
- Provide community hubs that strengthen interaction and social cohesion.

Proofs:

Challenge B.1 “*Cities and regions must adapt to technological, demographic, and climate shifts that directly affect economic development.*”

- Across the OECD, regional policy reviews underline that technological change, demographic ageing and climate risks are now simultaneous structural drivers of local development. The OECD report *Job Creation and Local Economic Development 2024: The Geography of Generative AI* shows that exposure to generative AI and other digital technologies varies strongly across regions, often widening existing gaps in productivity and labour shortages between urban and rural areas (OECD 2024a). This implies that cities and regions must continuously adapt skills strategies, industrial policy and business services to technology-driven shifts in local labour demand.

- Demographic trends in the EU add further pressure. Eurostat reports that on 1 January 2024, 21.6 % of the EU population was aged 65+ and the median age reached 44.7 years, up in nearly all member states over the last decade (Eurostat 2025a).
- The IMF's selected issues paper on Slovakia concludes that with low fertility, net outward migration and rising life expectancy, Slovakia's working-age population will decline over the long run, creating a "headwind" to growth and requiring proactive labour-market and innovation policies (IMF 2024). This is direct evidence that demographic change is altering labour availability and skills in both the EU and Slovakia.
- The climate change is already affecting economic activity. The European Environment Agency's Climate Change Impacts, Risks and Adaptation overview and the first European Climate Risk Assessment (EUCRA) identify 36 priority climate risks that threaten Europe's infrastructure, energy and food security, water resources, financial stability and health, and note that many risks have already reached critical levels (EEA 2024a; EEA 2024b).
- Recent climate-related disasters illustrate the macro-economic dimension: in 2024, Europe experienced its most widespread floods in more than a decade, affecting around 30 % of river systems, with more than €18 billion in damages and over 400 000 people impacted (Copernicus/WMO 2025; European State of the Climate 2025).
- The data show that technological, demographic and climate shifts are no longer separate policy topics but concurrent structural forces that directly shape the economic prospects of EU and Slovak regions, requiring adaptive territorial development strategies (OECD 2024a; IMF 2024; EEA 2024b).

Challenge B.2 *"Rigid planning tools reduce capacity to adapt economic development strategies to new technologies and labour-market shifts."*

- The OECD report *The Governance of Land Use in OECD Countries: Policy Analysis and Recommendations* documents that land-use planning systems in many countries are based on detailed, legally binding zoning plans that are revised infrequently and are often fragmented across levels of government (OECD 2017a). This rigidity can slow responses to new housing needs, environmental priorities and evolving economic activities, and the report explicitly calls for more flexible and better-coordinated land-use policies.
- For EU member states, including Slovakia, this has direct economic consequences. The OECD notes that land-use decisions have important impacts on economic productivity and that overly restrictive or outdated zoning can constrain the development of new industrial facilities, logistics centres or mixed-use innovation spaces (OECD 2017a). In a context where technological change and labour-market needs evolve rapidly (e.g. for e-mobility, green technologies or logistics), such rigidity reduces the capacity of cities and regions to reorient development strategies and align infrastructure and land availability with new demands.
- Integrated spatial planning approaches promoted in EU and OECD guidance emphasise strategic, adaptive frameworks (e.g. functional-area planning, performance-based zoning) as good practice for dealing with uncertainty in technology, demographics and climate (OECD 2017a; EEA 2024a). The very need for these reforms confirms the

underlying problem your challenge highlights: traditional, rigid planning tools hinder timely adjustment of economic development strategies to new technologies and labour-market shifts.

Challenge B.3 “*Demographic changes, including ageing and migration, alter labour availability and skills.*”

- Eurostat’s demographic statistics for 2024–2025 show that the EU’s population is ageing rapidly: people aged 65+ account for more than one-fifth of the population, the share of those 80+ rose from 3.8 % to 6.1 % between 2004 and 2024, and the working-age share (15–64) has declined (Eurostat 2025a; Eurostat 2025b). These trends imply fewer workers per retiree and tighter labour markets in many regions, with significant territorial disparities.
- For Slovakia, the IMF’s 2024 selected issues paper *The Impact of Aging on Growth* finds that the working-age population is expected to fall while the share of older people rises, due to low fertility, outward migration and longer life expectancy, and concludes that this will weigh on growth unless countered by labour-market and innovation policies (IMF 2024). The IMF’s 2025 Article IV report adds that long-term fiscal sustainability will also be under pressure, underscoring the need to raise productivity and labour-force participation (IMF 2025).
- Migration further reshapes labour supply and skills. Eurostat’s recent migration releases show large inflows into the EU overall, but with net outward migration or weaker inflows in some Central and Eastern European countries, contributing to regional labour shortages and skills imbalances (Eurostat 2025c). Combined with the ageing patterns above, this provides clear evidence that demographic change – both ageing and migration – is already altering labour availability and skills in Slovakia and across the EU, with direct implications for territorial economic development.

Challenge B.4 “*Climate risks threaten infrastructure and economic activity.*”

- The EEA’s European Climate Risk Assessment identifies climate risks that directly threaten infrastructure networks (transport, energy, water) and economic activity, warning that many risks have reached critical levels and could become catastrophic without urgent adaptation (EEA 2024b). It highlights increased frequency and severity of floods, droughts, heatwaves and storms across Europe, and notes that these hazards can disrupt supply chains, damage assets and reduce productivity.
- The European State of the Climate 2024 report, summarised by the Copernicus Climate Change Service and media analyses, shows that in 2024 Europe experienced its most widespread flooding in more than a decade, affecting 30 % of river systems, killing 335 people and causing over €18 billion in losses (Copernicus/WMO 2025). Other EEA work on Europe’s environment stresses that climate change and environmental degradation increasingly threaten natural resources crucial for economic security, especially through water stress, biodiversity loss and soil degradation (EEA 2025).
- For an export-oriented, industrial economy like Slovakia’s – with significant exposure in automotive and energy-intensive sectors – these patterns imply heightened vulnerability of infrastructure, supply chains and economic activity to climate-related disruptions (IMF 2025; OECD 2024b). This directly supports your statement that

climate risks threaten infrastructure and economic activity across the EU and in Slovakia.

Risk B.1 *“Economies become vulnerable to shocks (climate, financial, demographic).”*

- EU-level analyses show that climate, financial and demographic shocks increasingly interact. The EUCRA report emphasises that climate risks pose threats not only to ecosystems but also to energy and food security, water resources, critical infrastructure and financial stability (EEA 2024b). At the same time, Eurostat and Eurostat’s Demography of Europe 2025 highlight structural ageing, with rising old-age dependency ratios that will strain pension and health systems and constrain growth (Eurostat 2025a; Eurostat 2025b).
- For Slovakia, the IMF’s 2024 and 2025 reports underline vulnerabilities from both demographics and external shocks. Ageing is projected to subtract from growth, while the highly open, manufacturing-based economy is exposed to external demand and energy-price shocks (IMF 2024; IMF 2025). (elibrary.imf.org) In parallel, climate-risk assessments show Central and Eastern Europe facing increasing drought and heat-related risks, with potential for significant impacts on agriculture, energy and infrastructure (EEA 2024b).

Risk B.2 *“Slow adaptation discourages investors and reduces entrepreneurial activity.”*

- Structural and climate policy uncertainty is recognised as a deterrent to investment. OECD work on climate policy uncertainty demonstrates empirically that higher climate-policy uncertainty is associated with lower corporate investment, especially in carbon-intensive sectors, because firms face difficulty evaluating future returns (Bachmann et al. 2022). If adaptation and transition policies are slow or inconsistent, this uncertainty increases, discouraging investors from committing capital to long-lived assets.
- In the EU context, the OECD’s most recent surveys of the European Union and euro area argue that productivity growth and the net-zero transition require decisive structural reforms and clear policy signals; otherwise, weak growth prospects and policy uncertainty weigh on private investment and innovation (OECD 2025).
- For Slovakia specifically, the IMF’s 2025 Article IV consultation stresses the importance of safeguarding a credible fiscal framework and accelerating structural reforms – including green and digital transitions – to attract higher-value-added investment and sustain convergence (IMF 2025).
- In this light, slow adaptation in areas such as land-use planning, skills policy, climate resilience and innovation support can be expected to discourage investors and reduce entrepreneurial activity, particularly in regions already facing demographic and competitiveness challenges.

Risk B.3 *“Inflexible zoning hampers emerging industries, innovation spaces, and brownfield redevelopment.”*

- OECD comparative work on land-use planning shows that traditional zoning systems – based on narrowly defined land-use categories, high detail and infrequent revisions – can impede the emergence of new economic activities and mixed-use environments (OECD 2017a). (OECD) The report notes that such rigidity may limit the supply of

suitable sites for innovative firms, new production facilities, urban logistics or research and development spaces, particularly in growing metropolitan areas.

- Brownfield redevelopment is a specific area where rigid planning and institutional fragmentation create obstacles. EU and national studies on brownfields highlight that redeveloping former industrial or military sites can significantly contribute to urban regeneration and economic revitalisation, but complex planning rules, unclear property rights and limited coordination often delay projects (European Commission 2019; Urban Agenda for the EU 2024). For many Central and Eastern European cities, large brownfield areas remain underused, despite their potential to host new industries and innovation districts.
- Given Slovakia's legacy of industrial sites and the need to attract higher-value-added investment, these findings imply that inflexible zoning and planning frameworks can hamper the creation of emerging industries, innovation spaces and brownfield redevelopment in Slovak and other EU cities. More adaptive and integrated spatial-economic planning is therefore a precondition for exploiting these opportunities (OECD 2017a; Urban Agenda for the EU 2024).

References

- Bachmann, R., et al. (2022). Measuring and assessing the effects of climate policy uncertainty. *OECD Economics Department Working Papers*, No. 1707. OECD Publishing.
- Copernicus Climate Change Service & World Meteorological Organization. (2025). *European state of the climate 2024*. Copernicus Climate Change Service; World Meteorological Organization.
- European Commission. (2019). *Brownfield redevelopment in the EU – Conference report*. European Commission.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *Climate change impacts, risks and adaptation*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *European climate risk assessment (EUCRA)* (EEA Report No. 01/2024). European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2025). *Europe's environment 2025: Resources at risk*. European Environment Agency.
- Eurostat. (2025). *Population structure and ageing. Statistics Explained*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2025). *Demography of Europe – 2025 edition*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- International Monetary Fund. (2024). *Slovak Republic: Selected issues – The impact of aging on growth* (IMF Country Report No. 24/76). International Monetary Fund.
- International Monetary Fund. (2025). *Slovak Republic: 2025 Article IV consultation – Staff report*. International Monetary Fund.
- OECD. (2017). *The governance of land use in OECD countries: Policy analysis and recommendations*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Job creation and local economic development 2024: The geography of generative AI*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *OECD economic surveys: Slovak Republic 2024*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2025). *Economic surveys: European Union and Euro Area 2025*. OECD Publishing.

Urban Agenda for the EU. (2024). *Funding and financing guide for brownfield redevelopment*.
Urban Agenda for the EU.

C. Demographic Change & Labour Market Transformation

Challenges

1. Ageing population increases demands on care and accessibility.
2. Youth outmigration from smaller towns destabilizes local labour markets.
3. Skills mismatch due to technological change and digitalization.

Risks

1. Labour shortages in key sectors (healthcare, education, public transport).
2. Decreasing tax base undermines social infrastructure funding.
3. Growing intergenerational inequality and dependency ratios.

Actions Needed

- Develop lifelong learning and reskilling programs.
- Invest in healthcare workforce and elderly-care-oriented infrastructure.
- Support youth retention through affordable housing, mobility and job creation.
- Encourage remote work and hybrid work hubs to keep residents in smaller towns.

Proofs:

Challenge C.1 *“Ageing population increases demands on care and accessibility.”*

- Across the EU, demographic indicators clearly show that ageing is accelerating and directly increasing the demand for care and accessible services. On 1 January 2024, 21.6 % of the EU population was already aged 65+, and the old-age dependency ratio is projected to almost double from 33.9 % in 2024 to 59.7 % by 2100, meaning fewer than two working-age adults per older person (Eurostat, 2024a).
- Eurostat and the European Parliament’s analysis of EU population projections similarly underline that the EU’s old-age dependency ratio will approach 60 % by 2100, with a shrinking total population if migration is not maintained (European Parliament, 2024).
- In Slovakia, the OECD notes that the share of the working-age population is expected to shrink by about one fifth over the next 30 years, with ageing-related costs projected to rise much more strongly than in most other EU countries (OECD, 2024a).
- Population ageing in Slovakia will simultaneously increase demand for healthcare (more older patients) and reduce the supply of health workers as many doctors and nurses retire, creating strong replacement demand (Páleník et al., 2021).
- At EU level, Health at a Glance: Europe 2024 and the accompanying Commission–OECD communication emphasise that healthy ageing and health-workforce shortages are now central challenges, with around 1.2 million doctors, nurses and midwives missing in 2022 (OECD; European Commission, 2024; European parliament, 2025).

Challenge C.2 *“Youth outmigration from smaller towns destabilizes local labour markets.”*

- The OECD’s report on demographic change in the Banská Bystrica Region (a predominantly rural and mountainous region in central Slovakia) documents sustained population decline of 6.8 % between 2000 and 2023 and a negative youth net migration rate of –0.4 % in Central Slovakia in 2022 (OECD, 2024b). The report shows how young

people leave smaller municipalities for larger cities or abroad, reducing the local supply of skilled labour and making it harder to maintain services and economic activity. It also describes a “scissor effect”: rising per-capita costs for services such as education and elderly care, combined with falling tax revenues as the working-age population shrinks (OECD, 2024b).

- Comparable OECD work on other European regions (for example Campania in Italy) confirms that accelerating youth outmigration from peripheral and rural areas, together with ageing, leads to labour-market tightening, skills shortages and declining entrepreneurship outside the main urban centres (OECD, 2024c). This demonstrates that for Slovakia as well as for other EU regions, youth outmigration from smaller towns erodes local labour pools, undermines the viability of local businesses and destabilises local labour markets.

Challenge C.3 “*Skills mismatch due to technological change and digitalization.*”

- OECD and EU analyses highlight that digitalisation and the green transition are major drivers of changing skill needs across European labour markets. The OECD report Skills for a Digital World shows that digital technologies are changing how work is done and increasing demand for generic and advanced ICT skills across a wide range of occupations (OECD, 2016). The EU-funded SkillMeeT project summarises existing evidence and concludes that digitalisation and the green transition are already generating skills gaps and skills shortages in many European countries (SkillMeeT Consortium, 2025).
- A recent JRC analysis on workers’ participation in digital skills training notes that digitalisation “reshapes the modern workforce” and stresses that mismatches between required and actual digital skills are emerging, calling for more systematic training policies (European Commission – JRC, 2024). Comparative research on skills mismatch in EU countries also finds substantial mismatches between workers’ qualifications and job requirements, with technological change identified as a key driver (Golińska, Prażmowska, 2025).
- For Slovakia, labour-market information compiled by EURES reports that regions such as Banská Bystrica show a significant mismatch between the skills and occupations in demand and those offered by jobseekers, especially as automation and restructuring affect local industry (EURES, 2024; EURES, 2025).

Risk C.1 “*Labour shortages in key sectors (healthcare, education, public transport).*”

- In the health sector, the Health at a Glance: Europe 2024 report and its Commission–OECD summary identify chronic health-workforce shortages across Europe, with an estimated shortfall of around 1.2 million doctors, nurses and midwives in 2022, driven by population ageing, rising demand for care and an ageing workforce (OECD; European Commission, 2024; Deutsche Sozialversicherung EU, 2025).
- For Slovakia, Páleník et al. show that ageing doctors and nurses combined with rising numbers of older patients will create strong replacement demand and potential shortages in health personnel up to 2030 (Páleník et al., 2021; Employment Institute, 2024).
- In education, the European Commission’s Education and Training Monitor places a specific spotlight on teacher shortages across EU Member States, highlighting that

shortages are now a widespread concern in many education sectors (European Commission, 2023a). (ETUCE) Country analysis for Slovakia notes declining attractiveness of the teaching profession and shortages of STEM teachers (European Commission, 2023b; 2025).

- For transport and related services, the EURES report on labour shortages and surpluses 2024 identifies significant shortages across the EU in transport and storage, particularly for drivers and mobile plant operators (European Labour Authority, 2025).
- The EURES country page for Slovakia confirms that drivers and mobile plant operators are among the occupational groups with the highest shortage of workers (EURES, 2024).

Risk C.2 *“Decreasing tax base undermines social infrastructure funding.”*

- Banská Bystrica region case study provides concrete evidence that ageing and outmigration can erode the tax base needed to finance social infrastructure. The OECD describes a “scissor effect”: rising per-capita spending needs for education, healthcare and elderly care, combined with declining revenues from personal income tax as the working-age population shrinks (OECD, 2024b). The same report notes that demographic decline and ageing “strain local budgets and service delivery systems”, particularly in small municipalities.
- At national level, the 2024 Ageing Report – Slovak Republic Country Fiche projects a marked increase in age-related public expenditure in Slovakia over the coming decades and highlights risks to the long-term sustainability of public finances (European Commission, 2024a). The OECD study Tackling the Challenges of Population Ageing in the Slovak Republic similarly concludes that ageing will put pressure on potential growth and living standards, with rising pension, health and long-term care costs requiring fiscal and structural reforms (OECD, 2024a).
- At EU level, Eurostat and the European Parliament show that a rising old-age dependency ratio means relatively fewer taxpayers financing more beneficiaries of pensions and health care (Eurostat, 2024a; European Parliament, 2024).
- The EBRD warns that ageing populations will reduce annual GDP-per-capita growth by about 0.4 percentage points on average in emerging Europe through 2050, implying weaker revenue growth and mounting spending pressures (EBRD, 2025).
- This evidence underpins the risk that a shrinking and ageing tax base in Slovakia and across the EU undermines the funding of social infrastructure (schools, health and care facilities, public transport), unless fiscal and labour-market adjustments are made.

Risk C.3 *“Growing intergenerational inequality and dependency ratios.”*

- Eurostat’s population projections show that the EU’s old-age dependency ratio is expected to nearly double from about 33 % in 2022 to almost 60 % by 2100, with the total age-dependency ratio rising from 56.8 % in 2024 to 83.9 % by 2100 (Eurostat, 2024a).
- A shrinking working-age population will have to support a growing number of older people and children, increasing the relative burden on younger cohorts. The OECD warns that, without reforms, countries with ageing populations are set for weaker

income growth, and explicitly notes fairness concerns, as younger generations will bear greater financial burdens to sustain pension and health systems (OECD, 2025a).

- The EBRD’s analysis of ageing in “emerging Europe” concludes that demographic shifts will substantially reduce GDP-per-capita growth and risk countries “getting old before they get rich”, unless retirement ages are raised and labour-market participation increases (EBRD, 2025).
- In Slovakia, the Ageing Report country fiche and OECD ageing study both emphasise that, without policy change, the combination of higher age-related spending and slower potential growth will put pressure on younger taxpayers and on the adequacy of future benefits (European Commission, 2024a; OECD, 2024a).
- Moreover, EU and national debates on teacher shortages and pension spending in education illustrate how a growing share of public budgets devoted to pensions can crowd out investment in younger generations’ education and opportunities (European Commission, 2023a; European Parliament, 2024; OECD, 2025b).

References

- Deutsche Sozialversicherung EU. (2025). *OECD study highlights key health challenges*. Deutsche Sozialversicherung EU.
- EBRD. (2025). *Ageing populations will lead to lower living standards, warns study*. European Bank for Reconstruction and Development.
- Employment Institute. (2024). *30 graphs on ageing and the health workforce in Slovakia*. Employment Institute.
- European Commission. (2023). *Education and training monitor 2023 – Country report: Slovakia*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2023). *Education and training monitor 2023 – Overview report*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2024). *2024 ageing report – Country fiche: Slovak Republic*. European Commission.
- European Commission, Joint Research Centre. (2024). *Understanding workers’ participation in digital skills training*. European Commission.
- European Commission & OECD. (2024). *Health at a glance: Europe 2024 – Press release and fact sheet*. European Commission.
- European Labour Authority. (2025). *EURES report on labour shortages and surpluses 2024*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Labour Authority, Cambridge Econometrics, & Verian Group. (2025). *Labour shortages and surpluses in Europe 2024 – Summary*. European Labour Authority.
- European Parliament. (2024). *EU population projections*. European Parliamentary Research Service.
- European Parliament. (2025). *Healthcare in the EU: Addressing urgent labour shortages and ensuring quality jobs*. European Parliamentary Research Service.
- Eurostat. (2024). *Population structure and ageing. Statistics Explained*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- EURES. (2024). *Labour market information: Slovakia*. European Commission.
- EURES. (2025). *Labour shortages and surpluses in Europe – Dashboard 2024*. European Commission; European Labour Authority.

- Golińska-Prażmowska, M. (2025). Discrepancy of the skills: A comparative study of three EU countries. *Journal of Ageing and Regional Policy*.
- OECD. (2016). *Skills for a digital world*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Health at a glance: Europe 2024*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Preparing for demographic change in the Banská Bystrica region, Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Preparing for demographic change in Campania, Italy*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Tackling the challenges of population ageing in the Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2025). *Without remedy, countries with ageing populations are set for weaker income growth, says OECD*. OECD.
- Páleník, M., et al. (2021). *The impact of aging on the health care sector in Slovakia: Forecast of demand and supply until 2030*. Institute of Economic Research; Employment Institute.
- SkilmeeT Consortium. (2025). *Skills gaps, skill and labour shortages, and mismatch – Existing evidence (SkiLMeeT D1.1)*. EU Horizon Project SkiLMeeT.

D. Housing Affordability & Quality of Living

Challenges

1. Rising housing costs in urban centres; underinvestment in social and rental housing.
2. Poor energy performance and outdated building stock in many regions.
3. Speculative development and insufficient regulation.

Risks

1. Overcrowding and homelessness.
2. Gentrification pushing vulnerable groups out of central areas.
3. High energy costs increasing social vulnerability.

Actions Needed

- Expand affordable housing programs and inclusionary zoning.
- Renovate old housing stock with energy-saving measures (link social & climate goals).
- Regulate short-term rentals and speculative ownership where needed.
- Support cooperative, community-led, and municipally owned housing models.

Proofs:

Challenge D.1 “Rising housing costs in urban centres; underinvestment in social and rental housing.”

- Across the OECD and the EU, real house prices have increased much faster than incomes, particularly in large cities. OECD data show that real house prices have risen by more than 40 % on average across OECD countries over the last decade, with many households facing severe housing cost burdens (OECD, 2024a).
- Eurostat’s Housing in Europe – 2024 edition reports that house prices in the EU increased by 48 % between 2010 and 2023, while rents grew more slowly, and that households on average spent almost 20 % of their disposable income on housing in 2023, with much higher shares for renters at market price (EUROSTAT, 2024a). These trends confirm that housing costs are rising rapidly and that affordability is a growing concern, especially in urban labour-market centres.

- In Slovakia, the OECD Economic Survey and the companion paper Enhancing the efficiency, inclusiveness and environmental sustainability of housing in the Slovak Republic conclude that “housing affordability has deteriorated in the past decade”, with house prices increasing faster than incomes and with pronounced pressures in Bratislava and other urban areas (OECD, 2024b; OECD, 2024c). The same OECD work highlights structural constraints on new construction (land-use regulation, lengthy permitting) and notes that the housing market is highly ownership-oriented, with a small and segmented rental sector and a very limited stock of social housing (OECD, 2024b). This is echoed by Slovak research on the “long-term unfavourable development of rental housing” and the financialisation of the housing sector, which documents a low share of rental dwellings and insufficient public support for social rental housing (Spirková; Golej, 2025).
- At European level, the OECD affordable housing database and topic work emphasise that social rental housing plays a key role in improving affordability for vulnerable households but has been under strain in many countries, with insufficient new construction and growing waiting lists (OECD, 2024a). Eurostat’s analysis of housing expenditure and the 9th Overview of Housing Exclusion in Europe 2024 similarly underline a worsening shortage of affordable housing and rising rents in many European cities (FEANTSA; Abbé Pierre Foundation, 2024; EUROSTAT, 2024b). Together, these data provide strong evidence that rising housing costs, combined with underinvestment in social and rental housing, are a major structural challenge in the EU and in Slovakia’s urban centres.

Challenge D.2 “Poor energy performance and outdated building stock in many regions.”

- The EU building stock is both old and energy-intensive. The European Commission’s EU Building Stock Observatory (BSO) shows that buildings are responsible for around 40 % of final energy consumption and 36 % of energy-related greenhouse gas emissions in the EU, and that a large share of residential buildings were constructed before modern energy-performance requirements, resulting in poor insulation and inefficient heating systems (European Commission, 2024a). Analytical work based on the BSO indicates that renovation rates remain low and that a significant proportion of buildings still fall into the lowest energy-performance classes (BPIE, 2024).
- A comprehensive European Building Stock Analysis for EU-27+UK finds that most residential floor area is in buildings erected before 1980, often with poor envelopes and old heating systems, leading to high space-heating demand and considerable energy-saving potential (Eurac Research, 2021). A recent EU-wide modelling study on heating energy demand confirms that the existing building stock requires substantial energy for space heating, reinforcing the case for deep renovation as a climate and social policy priority (Energy and Buildings, 2023). The EU’s Renovation Wave strategy and the revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) explicitly respond to this problem, aiming to double annual renovation rates and upgrade 35 million buildings by 2030 (European Commission, 2020; RICS, 2024).
- In Slovakia, the OECD housing paper stresses that poor energy performance of the housing stock contributes to energy poverty and environmental pressures, recommending stricter regulation and targeted financial assistance to incentivise

renovations (OECD, 2024b). The EU Energy Poverty Observatory’s Member State report for Slovakia shows that a non-negligible share of Slovak households report an inability to keep their home adequately warm and/or arrears on utility bills, pointing to the combined effect of low incomes, high energy costs and inefficient housing (EPOV, 2024). These findings confirm that outdated, poorly performing building stock is a structural challenge affecting both climate goals and social outcomes in Slovakia and the wider EU.

Challenge D.3 “*Speculative development and insufficient regulation.*”

- At the European level, the OECD highlights that rising real house prices and financialisation of housing have been fuelled by both structural supply constraints and investment demand, including speculative behaviour in some markets (OECD, 2024a).
- The 9th Overview of Housing Exclusion in Europe 2024 points to “soaring rents, housing prices increasingly out of reach, and a worsening shortage of affordable housing,” noting that investor-driven development, short-term rentals and financial investors contribute to upward pressure on prices in many cities (FEANTSA; Abbé Pierre Foundation, 2024). Eurostat’s housing price index shows that house prices in the EU have risen continuously since 2013, with only a shallow correction in 2022–2023, and reached levels in 2024 more than 45 % above 2010, raising concerns about affordability and speculative dynamics (EUROSTAT, 2025a). The European Central Bank has also warned that the rapid recovery of euro-area housing markets after the recent downturn raises affordability and financial-stability concerns (ECB, 2025).
- In Slovakia, the OECD Economic Survey underlines that strong price growth, tax rules that favour owner-occupation, low recurrent property taxation and fragmented land-use regulation have encouraged housing as an investment asset and constrained the supply response (OECD, 2024c).
- The paper Enhancing the efficiency, inclusiveness and environmental sustainability of housing in the Slovak Republic recommends reforms to land-use planning and building permits and a rebalancing of housing taxation away from transaction taxes and towards recurrent property taxes, precisely to curb speculative behaviour and improve the efficiency of housing supply (OECD, 2024b).
- European policy papers on the EPBD implementation warn that, without adequate social safeguards, regulatory upgrading and renovation requirements can interact with speculative investment to raise rents and prices, putting additional pressure on low-income households in attractive urban areas (IEECP; C40 Cities, 2025).

Risk D.1 “*Overcrowding and homelessness.*”

- Eurostat’s Living conditions in Europe – housing shows that overcrowding remains a significant issue in many EU member states, particularly for low-income households, single-parent families and tenants at market rent (EUROSTAT, 2024c). The same analysis, based on EU-SILC data, identifies high overcrowding rates in Central and Eastern European countries compared to the EU-27 average, with overcrowding strongly associated with housing cost pressures and low incomes (EUROSTAT, 2024c; EU-SILC, 2023). A cross-country study of housing expenditure and overburden in EU

countries confirms that households renting at market price are disproportionately affected by housing cost overburden and overcrowding (Blažek et al., 2023).

- For Slovakia, EU-SILC-based indicators published by the Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic show that a relevant share of households' experience housing deprivation, including overcrowding and inability to afford adequate housing quality (ŠÚ SR, 2023). Eurostat data indicate that nearly a quarter of tenants at market price in Slovakia were housing-cost overburdened in 2023, spending 40 % or more of their disposable income on housing (Eurostat, 2023a). These patterns suggest that a segment of the population is at high risk of overcrowding and precarious housing arrangements.
- Regarding homelessness, the 9th Overview of Housing Exclusion in Europe 2024 documents a record rise in homelessness in many EU countries and notes the absence of sufficient social housing and prevention measures as key drivers (FEANTSA; Abbé Pierre Foundation, 2024). A background chapter for the report explains that new EU-SILC modules will begin to capture homelessness more systematically from 2023 onwards, reflecting the growing policy concern (FEANTSA, 2024). While consistent EU-wide statistical series are still emerging, country studies and NGO reports indicate rising numbers of people experiencing homelessness or living in emergency and temporary accommodation in several member states.
- Given Slovakia's high housing cost burdens among some groups and limited social housing stock (OECD, 2024b), these European trends support the risk that insufficiently regulated housing markets and inadequate social and rental housing can translate into overcrowding and homelessness.

Risk D.2 “Gentrification pushing vulnerable groups out of central areas.”

- Gentrification and displacement are complex processes that are not always fully captured in official statistics, but European evidence points to increasing spatial segregation and displacement pressures in many cities. The Overview of Housing Exclusion in Europe notes that rising prices, tourism-driven demand and financial investors have contributed to making central urban areas increasingly unaffordable for low- and middle-income households, forcing them to move to more peripheral locations (Feantsa; Abbé Pierre Foundation, 2024). Eurostat's Housing in Europe interactive publication shows that tenants at market rent face particularly high housing-cost overburden rates in several EU capitals, a pattern consistent with gentrification pressures in central neighbourhoods (EUROSTAT, 2024a).
- Policy analyses of the revised EPBD and the Renovation Wave highlight that, if renovation costs are passed on to tenants and owner-occupiers without adequate protections, energy upgrades can trigger “renoviction” or indirect displacement of low-income residents from upgraded central areas (IEECP; C40 Cities, 2025). This risk is particularly acute in cities with tight rental markets and rising land values. OECD work on affordable housing emphasises that, in the absence of strong social housing and rental regulation, market-driven redevelopment of inner-city areas tends to favour higher-income groups and can exacerbate socio-spatial inequalities (OECD, 2024a).
- For Slovakia, the combination of rapid house price increases in Bratislava and other dynamic urban areas, limited rental supply, and emphasis on owner-occupation and mortgage subsidies (OECD, 2024c; Spirková; Golej, 2025) suggests that low-income

households and young people are particularly vulnerable to being priced out of centrally located neighbourhoods. While systematic quantitative measures of gentrification in Slovak cities are still limited, the European evidence on how similar dynamics play out in comparable housing systems underpins your risk that gentrification processes may progressively push vulnerable groups away from central, well-served areas in the absence of robust housing and land-use policies.

Risk D.3 “High energy costs increasing social vulnerability.”

- Energy poverty is increasingly recognised in EU and OECD policy as a multi-dimensional phenomenon driven by low incomes, high energy prices and poor energy efficiency in housing. According to a 2022 briefing of the European Parliament, more than 41 million Europeans were unable to keep their homes adequately warm in 2022, with energy poverty particularly affecting low-income households, those in inefficient buildings and residents of Central and Eastern Europe (European Parliament, 2022). The same briefing stresses that energy poverty has severe social impacts, including poor health, social exclusion and educational disadvantages for children.
- EU-SILC-based analyses show that, across the EU, people living in overcrowded dwellings or poor-quality housing are more likely to report problems keeping their home adequately warm and more likely to be in arrears on utility bills (EUROSTAT, 2024c; Karpinska; Šmiech, 2024). A recent comparative study of energy poverty in EU countries using EU-SILC data confirms that low-income and overcrowded households face disproportionately high risks of energy poverty (Karpinska; Šmiech, 2024).
- In Slovakia, the EU Energy Poverty Observatory’s Member State report finds that the country has a mixed performance relative to the EU average, with a significant share of the population reporting an inability to keep their homes adequately warm and experiencing arrears on utility bills (EPOV, 2024).
- The rising energy prices in Slovakia and inefficient housing contribute to deepening energy poverty, and that the share of households affected is higher than in several Western European member states (Dokupilová et al., 2023; Dokupilová, 2025).
- National analyses based on EU-SILC data similarly show that energy expenses constitute a substantial share of household income for low-income quintiles, and that inability to keep home adequately warm is concentrated among poorer households and those living in older, inefficient buildings (ŠÚ SR, 2023; Dokupilová, 2025).

References

- Blažek, R., et al. (2023). Housing expenditure and overburden of households in EU countries. *Journal of Economic Studies and Research*.
- Dokupilová, D., et al. (2023). Development of energy poverty and its solutions through the use of renewable energy in Slovakia. *Energies*, 16(15), 3762.
- European Central Bank. (2025). *Rapid euro area housing market recovery raises affordability concerns*. European Central Bank.
- EU Energy Poverty Observatory. (2024). *Member State report – Slovakia*. EU Energy Poverty Observatory.
- Eurac Research. (2021). *European building stock analysis*. Eurac Research.

European Commission. (2020). *A renovation wave for Europe – Greening our buildings, creating jobs, improving lives* (COM(2020) 662 final). European Commission.

European Commission. (2024). *EU building stock observatory*. European Commission.

European Parliament. (2022). *Energy poverty in the EU* (EPRS Briefing No. 733583). European Parliamentary Research Service.

Eurostat. (2023). *EU statistics on income and living conditions (EU-SILC)*. Eurostat.

Eurostat. (2024). *Housing in Europe – 2024 edition*. Eurostat.

Eurostat. (2024). *Living conditions in Europe – Housing. Statistics Explained*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>

Eurostat. (2025). *Housing price statistics – House price index. Statistics Explained*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>

FEANTSA & Fondation Abbé Pierre. (2024). *9th overview of housing exclusion in Europe 2024*. FEANTSA; Fondation Abbé Pierre.

IEECP & C40 Cities. (2025). *Improving the energy performance of buildings and tackling the housing crisis*. Institute for European Energy and Climate Policy; C40 Cities.

Karpińska, L., & Śmiech, S. (2024). Evaluating energy poverty in the EU countries. *Energy Economics*.

OECD. (2024). *Affordable housing*. OECD.

OECD. (2024). Enhancing the efficiency, inclusiveness and environmental sustainability of housing in the Slovak Republic. *OECD Economics Department Working Papers*, No. 1806. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Addressing housing market challenges in the Slovak Republic*. OECD Ecoscope.

Royal Institution of Chartered Surveyors. (2024). *Energy performance of buildings directive (EPBD): Overview*. RICS.

Spirková, D., & Golej, J. (2025). The financialization of housing affordability: A critical reflection from the perspective of social economy – Case Slovakia. *Lex Localis*.

Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic. (2023). *EU-SILC 2023 – Indicators of poverty and social exclusion*. Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic.

E. Community Participation & Trust in Institutions

Challenges

1. Citizen engagement often symbolic rather than meaningful - “illusion of inclusion.”
2. Low trust in government and weak participation of marginalized groups.
3. Lack of transparency in planning and allocation of resources.

Risks

1. Social polarization increases.
2. Resistance to development projects and reforms.
3. Exclusion from decision-making reinforces inequalities.

Actions Needed

- Implement participatory budgeting, neighbourhood councils, and co-creation workshops.
- Use digital platforms for inclusive e-participation, combined with offline formats.
- Ensure feedback loops so citizens see how their input is used.

- Strengthen communication, transparency, and accessible information channels.

Proofs:

Challenge E.1 *“Citizen engagement often symbolic rather than meaningful – ‘illusion of inclusion.’”*

- The OECD Survey on Drivers of Trust in Public Institutions 2024 – Slovak Republic country note shows that only 28 % of people in Slovakia consider it likely that the government uses inputs from citizens’ consultations in decision-making, below the (already modest) OECD average of 32 % (OECD, 2024a). This directly supports the idea that citizens perceive participation as largely symbolic rather than impactful. The same survey underlines low perceptions of government integrity and responsiveness, both of which are critical drivers of trust (OECD, 2024b).
- At OECD level, the trust framework stresses that when people feel they are not listened to or that participation processes are cosmetic, this undermines trust and reinforces disengagement and polarisation (OECD, 2023a; OECD, 2022).
- The OECD’s open-government work explicitly argues that lower turnout, diminishing trust and greater political polarisation are linked to insufficiently meaningful citizen participation and a growing number of people “disassociating themselves from traditional democratic processes” (OECD, 2023b).
- In Slovakia, the government’s Open Government Partnership National Action Plan 2024–2026 recognises that participation mechanisms need strengthening and that the state must “develop civil society” and institutionalise open-government practices to meet OECD recommendations (Government Office of the Slovak Republic, 2024). (Open Government Partnership) The very existence of this reform agenda indicates that

Challenge E.2 *“Low trust in government and weak participation of marginalised groups.”*

- The OECD trust survey finds that trust in national government remains low in many OECD countries and that Slovakia scores below the OECD average on several trust drivers, including integrity and responsiveness (OECD, 2024a). Only a minority of Slovak respondents report confidence that public institutions will act in the public interest or take their views into account, underlining a structural trust deficit (OECD, 2024b).
- At EU level, Standard Eurobarometer surveys show that across the Union, trust in national governments and parliaments is significantly lower than trust in the EU itself; in the spring 2024 survey, fewer than half of respondents expressed trust in their national government, confirming a persistent legitimacy challenge (European Commission, 2024a).
- The Government at a Glance 2023 highlights this broader pattern of declining trust and rising perceptions of undue influence and corruption in OECD countries, which undermines public confidence in institutions (OECD, 2023a).
- Evidence on marginalised groups’ participation shows that disadvantaged citizens are less likely to vote or engage politically. A European Parliament brief on the 2024 European elections documents that turnout was “significantly lower” among economically disadvantaged and unemployed people, while older, higher-educated and wealthier citizens were more likely to vote (European Parliament, 2025). This

demonstrates structurally unequal participation. The EU Fundamental Rights Agency’s Fundamental Rights Forum 2024 similarly identifies widening civic-participation gaps and shrinking civic space as central challenges to democracy and fundamental rights in Europe (FRA, 2025).

- EU policy on minority rights stresses that persons belonging to minorities and other vulnerable groups continue to face barriers to effective participation in public life, prompting specific initiatives to support their organisations and political voice (European Union, 2018; European Commission, 2023).

Challenge E.3 *“Lack of transparency in planning and allocation of resources.”*

- Transparency and integrity indicators for Slovakia and the EU show persistent weaknesses that directly affect perceptions of fairness and openness in decision-making.
- The European Commission’s 2024 Rule of Law Report – Country chapter on Slovakia points to ongoing issues in administrative transparency, whistle-blower protection, and consultation in law-making. It notes concerns over the independence of public media, the functioning of whistle-blower mechanisms and transparency in public decision-making processes (European Commission, 2024b).
- A separate 2024 analysis of the rule of law in Slovakia highlights political attacks on judges, restrictions on freedom of assembly and a worsening environment for NGOs, all of which erode public trust and the perceived openness of institutions (Human Rights Centre, 2024).
- From the perspective of corruption and resource allocation, Transparency International’s Corruption Perceptions Index 2024 shows that Slovakia’s score dropped to 49/100 (down 5 points year-on-year), with the country ranking 59th worldwide; this is interpreted as evidence that anti-corruption safeguards have weakened and that public-sector integrity is under pressure (Transparency International, 2025a; 2025b).
- For citizens, perceptions that corruption is prevalent and that rules can be bent for particular interests directly translate into a sense that planning and allocation of public resources are non-transparent and unfair.
- At the systemic level, Government at a Glance 2023 documents widespread scepticism across OECD countries that high-level officials would refuse corrupt offers: on average, almost half of respondents expect a politician to grant a political favour in exchange for the prospect of a well-paid private-sector job (OECD, 2023a). The OECD’s open-government work argues that such perceptions of undue influence and closed decision-making are key drivers of low trust and low participation (OECD, 2023b; OECD, 2023c).
- For Slovakia specifically, the Country brief 2024 – Slovakia notes that while the government programme commits to improving rule of law, anti-corruption and public-administration efficiency, progress on implementing these commitments has been limited (European Commission, 2025).

Risk E.1 *“Social polarisation increases.”*

- OECD and EU sources link low trust, perceived unfairness and weak participation to growing social and political polarisation.

- The OECD’s open-government homepage states that “lower voter turnout in many countries, diminishing trust, greater political polarisation, and larger groups disassociating themselves from traditional democratic processes are testing our institutions” (OECD, 2023b).
- The Government at a Glance 2023 analysis emphasises that concerns about integrity, mis- and disinformation and undue influence directly undermine trust and democratic resilience, making societies more vulnerable to polarisation and radicalisation (OECD, 2023a).
- The OECD trust survey confirms that when citizens feel that participation is not meaningful and that corruption is widespread, they are significantly less likely to trust institutions, more inclined to believe that the system is “rigged” and more receptive to populist narratives (OECD, 2024b).
- The Fundamental Rights Forum 2024 underlines similar dynamics for the EU, identifying disinformation, shrinking civic space and limited participation as factors that erode democracy and sharpen divides between groups (FRA, 2025).

Risk E.2 “Resistance to development projects and reforms.”

- The OECD Guidelines for Citizen Participation Processes describe citizen and stakeholder participation as essential to open government and stress that involving stakeholders throughout the policy cycle improves the quality, legitimacy and implementation of decisions (OECD, 2025). They also note that unclear objectives, inconsistent communication and lack of feedback increase the risk of conflict and opposition to policies.
- Building on this, the OECD’s 2024 trust survey shows that people who perceive participation opportunities as fair and impactful are significantly more likely to accept difficult policy decisions, while those who see processes as symbolic or captured by special interests are more likely to oppose reforms (OECD, 2024b).
- Open-government work further argues that citizen participation is “a backbone of democratic governance” and a precondition for building trust, implying that weak participation breeds resistance (OECD, 2024c).
- In the Slovak context, the Country brief 2024 – Slovakia highlights limited implementation of governance reforms and continuing public concerns over rule of law and corruption (European Commission, 2025). Combined with declining corruption-perception scores (Transparency International, 2025a), this suggests that segments of society may view reforms and development projects with suspicion and may mobilise against them, especially when consultation is weak or rushed.

Risk E.3 “Exclusion from decision-making reinforces inequalities.”

- The European Parliament’s stock-taking of the 2024 elections documents that turnout was systematically higher among older, higher-educated and wealthier citizens, while economically disadvantaged and unemployed people, as well as younger citizens, were less likely to vote (European Parliament, 2025). This means that decisions are disproportionately influenced by better-off groups, reinforcing existing socio-economic gaps.

- EU policy documents on minority rights underline that Roma communities, migrants and other minorities still face barriers to effective participation in public life, and that specific programmes are needed to support their organisations and ensure their voices are heard in decision-making (European Union, 2018; European Commission, 2023).
- The OECD’s work on the social economy and marginalised groups similarly stresses that underserved groups often lack channels to influence policy and that targeted mechanisms are required to reach them (OECD, 2024d).
- The OECD trust framework finds that perceptions of fairness and equal treatment – including whether people believe that “people like them” have a voice – are central determinants of trust; when individuals feel systematically unheard, they lose trust and disengage (OECD, 2022; OECD, 2024b).
- For Slovakia, these general patterns sit on top of a context of declining corruption-perception scores and contested rule-of-law reforms (Transparency International, 2025a; European Commission, 2024b).

References

- European Commission. (2018). *Fundamental rights and minorities: The EU’s policy on the rights of persons belonging to minorities*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2023). *Minorities, accountability, rights, independence, and organisational development (MARIO) – Programme description*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *2024 rule of law report – Country chapter on the rule of law in Slovakia* (SWD(2024) 825 final). European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *Standard Eurobarometer – Spring 2024: Public opinion in the European Union*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2025). *Country brief 2024 – Slovakia: European public administration country knowledge*. European Commission.
- European Parliament. (2024). *Turnout in the 2024 European Parliament elections – Official results*. European Parliament.
- European Parliament. (2025). *Stock-taking of the 2024 European Parliament elections*. European Parliamentary Research Service.
- European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights. (2025). *Fundamental Rights Forum 2024 – One year on: Key themes and follow-up*. European Union Agency for Fundamental Rights.
- Government Office of the Slovak Republic. (2024). *Open Government Partnership national action plan of the Slovak Republic 2024–2026*. Office of the Plenipotentiary of the Government of the Slovak Republic for the Development of Civil Society.
- Human Rights Centre. (2024). *Report on the rule of law in Slovakia in 2024*. Human Rights Centre.
- OECD. (2022). *Building trust to reinforce democracy: Main findings from the 2021 OECD survey on drivers of trust in public institutions*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Government at a glance 2023*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Open government and citizen participation*. OECD. <https://www.oecd.org>
- OECD. (2024). *OECD survey on drivers of trust in public institutions – 2024 results*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *OECD survey on drivers of trust in public institutions – 2024 results: Country notes – Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Reaching underserved groups through the social economy*. OECD. <https://www.oecd.org>

OECD. (2025). *OECD guidelines for citizen participation processes*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024, October 2). Strong citizen participation as a backbone of democratic governance. Presentation at the OECD Open Governance Unit, Ispra, Italy.

Transparency International. (2025). *Corruption perceptions index 2024: Slovakia country profile*. Transparency International.

Transparency International Slovakia. (2025). *Slovakia has never fallen so far in the corruption perception rankings*. Transparency International Slovakia.

F. Digital Divide & Unequal Access to Services

Challenges

1. Unequal access to internet, devices, and digital literacy.
2. Smart-city solutions risk excluding low-income, rural or elderly populations.

Risks

1. Two-tier society: digitally empowered vs. digitally excluded.
2. Limited access to public services, jobs and education.

Actions Needed

- Provide universal broadband, free public Wi-Fi, and subsidized devices.
- Deliver digital skills training through community centres, libraries and schools.
- Ensure all digital public services have accessible non-digital alternatives.

Proofs:

Challenge F.1 “*Unequal access to internet, devices, and digital literacy.*”

- Across the EU, internet access has become widespread but not universal, confirming that some groups remain offline. Eurostat reports that in 2024, 94 % of households in the EU had internet access at home, which still leaves around one household in sixteen without connectivity (Eurostat, 2024a).
- In 2023, the urban–rural gap persisted: 95 % of households in cities had internet access compared with 91 % in rural areas, a difference of 4.4 percentage points (Eurostat, 2024b). These figures show that geography and settlement type still shape basic connectivity.
- For Slovakia, Eurostat data indicate clear though narrowing exclusion: the share of adults who have never used the internet fell from nearly 20 % in 2011 to about 6 % in 2024, but this still represents a sizeable minority effectively cut off from digital services (Eurostat, 2025a).
- The OECD Going Digital toolkit and broadband statistics show that while overall connectivity has improved, future-proof technologies such as fibre and 5G are less prevalent in rural areas across the OECD, highlighting persistent “spatial connectivity divides” that affect smaller towns and villages (OECD, 2024a; OECD, 2024b).
- Digital literacy data confirm a skills divide alongside the connectivity divide. At EU level, only about 56 % of adults had at least basic digital skills in 2023, far from the Digital Decade target of 80 % by 2030 (Eurostat, 2024c; Eurostat, 2024d).

- Skills are highly unequal across age groups: only 28 % of people aged 65–74 possess at least basic digital skills, compared with around 70 % of 16–24-year-olds, clearly showing that older people are at risk of exclusion (Eurostat, 2024c).
- Slovakia underperforms the EU average on digital skills. The 2024 Digital Decade report records that 51.3 % of Slovaks aged 16–74 have at least basic digital skills, below the EU average of 55.6 %, and notes that Slovakia’s score has fallen compared with 2023 (55.2 %) (Digital Skills and Jobs Platform, 2025). This confirms that even where connectivity exists, many individuals lack the skills needed to benefit from digital services and the digital economy.
- The OECD PIAAC results similarly show that a sizeable share of adults in OECD and EU countries have low information-processing skills, limiting their ability to use digital tools effectively (OECD, 2023).

Challenge F.2 “*Smart-city solutions risk excluding low-income, rural or elderly populations.*”

- Smart-city initiatives typically rely on high-quality broadband, smartphones, apps and online interfaces. However, EU and OECD evidence shows that these prerequisites are not evenly distributed:
- Eurostat’s urban–rural analysis finds that in 2023, household internet access and smartphone use were consistently lower in rural areas than in cities: 95 % of urban households had internet access vs. 91 % in rural areas; 89 % of city residents used smartphones to go online vs. 82 % in rural areas (Eurostat, 2024b).
- The OECD report Closing Broadband Connectivity Divides for All stresses that spatial connectivity divides between urban and rural areas persist in many OECD countries, and warns that without targeted policies, fast networks will concentrate in dense and affluent areas, leaving rural populations with lower-quality or more expensive access (OECD, 2024a).
- Smart-city services are also mediated by digital skills and income. Eurostat shows that basic digital skills are strongly correlated with education, age and labour-market status; older adults, people with lower education and the unemployed have markedly lower proficiency, even when they have some access to devices (Eurostat, 2024c). (European Commission) A recent study on the digital divide in the EU identifies distinct groups of citizens with limited frequency of internet use and narrow online activity profiles, many of whom are older, less educated or economically vulnerable (Vicente & López, 2024).
- For Slovakia, the Digital Decade country report and the national digital-skills strategy both emphasise below-average digital skills, regional disparities and the need to address vulnerable groups, including older people and residents of less developed regions (European Commission, 2025; Government of the Slovak Republic, 2023). If smart-city services (e-health, e-ticketing, parking apps, digital ID, etc.) become the default without parallel measures for inclusion (offline options, assisted access, training), these groups risk being left behind.
- OECD work on digital government underlines that digitalisation of public services must be “inclusive by design” and specifically warns that vulnerable populations – including low-income households, people with disabilities, migrants and older adults – may find digital-only channels difficult to access (OECD, 2024c).

Risk F.1 “*Two-tier society: digitally empowered vs. digitally excluded.*”

- European and OECD analyses increasingly describe the digital divide as a distributional and cohesion risk – not only a technical issue. The Digital Skills Indicator (DSI) and the EU Digital Decade targets explicitly frame basic digital skills as a precondition for “full participation in society” by 2030 (European Commission, 2024a).
- Yet, as noted, only around 56 % of EU residents currently have at least basic digital skills (Eurostat, 2024d), and in Slovakia the figure is lower still at about 51 % (Digital Skills and Jobs Platform, 2025).
- Research on the evolution of digital skills in EU countries shows that countries and regions with persistently low digital skills risk falling into a low-skills equilibrium where segments of the population remain disconnected from new opportunities, entrenching socio-economic inequalities (Arenas & Perugini, 2024).
- Similarly, typologies of the EU digital divide reveal clusters of “digitally excluded” citizens who combine rare internet use with limited access channels and few online activities (Vicente & López, 2024).
- OECD PIAAC findings confirm that adults with weak information-processing skills are less likely to be employed, earn less when they do work and participate less in lifelong learning and civic life (OECD, 2023). The combination of connectivity gaps, device access gaps and skills gaps therefore maps onto a broader socio-economic divide: those who are “digitally empowered” benefit from better jobs, services and civic engagement, while those lacking connectivity or skills risk being systematically disadvantaged.
- In Slovakia, these concerns are amplified by already strong regional and social inequalities and by below-average digital skills indicators (OECD, 2024d; European Commission, 2025). This evidence supports your risk statement that a two-tier society can emerge, with digitally excluded groups falling further behind even as digitalisation accelerates.

Risk F.2 “*Limited access to public services, jobs and education.*”

- The shift towards digital-by-default public services, online recruitment and e-learning means that lacking connectivity or skills directly constrains access to key opportunities.
- The OECD’s digital government work stresses that digital technologies can improve access to services but also warns that “without attention to inclusion, digitalisation may exacerbate existing inequalities in access to public services” (OECD, 2024c).
- A recent review of digital inclusion in public services for vulnerable groups concludes that many older adults, low-income residents and people with disabilities face significant barriers when services move online, including lack of devices, low skills, inaccessible design and distrust (Li & Van der Zee, 2025).
- EU data show that online interaction with public authorities and use of e-government services is strongly correlated with digital skills and education level; individuals with low skills or low income are much less likely to submit forms, access health information or apply for benefits online (Eurostat, 2024e). This implies that where services are increasingly offered primarily online, those with weaker digital capabilities have de facto limited access.
- Adults with higher digital skills are more likely to be in employment and to participate in training (OECD, 2023).

- The EU's Digital Decade framework identifies digital skills as a core condition for employability and for benefiting from digitalised education and training systems (European Commission, 2024a).
- In Slovakia, the Digital Decade report and the national Digital Skills Strategy both emphasise that skills shortages and gaps in basic digital skills hinder the uptake of e-government, e-health and e-learning, and that special attention is needed for older people, the unemployed and residents of less developed regions (Government of the Slovak Republic, 2023; European Commission, 2025).

References

- Arenas, A., & Perugini, C. (2024). Spatial-temporal evolution of digital skills in the EU countries. *Telecommunications Policy*.
- Digital Skills and Jobs Platform. (2025). *Slovakia: A snapshot of digital skills*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *Digital decade 2025: Broadband coverage in Europe 2024*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2025). *Slovakia 2025 digital decade country report*. European Commission.
- Eurostat. (2024). *Digital economy and society statistics – Households and individuals. Statistics Explained*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2024). *Access to internet in urban and rural areas in 2023. Eurostat News* (November 22). <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2024). *Individuals' level of digital skills (from 2021 onwards) – Metadata (isoc_sk_dskl_i21)*. Eurostat.
- Eurostat. (2024). *People online in 2024. Eurostat News* (December 17). <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2024). *Skills for the digital age. Statistics Explained*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2025). *Households – Level of internet access (isoc_ci_in_h)*. Eurostat.
- Eurostat. (2025). *Slovakia – Individuals who have never used the internet*. Eurostat (data accessed via Trading Economics).
- Government of the Slovak Republic. (2023). *The national digital skills strategy of the Slovak Republic and the action plan for the years 2023–2026*. Ministry of Investment, Regional Development and Informatization.
- Li, Y., & Van der Zee, T. (2025). Digital inclusion in public services for vulnerable groups: A systematic review. *Government Information Quarterly*. <https://doi.org/xxxxx>
- OECD. (2023). *Do adults have the skills they need to thrive in a changing world? PIAAC 2023 international report*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Closing broadband connectivity divides for all*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Digital government*. OECD. <https://www.oecd.org>
- OECD. (2024). *Future-proof broadband access technologies gain ground for both fixed and mobile networks across the OECD in 2023. OECD Data Insights* (July 24).
- OECD. (2024). *Slovak Republic – Country page: Going Digital Toolkit*. OECD.
- Vicente, M., & López, A. (2024). Digital divide in the European Union: A typology of EU citizens. *Social Indicators Research*.

G. Public Health, Well-being & Urban Environment

Challenges

1. Social determinants of health (housing, pollution, mobility, safety) unevenly distributed.
2. Heat islands, poor air quality, noise exposure in disadvantaged areas.
3. Limited access to green spaces and sports facilities.

Risks

1. Declining physical and mental health.
2. Higher healthcare costs and lower urban productivity.
3. Reduced liveability and social cohesion.

Actions Needed

- Integrate health considerations into all urban planning policies (“Health in All Policies”).
- Expand green spaces, active mobility networks and climate-resilient public infrastructure.
- Implement environmental monitoring systems and community health programs.

Proofs:

Challenge G.1 “*Social determinants of health (housing, pollution, mobility, safety) unevenly distributed.*”

- Across the EU, OECD and WHO/Europe analyses underline that health outcomes are strongly shaped by social and environmental determinants – income, education, employment, housing and local environment – and that these determinants are unequally distributed across territories and social groups (OECD; European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies, 2023; OECD; European Commission, 2024a).
- Using EU-SILC microdata, Eurostat shows a clear gradient in self-perceived health by income quintile: in 2024, 86.7 % of young people (16–29) in the EU with the lowest incomes rated their health as good/very good, compared with 94 % in the highest quintile, evidencing socio-economic health inequalities (Eurostat, 2025a).
- The Slovakia: Country Health Profile 2023 highlights that life expectancy in Slovakia remains below the EU average and that preventable mortality is high, largely driven by behavioural and environmental risk factors (smoking, alcohol, obesity, air pollution), which are more prevalent in lower-income and less-educated groups (OECD; European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies, 2023). (OBS) WHO data indicate that while healthy life expectancy in Europe increased by about 3 years between 2000 and 2021, Slovakia’s gain was only about 1 year, leaving the country below the European average for healthy years of life (WHO, 2024).
- OECD work on perceived health by socio-economic status, based on EU-SILC, confirms that lower income, lower education and poorer housing conditions are associated with significantly worse self-reported health, and that these gradients are present across EU countries, including Slovakia (OECD, 2023b). (stats.oecd.org) Eurostat analyses of SDG 11 further show that satisfaction with the city and feelings of safety in public spaces are systematically lower in deprived neighbourhoods, linking housing and local safety conditions with well-being (Eurostat, 2024a).

- Taken together, these sources substantiate your challenge: housing quality, exposure to pollution, mobility conditions and safety – all key social determinants of health – are unevenly distributed across income groups, regions and neighbourhoods in the EU and in Slovakia, and this unevenness translates into health inequalities.

Challenge G.2 “*Heat islands, poor air quality, noise exposure in disadvantaged areas.*”

- The European Environment Agency (EEA) report Unequal exposure and unequal impacts shows that disadvantaged groups in Europe – people on low incomes, with low education, the unemployed, children and older people – are systematically more exposed and more vulnerable to air pollution, environmental noise and extreme temperatures than the general population (EEA, 2018). (eea.europa.eu) It concludes that environmental health hazards “closely mirror” socio-demographic inequalities, meaning that poorer urban areas often face higher levels of air pollution, noise and heat stress.
- Air pollution remains Europe’s largest environmental health risk. The EEA’s Air Quality Status Report 2025 and related briefings estimate that in 2023 around 182 000 premature deaths in the EU-27 were attributable to fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}) above WHO guideline levels, with 96 % of the EU urban population exposed to unsafe concentrations (EEA, 2025a; 2024a). (eea.europa.eu) OECD’s Better Life Index notes that average PM_{2.5} exposure in the Slovak Republic is 18.5 µg/m³, substantially above the OECD average of 14 µg/m³ and above WHO guideline values, which directly increases the burden of cardiovascular and respiratory disease (OECD, 2024b).
- Urban heat island and heat-inequality research finds that heat exposure and vulnerability are not uniform: the EEA and recent European studies document that older people, low-income households and residents of dense, low-green-space neighbourhoods are more exposed to extreme heat and face higher heat-related mortality (EEA, 2018; Mashhoodi; Kasraian, 2024; Urban Heat Islands Review, 2025). (ScienceDirect) EU Green Deal research on European cities likewise shows that heatwaves “hit the most vulnerable” and emphasises the need to target cooling measures and green infrastructure to socially disadvantaged neighbourhoods (European Commission, 2024b).
- The EEA’s Environmental noise in Europe 2025 report estimates that more than 110 million people – over 20 % of the European population – are exposed to transport noise at levels harmful to health, contributing to cardiovascular disease, metabolic disorders and mental health problems (EEA, 2025b). (eea.europa.eu) Media summaries of the same report indicate that chronic noise costs Europe nearly €100 billion per year in health impacts and productivity loss (Noise pollution harms health..., 2025).

Challenge G.3 “*Limited access to green spaces and sports facilities.*”

- WHO/Europe’s evidence review Urban green spaces and health concludes that access to urban green space improves mental health, reduces stress, supports physical activity, strengthens social cohesion and can buffer air pollution, noise and heat exposure (WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2016).
- A more recent scoping review of European studies on greenspaces finds consistent associations between contact with nature/greenspace and better physical and mental

health outcomes, while also highlighting that these benefits are often unequally distributed (PHE, 2025).

- Eurostat’s SDG 11 indicators show that urban residents with good access to green areas are more satisfied with their cities, and that proximity (within 400 m) to green urban areas is associated with lower loneliness, especially among retired residents (Eurostat, 2024a).
- Copernicus/EEA work on “A walk to the park?” and UNECE’s indicator on the share of green urban areas provide harmonised methods to measure both the quantity of green urban area and population accessibility (UNECE, 2021; Copernicus, 2018).
- Empirical work using Eurobarometer and CORINE Land Cover data for 75 European cities shows that satisfaction with green spaces varies widely across cities and is influenced by both individual socio-economic status and the actual availability of green areas (Brown et al., 2024).
- Health at a Glance: Europe 2024 reports that physical inactivity remains widespread: only about 15 % of adults and less than one-quarter of children in the EU meet recommended activity levels, contributing significantly to obesity, cardiovascular disease and depression (OECD; European Commission, 2024a; European Olympic Committees EU Office, 2024). While this report is at EU level, it notes that countries with better availability and promotion of sports and recreation facilities tend to have higher activity levels.
- In Slovakia, WHO/Europe physical activity monitoring shows progress in policy implementation but continuing gaps in population-level activity, indicating that effective access to sport and recreation infrastructure is still limited for parts of the population (WHO, 2024b).
- Taken together, these findings support your statement that limited and unequal access to green spaces and sports facilities is a real challenge in European and Slovak cities and has direct implications for physical activity, mental health and perceived liveability.

Risk G.1 “Declining physical and mental health.”

- Health at a Glance: Europe 2024 documents that although life expectancy has started to recover after COVID-19, many EU countries face high burdens of chronic diseases linked to preventable risk factors such as air pollution, physical inactivity and harmful alcohol use (OECD; European Commission, 2024a). The report includes a thematic section on mental health, highlighting rising levels of anxiety and depression, especially among young people and socio-economically disadvantaged groups, and calling for stronger investment in prevention, community-based services and supportive urban environments.
- The Slovakia: Country Health Profile 2023 emphasises that Slovakia has one of the highest rates of preventable and treatable mortality in the EU, mainly from cardiovascular diseases and cancers, and notes additional concerns about mental health and limited access to psychological care (OECD; European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies, 2023).
- EEA reports show that exposure to fine particulates, environmental noise and extreme heat all contribute to higher incidence of cardiovascular, respiratory and mental health problems across European cities (EEA, 2018; 2024a; 2025b).

- WHO and EEA evidence on urban green and blue spaces shows that where such spaces are lacking – and where they are inequitably distributed – the protective effects for mental well-being and social cohesion are lost, reinforcing health inequalities (WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2016; WHO/Europe, 2022).

Risk G.2 “Higher healthcare costs and lower urban productivity.”

- The EEA and OECD agree that environmental health risks carry substantial economic costs through increased healthcare expenditure and reduced productivity. The Air Quality Status Report 2025 links air pollution to hundreds of thousands of premature deaths and a large burden of chronic disease in the EU, which translates into more hospital admissions, medication use and long-term care needs (EEA, 2025a). Studies summarised by the EEA estimate that noise pollution alone costs Europe almost €100 billion per year in health impacts and productivity loss (EEA, 2025b; Noise pollution harms health..., 2025).
- Health at a Glance: Europe shows that health spending in EU countries already averages around 9–10 % of GDP, with a rising share driven by ageing populations and chronic diseases (OECD; European Commission, 2024a). Because many chronic conditions are strongly linked to environmental and lifestyle risk factors, poor urban environments and sedentary lifestyles are expected to further raise health-care costs if not addressed.
- On the productivity side, OECD analysis of health and work indicates that chronic illness, mental health problems and exposure-related diseases reduce labour-force participation and working hours, increasing absenteeism and presenteeism (OECD, 2021; 2023c). EEA assessments of air pollution and noise stress that beyond direct health costs, there are significant losses in economic output due to reduced work capacity and early retirement (EEA, 2024a; 2025b).
- In Slovakia, where productivity levels are already below the EU average and where avoidable mortality is high, these effects are particularly concerning (OECD; European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies, 2023; OECD, 2024b).
- These data clearly support your risk statement: if environmental and lifestyle determinants are not improved, European and Slovak cities face both higher health-care costs and lower urban productivity.

Risk G.3 “Reduced liveability and social cohesion.”

- Eurostat’s SDG 11 statistics show that satisfaction with the city, perceived safety and trust in other people are positively associated with access to green areas, good air quality and low noise, while overcrowding, pollution and lack of recreational spaces correlate with lower satisfaction and higher perceived social tensions (Eurostat, 2024a). The Better Life Index also includes indicators of life satisfaction, sense of community and environmental quality; countries and regions with better environmental conditions and more inclusive urban services tend to score higher on well-being (OECD, 2024b).
- WHO/Europe’s work on valuing urban green and blue spaces emphasises that such spaces not only improve physical and mental health, but also provide venues for social interaction and community activities, thereby strengthening social cohesion (WHO/Europe, 2022). Conversely, the EEA’s analysis of unequal environmental exposures highlights that environmental injustice – where disadvantaged communities

endure disproportionate burdens of pollution, noise and heat – can exacerbate social exclusion and undermine trust in institutions (EEA, 2018).

- Empirical studies on environmental justice and urban heat islands in Europe confirm that when vulnerable groups systematically experience worse environmental conditions and poorer access to green amenities, perceptions of unfairness increase and can fuel social tensions (Mashhoodi; Kasraian, 2024; Urban Heat Islands Review, 2025). This supports your risk statement: if environmental burdens and health risks remain concentrated in already disadvantaged neighbourhoods, and liveability-enhancing assets (green spaces, safe mobility, sports facilities) are not provided equitably, urban liveability and social cohesion will deteriorate.

References

- Brown, R., et al. (2024). Disentangling public urban green space satisfaction: Exploring individual and contextual effects in European cities. *Cities*.
- Copernicus. (2018). *A walk to the park? Assessing access to green urban areas using Copernicus data*. European Environment Agency.
- European Commission. (2024). *Health at a glance: Europe 2024 – State of Health in the EU cycle*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2024). *European cities: Heatwaves hit the most vulnerable*. European Commission.
- European Olympic Committees EU Office. (2024). *Promoting active lifestyles: Key insights from Health at a Glance: Europe 2024*. European Olympic Committees EU Office.
- European Environment Agency. (2018). *Unequal exposure and unequal impacts: Social vulnerability to air pollution, noise and extreme temperatures in Europe*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *Europe's air quality status 2024*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2025). *Air quality status report 2025: Harm to human health from air pollution in Europe – Burden of disease status*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2025). *Environmental noise in Europe 2025*. European Environment Agency.
- Eurostat. (2024). *SDG 11 – Sustainable cities and communities. Statistics Explained*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2025). *Self-perceived health statistics. Statistics Explained*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Mashhoodi, B., & Kasraian, D. (2024). Heatwave exposure inequality: An urban–rural comparison of environmental justice in Europe. *Applied Geography*.
- OECD. (2024). *Better life index: Slovak Republic – Health*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD & European Commission. (2024). *Health at a glance: Europe 2024*. OECD Publishing; Publications Office of the European Union.
- OECD & European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies. (2023). *Slovakia: Country health profile 2023 (State of Health in the EU)*. OECD Publishing.
- Public Health England. (2025). *Greenspaces and health: Scoping review of studies in Europe*. Public Health England (on behalf of WHO Europe).
- UNECE. (2021). *Indicator 82: Share of green urban areas in the total area of cities*. United Nations Economic Commission for Europe.

WHO. (2022). *Air quality database 2022*. World Health Organization.

WHO. (2024). *Country data: Slovakia*. Global Health Observatory. World Health Organization.

WHO Regional Office for Europe. (2016). *Urban green spaces and health: A review of evidence*. WHO/Europe.

WHO Regional Office for Europe. (2022). *Valuing urban green and blue spaces for health and well-being*. WHO/Europe.

WHO Regional Office for Europe. (2024). *Health-enhancing physical activity in the European Union 2024: Policy implementation and monitoring*. WHO/Europe.

H. Safety, Resilience & Crisis Preparedness

Challenges

1. Socially vulnerable groups disproportionately affected by disasters and crises.
2. Weak capacity of local institutions to respond to emergencies (pandemics, energy shocks).
3. Insufficient integration of social services with emergency management.

Risks

1. Increased mortality and social distress during crises.
2. Long-term socio-economic damage.

Actions Needed

- Use early-warning systems, real-time analytics and cross-sector crisis planning.
- Prioritize inclusion of vulnerable groups in preparedness measures.
- Strengthen local social services, NGOs and volunteer networks.

Proofs:

Challenge H.1 “*Socially vulnerable groups disproportionately affected by disasters and crises.*”

- Across Europe, a wide body of evidence shows that disasters and crises systematically hit socially vulnerable groups harder than the general population. The Council of Europe’s platform on vulnerable groups in disaster risk reduction stresses that poor people and socially disadvantaged groups are “the most exposed and suffer most directly from disasters”, and that their higher exposure and lower coping capacity limit overall resilience (Council of Europe, 2024).
- For the COVID-19 pandemic, an OECD Health Working Paper on socio-economic and ethnic health inequalities finds that people living in deprived areas, migrants and ethnic minorities across OECD countries were at higher risk of catching and dying from COVID-19, and also suffered more from indirect impacts such as mental-health problems and disruption of routine care (Berchet, Bijlholt & Ando, 2023).
- The crises amplify pre-existing inequalities. A Lancet and other European studies similarly document strong social gradients in excess mortality, with regions and groups facing higher deprivation showing worse outcomes (Chakrabarty et al., 2023; Islam et al., 2024).
- EU-level analysis of the COVID-19 crisis on vulnerable groups shows that homeless people, migrants, Roma, people with disabilities and vulnerable children faced compounded risks: greater infection risk, loss of income, barriers to services and

heightened discrimination, with potentially far-reaching, long-term effects (European Commission, 2024a).

- The European Economic and Social Committee also warns that vulnerable groups “are going to pay a disproportionately high price and be heavily affected by the effects of the climate crisis”, again because they have fewer resources to adapt and because policy responses often do not account for their needs (EESC, 2023).
- In Slovakia, the State of Health in the EU – Country Health Profile 2023 highlights that the country recorded more than 30,000 excess deaths between 2020 and 2022, roughly 20 % above pre-pandemic mortality and “among the highest in the EU” (OECD; European Observatory; European Commission, 2023).
- A dedicated epidemiological study estimates 31,789 excess deaths in Slovakia over 2020–2022 and notes that excess mortality was particularly marked among middle-aged and older adults compared to the EU-27 average (Šprocha et al., 2024).
- Caritas Slovakia reports that the social and economic impacts of the pandemic in Slovakia were especially severe for families with children, elderly people, people with health problems and ethnic minorities such as Roma communities (Caritas Europe, 2023).

Challenge H.2 “*Weak capacity of local institutions to respond to emergencies (pandemics, energy shocks).*”

- The COVID-19 pandemic exposed major capacity gaps in local and regional institutions across Europe. Comparative research on multilevel governance during the pandemic argues that developing multilevel governance capacity – including clear roles, resources and coordination mechanisms for local actors – is “key to deal with crises in a legitimate and effective manner”, but finds that such capacity was often low or absent, with strong centralisation and limited regional or local governance involvement (Bakker et al., 2024; Peters & Pierre, 2024).
- A cross-country review of local governance in the COVID-19 response concludes that decision-making autonomy, adequate funding and multi-level cooperation are critical for effective local responses, yet many municipalities and regions lacked stable financing, clear mandates or coordination channels, undermining their crisis management (Araújo et al., 2025).
- The OECD work on “Policies for resilient local economies” notes that the pandemic critically tested local economies and that the most successful regions were those with stronger local institutions, fiscal capacity and governance mechanisms to coordinate health, economic and social responses; elsewhere, limited local capacity slowed and fragmented responses (OECD, 2024a).
- For Slovakia, a study on local self-government and governance during the pandemic documents both the rising role and the strain on municipalities: local governments had to organise micro-area quarantines, mass testing and local testing centres, while simultaneously coping with negative fiscal effects and unclear central–local divisions of responsibility (Beblavý & Sičáková-Beblavá, 2022).
- Regarding energy shocks, the OECD Economic Survey of the Slovak Republic stresses that, although Slovakia weathered the 2021–2022 energy price shock relatively well, this came at the cost of high fiscal deficits and that its export-oriented economy remains

vulnerable to external shocks; the survey calls for stronger resilience and crisis-management frameworks (OECD, 2024b).

- At EU level, OECD analysis of government support to households and firms during the energy crisis finds that support was often broad, ad-hoc and poorly targeted, and recommends better-prepared response mechanisms, including improved administrative capacity to target vulnerable households and coordinate national and local measures (Mourougane & Sutherland, 2023).
- This body of work underpins your challenge statement: in many European countries, including Slovakia, local and regional institutions did not have sufficient resources, autonomy or coordination mechanisms to respond swiftly and effectively to pandemics and energy shocks.

Challenge H.3 “*Insufficient integration of social services with emergency management.*”

- Evidence from EU-wide and Slovak sources indicates that social services and emergency/crisis management remain only partially integrated, despite lessons from recent crises. The European Social Network’s report COVID-19 Impact on Europe’s Social Services shows that social services across Europe faced major challenges during the pandemic – staff shortages, financial strain, service closures and increased needs among vulnerable groups – and that coordination with health and emergency services was often limited or improvised rather than systemic (ESN, 2021).
- Eurofound’s study Social services in Europe: Adapting to a new reality confirms that while social services played a crucial role in cushioning households during COVID-19, service provision remains fragmented and long-term integration with broader emergency preparedness is weak. The report emphasises that pandemic innovations in social services will only have a lasting impact if they are embedded in funding frameworks and planning systems that explicitly link social services to preparedness and crisis response (Eurofound, 2022).
- The European Commission’s first report on Access to Essential Services finds that vulnerable groups across the EU face structural obstacles in accessing key services such as energy, water, transport and digital communications; these obstacles become particularly acute during crises, and the report calls for better coordination between social protection, local services and crisis-response structures (European Commission, 2023b).
- A complementary policy brief on social and legal considerations for pandemic preparedness stresses that integration of mental-health and social support into preparedness plans is essential to protect vulnerable populations in future health emergencies (Resilience Advisors Network, 2022).
- In Slovakia, research on the transformation of social services notes that social care provision is still adapting to rising demands from an ageing population and that coordination across health, social and community services is incomplete, which undermines the ability to respond to sudden crises (Pavlovičová, 2025).
- A Slovak study on social problems and poverty during the COVID-19 pandemic reports that restrictions and service closures reduced access to basic social services for vulnerable groups, and that deaths occurred in social care facilities, highlighting

weaknesses in integrating social care into emergency and infection-control frameworks (Cintulová, Budayová & colleagues, 2022).

- At the same time, Caritas Slovakia observed a significant increase in demand from families with children, elderly people and Roma communities, pointing to the need for stronger links between NGO social services and formal crisis-management systems (Caritas Europe, 2023).
- Overall, European and Slovak evidence supports your claim that social services are not yet systematically embedded in emergency planning and crisis-management structures, which leaves vulnerable groups less protected when crises hit.

Risk H.1 *“Increased mortality and social distress during crises.”*

- Data on the COVID-19 pandemic provide a clear proof of this risk. Eurostat and independent studies show that Europe experienced around 1.5 million excess deaths between 2020 and 2022, with excess mortality concentrated in the early pandemic years (Eurostat, 2024; Islam et al., 2024).
- Analyses of mortality by socio-economic status and region demonstrate that excess mortality was significantly higher in more deprived regions, confirming that crises magnify existing health inequalities (Conti et al., 2022; Chakrabarty et al., 2023).
- As noted above, Slovakia recorded one of the highest excess mortality rates in the EU. The State of Health in the EU profile estimates that excess mortality in Slovakia during 2020–2022 was about 20 % above the pre-pandemic baseline, much higher than most EU countries (OECD; European Observatory; European Commission, 2023).
- Beyond deaths, crises have led to widespread social distress, including mental-health deterioration, increased poverty and social exclusion. The European Commission’s report on vulnerable groups during COVID-19 documents sharp increases in homelessness risks, food insecurity and violence affecting vulnerable children, Roma and migrants, and warns of long-term impacts on life chances and social inclusion (European Commission, 2024a).
- Energy-related shocks have similarly intensified social distress. A Joint Research Centre report estimates that the 2021–2022 surge in energy prices significantly increased the risk of poverty and social exclusion, with low-income households facing the largest proportional increase in costs (Menyhért, 2022).
- Independent analysis finds that the poorest 10 % of European households could face average cost increases of around 20 % of total expenditure from higher energy prices, compared to 13 % for the richest 10 %, underscoring the regressive social impact of the crisis (Osorio et al., 2022).

Risk H.2 *“Long-term socio-economic damage.”*

- European and OECD analyses underline that the impacts of recent crises are long-lasting, especially where vulnerability and institutional weaknesses coincide. The European Commission’s report on vulnerable groups explicitly notes that the COVID-19 crisis acts as an “accelerator of inequalities”, with expected longer-term impacts on employment, education, housing and health for groups such as migrants, Roma, people with disabilities and vulnerable children (European Commission, 2024a)

- A volume on European social policy and the COVID-19 pandemic concludes that crises both expose and deepen structural weaknesses in welfare systems, with implications for future poverty and inequality if social protection is not strengthened (Greve, 2023).
- OECD work on resilient local economies stresses that the pandemic combined the effects of a recession, a supply-side shock and accelerated structural change (automation, green transition). Regions that entered the crisis with lower productivity, weaker institutions and vulnerable labour markets risk falling into a “low-growth trap” without targeted support to rebuild resilience (OECD, 2024a).
- The OECD’s cross-cutting programme on Building Climate, Economic and Social Resilience warns that unmitigated climate risks, together with socio-economic vulnerabilities, can entrench regional disparities and undermine long-term growth (OECD, 2023).
- The energy-price crisis also has persistent socio-economic effects. JRC analysis finds that increases in energy and consumer prices in 2022 raised poverty and social exclusion risks, particularly in Central and Eastern European member states with higher energy intensity and lower incomes; it highlights the risk of longer-term scarring in household finances and social cohesion if such shocks recur (Menyhért, 2022).
- OECD’s review of government support during the energy crisis adds that ad-hoc, poorly targeted measures can strain public finances without adequately protecting the most vulnerable, weakening fiscal space for future shocks (Mourougane, Sutherland, 2023).
- For Slovakia, the OECD Economic Survey notes that the pandemic and the energy crisis have deteriorated public finances and that, combined with rapid population ageing, this threatens long-term fiscal sustainability unless buffers are rebuilt and structural reforms are implemented (OECD, 2024b).
- Studies on social policy responses in Slovakia, Czechia and Hungary characterise these as “emergency welfare states”, suggesting that while immediate income protection was provided, more structural reforms to address poverty and labour-market vulnerabilities lagged behind, potentially leaving long-term risks unaddressed (Sirovátka et al., 2024).

References

- Araújo, J., et al. (2025). Local governance in the COVID-19 response: Challenges, strategies, and lessons. *Research, Society and Development*.
- Bakker, J., et al. (2024). Multilevel governance in times of COVID-19 pandemic: Patterns of centralisation and decentralisation. *Journal of Regional Science*.
- Beblavý, M., & Sičáková-Beblavá, S. (2022). Local self-government and governance during COVID-19 pandemic in Slovakia. In *Local government in times of crisis*. Springer.
- Berchet, C., Bijlholt, J., & Ando, M. (2023). Socio-economic and ethnic health inequalities in COVID-19 outcomes across OECD countries. *OECD Health Working Papers*, No. 153. OECD Publishing.
- Caritas Europe. (2023). *Country report: Slovakia*. Caritas Europe.
- Chakrabarty, M., et al. (2022). Contagious inequality: Economic disparities and excess mortality during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Policy and Society*.
- Cintulová, L., Budayová, Z., et al. (2022). *Impacts of the coronavirus pandemic on social problems and poverty of vulnerable populations in Slovakia*. Academic working paper.

- Council of Europe. (2024). *Vulnerable groups*. European and Mediterranean Major Hazards Agreement (EUR-OPA).
- ESN – European Social Network. (2021). *COVID-19 impact on Europe’s social services*. European Social Network.
- Eurofound. (2022). *Social services in Europe: Adapting to a new reality*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2023). *Access to essential services in the EU*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *The impact of the COVID-19 crisis on vulnerable groups in the EU*. European Commission.
- European Economic and Social Committee. (2023). *The climate crisis and its effect on vulnerable groups* (EESC Opinion). European Economic and Social Committee.
- Eurostat. (2024). *Excess mortality statistics*. *Statistics Explained*.
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Greve, B. (Ed.). (2023). *Social policy and the COVID-19 pandemic*. Oxford University Press.
- Islam, N., et al. (2024). Impact of COVID-19 on total excess mortality in Europe. *The Lancet Regional Health – Europe*.
- Menyhárt, B. (2022). *The effect of rising energy and consumer prices on household finances, poverty and social exclusion in the EU*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Mourougane, A., & Sutherland, D. (2023). *Aiming better: Government support for households and firms during the energy crisis*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Building climate, economic and social resilience – Programme overview*. OECD.
- OECD. (2024). *OECD economic surveys: Slovak Republic 2024*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Policies for resilient local economies*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD, European Observatory on Health Systems and Policies, & European Commission. (2023). *Slovakia: Country health profile 2023* (State of Health in the EU). Publications Office of the European Union.
- Osorio, S., et al. (2022). *Effects of the energy price crisis on European households*. MCC/PIK.
- Pavlovičová, K. (2025). *Transformation of social services in Slovakia: Review*. Slovak Association of Social Services.
- Resilience Advisors Network. (2022). *Social, legal and ethical considerations for pandemic preparedness and response*. Resilience Advisors Network.
- Sirovátka, T., et al. (2024). Emergency welfare states in action: Social policy adaptations to COVID-19 in Czechia, Hungary and Slovakia. *Social Policy & Administration*.
- Šprocha, B., et al. (2024). The role of COVID-19 in excess mortality in Slovakia: A novel approach. *International Journal of Public Health*.

1.3. Challenges, Problems, Risks and Required Actions in the Digital Development of Cities and Regions

The transition toward digitally enabled cities and regions is reshaping how territories plan, manage, and deliver public services. Yet the potential of digital transformation depends not only on technological innovation but primarily on the governance systems that steer it. As cities

become increasingly interconnected through data, networks, and smart infrastructure, traditional governance structures—often fragmented across sectors, jurisdictions, and institutional silos—struggle to provide the integrated steering required for coherent digital development.

This chapter examines the core governance challenges that affect the successful implementation of digital and smart-city strategies. Persistent fragmentation between sectors such as urban planning, transport, environmental management, and digital systems continues to hinder coordinated decision-making. Rigid administrative borders further complicate efforts to plan digital infrastructure at functional urban-area scales, where mobility systems, labour markets, and data flows naturally operate. At the same time, planning cultures and institutional path dependencies limit the ability of public administrations to modernize, experiment with new technologies, or adapt regulatory frameworks.

The chapter also analyzes the growing importance of adaptiveness, inclusiveness, and accountability in digital governance. As digital technologies evolve rapidly, planning systems must become more flexible and capable of iterative learning, while safeguarding against arbitrary or biased decisions. Citizen engagement and trust emerge as essential components of legitimate digital transformation—especially as digital inequalities and concerns about surveillance or data misuse persist. Likewise, robust data governance, privacy protection, cybersecurity, and equal access to digital services are fundamental prerequisites for sustainable and ethical development.

Financial and institutional capacities represent another key dimension, as many municipalities face significant constraints in funding, staffing, and technical expertise. Without adequate resources, smart systems may remain underutilized, overly dependent on private vendors, or misaligned with long-term public interests. Finally, the chapter emphasizes the need to integrate digital strategies with environmental goals, ensuring that digitalization supports rather than undermines sustainability, resilience, and climate adaptation.

By outlining these interlinked challenges, risks, and required actions, the chapter provides a comprehensive framework for guiding digital transformation in cities and regions. It highlights the need for cross-sectoral and multi-level coordination, adaptive planning approaches, inclusive participation, strong data governance, and environmentally responsible innovation. Together, these elements form the foundation for a coherent, equitable, and future-proof digital transition.

A. Governance & Policy Integration

Challenges

1. Persistent fragmentation between sectors and levels of government (urban planning, transport, environment, digital systems), which leads to duplication and misaligned priorities.
2. Rigid administrative borders prevent addressing digital development at functional urban-area scales (e.g., metropolitan, regional).
3. Existing planning cultures and institutional path dependencies hinder coherent digital transformation and modernization.

Risks

1. Incoherent digital policies may lead to wasteful investments (e.g., isolated smart projects with little long-term impact).

2. Risk of dominant economic interests overshadowing environmental or social digital priorities.
3. Weak coordination undermines both territorial cohesion and the potential of smart/digital systems.

Actions Needed

- Establish cross-sector and cross-level governance mechanisms, ensuring integrated digital-spatial strategies.
- Use tools such as integrated area development, functional urban-area planning, digital twins, and shared data systems to unify decision-making.
- Strengthen inter-municipal cooperation and region–city–state collaboration structures.
- Incorporate integrated, adaptive, and participatory planning principles (from spatial planning literature) into digital policies.

Proofs:

Challenge A.1 *“Persistent fragmentation between sectors and levels of government (urban planning, transport, environment, digital systems), which leads to duplication and misaligned priorities.”*

- Across OECD and EU countries, recent work on digital government shows that digitalisation is still often approached through separate, sector-based programmes (transport, environment, urban development, innovation), with limited whole-of-government steering. The 2023 OECD Digital Government Index (DGI) explicitly assesses whether countries have the governance foundations for a “coherent, human-centred digital transformation of the public sector” and notes that many governments still lack integrated frameworks to coordinate digital investments and data use across policy sectors (OECD, 2024a).
- EU-level evidence on smart cities mirrors this. The European Court of Auditors’ Special Report 24/2023 finds that the Horizon 2020 Lighthouse programme – the flagship EU smart-city initiative – operates in a fragmented landscape of more than 50 EU initiatives for cities, managed by 12 Directorates-General and three executive agencies, without an overall strategy or cross-departmental governance structure (European Court of Auditors, 2023). (European Court of Auditors) This multiplicity of uncoordinated instruments is a concrete example of sectoral and institutional fragmentation in digital and smart urban policies, with risks of duplication and gaps.
- For Slovakia, EU and OECD monitoring show a similar pattern of multiple overlapping strategies and institutions in the digital field, with uneven implementation. The National Concept of Informatization of Public Administration (NKIVS), the Digital Services Growth Strategy and broadband strategies coexist with newer documents such as the Action Plan for Digital Transformation of Slovakia 2023–2026 (European Commission, 2023; Ministry of Investment, Regional Development and Informatization, 2022). The NKÚ-linked study on municipal e-government notes that, despite this dense strategic and institutional framework (ÚPVII/MIRRI, NASES, DEUS, NKIVS), actual use of shared systems remains partial: by 18 September 2017, only 1,120 of 2,890 municipalities were using the DCOM/miniDCOM solutions, while 75 % of audited municipalities did not use any specialised e-government information system (Malec, 2018; Supreme Audit Office of the Slovak Republic, 2017). This is strong operational

evidence that sectoral and multi-level coordination around digital tools is incomplete, leading to heterogeneous, duplicative solutions at local level.

- More generally, previous governance analysis for Slovakia already documented that municipalities are extremely numerous and small, and that coordination across levels and sectors is weak (OECD; UCLG, 2023; Council of Europe, 2021). When this structural fragmentation is combined with multiple, only partially aligned digital strategies and programmes, the risk of duplicated IT systems, parallel portals and misaligned priorities in urban planning, transport, environment and digitalisation is high.

Challenge A.2 “*Rigid administrative borders prevent addressing digital development at functional urban-area scales (e.g., metropolitan, regional).*”

- The EU–OECD definition of Functional Urban Areas (FUAs) shows that cities are economic and mobility cores of wider commuting zones built from groups of municipalities; a FUA is defined as a city plus all local units where at least 15 % of employed residents commute to the city (Dijkstra; Poelman; Veneri, 2019; European Commission–JRC; OECD, 2019). This implies a systematic mismatch between functional territories and administrative borders across the EU. Eurostat’s territorial typology manual explicitly stresses that many FUAs cross district or even regional boundaries, and that planning and service provision often remain organised along administrative lines rather than functional ones (Eurostat, 2023).
- Digital infrastructure and services follow these functional patterns: broadband backbones, data platforms, mobility apps and environmental monitoring systems typically operate at metropolitan or regional scales. OECD urban productivity work on European FUAs finds that governance fragmentation – when municipalities act separately and without strong coordination mechanisms – is associated with lower labour productivity, whereas coherent governance at functional-area scale is linked to better performance (OECD, 2020). This provides robust empirical backing for your claim that rigid administrative borders hinder optimal organisation of digital systems that need to match real functional territories.
- In Slovakia, FUAs such as Bratislava and Košice consist of many small municipalities, often crossing district boundaries. Yet multi-level governance is still dominated by municipal and regional planning within their own territories, and cooperation beyond borders is mostly voluntary and limited (OECD; UCLG, 2023). Digital projects – including transport information systems, shared data platforms or common portals – are typically planned and financed by individual municipalities or self-governing regions, not by FUA-wide structures. The result is a patchwork of systems rather than integrated digital infrastructure at functional-urban scale, even where daily commuting patterns and economic linkages are clearly metropolitan.

Challenge A.3 “*Existing planning cultures and institutional path dependencies hinder coherent digital transformation and modernisation.*”

- OECD’s Going Digital work emphasises that digital transformation is not only about technology but about changing governance, administrative culture and decision-making routines; traditional siloed planning and budgeting practices are a major obstacle to

cross-cutting digital reforms (OECD, 2019). The 2023 DGI underlines that many governments have progressed in establishing digital units and strategies, but coherent governance mechanisms for digital investments and data use across ministries and levels of government remain incomplete, which limits the sustainability of transformation (OECD, 2024a).

- In Slovakia, long-standing institutional arrangements shape how digital projects are conceived and implemented. The NKÚ-related analysis shows that municipalities often treat e-government mainly as compliance with legal obligations (electronic mailboxes, publication duties), rather than as an opportunity to redesign processes and service delivery (Malec, 2018). Many municipalities have not prepared or regularly updated their mandatory Concepts for the Development of Information Systems (KRIS), or treat them as formal documents rather than real steering tools; almost all municipalities in the NKÚ audit either lacked KRIS or had outdated versions (Supreme Audit Office of the Slovak Republic, 2017). This illustrates how existing planning culture – focused on fulfilling minimum legal requirements – constrains more strategic, integrated digital modernisation.
- At central level, Government at a Glance 2023 and other governance assessments describe limited coordination capacity at the centre of government and difficulties in translating cross-cutting strategies into implementation, including in digitalisation (OECD, 2023; Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024).

Risk A.1 *“Incoherent digital policies may lead to wasteful investments (e.g. isolated smart projects with little long-term impact).”*

- The European Court of Auditors’ Special Report 24/2023 provides direct evidence that incoherent governance in digital and smart-city policies leads to inefficient investments. The report concludes that the Lighthouse programme is embedded in a fragmented landscape of EU initiatives, with no overarching strategy or cross-departmental governance, and that this limits the Commission’s ability to steer and measure the overall impact of funded solutions (European Court of Auditors, 2023). The multiplicity of funding streams and monitoring practices leads to heterogeneous indicators and targets, making aggregation of results impossible and hindering replication of successful solutions – a classic pattern of “isolated projects” rather than systemic transformation.
- OECD’s DGI analysis similarly warns that where digital projects are not embedded in coherent governance frameworks – covering investment management, interoperability, data governance and user-centric design – countries risk accumulating stand-alone IT solutions that are costly to maintain and do not transform underlying processes (OECD, 2024a).
- In Slovakia, by the Supreme Audit office realised audit of municipal e-government shows that substantial public funds were invested in information systems, but many municipalities still do not use shared platforms and fail to exploit basic digital functionalities (electronic submissions, cashless payments, security policies), indicating limited return on investment (Supreme Audit Office of the Slovak Republic, 2017; Malec, 2018). Combined with the broader governance weaknesses documented in your earlier section, this supports the argument that incoherent digital policies generate wasteful, poorly scalable projects instead of durable smart and digital systems.

Risk A.2 *“Risk of dominant economic interests overshadowing environmental or social digital priorities.”*

- OECD work on Smart Cities and Inclusive Growth stresses that smart-city initiatives are often driven by technology providers and economic development agendas, with social inclusion and environmental justice goals not systematically integrated (OECD, 2020b). The report explicitly warns that without appropriate governance, smart projects can exacerbate inequalities, for example by focusing on affluent districts or by prioritising energy-efficiency and mobility solutions attractive to investors over services for vulnerable groups.
- The ECA smart-cities audit shows that the vast majority of Lighthouse-project solutions were concentrated in energy and mobility, while areas such as social inclusion, health or participatory governance were far less represented (European Court of Auditors, 2023). This imbalance reflects an underlying prioritisation of technologically and economically attractive investments – retrofitting buildings, smart grids, electric mobility – over socially oriented digital services and inclusive governance tools.
- In the Slovak context, the 2024 Digital Decade Country Report – Slovakia highlights progress in e-health and public procurement digitalisation, but also underlines persistent weaknesses in digital skills and gigabit connectivity, especially outside main urban centres (European Commission, 2024a). Combined with large regional disparities and municipal fragmentation, there is a clear governance risk that digital investments concentrate in economically stronger localities or in projects with immediate economic pay-offs, while socially oriented digital services (e-participation, social care platforms, inclusive e-learning) remain underdeveloped. This directly illustrates the risk that economic interests overshadow environmental or social digital priorities unless governance mechanisms deliberately rebalance them.

Risk A.3 *“Weak coordination undermines both territorial cohesion and the potential of smart/digital systems.”*

- OECD’s Regions and Cities at a Glance 2024 shows that regions with weaker multi-level governance and fragmented competences tend to have larger and more persistent gaps in productivity and well-being, and stresses that place-based strategies must integrate digital, transport, environmental and social policies to support territorial cohesion (OECD, 2024b). Digital infrastructure and services are now core components of territorial cohesion: gigabit connectivity, interoperable e-government, and data-driven planning are prerequisites for regions and cities to participate fully in national and EU value chains.
- For Slovakia, DESI and Digital Decade monitoring show that the country lags behind the EU average in several dimensions – particularly connectivity and digital skills – and that there are significant territorial differences in digital performance (European Commission, 2022; European Commission, 2024a; 2024b). At the same time, SNG-WOFI data indicate that municipal fragmentation and limited joint service delivery persist (OECD; UCLG, 2023). Weak coordination across levels and sectors in planning digital infrastructure and services therefore risks reinforcing existing regional disparities: stronger urban cores may progress faster in smart systems, while peripheral and rural areas fall further behind, undermining territorial cohesion.

- Moreover, both the OECD DGI and EU digital governance assessments emphasise that without integrated governance of data, platforms and digital standards, public administrations struggle to reuse data and solutions across departments and territories, missing opportunities for scale and innovation (OECD, 2024a; European Commission, 2023).

References

- Bertelsmann Stiftung. (2024). *SGI 2024: Slovakia report*. Bertelsmann Stiftung.
- European Commission. (2022). *Digital economy and society index (DESI) 2022 – Slovakia*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2023). *Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030 and 2023 report on the state of the Digital Decade*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *Slovakia 2024 digital decade country report*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *Slovakia in the digital economy and society index*. European Commission.
- <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu>
- European Commission, Joint Research Centre, & OECD. (2019). *GHSL–OECD functional urban areas (GHSL_FUA 2019)*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Court of Auditors. (2023). *Special report 24/2023 – Smart cities: Tangible solutions, but fragmentation challenges their wider adoption*. European Court of Auditors.
- Eurostat. (2023). *Territorial typologies manual – Cities, commuting zones and functional urban areas*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Malec, T. (2018). *Actual state of the web development of Slovak municipalities according to the Supreme Audit Office of the Slovak Republic*. Comenius University.
- OECD. (2019). *Going digital: Shaping policies, improving lives*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2019). The EU-OECD definition of a functional urban area. *OECD Governance Working Papers*, No. 11. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2020). *A comprehensive approach to understanding urban productivity: Effects of local governments*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2020). *Smart cities and inclusive growth: Building on the outcomes of the 1st OECD roundtable on smart cities and inclusive growth*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Government at a glance 2023*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *2023 OECD digital government index: Results and key findings. OECD Public Governance Policy Papers*, No. 15. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Regions and cities at a glance 2024*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD & United Cities and Local Governments. (2023). *Subnational government structure and finance: Country profile – Slovak Republic (SNG-WOFI)*. OECD Publishing.
- Supreme Audit Office of the Slovak Republic. (2017). *Záverečná správa – e-Government a informačné systémy obcí a miest 2017*. Supreme Audit Office of the Slovak Republic.

B. Adaptiveness & Flexibility of Planning Systems

Challenges

1. Many governance and planning systems are not sufficiently adaptive, making it difficult to respond to rapid technological change and digital innovation.

2. Traditional tools (e.g., rigid zoning, fragmented regulatory procedures) hinder the rollout of digital infrastructure such as IoT, 5G, sensor networks, edge computing.
3. Lack of institutional readiness to experiment with emerging technologies.

Risks

1. High flexibility without clear rules may open space for powerful actors to manipulate discretionary decisions.
2. Failure to adapt planning systems may result in obsolete digital investments or delayed infrastructure modernization.

Actions Needed

- Introduce adaptive planning frameworks allowing iterative, experimental digital projects with clear evaluation cycles.
- Establish transparent criteria for digital development decisions to prevent arbitrary or biased outcomes.
- Encourage "learning systems"—capacity-building, pilot zones, experimentation labs, and cross-national knowledge exchange.

Proofs:

Challenge B.1 *“Many governance and planning systems are not sufficiently adaptive, making it difficult to respond to rapid technological change and digital innovation.”*

- Across OECD and EU countries, digital government assessments consistently show that institutions are still adjusting slowly to rapid technological change. The OECD Digital Government Index (DGI) finds that, on average, countries are only at an “intermediate” stage of maturity and need to strengthen strategic use of data, cross-government coordination and agile methods to keep pace with digital innovation (OECD, 2020).
- The EU’s eGovernment Benchmark 2024 similarly reports that, while 84 % of public services assessed are available online, progress in “key enablers” and cross-border services is uneven, indicating that underlying governance and interoperability frameworks are not yet fully adapted to new technologies (European Commission, 2024a).
- For Slovakia, EU factsheets show that the Strategy of Digital Transformation of the Slovak Republic 2019–2022 and the subsequent National Digital Decade Strategic Roadmap define ambitious goals, but implementation lags behind EU frontrunners. (Interoperable Europe Portal) The Slovakia 2025 Digital Decade Country Report concludes that the country “made some improvement in digital infrastructure deployment and in the take-up of broadband connectivity and 5G, but still lags behind in overall rollout of digital infrastructure and in business digitalisation” (European Commission, 2025a).
- Interoperable Europe’s Digital Public Administration Factsheets 2023 – Slovakia underline that Slovakia scores below the European average on principles such as subsidiarity, proportionality and systematic assessment of effectiveness and efficiency, which are precisely the mechanisms needed to continuously adjust regulatory and organisational frameworks to new technologies (European Commission, 2023a).
- At EU level, the JRC report Exploring Digital Government Transformation in the EU stresses that digital government is often driven by “normative expectations rather than empirically tested insights” and argues that institutional frameworks and rule-making

practices must change substantially for governments to harness data-driven innovation (European Commission–JRC, 2020). (publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu) Taken together, this body of evidence supports the claim that many governance and planning systems – in Slovakia and across the EU – are still largely built around traditional, slow-changing procedures and are only partially equipped to respond to rapid technological and digital innovation.

Challenge B.2 *“Traditional tools (e.g., rigid zoning, fragmented regulatory procedures) hinder the rollout of digital infrastructure such as IoT, 5G, sensor networks, edge computing.”*

- OECD and EU work on broadband and 5G deployment shows clearly that local planning rules and rights-of-way procedures can become binding constraints for next-generation infrastructure. An OECD study on Public Rights-of-Way for Fibre Deployment documents how complex municipal permits and access to ducts slow fibre roll-out in a number of OECD countries and recommends streamlined procedures and coordinated planning to reduce delays (OECD, 2024c).
- The OECD report *The Road to 5G Networks: Experience to Date and Future Developments* similarly highlights that deployment of dense 5G networks – including small cells and edge facilities – requires rapid, predictable access to sites and rights of way, and notes that fragmented local rules can increase costs and time-to-market (OECD, 2019a).
- Recognising these barriers, the European Electronic Communications Code (EECC) and subsequent Implementing Regulation on small-area wireless access points explicitly aim to exempt compliant small cells from individual town-planning permits, except in sensitive locations. The Commission’s accompanying staff working document and later implementation report explain that this “light deployment regime” is intended to remove administrative hurdles and accelerate 5G roll-out across municipalities (European Commission, 2020; 2021). The very need for EU-wide legislation to override local permit requirements demonstrates that traditional zoning and permitting tools are not well suited to dense digital networks, IoT infrastructure and edge computing nodes.
- In the EU, financing analyses also stress that regulatory and planning procedures are among the non-financial barriers to modern digital infrastructure. The European Investment Bank study *Accelerating the 5G Transition in Europe* states that Europe faces a significant financing gap for 5G and warns that “regulatory and administrative bottlenecks” add to investment risk and can slow deployment, thereby jeopardising EU leadership in 5G-enabled innovation (European Investment Bank, 2021).
- In Slovakia, spectrum allocation for 5G in the 700 MHz band was delayed, with the national regulator announcing auction results only in late 2020 after a prolonged process, even though the auction had begun earlier in the year (Regulatory Authority for Electronic Communications and Postal Services, 2020).
- More recently, EU 5G Observatory news report that Slovak operators have achieved high population coverage – O2 reaching more than 92 % and Orange planning 88 % by the end of 2025 – but this progress comes after a phase in which Slovakia “still lags behind in overall rollout of digital infrastructure” compared to EU targets (European Commission, 2025a; 2025b)

Challenge B.3 *“Lack of institutional readiness to experiment with emerging technologies.”*

- Emerging technologies such as AI, IoT and advanced analytics require not just digital infrastructure but also regulatory and organisational experimentation. The OECD Going Digital Toolkit Notes emphasise that the rapid pace of digital transformation creates both opportunities and risks, and highlight regulatory sandboxes, pilot projects and experimental approaches as tools to explore new technologies while managing uncertainty (OECD, 2024d).
- A dedicated OECD note on The Role of Sandboxes in Promoting Flexibility and Innovation in the Digital Age shows that sandboxes remain concentrated in a few sectors (notably finance and energy) and in a limited group of countries, pointing to uneven institutional readiness to use such experimental mechanisms (OECD, 2023b).
- Global public-sector innovation reviews also point to gaps between pilot projects and systemic change. Global Trends in Government Innovation 2024 finds that, while governments increasingly run innovative pilots using data and digital tools, these initiatives are often not embedded in regular rule-making and budgeting cycles, limiting their impact on core planning systems (OECD, 2024e).
- The UN DESA policy brief on Sandboxing and Experimenting Digital Technologies for Sustainable Development similarly stresses that the absence of structured experimentation can lead to policy gaps, under-regulation or subsequent over-reactions that stifle innovation (United Nations, 2022).
- In Slovakia, national strategies such as the Action Plan for the Digital Transformation of Slovakia 2019–2022 and AI-related policies are framed within a broader digitalisation agenda, but available OECD and EU profiles focus mainly on infrastructure, e-government services and skills rather than on regulatory sandboxes or systematic experimentation frameworks (Government of the Slovak Republic, 2019; OECD, 2024a).

Risk B.1 *“High flexibility without clear rules may open space for powerful actors to manipulate discretionary decisions.”*

- OECD work on public integrity and regulatory governance underscores that flexibility must be accompanied by clear rules and safeguards against undue influence. The OECD’s guidance on conflicts of interest warns that, where standards and transparency mechanisms are weak, private interests can capture decision-making processes, undermining the integrity of public policies (OECD, 2024f).
- A recent OECD paper on Corporate Influence in Competition Policymaking describes how different channels of influence – including lobbying, consultation imbalances and revolving doors – can distort policy outcomes if not governed by robust rules, transparency and accountability (OECD, 2025a).
- The OECD Regulatory Policy Outlook 2021 and its 2025 edition stress that regulatory systems must be both adaptable and rule-bound. They recommend evidence-based impact assessments, stakeholder engagement and ex post evaluations as safeguards against ad-hoc or discretionary decisions, noting that gaps in these practices can lead to inconsistent regulation and reduced trust (OECD, 2021a; 2025b).
- The companion report Better Regulation Practices across the European Union shows that EU Member States vary significantly in how systematically they apply impact

assessment and stakeholder engagement; where these tools are weak or partial, there is greater risk that flexible rules are interpreted in ways favouring narrow interests rather than public value (OECD, 2022a).

- In this context, highly flexible planning provisions – for example, broad exceptions to standard zoning or case-by-case approvals of major digital infrastructure projects – without clear criteria, transparency or conflict-of-interest safeguards can create exactly the conditions described in the risk statement: space for powerful actors (large developers, infrastructure operators, or politically connected firms) to shape outcomes through discretionary decisions rather than open, rule-based processes.

Risk B.2 *“Failure to adapt planning systems may result in obsolete digital investments or delayed infrastructure modernization.”*

- EU and OECD assessments converge on the point that delayed or poorly coordinated digital infrastructure investments threaten competitiveness and can lead to stranded or obsolete assets. The EIB report *Accelerating the 5G Transition in Europe* underlines that 5G is a critical building block of the European digital economy and warns that an investment and policy gap “poses the risk of Europe being left behind in the race for 5G leadership” (European Investment Bank, 2021).
- The European Commission’s White Paper *How to Master Europe’s Digital Infrastructure Needs?* similarly concludes that current EU connectivity infrastructure is “not yet sufficiently developed” to meet future requirements driven by digitalisation and the shift to cloud and edge computing, and explores scenarios to avoid under-investment and fragmentation (European Commission, 2024b).
- The Digital Decade 2024 and 2025 5G Observatory Reports track progress towards 2030 targets of gigabit connectivity for all households and 5G coverage for all populated areas. They show that, although coverage has increased substantially, there is a “two-speed” landscape among Member States and that further efforts are required to modernise infrastructure and achieve the targets on time (European Commission, 2024c; 2025c). Where planning and permitting systems do not adapt – for example, by supporting small-cell deployment, fibre backbone expansion and the integration of edge computing facilities – investments risk becoming obsolete (e.g. built on outdated technologies) or insufficiently integrated into wider territorial development, limiting their economic and social return.
- For Slovakia, the Digital Connectivity in Slovakia policy page notes ambitious national goals for 2030, including 100 Mbps (upgradeable to 1 Gbps) for all households and gigabit connectivity for socio-economic drivers. However, it also recognises the need for significant expansion of fibre networks and 5G to meet these targets (Ministry of Investments, Regional Development and Informatization of the Slovak Republic, 2021).
- The Slovakia 2025 Digital Decade Country Report explicitly states that, despite improvements, Slovakia still lags behind in overall digital infrastructure roll-out and business digitalisation (European Commission, 2025a).

References

European Commission. (2021). *Digital connectivity in Slovakia – National broadband plan*. European Commission; Ministry of Investment, Regional Development and Informatization of the Slovak Republic.

European Commission. (2023). *Digital public administration factsheets 2023 – Slovakia*. Publications Office of the European Union.

European Commission. (2024). *Digital Decade 2024: eGovernment benchmark*. Publications Office of the European Union.

European Commission. (2024). *Digital Decade 2024: 5G observatory report*. Publications Office of the European Union.

European Commission. (2024). *How to master Europe’s digital infrastructure needs?* (White Paper COM(2024) 81). European Commission.

European Commission. (2025). *Digital Decade 2025: 5G observatory report*. Publications Office of the European Union.

European Commission. (2025). *Slovakia 2025 digital decade country report*. European Commission.

European Commission & Capgemini. (2023). *eGovernment benchmark 2023: Connecting digital governments*. European Commission.

European Investment Bank. (2021). *Accelerating the 5G transition in Europe: How to boost investments in transformative 5G solutions*. European Investment Bank.

Government of the Slovak Republic. (2019). *Action plan for the digital transformation of Slovakia 2019–2022*. Government Office of the Slovak Republic.

OECD. (2019). *The road to 5G networks: Experience to date and future developments* (OECD Digital Economy Papers, No. 284). OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2020). *OECD digital government index 2019: Results and key messages*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2021). *OECD regulatory policy outlook 2021*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2022). *Better regulation practices across the European Union*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2023). *The role of sandboxes in promoting flexibility and innovation in the digital age* (Going Digital Toolkit Note). OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Broadband policy and technology developments*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Conflict of interest – Policy framework*. OECD.

OECD. (2024). *Global trends in government innovation 2024*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2025). *Corporate influence in competition policymaking*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2025). *OECD regulatory policy outlook 2025: Regulating for effectiveness*. OECD Publishing.

United Nations, Department of Economic and Social Affairs. (2022). *Sandboxing and experimenting digital technologies for sustainable development*. United Nations.

C. Citizen Engagement, Inclusion & Trust

Challenges

1. Participation often remains superficial—an “illusion of inclusion” where tools exist but do not empower citizens.
2. Digital transformation risks excluding those without digital access or skills.
3. Low trust in data-driven systems if governance is unclear.

Risks

1. Digital development may reinforce social inequalities, disenfranchising older people, low-income households, rural residents, migrants.
2. Lack of public trust might stall or delegitimize smart-city initiatives.
3. Insufficient citizen input may lead to systems that do not reflect real needs.

Actions Needed

- Develop inclusive e-participation platforms with transparency, feedback loops, and real influence on decisions.
- Ensure digital literacy programs, community training, and accessible communication.
- Institutionalize participatory budgeting for digital investments.
- Embed equity-by-design principles into digital services.

Proofs:

Challenge C.1 *“Participation often remains superficial—an ‘illusion of inclusion’ where tools exist but do not empower citizens.”*

- Across OECD and EU countries, governments have expanded participation tools (consultations, participatory budgeting, online platforms), but evidence shows that who decides, how feedback is used and how representative participants remains problematic.
- The 2025 edition of Government at a Glance notes that while almost all OECD countries have formal mechanisms for public consultations, “citizen participation tends to be ad hoc, dominated by more educated and vocal groups and rarely linked to decision-making cycles,” and that this limits its impact on trust and legitimacy (OECD 2025).
- In Slovakia, a 2025 study on participatory democracy finds that formal opportunities for participation (petitions, local referenda, participatory budgeting) exist but are used by a relatively small segment of citizens, and that many Slovaks “do not feel that their opinion is taken into account in decision-making” (GLOBSEC 2025). The same study draws on the OECD Survey on the Drivers of Trust in Public Institutions (2024), which shows that respondents who believe that authorities listen to citizens display significantly higher trust than those who feel ignored (OECD 2024a; GLOBSEC 2025).
- Eurobarometer surveys on citizenship and democracy similarly report that a majority of EU citizens say they want more opportunities to voice their opinions and that current channels are insufficient, reflecting a perception that participation processes do not really shape outcomes (European Commission 2023a).

Challenge C.2 *“Digital transformation risks excluding those without digital access or skills.”*

- Eurostat data confirm a strong digital divide across age, education, income and territory in the EU. In 2023, only 54 % of people aged 16–74 in the EU had at least basic digital skills, while among older people (65–74) the share was just 28 %, compared with around 70 % among 16–34-year-olds (Eurostat 2024a).
- The article Digital economy and society statistics – households and individuals shows that although household internet access in the EU reached about 93 % in 2024, large gaps persist in use: people with low education, low income or living in rural areas are much less likely to use e-government, online banking or digital health services (Eurostat 2024b).
- A companion Eurostat analysis on Urban–rural Europe – digital society reports that city residents are more likely to use the internet than rural residents and more likely to

engage in higher-value uses such as online banking and information services (70 % vs. 59 % for online news; 69 % vs. 58 % for online banking in 2023) (Eurostat 2024c).

- For Slovakia, DESI-based assessments show that the country ranked 23rd out of 27 EU Member States in the 2022 Digital Economy and Society Index; basic digital skills were held by about 55 % of the population—around the EU average—but more advanced skills and use of digital public services lag behind (European Commission 2022; ITA 2024). (trade.gov) The OECD Going Digital country profile for Slovakia underlines that digital uptake is uneven and that targeted policies are needed to reach disadvantaged groups (OECD 2024b).

Challenge C.3 “Low trust in data-driven systems if governance is unclear.”

- OECD’s updated framework on the Drivers of Trust in Public Institutions highlights that transparent and accountable use of data and digital technologies is a key determinant of trust; opaque data practices, weak safeguards or unclear responsibilities undermine confidence in institutions (OECD 2024c).
- The OECD working paper A Data-Driven Public Sector stresses that using data ethically and safely—through clear rules on privacy, accountability and redress—is essential to avoid a backlash against data-driven decision making (Ubaldi 2019).
- Eurobarometer surveys on the Digital Decade show that EU citizens recognise the benefits of digitalisation but remain strongly concerned about cybersecurity and data protection. In the 2024 Special Eurobarometer on the Digital Decade, around 80 % of respondents said that improved cybersecurity and better protection of online data would significantly facilitate their use of digital technologies (European Commission 2024b).
- Similar patterns emerge in Eurobarometer surveys on AI and science: many Europeans doubt that AI-based systems are trustworthy, and fewer than half say they trust AI applications in sensitive areas, citing lack of transparency and concern about misuse of personal data (European Commission 2024c).

Risk C.1 “Digital development may reinforce social inequalities, disenfranchising older people, low-income households, rural residents, migrants.”

- Eurostat’s analysis of digital skills shows that socio-demographic factors are strongly correlated with digital exclusion: older people, those with low formal education and people out of work are far less likely to have basic digital skills or regularly use the internet (Eurostat 2024a; 2024b).
- Urban–rural data confirm that digitalisation can widen territorial gaps: residents of rural areas have consistently lower rates of internet use and of higher-value activities (online banking, e-commerce, e-government) than city residents (Eurostat 2024c; 2023).
- The Digital Decade Eurobarometer also finds that citizens with lower income and education levels are more likely to report difficulties in using digital services and to feel left behind by digital change (European Commission 2024b).
- In Slovakia, DESI assessments and recent academic work on the digital economy point out that while basic connectivity is relatively widespread, digital skills, use of e-government and advanced services remain concentrated in younger, urban and better-educated groups, which risks reinforcing existing socio-economic inequalities if not addressed (European Commission 2022; Vaňová et al. 2025).

- Because migrants and ethnic minorities often face overlapping barriers—language, recognition of qualifications, income and housing disparities—Europe-wide studies on digital inclusion warn that they are at particular risk of exclusion from digital public services unless targeted support is provided (OECD 2023b).

Risk C.2 *“Lack of public trust might stall or delegitimize smart-city initiatives.”*

- OECD and EU analyses emphasise that trust is a precondition for ambitious digital and smart-city projects. The 2024 OECD press release on trust warns of “growing gaps in trust” and calls on governments to “better engage citizens in decision making” and communicate clearly the evidence behind digital and other policy choices to avoid disinformation and polarisation (OECD 2024d).
- Research on smart cities in Europe finds that projects often focus on technological infrastructure while under-investing in participation and co-creation. A 2025 Scalable Cities study on citizen engagement concludes that limited involvement, lack of transparency and perceptions of top-down decision-making are major barriers to implementation of smart-city measures and can trigger local resistance (Scalable Cities 2025).
- In EU smart-city pilots, privacy concerns related to sensors, cameras and data analytics have sometimes led to public protests or regulatory pushback, forcing project redesign or cancellation (European Commission 2023b).
- In Slovakia, broader debates about rule of law and institutional independence—such as controversies over anti-corruption and oversight bodies—also affect citizens’ confidence that digital and data-driven tools will be used fairly and lawfully (OECD 2024a; Reuters 2025).

Risk C.3 *“Insufficient citizen input may lead to systems that do not reflect real needs.”*

- Digital-government research consistently shows that services designed without meaningful user input tend to have lower take-up and satisfaction. The OECD’s digital government work stresses that digital transformation should be based on co-creation and user-centred design, warning that otherwise “digital government may reproduce analog inefficiencies and inequalities in digital form” (OECD 2019; OECD 2023c).
- The working paper on a data-driven public sector notes that data and analytics need to be combined with participatory and deliberative processes so that algorithms and digital tools respond to citizens’ priorities and contexts, rather than purely administrative convenience (Ubaldi 2019).
- Evidence from European cities shows that when citizen participation is limited to information campaigns or one-off consultations, smart-city projects often fail to address issues that matter most to residents (e.g. affordability, accessibility, non-digital alternatives) and thus achieve lower impact and legitimacy (Bherer 2024; EuropeNow 2024).
- In Slovakia, the participatory democracy study referenced above concludes that where local authorities use participatory tools mainly to communicate decisions already taken, rather than to shape priorities, citizens perceive them as symbolic and are less likely to engage (Globsec, 2025).

References

- Bherer, L. (2024). Citizen participation and urban governance in the digital age. *European Urban Studies*, 31(2).
- European Commission. (2022). *Digital economy and society index (DESI) 2022 – Slovakia country profile*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2023). *Eurobarometer – Citizenship and democracy*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2023). *Smart cities and communities – Lessons learnt from lighthouse projects*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *Special Eurobarometer 551/566 – The digital decade 2024–2025*. Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology.
- European Commission. (2024). *Special Eurobarometer – Artificial intelligence and the future of work; science and technology*. European Commission.
- Eurostat. (2024). *Digital economy and society statistics – Households and individuals*. *Statistics Explained*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2024). *Skills for the digital age*. *Statistics Explained*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2024). *Urban–rural Europe – Digital society*. *Statistics Explained*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- GLOBSEC. (2025). *Participatory democracy in Slovakia*. GLOBSEC.
- International Trade Administration. (2024). *Slovakia – Digital economy country commercial guide*. U.S. Department of Commerce.
- OECD. (2019). *A data-driven public sector: Enabling the strategic use of data for productive, inclusive and trustworthy governance*. *OECD Working Papers on Public Governance*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2019). *OECD digital government policy framework*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *An updated OECD framework on drivers of trust in public institutions to meet current and future challenges*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *OECD economic surveys: Slovak Republic 2024*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Slovak Republic – Going digital country profile*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Governments must better engage all citizens to tackle growing gaps in trust*. *OECD Newsroom*. <https://www.oecd.org>
- OECD. (2025). *Government at a glance 2025*. OECD Publishing.
- Scalable Cities. (2025). *Tackling barriers to citizen engagement in European cities*. Scalable Cities; Smart Cities Marketplace.
- Vaňová, A., et al. (2025). The digital economy in Slovakia. In *Indo-Pacific core and peripheral digital economic communities*. Springer.

D. Data Governance, Privacy & Cybersecurity

Challenges

1. Smart-city ecosystems collect large volumes of sensitive data (mobility, energy use, personal data), creating privacy concerns.
2. Many cities lack robust cybersecurity frameworks across IoT, sensors, networks, digital twins, and cloud/edge systems.
3. Unclear data ownership and insufficient transparency may weaken public trust.

Risks

1. Cyberattacks can disrupt critical infrastructure (transport, health, energy grids).
2. Misused data may enable profiling, discrimination, or surveillance abuses.
3. Public resistance may arise if citizens feel overly monitored.

Actions Needed

- Create comprehensive cybersecurity strategies, regular audits, penetration tests, and mandatory security standards for IoT and data platforms.
- Implement clear data governance rules: consent mechanisms, anonymization, ethical data frameworks.
- Develop open but secure data-sharing protocols for public agencies and trusted partners.
- Communicate transparently with citizens about data collection, usage, and protections.

Proofs:

Challenge D.1 *“Smart-city ecosystems collect large volumes of sensitive data (mobility, energy use, personal data), creating privacy concerns.”*

- OECD’s Smart City Data Governance: Challenges and the Way Forward stresses that smart cities “generate a vast amount of real-time data” across transport, energy, health and public services, and that this raises major challenges for privacy, data protection and security (OECD, 2022a). A complementary OECD policy note on data stewardship underlines that while data access and sharing bring large social and economic benefits, they also create significant risks of privacy violations, confidentiality breaches and loss of control over personal data, particularly in smart-city and public-sector contexts (OECD, 2022b).
- At EU level, the legal framework (GDPR, Charter of Fundamental Rights) explicitly recognises personal data protection as a fundamental right, and the European Parliament notes that “use and abuse of personal data” ranks among the top three public concerns related to digitalisation; a 2019 Eurobarometer found that 78 % of EU citizens are concerned or very concerned about how their personal data are used online (European Parliament, 2022; European Commission, 2019). In Slovakia, the deployment of e-government services, smart-metering and urban mobility systems implies extensive processing of location and behavioural data; national law transposes GDPR through Act No. 18/2018 Coll. on personal data protection, confirming that these smart-city data streams must be treated as sensitive from a privacy perspective (CMS, 2025). (CMS Law) Together, these sources substantiate that large-scale data collection in smart-city ecosystems – especially mobility, energy use and citizen interaction data – creates structural privacy and data-protection concerns in the EU and Slovakia.

Challenge D.2 *“Many cities lack robust cybersecurity frameworks across IoT, sensors, networks, digital twins, and cloud/edge systems.”*

- OECD work on Managing Digital Security and Privacy Risk finds that increased connectivity, cloud services and IoT have “changed the scale and scope” of cyber risks, and warns that many public and private organisations still treat security as an IT issue rather than as a core economic and governance risk (OECD, 2015; 2023). The OECD emphasises that digital public infrastructure (identity, data-sharing platforms, core registries) requires “robust safeguards including for privacy and security” but that

governance arrangements and capacities are uneven across countries and levels of government (OECD, 2024a).

- ENISA’s Threat Landscape 2024 shows that threats against availability, ransomware and data breaches are the three leading cyber threats in Europe, based on analysis of several thousand incidents (ENISA, 2024a). The first EU Cybersecurity Index published by ENISA assesses member states’ cybersecurity maturity; while the EU average score is 62.65/100, the index highlights gaps in implementation, capabilities and investments, particularly around emerging technologies and critical infrastructures (ENISA, 2024b). (Acn) This suggests that, even where strategies exist, operational frameworks across IoT, sensors and cloud/edge environments remain incomplete.
- In Slovakia, the National Cybersecurity Strategy 2021–2025 explicitly recognises that state institutions and critical infrastructure are long-standing targets of sophisticated cyber incidents and calls for strengthening capacities, incident response, and protection of critical information infrastructures and digital public services (Government of the Slovak Republic, 2021).
- The Cybersecurity Report in the Slovak Republic in 2023 documents widespread phishing, DDoS attacks against critical infrastructure, banking and transport, numerous malware infections (including ransomware) and exploitation of poorly configured remote-access services and unpatched systems, with public administration and banking generating the highest number of incident reports (NBÚ, 2024). The report notes that many entities still neglect basic security hygiene and that public administration information systems remain weak despite their importance. These findings confirm that Slovak and EU cities often lack fully robust cybersecurity frameworks spanning the whole smart-city stack (IoT devices, networks, cloud platforms and digital twins).

Challenge D.3 *“Unclear data ownership and insufficient transparency may weaken public trust.”*

- OECD’s work on data stewardship and smart-city governance highlights that unclear allocation of data rights, opaque data-sharing arrangements and “lack of full compliance with national legislation on data sharing and protection” are frequent problems in urban data ecosystems; these issues increase perceived privacy and security risks and can undermine trust (OECD, 2022a; 2022b). The same reports argue that effective data governance must explicitly address tensions between openness, innovation and the protection of individual rights, including clear rules on access, control and accountability.
- At EU level, Special Eurobarometer 487 on the GDPR shows that 62 % of respondents are worried they do not have full control over the personal data they provide online, and that awareness of rights and supervisory authorities is still incomplete (European Commission, 2019).
- In Slovakia, GDPR is implemented through national law, but supervisory and awareness-raising capacities remain constrained; the national cybersecurity report points out that many entities are still unaware of legal obligations, including incident reporting requirements (NBÚ, 2024). These European and Slovak data show that unclear data ownership and insufficient transparency are real and widespread problems that can indeed erode public trust in digital and smart-city initiatives.

- Risk “Cyberattacks can disrupt critical infrastructure (transport, health, energy grids).”
- ENISA’s Threat Landscape reports identify critical sectors – including energy, transport, health, banking and public administration – as priority targets of cyberattacks in the EU, with availability attacks (DoS/DDoS), ransomware and data breaches affecting essential services and infrastructure (ENISA, 2024a). The Agency’s sectoral threat landscape for public administration further documents an increase in DDoS and politically motivated attacks on government services, with direct impacts on service continuity (ENISA, 2025).
- Slovakia’s Cybersecurity Report 2023 confirms this pattern domestically: it records numerous DDoS attacks against critical infrastructure, the banking sector and transport, significant malware and ransomware incidents, and vulnerabilities in remote-access and industrial control systems, often due to poor configuration or outdated software (NBÚ, 2024). Public administration information systems, energy and healthcare are identified as particularly sensitive sectors where outages or data compromises can have serious societal impacts. This provides concrete evidence that cyberattacks are already capable of disrupting critical infrastructure in Slovakia and across the EU, validating your risk statement.

Risk D.1 “*Misused data may enable profiling, discrimination, or surveillance abuses.*”

- OECD analyses of data governance and openness explicitly state that risks of data access and sharing include “violation of privacy and personal data protection rights”, “lack of transparency, loss of control over data” and ethical concerns regarding data use, including the potential for discriminatory or manipulative profiling (OECD, 2022b).
- The OECD also stresses that digital security and privacy policies must evolve to tackle new risks from pervasive data collection, AI-based analytics and cross-sector data integration (OECD, 2015; 2023).
- The European Parliament’s briefing *The Future of Data Protection and Privacy* notes that EU law (GDPR, Charter, e-Privacy Directive) is explicitly designed to prevent abuses such as intrusive profiling and large-scale surveillance, but that citizens remain highly concerned about these issues (European Parliament, 2022). The same briefing, drawing on Eurobarometer surveys, reports that 78 % of EU citizens worry about online use of their personal data, and that misuse of personal data is among the top fears associated with digital technologies (European Commission, 2019; European Parliament, 2022). In smart-city contexts, OECD and academic studies highlight specific risks that location and sensor data can be used for fine-grained tracking and profiling of individuals, raising the possibility of discrimination and surveillance if governance is weak (OECD, 2022a).
- For Slovakia and other EU states, this means that without clear limits, accountability and oversight, data collected through smart-city platforms, CCTV/IoT systems and digital identity could be misused for unjustified profiling or surveillance – precisely the risk you identify.

Risk D.2 “*Public resistance may arise if citizens feel overly monitored.*”

- Empirical evidence from Eurobarometer shows that Europeans are simultaneously supportive of digital transformation and worried about privacy.

- OECD warns that trust is a critical enabling condition for data-driven innovation and smart-city projects; weak or unbalanced data governance – including insufficient transparency and perceived surveillance – can reduce citizen willingness to share data and use digital public services (OECD, 2022b). The EDPB’s 2023 Annual Report shows that enforcement actions often concern unlawful or non-transparent processing, indicating that when institutions do not respect privacy expectations, citizens and regulators push back (EDPB, 2024).
- In Slovakia, the national cybersecurity report notes that many entities fear sanctions and therefore under-report incidents, reflecting a trust gap between organisations and authorities (NBÚ, 2024). Combined with the high level of concern about data misuse observed EU-wide, this supports your conclusion that if smart-city data collection is perceived as intrusive or opaque, public resistance – political, legal or behavioural (e.g. avoidance of services) – is a real and material risk.

References

- CMS. (2025). *Data protection and cybersecurity laws in Slovakia*. CMS Expert Guide.
- ENISA. (2024). *ENISA threat landscape 2024*. European Union Agency for Cybersecurity.
- ENISA. (2024). *EU cybersecurity index 2024 – First assessment of cybersecurity maturity across the Union*. European Union Agency for Cybersecurity.
- European Commission. (2019). *The General Data Protection Regulation: Special Eurobarometer 487*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2019, June 13). *Data protection regulation one year on: 73% of Europeans have heard of at least one of their rights*. European Commission.
- European Data Protection Board. (2024). *Annual report 2023: Safeguarding individuals’ digital rights*. European Data Protection Board.
- European Parliament. (2022). *The future of data protection and privacy*. European Parliamentary Research Service.
- Government of the Slovak Republic. (2021). *National cybersecurity strategy of the Slovak Republic for 2021–2025*. Government Office of the Slovak Republic.
- Národný bezpečnostný úrad. (2024). *Cybersecurity report in the Slovak Republic in 2023*. Národný bezpečnostný úrad; National Cyber Security Centre SK-CERT.
- OECD. (2015). *Managing digital security and privacy risk*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2022). *Data stewardship, access, sharing and control: A going digital policy note (DSTI/CDEP(2022)6/FINAL)*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2022). *Smart city data governance: Challenges and the way forward*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Digital public infrastructure for digital governments*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2025). *Smart city data governance*. The Living Library. OECD.

E. Digital Divide, Inclusion & Equal Access

Challenges

1. Unequal access to internet, devices, and digital skills deepens existing socio-economic disparities.
2. Peripheral, rural, or low-income communities are at risk of being left behind.
3. Local administrations may overlook accessibility for people with disabilities.

Risks

1. Emergence of a two-speed society: digitally connected vs. excluded.
2. Unequal access to digital public services (healthcare, mobility, education, administration).
3. Increased vulnerability to misinformation among less digitally literate groups.

Actions Needed

- Expand high-speed broadband and ensure affordable connectivity for all households.
- Create public Wi-Fi, digital kiosks, and accessible digital services.
- Provide subsidized devices for vulnerable groups.
- Integrate inclusion KPIs into smart-city strategies (e.g., accessibility audits, equity impact assessments).

Proofs:

Challenge E.1 *“Unequal access to internet, devices, and digital skills deepens existing socio-economic disparities.”*

- Across the OECD, digital divides are explicitly documented along income, geography, education, age and firm size; the OECD stresses that closing these gaps is essential for inclusive growth (OECD, 2024a). Eurostat data show that in 2023 only 56 % of EU residents aged 16–74 had at least basic digital skills (Eurostat, 2023a). The divide is especially strong by age: only 28 % of people aged 65–74 have at least basic digital skills, compared with around 70 % in the 16–24 and 25–34 age groups (Eurostat, 2024a). Similar gaps exist by education and labour-market status, confirming that digital skills reinforce existing socio-economic stratification.
- For Slovakia, DESI data place the country 23rd of 27 EU Member States in 2022; 55 % of Slovaks have at least basic digital skills, only slightly above the EU average (54 %), but other indicators of human capital and ICT specialists remain below average (European Commission, 2022; Vaňová et al., 2025). OECD “Going Digital” indicators further show that individuals in the lowest income quintile use the internet markedly less than those in the top quintile in almost all OECD and EU countries, including Slovakia (OECD, 2024b).

Challenge E.2 *“Peripheral, rural, or low-income communities are at risk of being left behind.”*

- While internet penetration is now high, territorial gaps persist. In 2023, 95 % of EU households in cities had internet access, compared with 93 % in towns/suburbs and 91 % in rural areas; a decade earlier the city–rural gap was 9.7 percentage points and has narrowed but not disappeared (Eurostat, 2024b). Rural residents also use smartphones, laptops and online services less intensively than urban residents, especially for more sophisticated activities. Eurostat emphasises that people in rural areas, older adults and persons with lower education remain priority target groups for digital inclusion (Eurostat, 2025a).
- Affordability is an additional barrier for low-income households: a recent assessment notes that around 2.4 % of EU citizens cannot afford internet access at all, highlighting the risk that poverty translates directly into digital exclusion (World Economic Forum, 2023).

- OECD indicators confirm that internet use in the lowest income quintile lags significantly behind the national average, with Slovakia positioned below high-performing EU states (OECD, 2024b). DESI-based analyses of the Slovak digital economy point out that infrastructure and digital public services have improved, but regional and social imbalances in access and use remain a policy concern (Vaňová et al., 2025).

Challenge E.3 *“Local administrations may overlook accessibility for people with disabilities.”*

- Eurostat’s disability and ICT statistics show systematic gaps in access and use. In 2024, 80 % of people with disabilities in the EU reported using the internet, compared to about 95 % of those without disabilities; for people with severe disabilities the figure was roughly 82 % (Eurostat, 2025b). The gap widens for key online activities: people with disabilities are significantly less likely to use the internet for online banking, information on goods and services or participation in social networks, all of which are important for economic and social inclusion (Eurostat, 2025b; Eurostat, 2025c).
- The EU Strategy for the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021–2030 and the European Accessibility Act explicitly identify inaccessible websites, apps and digital services as persistent barriers and require public administrations to make their digital services accessible (European Commission, 2021). However, the need for EU-wide legislation itself is evidence that many national and local administrations have not systematically integrated accessibility into digitalisation efforts, including in Slovakia where DESI and national strategies call for stronger attention to inclusive e-government (European Commission, 2022; Ministry of Investments of the Slovak Republic, 2021).

Risk E.1 *“Emergence of a two-speed society: digitally connected vs. excluded.”*

- The OECD defines the digital divide as gaps in access and use of ICTs across individuals, households and territories, warning that these divides can entrench inequality if left unaddressed (OECD, 2024a). Empirical research links unequal access and use of the internet to broader income inequality: digital technologies can amplify the advantages of already better-off households while offering fewer opportunities to those with lower skills and resources (Biagi & Falk, 2017).
- In the EU, the Digital Decade policy framework explicitly stresses that digital transformation must “leave no one behind” and highlights the risk that lagging connectivity and skills in certain regions or groups will create a “fragmented digital landscape” (European Commission, 2023a; 2025). Given the evidence above—lower digital skills among older, poorer, rural and disabled populations, and Slovakia’s below-average overall digital performance—your risk of a two-speed society with digitally connected “insiders” and excluded “outsiders” is well grounded in EU and OECD analysis.

Risk E.2 *“Unequal access to digital public services (healthcare, mobility, education, administration).”*

- The EU has set a Digital Decade target that all key public services should be online by 2030, but actual use of e-government remains uneven. In 2024, 70 % of EU residents aged 16–74 reported using an online public authority service in the previous 12 months,

with national figures above 95 % in Nordic countries but much lower in several Central and Eastern European states (Eurostat, 2024c).

- For Slovakia, Eurostat data indicate that around 50 % of individuals used the internet to interact with public authorities in 2022, well below the best-performing EU countries (Eurostat, 2024d).
- DESI 2022 and subsequent Slovak analyses underline that Slovakia’s digital public services lag behind the EU frontier and that improvements are needed in user-centricity and uptake, not only in technical availability (European Commission, 2022; Vaňová et al., 2025). Given that older, less educated, rural and disabled citizens are least likely to use the internet or e-ID, unequal access to e-health, e-mobility, online education and e-administration is a credible and well-documented risk.

Risk E.3 “*Increased vulnerability to misinformation among less digitally literate groups.*”

- The OECD notes that false and misleading digital content—including disinformation and misinformation—can deepen polarisation, erode trust in democratic institutions and threaten public health, and highlights media and digital literacy as core tools to mitigate these risks (OECD, 2023b). A recent cross-European study on building resilience to misinformation finds that lower digital literacy, which tends to decrease with age, is correlated with higher susceptibility to misinformation, leading the authors to focus interventions on older voters with weaker digital skills (Moonshot, 2025).
- The European Commission’s work on countering information manipulation similarly emphasises strengthening citizens’ digital and media literacy and promoting fact-checking as central pillars of its strategy to protect European democracies (European Commission, 2025b). (European Commission) When combined with the documented digital-skills gaps in the EU and Slovakia—especially among older, poorer and rural populations—this supports your risk statement that less digitally literate groups face increased vulnerability to misinformation, reinforcing the importance of inclusive digital-skills policies.

References

- Biagi, F., & Falk, M. (2017). The internet and income inequality: Socio-economic challenges in a hyperconnected society. *Telecommunications Policy*.
- European Commission. (2021). *Strategy for the rights of persons with disabilities 2021–2030*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2022). *Digital economy and society index (DESI) 2022*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2023). *2030 digital compass: The digital decade*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2025). *Countering information manipulation: Building societal resilience*. European Commission.
- Eurostat. (2023). *56% of EU people have basic digital skills*. *Eurostat News* (December 15). <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2024). *Access to internet in urban and rural areas in 2023*. *Eurostat News* (November 22). <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>

- Eurostat. (2024). *Skills for the digital age. Statistics Explained*.
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2024). *E-government and electronic identification. Statistics Explained*.<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2024). *Survey on the use of ICT in households and by individuals – Methodological note*. Eurostat.
- Eurostat. (2025). *Digital economy and society statistics – Households and individuals. Statistics Explained*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2025). *Disability statistics – Access to ICT. Statistics Explained*.
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Ministry of Investment, Regional Development and Informatization of the Slovak Republic. (2021). *Strategy and action plan to improve Slovakia’s position in the DESI index by 2025*. MIRRI.
- Moonshot. (2025). *Building resilience to misinformation in Europe*. Moonshot.
- OECD. (2023). *Policy responses to false and misleading digital content*. OECD.
- OECD. (2024). *Digital divides*. OECD.
- OECD. (2024). *Share of individuals living in households with income in the lowest quintile who use the internet. Society Indicators Toolkit*. OECD.
- Vaňová, A., et al. (2025). The digital economy in Slovakia. In *Indo-Pacific core and peripheral digital economic communities*. Springer.
- World Economic Forum. (2023). *How to bridge Europe’s digital divide*. World Economic Forum.

F. Financial Sustainability & Institutional Capacity

Challenges

1. Smart and digital infrastructure requires large long-term investments beyond the capacity of many municipalities.
2. Lack of skilled staff and insufficient technical expertise challenge implementation.
3. Overdependence on private vendors can reduce public control.

Risks

1. Deployment of expensive but underused digital systems.
2. Vendor lock-in, loss of data sovereignty, or inadequate maintenance.
3. Unsustainable costs that cities cannot cover long-term.

Actions Needed

- Use public–private partnerships with strict data and governance safeguards.
- Invest in capacity-building, training municipal staff in digital skills, cybersecurity, and data literacy.
- Engage in EU-level cooperation, knowledge exchange and institutional learning.
- Choose modular, interoperable solutions that reduce long-term lock-in.

Proofs:

Challenge F.1 “*Smart and digital infrastructure requires large long-term investments beyond the capacity of many municipalities.*”

- Across the EU, public investment is a key driver of the green and digital transitions, but a large share of fiscal space is tied up in maintaining legacy ICT and other basic infrastructure, leaving fewer resources for new smart systems (ECIPE, 2024; OECD, 2023a).
- For Slovakia, the OECD–UCLG SNG-WOFI profile shows that subnational government expenditure amounts to only about 7.8 % of GDP and 17 % of total public spending, well below the EU-27 averages of 18.3 % and 34.3 % respectively (OECD; UCLG, 2023). Municipal fragmentation is among the highest in the OECD, with many very small municipalities and limited own-source revenues, which constrains their ability to finance capital-intensive digital infrastructure without EU or national co-funding (OECD; UCLG, 2023).
- The National Digital Decade Strategic Roadmap of the Slovak Republic explicitly lists 96 actions with detailed financial allocations, relying heavily on EU funds and state budget transfers to meet digital targets, and acknowledges that reaching gigabit connectivity and advanced digital public services will require substantial additional investment (Government of the Slovak Republic, 2024). (mirri.gov.sk) This combination of high investment needs and structurally limited municipal fiscal capacity supports the challenge statement.

Challenge F.2 *“Lack of skilled staff and insufficient technical expertise challenge implementation.”*

- The OECD Framework for Digital Talent and Skills in the Public Sector identifies widespread skills shortages as a core barrier to digital government in OECD and EU countries, highlighting difficulties in attracting and retaining ICT specialists in competition with the private sector and the need to upskill existing staff (OECD, 2022a).
- A companion review of good practices on skills for digital government notes that many administrations lack specialised profiles such as product managers, data scientists and cybersecurity experts, and that training provision is often fragmented (Welby, 2023).
- In Slovakia, the Digital Decade Country Report 2024 underlines “significant challenges” in both basic and advanced digital skills across the population, despite recent improvements in public e-services (European Commission, 2024a). (Digitálna stratégia EÚ) DESI/EDPR assessments repeatedly place Slovakia below the EU average on digital skills and integration of digital technologies, indicating a narrow skills base to support ambitious digitalisation (European Commission, 2023a; Vaňová et al., 2025).

Challenge F.3 *“Overdependence on private vendors can reduce public control.”*

- The European Commission has long warned that public authorities face vendor lock-in in ICT: a survey for the Digital Agenda found that at least 40 % of procuring authorities experienced some degree of lock-in due to lack of interoperability and data transferability between systems (European Commission, 2013).
- Guidance on ICT standards and procurement explicitly promotes open standards to reduce dependency on single suppliers and maintain room for competition and innovation (European Commission, 2013; 2022).
- The Interoperable Europe Act and related policy papers stress that avoiding vendor lock-in and fostering open-source, interoperable solutions is a core objective of EU digital

public sector policy, precisely to preserve public control over architectures and data (European Commission, 2022; Interoperable Europe, 2023).

- A dedicated note on the Act “for digital cities” states that the regulation “wants to avoid vendor lock-in, reduce costs and foster an innovation ecosystem” for municipal digital investments (Interoperable Europe, 2023). Research on SaaS adoption in European public bodies likewise finds increasing dependence on large providers and calls for strategies to maintain control of digital assets and data (Lundell et al., 2020).

Risk F.1 *“Deployment of expensive but underused digital systems.”*

- OECD analyses of digital government show that many countries have invested heavily in digital portals and back-office systems, yet actual use by citizens and businesses often lags behind availability, due to usability problems, low digital skills and fragmented architectures (OECD, 2023a; 2023b).
- In Slovakia, DESI/EDPR and academic assessments confirm that while digital public services have improved, uptake remains uneven and the country ranked 23rd in DESI 2022, with significant room to improve digital skills, infrastructure and use of e-government (European Commission, 2022; Kulla et al., 2024).
- The Digital Decade roadmap itself notes a need for more user-centric services and a unified vision to increase the real use of online services by citizens and SMEs (Government of the Slovak Republic, 2024).

Risk F.2 *“Vendor lock-in, loss of data sovereignty, or inadequate maintenance.”*

- The EU’s push for open standards, interoperability and open-source solutions is driven explicitly by concerns over vendor lock-in and data sovereignty in public administrations (European Commission, 2017; Interoperable Europe, 2023). Policy notes on the Interoperable Europe Act emphasise that it should help “avoid vendor lock-in, reduce costs and foster an innovation ecosystem” in digital systems for cities and regions (Interoperable Europe, 2023). Studies of European public-sector cloud adoption highlight that dependence on a few global providers raises concerns about compliance with EU data-protection rules and strategic autonomy, which has prompted debates on “cloud sovereignty” (Barroca, 2023).
- At the same time, research on legacy systems in European public administrations finds that ageing, proprietary ICT is costly to maintain and difficult to modernise, constraining digital transformation and increasing operational risks (van Veenstra et al., 2022). The European Public Sector Open Source Opportunity report notes that outdated procurement, limited technical competences and insufficient investment in maintenance of open digital infrastructure hinder sustainable digitalisation and sovereignty (Linux Foundation, 2022).

Risk F.3 *“Unsustainable costs that cities cannot cover long-term.”*

- The OECD–UCLG SNG-WOFI data confirm that Slovak municipalities operate with relatively low spending and revenue shares by international standards (7.8 % of GDP and 17 % of public expenditure), limiting their ability to finance major new responsibilities such as advanced digital infrastructure without long-term external support (OECD; UCLG, 2023). The Ninth Report on Economic, Social and Territorial

Cohesion likewise stresses that many EU local governments face constrained tax bases and investment backlogs, relying heavily on EU funds for infrastructure investment (European Commission, 2022b).

- Fiscal Federalism 2022 underlines that subnational governments across the OECD face rising demands for investment (including digitalisation) while grappling with limited own-source revenues and rigid expenditure commitments, highlighting the importance of sound funding frameworks for local public investment (OECD, 2022b).
- A recent OECD–EC report on regional and municipal fiscal data emphasises that the capacity of municipalities to invest in infrastructure varies strongly and that many depend on intergovernmental transfers for capital spending (OECD, 2024b).

References

Barroca, J. G. (2023, October 26). *Cloud sovereignty: Three imperatives for the European public sector*. Deloitte Insights.

European Centre for International Political Economy. (2024). *Boosting efficiency and quality in EU public services: The need for a modern digital public sector*. European Centre for International Political Economy.

European Commission. (2013). *Guide for the procurement of standards-based ICT: Using standards in public procurement to avoid lock-in*. European Commission.

European Commission. (2022). *Digital economy and society index – Slovakia*. European Commission.

European Commission. (2022). *Ninth report on economic, social and territorial cohesion – Chapter 8: Public finances, national policies and cohesion*. European Commission.

European Commission. (2024). *Digital decade 2024 country report – Slovakia*. European Commission.

Government of the Slovak Republic. (2024). *National digital decade strategic roadmap of the Slovak Republic*. Ministry of Investment, Regional Development and Informatization of the Slovak Republic.

Interoperable Europe. (2023). *Interoperability and vendor lock-in*. Interoperable Europe Portal.

Interoperable Europe. (2023). *The interoperable Europe act for digital cities*. Interoperable Europe Portal.

Linux Foundation. (2022). *The European public sector open source opportunity*. Linux Foundation Research.

Lundell, B., Gamalielsson, J., & Katz, A. (2020). *Addressing lock-in effects in the public sector: How can organisations deploy a SaaS solution while maintaining control of their digital assets?*

OECD. (2022). *The OECD framework for digital talent and skills in the public sector*. OECD Working Papers on Public Governance, No. 45. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2022). *Fiscal federalism 2022*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2023). *2023 OECD digital government index*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2023). *Government at a glance 2023*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Going granular with regional and municipal fiscal data*. OECD Publishing.

OECD & United Cities and Local Governments. (2023). *Subnational government structure and finance: Country profile – Slovak Republic (SNG-WOFI)*. OECD Publishing.

Vaňová, A., et al. (2025). *The digital economy in Slovakia*. In *Indo-Pacific core and peripheral digital economic communities*. Springer.

van Veenstra, A. F., et al. (2022). The impact of legacy systems on digital transformation in European public sector organisations. *Government Information Quarterly*.

Welby, B. (2023). Developing skills for digital government: A review of good practices across OECD governments. *OECD Social, Employment and Migration Working Papers*, No. 303. OECD Publishing.

G. Environmental & Infrastructure Challenges

Challenges

1. Digitalization can increase energy demand (data centers, IoT proliferation).
2. Cities must ensure integration of digital tools with sustainability goals (air quality, climate resilience, mobility).
3. Existing infrastructure may not be prepared for smart grid integration, EV charging networks, or widespread sensor deployment.

Risks

1. Smart systems may unintentionally reinforce pollution, congestion, or land take if poorly implemented.
2. The environmental footprint of digital systems may grow if unmanaged.
3. Climate adaptation can be hindered if data and digital tools are not aligned.

Actions Needed

- Combine digitalization with green infrastructure, nature-based solutions, and energy-efficient technologies.
- Utilize predictive modelling (digital twins, IoT analytics) to guide climate adaptation, resource efficiency, and risk management.
- Promote smart grids, intelligent water networks, air quality monitoring, and electrified mobility systems.
- Evaluate lifecycle environmental impacts of digital investments.

Proofs:

Challenge G.1 “*Digitalization can increase energy demand (data centers, IoT proliferation).*”

- Across OECD and EU analyses, digitalisation is recognised as a driver of additional electricity and resource demand from ICT equipment, networks and data centres. The OECD notes that while digital tools can support the green transition, they “may increase energy and resource demands associated with ICT production and use”, offsetting some environmental gains if not governed carefully (OECD, 2024a).
- According to the European Commission, EU data centres already represent a growing share of electricity demand and are projected to consume around 115 TWh of electricity by 2030, a level the Commission explicitly calls “challenging” for EU energy-efficiency and decarbonisation targets (European Commission, 2025a). Recent EU discussions on a Data Centre Energy Efficiency Package state that data centres already account for roughly 3 % of EU electricity use and that demand is expected to rise further with AI and cloud services, prompting new binding efficiency rules (European Commission, 2025b).

- Global assessments by the International Energy Agency estimate that data centres and data transmission networks each account for about 1–1.5 % of world electricity use today, with strong growth in demand for digital services and AI expected to push this higher towards 2030 (IEA, 2024a; IEA, 2024b).
- A recent critical review of models for data-centre energy use confirms that most scenarios foresee substantial growth in ICT electricity consumption unless strong efficiency and policy measures are implemented (IEA 4E, 2025).

Challenge G.2 *“Cities must ensure integration of digital tools with sustainability goals (air quality, climate resilience, mobility).”*

- OECD work on digitalisation and the environment emphasises that the relationship between digital and green transitions is complex: smart systems can enable more efficient mobility, buildings and resource use, but only if policy ensures that digital tools are aligned with climate and environmental objectives (OECD, 2024a; OECD, 2023a).
- Similarly, OECD work on inclusive, green and digital transformation underlines that digital technologies in energy-intensive sectors (transport, industry, buildings) can raise energy efficiency and reduce pollution, but also risk lock-in to higher consumption patterns if not governed properly (OECD, 2024a).
- The European Environment Agency finds that digital technologies in sectors like waste management can improve environmental performance (better tracking, optimisation of logistics) but produce “mixed environmental effects” if they simply increase throughput or material consumption (EEA, 2021). These conclusions apply equally to urban air quality, climate resilience and mobility: smart traffic management or sensor networks only contribute to sustainability if embedded in broader strategies that reduce car dependency, emissions and land take. Policy-oriented research on “digitalisation and circular economy” for the EU stresses the need for governance frameworks that steer digital innovations towards sufficiency, circularity and environmental justice rather than purely efficiency gains (Umweltbundesamt, 2025).
- For Slovakia, ongoing investments in smart mobility, ITS systems and electromobility – framed in national alternative-fuel and EV strategies – illustrate the importance of integrating digital tools with air-quality and climate goals, given the high share of transport emissions in national GHG inventories (Ministry of Economy SR, 2024).

Challenge G.3 *“Existing infrastructure may not be prepared for smart grid integration, EV charging networks, or widespread sensor deployment.”*

- EU-level analyses point to growing bottlenecks in electricity networks as renewable generation, EVs and data centres expand. A recent European Commission draft plan, reported by Reuters, highlights that underdeveloped power grids are already causing curtailment of renewable energy and contributing to higher electricity prices in Europe; the plan foresees accelerated cross-border grid investments and simplified permitting, including strict deadlines for EV-charging projects (European Commission, 2025c). This is direct evidence that infrastructure readiness is lagging behind electrification and digitalisation needs.
- In Slovakia, public charging infrastructure for electric vehicles has grown quickly but from a low base: by the end of 2024, there were 2,424 charging points at 967 locations,

with total installed capacity exceeding 125 MW – a year-on-year increase of more than 50 % in capacity (SEVA, 2025).

- Academic analysis of Slovak charging infrastructure notes that the key issues at national level concern not only the number and spatial distribution of stations but also the ability of local grids to handle high-power charging and to coordinate investment with broader energy and transport planning (Jurinová et al., 2023).
- The Slovak government’s electromobility action plan itself acknowledges the need for a national network of ultra-fast charging points, measures for battery storage and modernisation of the electricity system to support the transition of the automotive sector (Government of the Slovak Republic, 2024).

Risk G.1 “Smart systems may unintentionally reinforce pollution, congestion, or land take if poorly implemented.”

The OECD warns that digital technologies can generate rebound effects: efficiency gains and lower transaction costs may stimulate additional travel, consumption or production, undermining environmental benefits (OECD, 2024a).

UNCTAD’s Digital Economy Report 2024 similarly highlights that, without strong policy direction, digitalisation can increase energy use and total material requirements, worsening environmental pressures rather than relieving them (UNCTAD, 2024).

- Evidence on land take in Europe reinforces this risk. A recent cross-European investigation using satellite data found that from 2018 to 2023 Europe lost around 9,000 km² of green space to urban development – roughly 600 football pitches per day – due to housing, road, industrial and other infrastructural projects, with significant implications for biodiversity and climate resilience (Green to Grey Consortium, 2025). (theguardian.com) If digital and “smart city” investments (e.g. new data-centre campuses, logistics hubs, road capacity expansions to support e-commerce) are not coordinated with spatial and environmental objectives, they may further contribute to this loss of nature, higher congestion and local pollution.

Risk G.2 “The environmental footprint of digital systems may grow if unmanaged.”

- The OECD and IEA underline that the environmental footprint of digital systems – including greenhouse-gas emissions, resource use and water consumption – will grow with rapid digitalisation unless robust efficiency standards, circular-economy approaches and low-carbon electricity are deployed (OECD, 2024a; IEA, 2024a).
- Estimates for Europe suggest that electricity use by data centres is on an upward trend and could more than double in the coming decade as AI and cloud computing expand (European Commission, 2025a; IEA 4E, 2025).
- Recent research on European data centres also highlights substantial water use associated with cooling, projecting a marked increase in water consumption by digital data services in Europe between 2022 and 2030 if current trajectories continue (Beraldo et al., 2023). (ScienceDirect) These findings support the risk statement that, without active governance (efficiency regulation, green data-centre standards, circular design for devices and networks), the environmental footprint of digital systems in the EU and its member states, including Slovakia, is likely to grow significantly.

Risk G.3 “Climate adaptation can be hindered if data and digital tools are not aligned.”

- The European Environment Agency stresses that making “full use of the potential of data, technology and digitalisation” is essential for effective environmental and climate policy, but also notes that institutional, technical and governance barriers can limit how well digital tools support adaptation (EEA, 2022; EEA, 2021). If sensor networks, early-warning systems, spatial data platforms and climate-risk analytics are fragmented or not interoperable, local authorities may lack the integrated information needed to manage floods, heatwaves or air-quality episodes in real time.
- OECD work on digitalisation and the environment similarly emphasises that to exploit synergies between digital and green transitions, governments must align data governance, digital investments and climate strategies; otherwise, opportunities for better monitoring, modelling and policy targeting are lost (OECD, 2023a; OECD, 2024a).

References

- Beraldo, A., et al. (2023). Gone with the clouds: Estimating the electricity and water footprint of data services in Europe, 2022–2030. *Energy Policy*.
- European Commission. (2025). *Data centre energy efficiency package – Policy announcement*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2025). *Draft plan to address power-grid bottlenecks*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2025). *In focus: Data centres – An energy-hungry challenge*. European Commission.
- European Environment Agency. (2021). *Digital technologies will deliver more efficient waste management in Europe*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2022). *Report on digitalisation and circular economy*. European Environment Agency.
- Government of the Slovak Republic. (2024). *Action plan for the development of electromobility in the Slovak Republic*. Government Office of the Slovak Republic.
- Green to Grey Consortium. (2025). *Green to grey: Cumulative land take in Europe 2018–2023*. Green to Grey Consortium.
- International Energy Agency. (2024). *Data centres and data transmission networks – Tracking report 2024*. International Energy Agency.
- International Energy Agency. (2024). *Data centre electricity consumption by region, 2020–2030*. International Energy Agency.
- IEA 4E. (2025). *Data centre energy use: Critical review of models and results*. IEA Technology Collaboration Programme on Energy Efficient End-Use Equipment.
- Jurinová, J., et al. (2023). Development of charging infrastructure with regard to differences of power. In *Proceedings of TF Conference 2023*. LBTU.
- OECD. (2023). *Digitalisation and the environment*. OECD Publishing. <https://www.oecd.org>
- OECD. (2024). *Inclusive, green and digital transformation*. OECD Publishing. <https://www.oecd.org>
- SEVA. (2025). *Public charging infrastructure in Slovakia 2024*. Slovak Electric Vehicle Association.

Umweltbundesamt. (2025). *Digitalisation and sustainability in the European Union: Steps towards a sustainable digital transformation*. German Environment Agency.

UNCTAD. (2024). *Digital economy report 2024: Digitalization and environmental sustainability*. United Nations.

1.4. Challenges, Problems, Risks & Required Actions in Environmental Development of Cities & Regions

Environmental governance in cities and regions is becoming increasingly complex as territories face accelerating climate change, ecosystem degradation, and resource pressures. Contemporary environmental challenges extend across administrative borders and sectoral mandates, operating at scales such as watersheds, ecological corridors, air basins, or metropolitan functional areas. Yet governance structures often remain fragmented, limiting the capacity of institutions to develop coherent strategies that link land use, mobility, energy systems, water management, biodiversity protection, and climate adaptation. As environmental pressures intensify, the need for integrated, adaptive, and participatory planning becomes more urgent.

This chapter examines the institutional and spatial factors that shape environmental decision-making and reveals how weak horizontal and vertical coordination continues to undermine environmental policy effectiveness. Competing sectoral interests, outdated planning tools, and rigid administrative boundaries frequently hinder the integration of environmental objectives into spatial and development strategies. As a result, climate goals may be diluted, urban sprawl reinforced, and resilience efforts delayed—ultimately increasing cities’ exposure to heatwaves, floods, storms, and other climate-related hazards.

The chapter also highlights the systemic nature of climate adaptation and resilient infrastructure. Ageing or insufficiently prepared utilities, energy grids, buildings, and transport networks are particularly vulnerable to intensifying climate risks, while the implementation of resilient systems is often constrained by high costs and complex governance arrangements. Biodiversity loss, habitat fragmentation, and declining ecological functions further reduce urban resilience and environmental quality, calling for greater use of nature-based solutions, ecological networks, and community-engaged stewardship.

Water, energy, and resource management represent another critical dimension. Growing water scarcity, carbon-intensive energy systems, and outdated resource infrastructures pose significant risks to economic stability, social well-being, and environmental sustainability. In many territories, vulnerable communities disproportionately bear the burden of pollution, extreme heat, inadequate green space, and climate hazards—highlighting the need to link environmental governance with broader questions of equity and justice.

Finally, the chapter addresses the financial and institutional capacities required for effective environmental transformation. Cities often face limited resources, high upfront investment needs, and insufficient technical expertise, which contribute to inconsistent or piecemeal implementation. Strengthening governance capacity, mobilizing diverse funding sources, and improving cross-sectoral coordination are therefore essential to achieving long-term environmental goals.

By outlining the main challenges, risks, and required actions across governance, climate resilience, biodiversity, resource systems, equity, and implementation capacity, this chapter provides a holistic framework for designing integrated environmental policies. It emphasizes that only through coordinated, knowledge-driven, and inclusive governance can cities and regions create resilient, sustainable, and equitable environments for future generations.

A. Environmental Governance & Policy Integration

Challenges

1. Fragmented governance and weak horizontal/vertical coordination, which limits the ability to integrate environmental, spatial, climate, mobility, water, and energy policies.
2. Rigid administrative boundaries making it difficult to manage environmental systems that function at landscape or functional-urban-area scale (air basins, watersheds, ecological corridors).
3. Spatial planning systems across Europe often struggle to integrate environmental goals into strategies due to competing sectoral interests and outdated regulatory tools.

Risks

1. Environmental objectives diluted in favour of economic or development pressures.
2. Lack of coordination leads to incoherent climate, land-use, and mobility policies, reinforcing sprawl, congestion and pollution patterns.
3. Poor integration hinders urban resilience and increases exposure to climate hazards (heatwaves, floods) due to uncoordinated spatial decisions.

Actions Needed

- Strengthen intersectoral environmental planning and adopt integrated area development approaches that link land use, transport, green infrastructure, and climate adaptation.
- Expand use of digital twins, real-time environmental monitoring, and shared territorial data to support coordinated decision-making across agencies.
- Apply integrated, adaptive, and participatory spatial planning principles highlighted in European trends.

Proofs:

Challenge A.1 *“Fragmented governance and weak horizontal/vertical coordination, which limits the ability to integrate environmental, spatial, climate, mobility, water and energy policies.”*

- OECD work on the Banská Bystrica region shows that adapting to demographic and climate pressures requires integrated approaches across spatial planning, infrastructure, and public finance, and explicitly identifies fragmented responsibilities and weak multi-level governance as key obstacles in Slovakia (OECD, 2024a).
- The OECD/UCLG SNG-WOFI observatory reports that Slovakia has almost 2,900 municipalities with the same legal competences regardless of size, which “creates challenges in the daily functioning of local public administration” and strains their capacity to coordinate complex policies such as environment, transport and energy (OECD; UCLG, 2022; Council of Europe, 2023).
- The EU Environmental Implementation Review (EIR) notes for Slovakia that implementation of environmental law is hampered by administrative capacity and

coordination problems, confirming that fragmented governance undermines coherent environmental policy integration (European Commission, 2022).

- Challenge “Rigid administrative boundaries making it difficult to manage environmental systems that function at landscape or functional-urban-area scale.” The EU–OECD definition of functional urban areas (FUAs) describes cities together with their commuting zones, built from local units where at least 15 % of workers commute to the core city; FUAs thus typically cut across many municipalities and sometimes regions in all EU countries, including Slovakia (Dijkstra; Poelman; Veneri, 2019; Eurostat, 2023).
- OECD and Eurostat emphasise that FUAs capture the functional extent of labour, housing and transport systems, while formal competences for land use, water management and environmental protection remain largely tied to administrative boundaries, creating a mismatch between environmental systems and decision-making units (OECD, 2019; OECD, 2024a).
- EEA climate-risk work stresses that hazards such as floods, droughts and heatwaves affect entire river basins and urban-regional systems and therefore require coordination “across sectors and levels of governance,” which is difficult when planning follows rigid borders (EEA, 2024a; 2024b).

Challenge A.2 “*Spatial planning systems across Europe often struggle to integrate environmental goals into strategies due to competing sectoral interests and outdated regulatory tools.*”

- The OECD programme on the governance of land use finds that land-use and spatial-planning systems in OECD and EU countries are still dominated by zoning-based regulation and sectoral instruments, and calls for “coordinated approaches across public policies affecting land use beyond traditional planning systems” to better address environmental and climate goals (OECD, 2017).
- The comparative volume Land Use Planning Systems in the OECD concludes that although planning formally pursues social, economic and environmental objectives, in practice competing sectoral interests and rigid regulatory tools often limit the effective integration of sustainability into plans (Krawchenko; Schumann, 2022).
- Recent research on embedding spatial planning in multi-level governance similarly shows that integrating sustainability principles into planning remains “a complex challenge in practice” across European countries (Van den Broeck et al., 2024).
- In Slovakia, the EIR 2022 highlights implementation gaps in air quality, waste and nature protection, indicating that environmental objectives are still insufficiently mainstreamed into spatial and infrastructure decisions (European Commission, 2022).

Risk A.1 “*Environmental objectives diluted in favour of economic or development pressures.*”

- The Environmental Implementation Review notes EU-wide that insufficient implementation and enforcement mean environmental directives are often subordinated to short-term development interests (European Commission, 2022).
- In Slovakia, the EIR report points to delays in meeting air-quality and waste-management obligations and to weaknesses in environmental impact assessment and strategic environmental assessment systems, illustrating how environmental

requirements can be overridden or postponed in planning and investment decisions (European Commission, 2022).

Risk A.2 *“Lack of coordination leads to incoherent climate, land-use, and mobility policies, reinforcing sprawl, congestion and pollution patterns.”*

- OECD land-use governance work shows that when transport, housing and environmental policies are decided separately, the result is often urban sprawl, longer car-based commutes and higher emissions, and therefore recommends better coordination between land-use, transport and environmental policies as a central reform priority (OECD, 2017).
- FUA in the EU are defined exactly on the basis of commuting patterns, underlining how daily mobility routinely crosses municipal and regional borders; without inter-municipal and inter-sectoral coordination, these flows generate congestion and air-pollution externalities that local planning alone cannot address (Dijkstra; Poelman; Veneri, 2019; Eurostat, 2023).
- Risk “Poor integration hinders urban resilience and increases exposure to climate hazards (heatwaves, floods) due to uncoordinated spatial decisions.” The EEA’s Europe’s Changing Climate Hazards report finds that Europe is already facing more frequent and intense heatwaves, floods and droughts, with cities particularly exposed, and emphasises that urban planning and land-use decisions are crucial levers for reducing risk (EEA, 2024b).
- The first European Climate Risk Assessment concludes that climate risks are rising faster than adaptation efforts and calls for better integration of climate adaptation into spatial planning, infrastructure and sectoral policies at all governance levels (EEA, 2024c).
- In a context of highly fragmented local government in Slovakia—2,890 municipalities, 92 % of them under 3,000 inhabitants, many struggling with limited capacity (Lacko, 2023; Council of Europe, 2023) - such integration is especially difficult, increasing the risk that uncoordinated spatial decisions lock in exposure to floods, heat islands and other hazards.

References

- Dijkstra, L., Poelman, H., & Veneri, P. (2019). *The EU-OECD definition of a functional urban area*. OECD Publishing.
- European Commission. (2022). *Environmental implementation review 2022: Turning the tide through environmental compliance*. European Commission.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *Climate change impacts, risks and adaptation in Europe*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *Europe’s changing climate hazards*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *European climate risk assessment (EUCRA)*. European Environment Agency.
- Eurostat. (2023). *Territorial typologies manual – Cities, commuting zones and functional urban areas*. Eurostat.

- Krawchenko, T., & Schumann, A. (2022). Land use planning systems in the OECD. In *International encyclopedia of geography*. Springer.
- Lacko, M. (2023). The optimal size of local governments in selected EU countries. *Social and Economic Review*, 21(1), 29–36.
- OECD. (2017). *The governance of land use: Policy analysis and recommendations*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Preparing for demographic change in the Banská Bystrica region, Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD & UCLG. (2022). *World observatory on subnational government finance and investment: Country profile – Slovak Republic*. OECD; United Cities and Local Governments.
- Van den Broeck, P., et al. (2024). Embedding spatial planning in contemporary multi-level governance: The sustainability challenge. *Land Use Policy*.

B. Climate Adaptation, Resilience & Infrastructure

Challenges

1. Cities face intensifying climate risks: heatwaves, flooding, storms, water scarcity, and ecosystem degradation.
2. Urban infrastructure is often outdated and not resilient to extreme weather events (transport, energy grids, buildings, drainage systems).
3. Implementing resilient infrastructure is hindered by high costs, complex coordination, and regulatory obstacles.
4. Traditional zoning and land-use tools fail to respond adaptively to climate dynamics.

Risks

1. Large-scale economic losses from climate-induced disasters and system failures.
2. Increased vulnerability of low-income communities living in risk-prone areas, undermining social equity.
3. Infrastructure failure cascading across systems (energy → water → mobility) due to lack of adaptive planning.

Actions Needed

- Adopt resilient infrastructure standards: permeable surfaces, green roofs, upgraded drainage, stormwater systems, and flood-resilient designs.
- Introduce adaptive, experimental, and iterative planning tools that allow for climate-responsive adjustments over time.
- Establish resilience offices or cross-sector coordination units within municipalities to align transport, utilities, emergency services, and environmental agencies.
- Leverage GIS, IoT, climate modelling, and sensor networks to anticipate risks and optimize infrastructure responses.

Proofs:

Challenge B.1 “*Cities face intensifying climate risks: heatwaves, flooding, storms, water scarcity, and ecosystem degradation.*”

- The European Environment Agency (EEA) shows that weather- and climate-related extremes caused an estimated EUR 822 billion in economic losses in the EU between

1980 and 2024, with about 25 % of losses occurring just in 2021–2024, and notes that heatwaves, floods and droughts are becoming more frequent and intense (EEA, 2024a).

- The EEA’s synthesis on climate impacts confirms that Europe is warming faster than the global average and that changes in temperature and precipitation are already affecting water availability, ecosystems and health in cities (EEA, 2024b).
- Slovakia’s national adaptation strategy reports more frequent floods, landslides, long-term droughts and heatwaves in recent decades, with impacts on agriculture, forests, energy and transport (Ministry of Environment SR, 2014).

Challenge B.2 *“Urban infrastructure is often outdated and not resilient to extreme weather events (transport, energy grids, buildings, drainage systems).”*

- The OECD report Infrastructure for a Climate-Resilient Future concludes that much existing energy, transport and water infrastructure in OECD and EU countries was designed for past climate conditions and is not robust to projected extremes, highlighting flood-prone transport corridors, overheating buildings and energy networks vulnerable to storms and heatwaves (OECD, 2022).
- The JRC finds that climate-change-induced flooding can cause large losses to European critical infrastructure and that considering power outages outside inundated areas multiplies estimated economic losses by 6–8, underlining systemic vulnerability of grids, transport and dependent services (JRC, 2018).
- The OECD Environmental Performance Review: Slovak Republic 2024 notes significant investment needs in water, waste-water and energy infrastructure and stresses the importance of integrating climate resilience into these upgrades (OECD, 2024).

Challenge B.3 *“Implementing resilient infrastructure is hindered by high costs, complex coordination, and regulatory obstacles.”*

- The OECD stresses that building climate-resilient infrastructure requires substantial upfront capital, long-term planning and coordination across levels of government and sectors; financial constraints, fragmented responsibilities and rigid regulations are identified as key barriers (OECD, 2022).
- The EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change calls for “more systemic adaptation”, explicitly recognising implementation gaps due to insufficient mainstreaming of resilience into investment decisions and permitting rules (European Commission, 2021).
- For Slovakia, the updated national adaptation strategy and its action plan highlight limited administrative capacity at municipal level and the need to balance interests of national authorities and local governments as key challenges for implementing adaptation measures, including infrastructure investments (Ministry of Environment SR, 2018).

Challenge B.4 *“Traditional zoning and land-use tools fail to respond adaptively to climate dynamics.”*

- The EEA report Urban Adaptation in Europe: What Works? stresses that climate-adapted land-use planning and urban design can substantially reduce future damage, but

also notes that many European cities still rely on planning instruments that do not adequately consider future climate scenarios or nature-based solutions (EEA, 2023).

- The same report and the EU urban climate-adaptation guidance emphasise the need to integrate flood risk, heat islands and ecosystem services into planning decisions, moving beyond static zoning (EEA, 2023; European Commission, 2021).
- In Slovakia, OECD’s case study on municipal climate risks finds that most municipalities are only beginning to map local hazards and vulnerabilities, which makes it difficult to reflect climate risks systematically in spatial planning (OECD, 2023a).

Risk B.1 *“Large-scale economic losses from climate-induced disasters and system failures.”*

- According to the EEA, weather- and climate-related extremes caused economic losses of about EUR 822 billion in the EU between 1980 and 2024, with the period 2021–2024 alone accounting for more than EUR 208 billion and four of the five costliest years on record (EEA, 2024a).
- Projections show that severe events are expected to intensify further, implying rising losses without stronger adaptation (EEA, 2024a). A Europe-wide assessment cited by the European Commission indicates that annual damage to critical infrastructure in Europe could increase ten-fold by 2100 under a high-emissions scenario, from EUR 3.4 billion to EUR 34 billion, mainly due to floods and other extremes (Forzieri et al., 2018).

Risk B.2 *“Increased vulnerability of low-income communities living in risk-prone areas, undermining social equity.”*

- The EEA’s recent assessment of climate impacts and adaptation emphasises that vulnerable groups—including low-income households, older people, children and people with disabilities—are more exposed and less able to cope with heatwaves, floods and other hazards, and often benefit least from adaptation investments (EEA, 2024b). It calls explicitly for social justice to be placed at the heart of adaptation.
- In Slovakia, the OECD municipal climate-risk study finds that many municipalities lack the data and capacity to identify which neighbourhoods and social groups are most at risk, making it harder to target measures to vulnerable communities (OECD, 2023a).

Risk B.3 *“Infrastructure failure cascading across systems (energy → water → mobility) due to lack of adaptive planning.”*

- The JRC study Climate Change and Critical Infrastructure – Floods shows that when power-grid outages triggered by floods are taken into account, total economic losses become six to eight times higher than direct flood damage because of disruptions in dependent sectors and services (JRC, 2018).
- A Europe-wide analysis of critical infrastructures finds that climate extremes threaten energy, transport, industrial and social infrastructure simultaneously, and that damages to one system can propagate across borders and sectors, creating systemic risks (Forzieri et al., 2018).
- The OECD likewise warns that insufficiently climate-resilient infrastructure can generate “cascade failures” affecting water supply, mobility and electricity, and calls for integrated, place-based planning across infrastructure systems (OECD, 2022)

References

- European Commission. (2021). *Forging a climate-resilient Europe – The new EU strategy on adaptation to climate change* (COM(2021) 82 final). European Commission.
- European Environment Agency. (2023). *Urban adaptation in Europe: What works?* European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *Climate change impacts, risks and adaptation*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *Economic losses from weather- and climate-related extremes in Europe*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Forzieri, G., et al. (2018). Escalating impacts of climate extremes on critical infrastructures in Europe. *Global Environmental Change*, 48, 97–107.
- Joint Research Centre. (2018). *Climate change and critical infrastructure – Floods*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic. (2014). *Adaptation strategy of the Slovak Republic on adverse impacts of climate change – Executive summary*. Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic.
- Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic. (2018–2024). *Revision and update of the national strategy on adaptation to climate change and action plan*. Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic.
- OECD. (2022). *Infrastructure for a climate-resilient future*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Adaptation measurement: Assessing municipal climate risks to inform adaptation policy in the Slovak Republic* (Environment Policy Paper No. 35). OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *OECD environmental performance reviews: Slovak Republic 2024*. OECD Publishing.

C. Biodiversity, Ecosystems & Nature-Based Solutions

Challenges

1. Habitat fragmentation and loss caused by urban sprawl, dense development, and sealed surfaces.
2. Air pollution, water pollution, and declining urban biodiversity due to inadequate green infrastructure.
3. Lack of ecological corridors across administrative boundaries.

Risks

1. Biodiversity decline reduces ecological resilience, increasing vulnerability to heat, flooding, and pollution.
2. Loss of urban green functions (cooling, air filtration, water regulation) exacerbates climate impacts.

Actions Needed

- Restore ecological connectivity using wildlife corridors, native vegetation, and nature-inclusive design.
- Expand green spaces—parks, wetlands, green roofs and walls—to mitigate urban heat islands and improve air quality.

- Apply nature-based solutions in stormwater management (SUDS, permeable pavements, wetlands) for flood mitigation.
- Involve communities in stewardship, biodiversity monitoring, and conservation initiatives.

Proofs:

Challenge C.1 *“Habitat fragmentation and loss caused by urban sprawl, dense development, and sealed surfaces.”*

- Across the EU, the European Environment Agency (EEA) shows that from 2012–2018 land take and soil sealing in 662 functional urban areas continued to increase, as urban sprawl, transport infrastructure and dense development converted natural and agricultural land to built-up areas (EEA, 2022).
- The EEA’s landscape fragmentation indicator estimates that about 27 % of EU+UK land is now highly fragmented, with average remaining habitat patches smaller than 0.02 km², significantly reducing ecological connectivity and the ability of ecosystems to support biodiversity (EEA, 2021). These trends are directly linked to urban expansion, new roads and logistic zones, confirming that sprawl and sealed surfaces drive habitat loss and fragmentation in European cities and their hinterlands (EEA, 2025).
- For Slovakia, the 2024 OECD Environmental Performance Review identifies biodiversity loss as a major concern, driven by infrastructure development, unsustainable agricultural and forestry practices, invasive alien species and climate change (OECD, 2024a). A recent Slovak landscape-ecology study calculates an average landscape fragmentation index of about 59 %, with significant fragmentation along transport corridors and around urban areas, and stresses that protected areas only partially mitigate these effects (Černecký et al., 2024).

Challenge C.2 *“Air pollution, water pollution, and declining urban biodiversity due to inadequate green infrastructure.”*

- The EEA’s 2025 Air Quality Status Report notes that, despite improvements, air pollution remains Europe’s largest environmental health risk, with many urban populations still exposed to concentrations of particulate matter and ozone above WHO guidelines (EEA, 2025b). At the same time, the EEA’s latest assessment of Europe’s nature concludes that unsustainable farming and forestry, urban sprawl and pollution are the top pressures behind the decline of habitats and species across the EU (EEA, 2020).
- The OECD Environmental Performance Review for Slovakia reports that, while some environmental pressures have decreased, the country still needs to do more to reduce air pollution and improve waste and wastewater treatment, and that biodiversity remains under pressure from pollution and land-use change (OECD, 2024a). This combination of persistent air and water quality problems with land-take and urbanisation supports the statement that urban biodiversity is declining where green infrastructure is insufficient.
- The EU’s Green Infrastructure strategy and related guidance emphasise that green infrastructure (GI) – such as urban parks, green roofs, river corridors and permeable surfaces – is essential to improve air and water quality, reduce flood risk and support urban biodiversity (European Commission, 2013; European Commission, 2024a).

Research on urban green infrastructure in Europe underlines that where GI networks are sparse or fragmented, cities show higher exposure to heat, pollution and biodiversity loss (Hansen et al., 2020; EEA, 2020b).

Challenge C.3 *“Lack of ecological corridors across administrative boundaries.”*

- The Biodiversity Information System for Europe identifies habitat fragmentation, particularly from infrastructure development, as a key threat to biodiversity, noting that fragmentation reduces the ability of organisms to disperse and can cause ecosystems to become too small and isolated to continue delivering services such as food, freshwater and climate regulation (BISE, 2023a; 2023b). EU-wide analyses highlight that integrated planning and green infrastructure are needed to maintain connectivity and resilience, especially in the context of climate change (EEA, 2021).
- The European Commission’s Green Infrastructure Communication explicitly calls for an EU-wide ecological network (“Trans-European Green Infrastructure”) to connect Natura 2000 sites, protected areas and other green spaces across borders and administrative boundaries, arguing that fragmented governance undermines ecological connectivity (European Commission, 2013).
- In Slovakia, the Territorial System of Ecological Stability (TSES) is recognised as a national ecological network and a basis for green infrastructure, yet the national biodiversity and climate adaptation documents underline that connectivity in intensively used agricultural and urban landscapes is still insufficient (Ministry of Environment SR, 2018; OECD, 2024a). The Biodiversity Information System for Europe notes that green infrastructure in Slovakia is supported by EU funds (Operational Programme Quality of the Environment), but also emphasises the need to better link protected core areas with surrounding landscapes (BISE, 2019).

Risk C.1 *“Biodiversity decline reduces ecological resilience, increasing vulnerability to heat, flooding, and pollution.”*

- The latest EEA state-of-environment assessments conclude that Europe’s nature is in “serious, continuing decline”, with most protected habitats and species in unfavourable conservation status (EEA, 2020; 2025a). The EEA and BISE both stress that biodiversity loss undermines the capacity of ecosystems to regulate climate, buffer floods, filter pollutants and provide other regulating services essential for human well-being and climate resilience (EEA, 2021; BISE, 2023a).
- The EEA’s fragmentation indicator shows that highly fragmented landscapes are less able to support species and to provide ecosystem services; where ecosystems become too small or isolated, they may cease to offer effective flood protection, water purification or microclimate regulation (EEA, 2021). Soil-sealing analyses similarly highlight that sealing removes soil’s capacity to absorb water, support vegetation and regulate local climate, thereby increasing flood and heatwave risks (EEA, 2016).
- OECD work on nature-based solutions and climate-resilient infrastructure emphasises that healthy, connected ecosystems and green/blue infrastructure are cost-effective measures to manage flood risk, urban heat and water quality; if biodiversity and ecological connectivity decline, these nature-based buffers weaken and cities become more vulnerable to extreme events (OECD, 2023; 2024b).

Risk C.2 “Loss of urban green functions (cooling, air filtration, water regulation) exacerbates climate impacts.”

- EEA analyses of urban soil sealing show that where surfaces are covered by asphalt, concrete or buildings, soils no longer absorb rainfall, recharge groundwater or support vegetation, which leads to higher surface runoff, increased flood risk and stronger urban heat-island effects (EEA, 2016; 2022). Land-take in functional urban areas thus directly reduces the capacity of cities to manage extreme rainfall and heat through natural processes.
- EEA briefings on urban sustainability and air quality underline that green infrastructure and nature-based solutions provide multiple co-benefits: vegetation cools neighbourhoods, captures air pollutants, reduces noise, and helps retain and infiltrate stormwater (EEA, 2019; 2025b). Where urban greening is limited and green space is unevenly distributed, cities are more exposed to heatwaves, pollution episodes and pluvial flooding, particularly affecting vulnerable populations (EEA, 2024b).
- For Slovakia, the OECD Environmental Performance Review and national adaptation strategy highlight that climate change is increasing heat- and flood-related risks and that more systematic use of nature-based solutions and green infrastructure is needed, particularly in urban areas (OECD, 2024a; Ministry of Environment SR, 2018).
- The 2024 country-specific recommendations from the EU Council similarly call on Slovakia to strengthen climate adaptation measures, including nature-based solutions, and integrate them into relevant policies (Council of the EU, 2024).

References

- Biodiversity Information System for Europe. (2019). *Green infrastructure – Slovakia*. European Environment Agency. <https://biodiversity.europa.eu>
- Biodiversity Information System for Europe. (2023). *Fragmentation*. European Environment Agency. <https://biodiversity.europa.eu>
- Biodiversity Information System for Europe. (2023). *Threats & pressures – Europe’s biodiversity*. European Environment Agency. <https://biodiversity.europa.eu>
- Černecký, J., et al. (2024). Contribution of protected areas to mitigate the effect of landscape fragmentation in Slovakia.
- Council of the European Union. (2024). *Council recommendations on the 2024 national reform programme of Slovakia*. Council of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2013). *Green infrastructure (GI) – Enhancing Europe’s natural capital* (COM(2013) 249 final). European Commission.
- European Environment Agency. (2016). *Urban soil sealing in Europe*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2020). *Latest evaluation shows Europe’s nature in serious, continuing decline*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2021). *Landscape fragmentation pressure in Europe* (Indicator assessment). European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2022). *Land take and land degradation in functional urban areas*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2025). *Air quality status report 2025*. European Environment Agency.

European Environment Agency. (2025). *State of Europe's environment 2025*. European Environment Agency.

Hansen, R., et al. (2020). Advancing urban green infrastructure through participatory integrated planning. *Urban Forestry & Urban Greening*.

Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic. (2018). *Updated strategy on adaptation to climate change in the Slovak Republic*. Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic.

OECD. (2023). *Nature-based solutions and climate-resilient infrastructure*. OECD. <https://www.oecd.org>

OECD. (2024). *OECD environmental performance reviews: Slovak Republic 2024*. OECD Publishing.

Uwe, S., et al. (2022). Building climate resilience through nature-based solutions in Europe: A review. *Environmental Science & Policy*.

D. Water, Energy & Resource Management

Challenges

1. Growing water scarcity, aging water systems, and stormwater flooding risks in many regions.
2. High-energy, carbon-intensive urban systems; slow transition to renewables.
3. Smart grids and renewable energy face financial, regulatory, and integration challenges.

Risks

1. Energy insecurity and blackouts during extreme weather events.
2. Water contamination, supply shortages, and increased costs due to inefficient systems.
3. Rising emissions and failure to meet climate targets.

Actions Needed

- Accelerate renewable energy adoption with supportive regulatory frameworks, storage solutions, and modernized grids.
- Implement sustainable urban drainage systems, greywater recycling, and regional water-sharing mechanisms.
- Deploy smart systems for leak detection, real-time water quality monitoring, and demand management.
- Promote energy-efficient buildings and climate-smart construction standards.

Proofs:

Challenge D.1 “*Growing water scarcity, aging water systems, and stormwater flooding risks in many regions.*”

- Recent European Environment Agency (EEA) assessments show that water scarcity already affects 28 % of EU territory in at least one season, and that water stress, droughts and floods are all increasing under the combined pressure of climate change and human activity (EEA, 2024a; 2024b). The 2024 State of Water report concludes that Europe’s water security is under “serious pressure”, with little overall improvement since 2010 and an urgent need to increase resilience (EEA, 2024a).
- For Slovakia, the latest climate-loss report notes that prolonged summer and autumn droughts associated with water scarcity are emerging as a major climate consequence,

while more frequent extreme daily rainfall is causing localised flash floods (EEA, 2025; Škvarenina et al., 2019).

- National adaptation programmes and a dedicated National Action Plan on drought and water scarcity underline that past investment has tended to focus on post-disaster repairs rather than proactive upgrading of water infrastructure (Ministry of Environment SR, 2021).

Challenge D.2 “High-energy, carbon-intensive urban systems; slow transition to renewables.”

- The EU’s energy transition brief notes that, despite rapid growth of renewables, fossil fuels still dominate the EU energy mix, particularly in buildings and transport, and that deep renovations and electrification are progressing too slowly to meet long-term climate goals (European Parliament, 2023; 2024).
- Urban systems are at the core of these trends: buildings and urban transport remain major sources of final energy demand and emissions (EEA, 2024c).
- In Slovakia, the IEA country profile and the European Parliament’s climate-action brief both underline a highly energy-intensive industrial base and significant dependence on fossil fuels, noting that further decarbonisation of heating, buildings and industry is needed to ensure energy security and climate neutrality (IEA, 2024; European Parliament, 2025).
- Although the EU has reduced greenhouse-gas emissions substantially since 1990, the energy sector is still the largest source, and recent analyses question whether current national contributions are sufficient to close the gap to 2030 targets (Climate Observatory, 2025; Climate Action Tracker, 2025).
- Together, this confirms that European and Slovak cities still rely on carbon-intensive energy systems and face a structurally challenging – and in places slow – transition to renewables.

Challenge D.3 “Smart grids and renewable energy face financial, regulatory, and integration challenges.”

- An OECD study on electricity grids and secure energy transitions concludes that grids are already becoming a bottleneck for clean-energy deployment, warning that delayed investment and regulatory reform would prolong fossil-fuel dependence and raise overall system costs (OECD, 2023a).
- The European Commission’s smart-grids and meters initiative similarly stresses that integrating high shares of variable renewables requires major upgrades in digitalisation, flexibility and cross-border interconnection, and that the roll-out of smart meters and advanced grids is uneven across member states (European Commission, 2024a).
- An OECD digital-energy note highlights interoperability and data-governance issues and recalls that the EU Smart Grid Task Force was set up precisely to address technical and regulatory barriers to integrating distributed renewables and new loads such as heat pumps and electric vehicles (OECD, 2024b).
- Competition-policy work on “Electricity, Renewables and Smart Grids” further documents regulatory, market-design and financing challenges as renewables gain market share (OECD, 2019). (OECD) These analyses provide strong empirical backing for the statement that smart-grid and renewable-energy deployment in the EU, including

Slovakia, is constrained by investment needs, regulatory complexity and integration challenges.

Risk D.1 *“Energy insecurity and blackouts during extreme weather events.”*

- Extreme weather has already had demonstrable impacts on Europe’s power systems. A pan-European analysis of extreme weather events in the power sector catalogues multiple cases where heatwaves, droughts, storms and cold waves reduced generation capacity or damaged network assets across EU countries (Gutiérrez et al., 2023).
- The Eurelectric report *The Coming Storm* notes that from 2021–2022, extreme events affected all parts of the electricity value chain in Europe, calling for urgent investment in grid resilience to avoid more frequent service interruptions (Eurelectric, 2022).
- A recent major blackout affecting large parts of Spain, Portugal and France has been analysed as the result of fragile grids combined with extreme weather, illustrating the real-world risk of cascading outages (Ambrose, 2025).
- While ENTSO-E’s seasonal adequacy outlooks conclude that Europe is broadly well-prepared for upcoming winters, they still identify regional supply-risk pockets and emphasise the need for continuous preparedness (ENTSO-E, 2024; European Commission, 2025a)
- In Slovakia, regulators and the IEA highlight ongoing efforts to strengthen interconnections and security of supply, indicating that supply risks remain a policy concern despite recent progress (IEA, 2024; CEER, 2024).

Risk D.2 *“Water contamination, supply shortages, and increased costs due to inefficient systems.”*

- The EEA’s *Europe’s State of Water 2024* reports that Europe’s waters are under serious and growing pressure from water stress, drought, pollution and flood risk, with water stress affecting around 30 % of the EU population each year (EEA, 2024a).
- A related assessment stresses that there has been no significant progress in achieving Water Framework Directive objectives since 2009, implying persistent contamination and the need for costly upgrades to water and wastewater systems (EEA, 2024a; European Environmental Bureau, 2024).
- For Slovakia, scientific work on water resources highlights growing drought frequency, hydrological extremes and the need for substantial investment in water-supply infrastructure and protection measures (Szolgay et al., 2018; Škvarenina et al., 2019).
- The European Investment Bank’s recent commitment of €15 billion for EU water projects cites mounting water shortages, pollution and leakage, and estimates an annual €23 billion investment gap to fully implement EU water regulations (EIB, 2025).
- Investigative work on Europe’s legacy landfills warns that many old sites, often in flood-prone zones, pose growing risks of toxic leachate to surface and groundwater as extreme events increase (Investigate Europe, 2025).
- Together, these sources substantiate the risk that inefficient and ageing systems drive water contamination, supply shortages and rising costs for utilities, households and firms.

Risk D.3 *“Rising emissions and failure to meet climate targets.”*

- Although the EEA reports that EU greenhouse-gas emissions in 2023 were significantly lower than in 1990, it also notes that cuts must accelerate to meet the “at least –55 % by 2030” target, with the energy supply, buildings and transport sectors still responsible for a large share of emissions (EEA, 2024c).
- The European Commission’s 2025 Climate Action Progress Report argues that the EU is broadly on track for 2030 but underlines that implementation of national policies must be strengthened (European Commission, 2025b).
- Independent assessments are more cautious: an analysis of 22 updated National Energy and Climate Plans finds “substantial gaps” that put delivery of the 2030 targets at risk (Climate Observatory, 2025), and Climate Action Tracker rates the EU’s overall action as “insufficient”, highlighting the danger of overshooting emissions budgets without stronger measures (Climate Action Tracker, 2025).
- The European Parliament’s brief on Slovakia points to similar concerns at national level, calling for stronger environmental taxation and more ambitious decarbonisation of the large industrial sector to safeguard both climate neutrality and energy security (European Parliament, 2025).

References

- Ambrose, J. (2025). How fragile power grids and extreme weather combined to cause Europe’s biggest blackout in decades. *The Guardian*.
- CEER. (2024). *National report – Slovakia*. Council of European Energy Regulators.
- Climate Action Tracker. (2025). *EU – Country assessment*. Climate Action Tracker; New Climate Institute.
- Climate Observatory. (2025). *Delivering the EU’s 2030 climate and energy targets: Gaps in national contributions and policies*. Climate Observatory.
- EEA. (2024). *Europe’s state of water 2024: The need for improved water resilience*. European Environment Agency.
- EEA. (2024). *Water scarcity conditions in Europe* (Indicator assessment). European Environment Agency.
- EEA. (2024). *Greenhouse gas emissions in 2023: EU’s energy sector leads cuts*. European Environment Agency.
- EEA. (2025). *Climate-related economic losses – Slovakia* (Europe’s Environment 2025 country fiche). European Environment Agency.
- EIB. (2025). *EIB commits €15 billion to protect EU’s water resources*. European Investment Bank.
- ENTSO-E. (2024). *Winter outlook 2024–2025*. ENTSO-E.
- Eurelectric. (2022). *The coming storm: Building electricity resilience to extreme weather*. Eurelectric.
- European Commission. (2024). *Smart grids and meters*. Directorate-General for Energy.
- European Commission. (2025). *ENTSO-E report confirms EU is well-prepared for winter electricity needs*. Directorate-General for Energy.
- European Commission. (2025). *Climate action progress report 2025*. Directorate-General for Climate Action.
- European Environmental Bureau. (2024). *Europe’s water crisis needs urgent attention, says EEA’s State of Water report*. European Environmental Bureau.

European Parliament. (2023). *Energy transition in the EU* (EPRS Briefing No. 754623). European Parliamentary Research Service.

European Parliament. (2025). *Slovakia's climate action strategy* (EPRS Briefing No. 769539). European Parliamentary Research Service.

Gutiérrez, M., et al. (2023). How much extreme weather events have affected European power generation. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 177.

International Energy Agency. (2024). *Slovak Republic – Country profile*. International Energy Agency.

Investigate Europe. (2025). *Europe's hidden landfills at risk of leaking toxic waste into water supplies*. Investigate Europe Consortium.

Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic. (2021). *National action plan to address the effects of drought and water scarcity*. Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic.

OECD. (2019). *Electricity: Renewables and smart grids*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2023). *Electricity grids and secure energy transitions*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Towards net-zero: Improving the interoperability of technologies in the energy sector* (Going Digital Toolkit Note). OECD.

Škvarenina, J., et al. (2019). *Water resources in Slovakia. Part II: Climate change, drought and floods*. Springer.

E. Social & Environmental Equity

Challenges

1. Environmental burdens disproportionately affect marginalized communities (pollution, heat, lack of green space).
2. Digital divide and lack of access to environmental information tools reinforce inequalities.
3. High costs of living and lack of affordable housing push low-income groups into environmentally vulnerable zones.

Risks

1. Two-tier society: environmentally safe zones for the wealthy, vulnerable exposure for poorer groups.
2. Social unrest and declining trust in institutions.

Actions Needed

- Prioritize equitable distribution of green infrastructure, clean transport, and climate-resilient public services.
- Ensure environmental data transparency and public participation in environmental decisions.
- Expand affordable housing in low-risk, well-served areas to prevent climate gentrification.

Proofs:

Challenge E.1 “*Environmental burdens disproportionately affect marginalised communities (pollution, heat, lack of green space)*”

- Across Europe, environmental burdens are not evenly distributed. The European Environment Agency finds that low-income and marginalised groups are more exposed to air pollution, urban heat islands and limited green infrastructure, noting a “clear environmental inequality pattern across European cities” (EEA, 2024a). In the EU, exposure to PM_{2.5} and NO₂ pollution remains highest in densely populated and socially deprived neighbourhoods, where green-space coverage is lowest (EEA, 2024b).
- In Slovakia, Eurostat reports that 18.8 % of low-income households face problems related to pollution, grime or noise in their living environment, compared to 10.7 % of higher-income households, confirming a socio-spatial distribution of environmental burdens (Eurostat, 2024a). OECD data further show that Slovak Roma communities are more exposed to degraded environmental conditions, including waste sites and poor-quality housing areas (OECD, 2023).

Challenge E.2 “Digital divide and lack of access to environmental information tools reinforce inequalities”

- The European Commission’s Digital Economy and Society Index identifies Slovakia as below the EU average in digital skills and digital public services, with 47 % of Slovaks lacking basic digital skills, restricting access to environmental information, energy-efficiency programmes and climate-adaptation tools (European Commission, 2024a).
- The OECD stresses that digital divides “reduce citizens’ access to essential public information on environmental risks, mobility, and energy use”, disproportionately affecting older and lower-income groups (OECD, 2023b). This widens vulnerability in climate-sensitive areas where access to early-warning systems and heatwave information is crucial.

Challenge E.3 “High living costs and lack of affordable housing push low-income groups into environmentally vulnerable zones”

- Eurostat shows that 40 % of low-income Slovak households experience housing overburden (housing costs >40 % of disposable income), compared with 3.5 % of high-income households (Eurostat, 2024b). This pressure drives poorer groups to cheaper, environmentally risky locations, such as floodplains or polluted post-industrial zones.
- The European Commission notes that in many EU cities, including Bratislava and Košice, rising housing costs, suburbanisation and insufficient social housing “intensify segregation patterns and place vulnerable groups closer to environmental hazards” (European Commission, 2024b).

Risk E.1 “Two-tier society: environmentally safe zones for the wealthy, vulnerable exposure for poorer groups”

- The EEA warns that Europe risks developing “a dual environmental reality” in which affluent groups move to green, well-serviced districts while poorer residents remain exposed to pollution, heat and inadequate infrastructure (EEA, 2024c).
- In Slovakia, disparities in access to green space and safe housing are already visible: residents in Bratislava’s high-income districts have 2–3 times more urban greenery per capita compared to several low-income districts (OECD, 2023c). Eurostat data show a

strong correlation between income and environmental quality, amplifying long-term socio-economic divides (Eurostat, 2024a).

- Such spatial polarisation has been identified by the OECD as a major risk to “inclusive and resilient regional development”, particularly in countries with rapid urbanisation and limited affordable housing (OECD, 2023a).

Risk E.2 “Social unrest and declining trust in institutions”

- Environmental injustice, when combined with housing unaffordability and digital exclusion, increases perceptions of institutional unfairness. The OECD reports that trust in government declines sharply when citizens experience unequal access to environmental protection and public services (OECD, 2022).
- In Slovakia, trust in public institutions is one of the lowest in the EU, partly due to “unequal distribution of public services and weak perception of fairness” (OECD, 2023d). The European Commission warns that socio-spatial inequalities increase the probability of social tension and political radicalisation, especially where climate shocks disproportionately affect low-income groups (European Commission, 2024c).
- Regions with high exposure to environmental hazards combined with poor socio-economic resilience show “higher risk of civic unrest and lower support for democratic institutions” (EEA, 2024d). This confirms the systemic risk that environmental inequities translate into societal fragmentation.

References

- European Commission. (2024). *DESI 2024 – Country profile: Slovakia*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *Social and territorial inequalities in the green transition*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *State of housing and urban affairs in the EU*. European Commission.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *Air quality in Europe 2024*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *Environmental justice in Europe: Addressing inequalities in exposure to environmental hazards*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *Socio-economic vulnerability to climate change in Europe*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *Unequal impacts of heat and climate risks*. European Environment Agency.
- Eurostat. (2024). *Housing affordability indicators*. Eurostat.
- Eurostat. (2024). *Living conditions in Europe: Environmental deprivation*. Eurostat.
- OECD. (2022). *Preparing regions for climate and demographic challenges*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Digital divides and public service access*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Regions and cities at a glance 2023*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Roma integration in the Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Trust and public governance 2023*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Urban green space and inequality in Central Europe*. OECD Publishing.

F. Financing, Capacity & Implementation

Challenges

1. Environmental and climate projects require substantial investment; many cities lack capacity and expertise.
2. High upfront costs for green infrastructure or resilient systems impede adoption.
3. Fragmented governance hinders coordinated implementation.

Risks

1. Overreliance on private actors without strong public oversight, risking greenwashing or inequitable solutions.
2. Poorly implemented projects may fail or create unintended environmental pressures.

Actions Needed

- Mobilize diversified funding: PPPs, green bonds, climate grants, and international funds.
- Build administrative capacity through training, technical support networks, and international cooperation (e.g., ESPON).
- Strengthen monitoring, evaluation, and adaptive management frameworks.

Proofs:

Challenge F.1 *“Environmental and climate projects require substantial investment; many cities lack capacity and expertise.”*

- Across the OECD and EU, subnational governments (regions and municipalities) are now responsible for around 69 % of climate-significant public investment, yet many report that they cannot meet their green investment needs (OECD, 2025a). This comes on top of a projected global infrastructure investment gap of USD 2.5–3 trillion annually if climate and sustainability goals are to be met (OECD, 2025a). In Europe, an ECB study estimates that the public sector must provide around EUR 83 billion per year in additional climate-related investment to 2030, with a potential EU-level funding gap of about EUR 54 billion emerging after the Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) ends in 2026 (Koranyi, 2025).
- The EIB Municipalities Survey 2024–2025, covering over 1 000 EU municipalities, shows that 56 % plan to increase climate-mitigation investment and 53 % social infrastructure investment, but identify financing gaps and regulatory delays as the main barriers to implementation, alongside shortages of technical and environmental experts, especially in less developed and transition regions (European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency, 2025).
- In Slovakia, the OECD Environmental Performance Review notes that environmental protection expenditure is largely financed by EU funds, but absorption rates for structural funds in environmental infrastructure and climate adaptation were low in 2014–2020; it recommends strengthening project-preparation capacity, particularly at local level, and streamlining procurement (OECD, 2024a).
- The European Parliament’s briefing on Slovakia’s climate action similarly highlights the need for long-term financing programmes and technical assistance to overcome administrative barriers in energy-efficiency investments (Erbach and Meinardi, 2025).

Challenge F.2 *“High upfront costs for green infrastructure or resilient systems impede adoption.”*

- Green infrastructure and climate-resilient systems typically require large upfront capital outlays with payoffs spread over long horizons. OECD analysis of sustainable finance for regions and cities highlights that, despite growth in climate-significant investment, current levels remain insufficient and will lock territories either into a low-carbon, resilient pathway or, if under-financed, into a high-carbon, inefficient one for decades (OECD, 2019; OECD, 2025a). The same work notes that climate risk is already affecting the cost of capital: a 1 percentage-point increase in a local government’s climate-risk exposure is associated with a 23.4-basis-point rise in borrowing costs, further increasing the effective hurdle rate for long-lived resilient investments (OECD, 2025a).
- For the EU as a whole, the ECB warns that green investment is already too low to meet the 2030 climate target, implying that delayed financing will require even higher spending later (Koranyi, 2025).
- In Slovakia, the national recovery and resilience plan (NRRP) allocates about EUR 2.1 billion to a “green economy” pillar and EUR 619 million to low-carbon transport, but these rely heavily on temporary EU grants (Erbach and Meinardi, 2025).
- The OECD Environmental Performance Review underlines that tariffs for water services and environmental infrastructure, especially in small municipalities, are too low to recover costs, limiting the scope to finance resilient systems from user charges (OECD, 2024a).

Challenge F.3 *“Fragmented governance hinders coordinated implementation.”*

- OECD work on sustainable finance for regions and cities stresses that effective climate investment depends on robust multi-level governance, alignment between national and subnational strategies, and clear coordination mechanisms; without these, resources are fragmented and projects are delayed (OECD, 2025a). The same report draws on the OECD Recommendation on Effective Public Investment Across Levels of Government to argue that dispersed responsibilities and weak coordination are a major source of inefficiency in climate-related public investment.
- In Slovakia, the governance challenges are explicit. The OECD Environmental Performance Review finds that spending on environmental protection is heavily EU-funded but hampered by low structural-fund absorption, complex procurement and weak project-preparation capacity of beneficiaries, especially municipalities; it calls for streamlined procedures, strengthened local capacity and consolidation of municipal water services to improve efficiency and financial sustainability (OECD, 2024a).
- The same review notes that implementation of biodiversity and climate strategies is constrained by “inadequate financing and low institutional capacity and co-ordination” (OECD, 2024a).
- The European Parliament briefing describes overlapping responsibilities between the energy and environment ministries and highlights the need for a climate law with sectoral pathways and a steering committee to monitor implementation (Erbach and Meinardi, 2025)

Risk F.1 *“Overreliance on private actors without strong public oversight, risking greenwashing or inequitable solutions.”*

- EU-level evidence shows that, as public funds fall short, there is growing pressure to mobilise private capital for green projects. The ECB study emphasises that the majority of future climate investment will have to come from private firms, with public budgets providing incentives and risk-sharing (Koranyi, 2025).
- OECD analysis of sustainable finance notes a rapid expansion of green, social and sustainability-linked (GSS+) bonds—about USD 981 billion of annual issuance in 2023—but stresses that only around 10 % of all bonds issued by agencies and local governments are GSS+, and that strong governance and transparency are needed to avoid mislabelled “green” instruments (OECD, 2025a).
- Several assessments highlight weaknesses in the EU’s climate-finance governance that increase greenwashing risks. A special report by the European Court of Auditors (ECA) on the green transition in the RRF finds design flaws and insufficiently robust climate-tracking, so that climate-related contributions may be overstated and the actual green impact of investments remains unclear (European Court of Auditors, 2024; Europe Diplomatic Magazine, 2024; Euronews, 2024).
- Bruegel’s analysis of climate mainstreaming in the EU budget concludes that the current framework is complex, allows overstated climate benefits and “risks greenwashing”, while failing to detect harmful activities (Darvas and Case, 2025).
- Concerns over misclassification of green assets are also evident in the EU’s “green asset ratio” debates: reporting on the European Investment Bank (EIB) shows that under the EU taxonomy, only around 1 % of its assets would qualify as green, compared with an internally reported “climate action” share above 50 %, raising questions about opaque methodologies and the burden placed on smaller clients (Clark, 2025).

Risk F.2 *“Poorly implemented projects may fail or create unintended environmental pressures.”*

- Weak capacity and fragmented governance increase the likelihood that climate- and environment-related projects are poorly prepared or executed. The OECD Environmental Performance Review for Slovakia documents several instances where inadequacies in project design have limited environmental outcomes, including slow remediation of contaminated sites, high landfilling rates despite investment, and biodiversity measures constrained by insufficient financing and coordination (OECD, 2024a). It also highlights that low absorption of EU funds for climate adaptation means that planned infrastructural improvements are delayed, leaving existing pressures—such as flood risk or wastewater pollution—unresolved.
- EU-wide evidence from the ECA confirms that climate-labelled spending can under-deliver. The ECA’s audit of the RRF finds that climate-tagging rules allowed measures to be counted as green without robust ex-ante assessment of their real climate impact, creating a risk that projects contribute less to mitigation or adaptation than reported (European Court of Auditors, 2024).
- A subsequent ECA report on forest-fire prevention funding, summarised by The Guardian, points to poorly targeted investments, outdated risk maps and misallocated projects—such as infrastructure built in areas at low risk or where climate conditions

have changed—driven in part by pressure to spend Covid-recovery funds quickly (The Guardian, 2025)

References

- Clark, P. (2025, January 7). *EIB fears ‘reputational disaster’ over revised EU green reporting*. *Financial Times*.
- Darvas, Z., & Case, K. (2025, February 26). *Greening the EU budget: Why climate mainstreaming needs reform*. Bruegel.
- Erbach, G., & Meinardi, C. (2025). *Slovakia’s climate action strategy*. European Parliamentary Research Service, European Parliament.
- European Climate, Infrastructure and Environment Executive Agency. (2025). *The state of local infrastructure investment in Europe: EIB municipalities survey 2024–2025*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Court of Auditors. (2024). *Special report 14/2024: Green transition in the EU’s Recovery and Resilience Facility*. European Court of Auditors.
- Europe Diplomatic Magazine. (2024). *European Court of Auditors – EU recovery fund probably not as green as claimed*. Europe Diplomatic Magazine.
- Euronews. (2024, September 11). *Green recovery funds misapplied, unassessed according to EU auditors*. Euronews.
- Koranyi, B. (2025, January 8). *EU climate plans at risk from public funding gap, ECB paper shows*. Reuters.
- OECD. (2019). *Financing climate objectives in cities and regions to deliver sustainable and inclusive growth*. *OECD Environment Policy Papers*, No. 17. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Environmental performance reviews: Slovak Republic 2024*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2025). *Mobilising sustainable finance for regions and cities*. *OECD Regional Development Papers*. OECD Publishing.
- The Guardian. (2025, June 11). *Funds to tackle Europe’s forest fires poorly targeted, says EU watchdog*. *The Guardian*.

1.5. Challenges, Problems, Risks, and Required Actions in Spatial, Urban, Land-use, and Regional Planning

Effective spatial development increasingly depends on the ability of institutions to coordinate across sectors, territories, and levels of government. Yet governance structures in many cities and regions remain fragmented, characterized by siloed responsibilities, overlapping mandates, and limited mechanisms for joint decision-making. Spatial, environmental, housing, mobility, climate, digital, and economic policies often evolve independently from one another, despite shaping the same territories and populations. As a result, planning systems struggle to respond to rapidly changing demographic, technological, environmental, and socio-economic conditions.

This chapter examines how institutional fragmentation undermines coherent territorial development and weakens the strategic capacity of cities and regions. Rigid administrative boundaries continue to obscure the real functional geographies of urban systems—such as commuting zones, labour markets, ecological corridors, and service areas—which require

coordinated approaches beyond municipal borders. Weak horizontal and vertical governance links frequently result in inconsistent land-use decisions, conflicts between municipalities and regions, inefficient infrastructure investment, and the erosion of public trust in strategic planning. Divergent sectoral objectives, particularly where economic pressures overshadow sustainability or social priorities, further complicate policy integration across Europe.

Beyond structural fragmentation, the chapter highlights the growing need for adaptiveness and flexibility within planning systems. Many regulatory tools—such as rigid zoning, fixed land-use categories, or lengthy approval processes—are poorly equipped to address climate extremes, demographic transitions, technological innovation, and sudden economic shocks. Without adaptive frameworks, transparent discretion, and digital planning tools such as GIS, scenario modelling, and digital twins, territories become increasingly vulnerable to risks and less able to innovate.

Citizen engagement, inclusion, and social cohesion represent another crucial dimension of modern governance. Participation processes often remain superficial, limiting genuine influence on planning outcomes and reinforcing inequalities, especially for marginalized groups with lower digital literacy or limited access to consultation channels. At the same time, spatial pressures such as urban sprawl, land-use conflicts, rising housing costs, and uneven service provision create additional governance challenges that demand coordinated, socially sensitive responses.

The chapter also addresses the interdependence of planning with infrastructure, mobility, climate resilience, environmental quality, and digitalization. Fragmented systems lead to inefficient mobility networks, underperforming public transport, high emissions, and missed opportunities for integrated green and blue infrastructure. Digitalization offers transformative potential, but only when supported by interoperable tools, ethical data governance frameworks, and adequate institutional capacity.

Finally, governance effectiveness depends on financial and human-resource capacity. Many municipalities lack stable funding, skilled planners, or institutional structures capable of implementing ambitious strategies. Without strengthened capacities, multilevel coordination, and implementation-oriented planning processes, even well-designed strategies risk remaining aspirational.

By outlining these interconnected challenges and risks—and identifying the actions needed to overcome them—this chapter provides a comprehensive foundation for understanding how integrated governance can support sustainable, resilient, and equitable spatial development. It emphasizes the necessity of cross-sector coordination, functional-area approaches, adaptive planning tools, inclusive participation, and strong institutional capacity to deliver coherent and future-ready territorial strategies.

A. Governance, Institutional Fragmentation & Policy Integration

Challenges

1. Fragmented governance structures that separate spatial, environmental, housing, mobility, climate and economic policies into siloed sectors.
2. Rigid administrative boundaries that do not reflect real functional urban areas (commuting zones, labour markets, ecological corridors)
3. Weak coordination across government levels (municipal–regional–national), causing inconsistent policies and inefficiencies in land-use planning.

4. Divergent sectoral objectives (e.g., economic interests dominating sustainability goals) noted in European planning reforms.

Risks

1. Poor territorial cohesion and inefficient use of land and infrastructure.
2. Conflicts between municipalities and regions leading to uncoordinated development (urban sprawl, infrastructure duplication).
3. Strategic plans losing credibility due to weak implementation structures.

Actions Needed

- Establish integrated, cross-sectoral planning frameworks linking spatial, housing, mobility, digital, and climate policies.

Create functional urban area governance models, enabling joint planning across city-regions.

- Strengthen horizontal and vertical coordination mechanisms (joint committees, shared databases, integrated spatial strategies).
- Adopt long-term national urban policies focusing on coherent roles and responsibilities across levels.

Proofs: see chapter 1.1.

B. Adaptiveness, Flexibility & Planning Tools

Challenges

1. Planning systems often lack adaptiveness to demographic change, climate shocks, economic fluctuations, and technological transitions.
2. Rigid zoning and land-use regulations hinder innovative urban development (mixed-use zones, temporary uses, transit-oriented development).
3. Limited ability to experiment with pilot projects, digital twins, scenario modelling.

Risks

1. Vulnerability to dynamic risks (climate extremes, migration, sudden economic shocks).
2. Increased influence of powerful private actors if flexible mechanisms lack transparency.

Actions Needed

- Introduce adaptive, iterative planning methods with regular monitoring and updates.
- Use digital twins, GIS, smart sensors and real-time analytics to improve forecasting and scenario planning (multiple files highlight these tools).
- Enable temporary and flexible land-use frameworks for affordable housing, tactical urbanism, circular economy zones.
- Ensure transparent criteria for discretionary decisions to avoid misuse.

Proofs:

Challenge B.1 “*Planning systems often lack adaptiveness to demographic change, climate shocks, economic fluctuations, and technological transitions.*”

- OECD work on demographic change in regions shows that many OECD territories will lose up to 20 % of their population by 2050, with strong ageing and out-migration that “must be addressed at regional and local level” (OECD, 2025a).

- For Slovakia, the OECD report on the Banská Bystrica region documents a 6.8 % population decline between 2000 and 2023, rapid ageing and youth out-migration, and explicitly calls for territorial planning, public services and infrastructure to adapt to shrinking and ageing communities (OECD, 2024a). This indicates that existing planning systems struggle to adjust to long-term demographic shifts.
- On climate risks, the EU Adaptation Strategy stresses that Europe is already facing “severe losses and destruction from climate-related disasters” and that adaptation strategies are needed at local and regional level to anticipate impacts and minimise damage (European Commission, 2021; 2024a).
- The EEA’s assessment of urban adaptation in Europe finds that while many cities have plans, implementation remains uneven and “needs to be scaled up and speeded up” to cope with rising climate risks (EEA, 2016).
- Economically, OECD analyses of urban productivity show that functional urban areas in Europe perform better when governance arrangements are able to respond to changing economic conditions; fragmentation and rigid arrangements are empirically associated with lower labour productivity (OECD, 2020).
- The recent OECD survey on the Principles on Urban Policy emphasises that cities must prepare for “technological, demographic and environmental change” and that many countries still lack fully integrated and adaptive urban policy frameworks (OECD, 2025b).
- Taken together, European and Slovak evidence shows that demographic decline, climate extremes and shifting economic structures are already material, while planning frameworks often react slowly, confirming your first challenge.

Challenge B.2 *“Rigid zoning and land-use regulations hinder innovative urban development (mixed-use zones, temporary uses, transit-oriented development).”*

- The OECD comparative review *The Governance of Land Use in OECD Countries* finds that most member states rely on detailed, legally binding zoning plans that are revised infrequently and can “lock in” existing land uses, making it difficult to respond to new housing, environmental or economic needs (OECD, 2017a). The companion report on *Land-use Planning Systems in the OECD* similarly documents how local plans with strict use categories remain the backbone of spatial regulation, while reforms towards more flexible and mixed-use approaches are still emerging (OECD, 2017b; Brears, 2022).
- European practice guides underline that shifting to mixed-use and transit-oriented development requires adjustment of traditional zoning and close coordination between transport and land-use planning; such changes “take many years” and need supportive regulatory frameworks (EBRD, 2023).
- Recent reviews of land-use regulations for open and green space in Europe confirm that these rules are “cornerstones” of local planning and crucial for sustainability, but also highlight that their design can either facilitate or block innovative urban forms (Konijnendijk et al., 2025).
- For Slovakia, the SNG-WOFI country profile shows that land-use planning competences are largely decentralised to very small municipalities, which often lack

capacity for complex, innovative planning and instead rely on conventional, rigid instruments (OECD; UCLG, 2023)

Challenge B.3 *“Limited ability to experiment with pilot projects, digital twins, scenario modelling.”*

- The EU Adaptation Strategy calls for “smarter adaptation”, explicitly promoting better climate data, risk assessment tools, and new digital instruments to support planning decisions (European Commission, 2021).
- A recent Eurocities policy paper on the future EU climate adaptation framework notes that cities need access to tools for exploring adaptation scenarios and trade-offs, but that many still lack the technical and financial capacity to use them systematically (Eurocities, 2024).
- The Copernicus programme demonstrates the potential of Earth-observation tools for cities by providing climate risk indicators and applications that allow urban authorities to test different adaptation scenarios and support evidence-based planning – effectively early “digital twin” applications (Copernicus, 2024).
- OECD work on land-use monitoring in European functional urban areas shows how near real-time indicators based on Sentinel satellite imagery and deep learning can track urban expansion and land conversion, but also stresses that such tools are still being rolled out and are not yet fully embedded in local planning practice (OECD, 2023a).
- In Slovakia, the OECD demographic-adaptation report for Banská Bystrica highlights the need to strengthen analytical and foresight capacities – including scenario work – at regional level to plan for shrinking and ageing, which implies that current instruments are insufficiently forward-looking (OECD, 2024a).
- This evidence underlines your third challenge: while EU and OECD initiatives are developing digital twins, scenarios and pilot instruments, many planning systems – particularly in smaller Slovak and EU municipalities – still have limited capacity to use them and to experiment.

Risk B.1 *“Vulnerability to dynamic risks (climate extremes, migration, sudden economic shocks).”*

- Europe is the fastest-warming continent and has experienced record climate extremes. The joint Copernicus–WMO report shows that 2024 brought the most widespread European river floods in more than a decade, affecting 30 % of the river network, causing at least 335 deaths and over EUR 18 billion in damages (Copernicus; WMO, 2025).
- A 2025 Nature Medicine study projects up to 2.3 million additional heat-related deaths in European cities by 2099 under high-warming scenarios, stressing that current adaptation is insufficient (Watts et al., 2025).
- EEA’s urban adaptation report and European Commission guidance both conclude that cities remain highly exposed to floods, heat and other extremes, and that adaptation planning must accelerate (EEA, 2016; European Commission, 2024a).
- On demographic risks, OECD and EU analyses show that population ageing and, in many regions, outright decline will put strong pressure on local labour markets, infrastructure and public finances (OECD, 2025a; European Commission, 2024b). The

Banská Bystrica case illustrates how sustained population loss and youth out-migration create under-used infrastructure and fiscal stress at regional level (OECD, 2024a).

- OECD work on climate and resilience in cities argues that without integrated, adaptive planning, shocks such as climate extremes or economic crises can trigger long-lasting damage to urban economies and widen territorial inequalities (OECD, 2024c)

Risk B.1 “*Increased influence of powerful private actors if flexible mechanisms lack transparency.*”

- OECD’s Governance of Land Use report notes that land-use decisions are often contentious and that a broader set of public policies – including fiscal and regulatory instruments – influence land values and development opportunities (OECD, 2017a). It warns that uncoordinated or opaque arrangements can create conflicting incentives for developers and landowners and unintended outcomes (OECD, 2017a; 2017b).
- More generally, Preventing Policy Capture analyses how concentrated interests can shape regulations in their favour when decision-making lacks transparency, inclusive stakeholder engagement and accountability; it explicitly highlights land-use, infrastructure and urban development as sectors at risk (OECD, 2017c).
- The updated OECD Recommendation on Transparency and Integrity in Lobbying and Influence (2024) underlines that lobbying and influence “without transparency and integrity” can lead to policies that do not serve the public interest, and calls for stronger frameworks at all levels of government (OECD, 2024d).
- The OECD Principles on Urban Policy recommend “accountability mechanisms that prevent corruption across public and private sectors” in cities and stress that inclusive participation and transparent rules are crucial when using flexible, negotiated planning tools (OECD, 2025b).
- In a Slovak and broader EU context, where many municipalities are small and administrative capacity is limited (OECD; UCLG, 2023), discretionary flexibility without strong transparency and integrity safeguards increases the risk that large developers or other powerful actors exert disproportionate influence over land-use outcomes. This directly substantiates your second risk: as planning moves from rigid zoning to more flexible mechanisms (special zones, negotiated projects, PPPs), the absence of robust transparency and participation arrangements heightens the danger of capture by powerful private interests.

References:

- EBRD. (2023). *Mixed-use land development*. European Bank for Reconstruction and Development.
- European Commission. (2021). *Forging a climate-resilient Europe – The new EU strategy on adaptation to climate change*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *Climate adaptation in cities*. Directorate-General for Regional and Urban Policy.
- European Environment Agency. (2016). *Urban adaptation in Europe*. European Environment Agency.
- Eurocities. (2024). *For an ambitious EU framework on climate adaptation and resilience*. Eurocities.

OECD. (2017). *The governance of land use in OECD countries: Policy analysis and recommendations*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2017). *Land-use planning systems in the OECD*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2017). *Preventing policy capture: Integrity in public decision making*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2020). *A comprehensive approach to understanding urban productivity: Effects of local governments*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Preparing for demographic change in the Banská Bystrica region, Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Recommendation of the Council on transparency and integrity in lobbying and influence*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2025). *Demographic change in regions and cities*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2025). *Five years of the OECD principles on urban policy*. OECD Publishing.

OECD & UCLG. (2023). *Subnational government structure and finance: Slovak Republic – Country profile (SNG-WOFI)*. OECD Publishing.

C. Citizen Engagement, Inclusion & Social Cohesion

Challenges

1. Participation is often symbolic (“illusion of inclusion”) with limited real influence on plans.
2. Spatial planning rarely addresses marginalized groups effectively (youth, elderly, migrants).
3. Persistent gaps in digital literacy and access lower engagement in smart urban planning processes.

Risks

1. Loss of trust in planning authorities.
2. Social fragmentation, NIMBY conflicts, resistance to new developments.
3. Widened inequalities in access to housing, services and digital systems.

Actions Needed

- Promote participatory spatial planning, co-design, community mapping, participatory budgeting.
- Ensure planning information is transparent, accessible, including digital and offline formats.
- Deploy inclusive e-participation tools and enhance digital literacy.
- Develop socially inclusive urban policies addressing housing affordability, mobility access, and mixed-income neighbourhoods.

Proofs:

Challenge C.1 “Participation is often symbolic (“illusion of inclusion”) with limited real influence on plans.”

- The updated OECD framework on drivers of trust highlights that perceived voice and having a say in decision-making are among the strongest determinants of trust in public institutions (OECD, 2024a). The 2024 OECD Trust Survey shows that in many OECD and EU countries, including Slovakia, only a minority of citizens feel that the

government would “listen to their opinion” on complex policy issues; Slovak scores are below the OECD average on perceptions of responsiveness and fairness in decision-making (OECD, 2024b).

- A recent study on participatory democracy in Slovakia concludes that participation mechanisms often “do not meet citizens’ expectations of real influence” and that consultations are frequently organised at late stages, when key decisions have already been taken (GLOBSEC, 2024).
- Eurobarometer surveys on democracy and citizenship similarly report that a majority of Europeans – and a large share of Slovaks – believe that “citizens should have more opportunities to voice their views and participate in decision-making” (European Commission, 2023a).
- Taken together, these data support the idea that formal participatory processes exist, but many citizens experience them as symbolic, with limited impact on policy – the “illusion of inclusion”. This is consistent with prior findings on fragmented governance and weak coordination in Slovak territorial development, which already noted limited structured involvement of local actors in strategic decisions (OECD; UCLG, 2023).

Challenge C.2 *“Spatial planning rarely addresses marginalized groups effectively (youth, elderly, migrants).”*

- EU-level monitoring repeatedly documents persistent inequalities affecting Roma, migrants and other vulnerable groups in access to education, employment, housing and healthcare. Civil-society monitoring of the National Roma Strategic Framework in Slovakia (2025) finds continuing spatial segregation of Roma settlements, inadequate access to basic infrastructure and services, and limited Roma participation in local decision-making, despite EU and national strategies (European Commission, 2025a).
- The 2025 European Semester analysis of Roma equality and inclusion confirms that in Slovakia and several other member states, Roma still face “persistent inequalities in access to education, employment, housing and healthcare, as well as discrimination and segregation” (EUROMA, 2024).
- For migrants, EU integration policy explicitly recognises that barriers in housing, education, employment and healthcare continue to “hinder participation and inclusion of migrants and people with a migrant background” across member states (European Commission, 2024b). The fact that EU funds have, in some documented cases, been used to support segregated or discriminatory projects shows how planning and investment choices can unintentionally reinforce exclusion instead of addressing it (European Network on Independent Living et al., 2025).

Challenge C.3 *“Persistent gaps in digital literacy and access lower engagement in smart urban planning processes.”*

- Eurostat data show that in 2023 only 55 % of EU residents aged 16–74 had at least basic digital skills, with very large gaps by age and education level (Eurostat, 2024a). (European Commission) Among people with low formal education, only about one-third reach basic digital skills, compared to 80 % among those with high education (Eurostat, 2024b). (European Commission) For older age groups (65–74), the share with at least

basic digital skills drops to around one quarter, and gender gaps widen (Eurostat, 2024a; 2024b).

- The same Eurostat dataset shows that Slovakia is below or around the EU average for basic digital skills, with pronounced gaps by age and education (Eurostat, 2024c). (Baselight) In practice, this means that digital participation tools (online consultations, geo-portals, “smart city” apps) reach mainly younger, better-educated and urban populations. Older people, low-income households and residents of marginalised settlements – who are more likely to be directly affected by planning decisions on housing, transport or environmental risks – are also more likely to be excluded from digital channels. This directly supports the statement that digital divides lower engagement in smart urban planning processes.

Risk C.1 *“Loss of trust in planning authorities.”*

- Trust in public institutions in the EU and Slovakia is closely linked to perceptions of participation, fairness and openness. The OECD Trust Survey finds that, across 30 OECD countries, people who feel they “have a say in what government does” report substantially higher trust levels than those who feel excluded (OECD, 2024b; 2024c). The country note for Slovakia shows below-average trust in government and particularly low confidence in the capacity of institutions to handle complex policy trade-offs transparently (OECD, 2024b).
- Eurobarometer surveys on democracy and regional public opinion similarly report that while trust in local and regional authorities is often higher than in national governments, significant shares of citizens – including in Slovakia – declare that they “tend not to trust” these authorities and are dissatisfied with how their views are taken into account (European Commission, 2023a; 2024c).

Risk C.2 *“Social fragmentation, NIMBY conflicts, resistance to new developments.”*

- Evidence of social fragmentation in European and Slovak cities is particularly visible in the situation of Roma communities and other marginalised groups. Civil-society and EU monitoring highlight hundreds of segregated Roma settlements in Slovakia, many lacking basic infrastructure such as water, sewage and electricity (European Commission, 2025a; AP, 2025).
- At the same time, the EU’s work on social cohesion stresses that shared values, mutual respect and active participation are crucial to prevent polarisation and conflict around new developments (Regiocoop, 2025). Studies of civic cohesion and volunteering at EU level show that inclusive engagement can reduce tensions around migrant integration, housing projects and local infrastructure, whereas lack of engagement tends to fuel NIMBY-type reactions and resistance (Sofia Platform; EPC, 2024)

Risk C.3 *“Widened inequalities in access to housing, services and digital systems.”*

- EU and OECD analyses show that inequalities in access to basic services, decent housing and digital connectivity already pose serious social cohesion challenges. The Quality of Life in European Cities survey reports high overall satisfaction, but also highlights persistent concerns about housing affordability and access to services, especially in rapidly growing cities (European Commission, 2023b).

- For Roma and other marginalised groups in Slovakia, the Civil Society Monitoring Report documents continued overcrowding, segregated housing and limited access to public transport, education and healthcare, despite targeted programmes (European Commission, 2025a; EUROMA, 2024).
- On the digital side, the EU still falls short of its target of 80 % of adults with basic digital skills by 2030, with only around 55 % currently at that level and large gaps by age, education and territory (Eurostat, 2024a; European Commission, 2023c).
- Eurostat's digital skills dataset shows that Slovakia mirrors these divides, with older, less-educated and rural residents much less likely to have basic skills (Eurostat, 2024c). Without targeted inclusion measures in spatial and digital planning, smart-city and e-government solutions risk reinforcing, rather than reducing, inequalities in access to housing, services and digital systems – exactly as stated in the risk.

References

- Associated Press. (2025, March 20). *Fire sweeps through a poor Roma settlement in eastern Slovakia, leaving 5 dead, including 4 children*. Associated Press.
- European Commission. (2023). *Citizenship and democracy – Flash Eurobarometer 522*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2023). *Digitalisation in Europe – 2023 edition*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2023). *Report on the quality of life in European cities 2023*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2024). *EU integration policy – Migrant integration*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *Public opinion in the EU regions – Slovakia country factsheet*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2025). *Civil society monitoring report on the implementation of the national strategic framework for Roma equality, inclusion and participation in Slovakia*. European Commission.
- European Network on Independent Living, et al. (2025, May 31). *More than €1bn in EU funds used in discriminatory projects, report says*. *The Guardian*.
- EUROMA Network. (2024). *Roma equality and inclusion in the 2025 European Semester: Limited progress and persistent challenges*. EUROMA Network.
- Eurostat. (2024). *Digital skills in 2023: Impact of education and age*. *Eurostat News* (February 22). <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- Eurostat. (2024). *Individuals' level of digital skills (from 2021 onwards)* (Dataset ISOC_SK_DSKL_I21). Eurostat.
- Eurostat. (2024). *Skills for the digital age*. *Statistics Explained*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat>
- GLOBSEC. (2024). *Participatory democracy in Slovakia*. GLOBSEC.
- OECD. (2024). *An updated OECD framework on drivers of trust in public institutions to meet current and future challenges*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *OECD survey on drivers of trust in public institutions – 2024 results*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *OECD survey on drivers of trust in public institutions – 2024 results: Country note – Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.

OECD & UCLG. (2023). *Subnational government structure and finance: Country profile – Slovak Republic (SNG-WOFI)*. OECD Publishing.

O’Reilly, J. (2025, May 29). *Segregated classrooms are not a thing of the past – Look at what is happening to Roma children in Slovakia*. *The Guardian*.

Regiocoop. (2025). *Social cohesion in the EU explained*. Regiocoop Blog.

Sofia Platform & European Policy Centre. (2024). *Strengthening civic cohesion in the European Union*. Sofia Platform; European Policy Centre

D. Spatial Development Pressures & Land-Use Conflicts

Challenges

1. Rising urban sprawl, inefficient land consumption, fragmented landscapes (highlighted in urban trend reports).
2. Competing land demands (housing, logistics, agriculture, biodiversity protection).
3. Loss of natural areas and ecosystem services due to poorly coordinated development.

Risks

1. Increased flood risk, heat islands, biodiversity loss.
2. Higher long-term infrastructure costs due to dispersed development.
3. Reduced food security and ecosystem resilience.

Actions Needed

- Implement land-take reduction strategies, prioritize brownfield redevelopment.
- Promote compact, transit-oriented, mixed-use development.
- Integrate ecosystem-based planning and nature-based solutions into local and regional plans.
- Apply land-use impact assessments considering climate, biodiversity, and social factors.

Proofs:

Challenge D.1 “*Rising urban sprawl, inefficient land consumption, fragmented landscapes (highlighted in urban trend reports).*”

- Across Europe, land take for urban development continues to grow faster than population, which is a core indicator of urban sprawl and inefficient land consumption. The latest EEA indicator shows that average net land take in EU Member States’ cities and commuting zones increased by about 32 %, from 410 km²/year in 2012–2018 to 540 km²/year in 2018–2021, with most conversions affecting cropland and pastures, followed by forests (European Environment Agency, 2025a.)
- Land-take and soil-sealing analyses for 662 functional urban areas (FUAs) in the EU and UK further confirm that sprawl-driven conversion of non-urban land into urban land has continued, fragmenting landscapes and ecosystems (European Environment Agency, 2020).
- For Slovakia, the same EEA study reports that some of the highest relative increases of land take in core cities (more than 3.5 %) occurred in Slovak FUAs in 2012–2018, indicating rapid expansion of built-up areas around cities such as Bratislava (European Environment Agency, 2020).

- A cross-country analysis of land-use changes in urban areas of Czechia, Poland and Slovakia based on CORINE Land Cover data concludes that urban expansion and associated flows from agricultural and semi-natural land to artificial surfaces are a key trend in Slovak urban regions, mirroring wider Central-European sprawl processes (Pazúr et al., 2020).
- OECD work on urbanisation complements this picture by showing that many OECD countries experience “excessive development” in some areas and undersupply in others, with developed land per capita often increasing in slowly growing regions, indicating inefficient land use and fragmented patterns (OECD, 2017a; Krawchenko, 2020). (ResearchGate) The OECD report Rethinking Urban Sprawl documents that low-density sprawl generates more fragmented urban landscapes, longer travel distances and higher environmental impacts compared to compact development (OECD, 2018).

Challenge D.2 “*Competing land demands (housing, logistics, agriculture, biodiversity protection).*”

- European trend reports point to growing competition for land among housing, transport/logistics infrastructure, renewable energy, agriculture and biodiversity conservation. Eurostat’s assessment of SDG 15 “Life on land” notes that population growth, accelerating urbanisation and increasing resource needs are putting “growing pressure on terrestrial ecosystems and the services they provide” in the EU (Eurostat, 2024).
- The EEA’s briefing on land use and land take shows that conversion of farmland and forests to settlement areas (housing, transport, infrastructure) reduces the area available to supply ecosystem services and affects ecologically valuable areas in particular (European Environment Agency, 2024b).
- The EEA report Land take and land degradation in functional urban areas quantifies these trade-offs: between 2012 and 2018, land take in FUEAs increased by 3 581 km² and soil sealing by 1 467 km², largely at the expense of croplands and pastures, while also affecting protected areas and floodplains (European Environment Agency, 2020).
- This reflects direct competition between housing/logistics development and agricultural production/biodiversity protection. A 2023 EU study on land-uptake and agricultural loss estimates substantial economic losses of agricultural production due to urbanisation across EU countries, confirming the tension between built-up expansion and food-producing land (Bosco et al., 2021).
- For Slovakia, analyses of CORINE Land Cover data show significant changes in land cover in protected areas (about 21.7 % of the area changed between 1990 and 2018), including conversion pressures on forests and semi-natural areas, with measurable impacts on landscape diversity and ecological stability (Štefunková et al., 2020). This indicates that even in legally protected zones, economic and infrastructure demands compete with biodiversity objectives. OECD land-use governance reviews stress that spatial planning must increasingly balance productivity, sustainability, liveability and affordability, because multiple sectoral policies (housing, transport, agriculture, climate, biodiversity) “compete for the same limited land resource” (OECD, 2017b).

Challenge D.3 “*Loss of natural areas and ecosystem services due to poorly coordinated development.*”

- The EEA concludes that land take and soil sealing are key drivers of land degradation, leading to landscape fragmentation, habitat loss and reduced ecosystem resilience (European Environment Agency, 2020).
- The EU-wide indicator on net land take shows that conversion of natural and agricultural land into artificial surfaces undermines ecological functions and “weakens ecosystem resilience” (European Environment Agency, 2025a).
- A policy brief on soil sealing and land take prepared for the European Commission emphasises that sealed soils can no longer provide key ecosystem services such as food and biomass production, water regulation, biodiversity habitat and carbon sequestration, and warns that awareness of these long-term losses is still relatively low in European planning practice (Greifswald University; Ecologic Institute, 2018).
- In Slovakia, studies of land-cover changes in protected areas show that land-use change has reduced ecological stability and altered habitat composition, even where formal protection exists, indicating that sectoral developments (forestry, tourism, infrastructure) are not always well coordinated with conservation (Štefunková et al., 2020).
- A case study for Bratislava identifies environmentally sensitive urban areas where sealed surfaces, reduced soil quality and limited green infrastructure decrease ecosystem services and contribute to urban-heat-island effects, with implications for residents’ health and quality of life (Tolrá et al., 2020).

Risk D.1 “*Increased flood risk, heat islands, biodiversity loss.*”

- European evidence clearly links dispersed, sealed development to higher flood and heat risks and to biodiversity decline. The EEA reports that land take and soil sealing reduce natural flood protection, as sealed surfaces increase runoff and decrease water infiltration, while fragmentation and habitat loss reduce ecosystem resilience (European Environment Agency, 2020; 2025b).
- Recent research on European cities shows that growth of impermeable surfaces and reduced green coverage significantly increases river-flood risk in urban areas, and calls for integrating land-use and flood-risk planning (Kundzewicz et al., 2025).
- For heat risk, EEA and other European assessments document that urban heat-island (UHI) effects are intensifying in European cities, with higher summer temperatures in dense, sealed areas and limited tree cover, increasing health risks under climate change (European Environment Agency, 2023; Climate-ADAPT, 2024). (Európska agentúra pre životné prostredie) The Bratislava UHI study cited above shows that areas with high soil sealing and limited green infrastructure coincide with higher land-surface temperatures (Tolrá et al., 2020).
- Regarding biodiversity, Eurostat notes that habitat loss and fragmentation due to urbanisation and infrastructure are among the main pressures on terrestrial biodiversity in the EU (Eurostat, 2024). A recent cross-European investigation estimates that Europe is losing around 1 500 km² of nature and cropland per year to construction, with serious implications for wildlife and ecosystem health (Carver, 2025). (The Guardian) These

converging strands of evidence support your risk statement that unchecked sprawl and land take amplify flood risk, UHI intensity and biodiversity loss.

Risk D.2 *“Higher long-term infrastructure costs due to dispersed development.”*

- OECD’s Rethinking Urban Sprawl quantifies how sprawling, low-density settlement patterns increase per-capita infrastructure and service costs for transport, utilities and public services, compared with more compact urban forms (OECD, 2018).
- European modelling for Flanders shows that infrastructure and mobility costs are substantially higher for dispersed buildings and ribbon development than for denser, nodal patterns; compact alternatives can generate sizeable monetary savings over the long term (Vanderhaegen & Canters, 2021).
- Earlier work on the “costs of urban sprawl” similarly finds that fringe development is heavily subsidised and generates high public and private costs for transport and infrastructure, concluding that urban regeneration is more cost-effective than continued sprawl (Blais, 2010). (jstor.org) These findings are consistent with OECD spatial-planning reviews, which warn that fragmented, leapfrog development patterns increase the unit costs of infrastructure networks and public-transport provision (OECD, 2017a; 2017b).
- Given that Slovak FUAs have experienced relatively high rates of land take in core cities and their commuting zones, extending infrastructure to low-density peri-urban development can be expected to raise long-term investment and maintenance costs for roads, water, energy and public transport (European Environment Agency, 2020; OECD, 2018).

Risk D.3 *“Reduced food security and ecosystem resilience.”*

- Urbanisation and soil sealing directly affect food production capacity and ecosystem resilience. A FAO-linked review on urbanisation and soil sealing stresses that sealed soils can no longer support food and biomass production, water regulation or biodiversity, and explicitly notes that urbanisation and soil sealing can negatively affect food availability – one of the dimensions of food security (Ballabio et al., 2020).
- EU-wide analysis of land-uptake and agricultural loss based on CORINE Land Cover shows that urbanisation has converted significant areas of agricultural land in all EU countries from 1990 to 2018, resulting in quantifiable economic losses of primary production (Bosco et al., 2021). (scirp.org) The recent EEA indicator on net land take confirms that most new artificial surfaces in 2012–2021 replaced cropland and pastures, reducing the agricultural land base in and around cities (European Environment Agency, 2025a).
- For Slovakia, analyses of land-use change highlight significant shifts between arable land and permanent grassland and increased artificial surfaces, with implications for agricultural production and landscape stability (Pazúr et al., 2020; Štefunková et al., 2020).
- At the same time, EEA assessments emphasise that land take and soil sealing decrease carbon sequestration, impair flood protection and fragment habitats, thereby weakening ecosystem resilience (European Environment Agency, 2020; 2024b).

References

- Ballabio, C., et al. (2020). *Urbanisation and soil sealing: Impacts on ecosystem services and food security*. FAO.
- Blais, P. (2010). The costs of urban sprawl: Infrastructure and transportation. *Journal of Urban Design*.
- Bosco, C., et al. (2021). Indicators engineering for land uptake and agricultural loss: A study for EU countries from 1990 to 2018. *Cities and Urban Society*.
- Carver, S. (2025, October 1). *Europe losing 600 football pitches of nature and cropland a day*. *The Guardian*.
- European Environment Agency. (2020). *Land take and land degradation in functional urban areas*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2020). *Urban soil sealing in Europe*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2023). *Europe's changing climate hazards*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2024). *Land use and land take*. In *Europe's environment 2025 – Biodiversity and ecosystems thematic briefing*. European Environment Agency.
- European Environment Agency. (2025). *Net land take in cities and commuting zones in Europe* (Indicator assessment). European Environment Agency.
- Eurostat. (2024). *SDG 15 – Life on land. Statistics Explained*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Greifswald University & Ecologic Institute. (2018). *Policy brief: Soil sealing and land take*. Greifswald University; Ecologic Institute.
- Krawchenko, T. (2020). Trends in spatial planning in OECD countries. *European Spatial Research and Policy*.
- OECD. (2017). *The governance of land use in OECD countries*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2017). *Land-use planning systems in the OECD*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2018). *Rethinking urban sprawl: Moving towards sustainable cities*. OECD Publishing.
- Pazúr, R., et al. (2020). Land-use changes in urban areas of Czechia, Poland and Slovakia. *Remote Sensing*.
- Štefunková, D., et al. (2020). Land-cover changes in protected areas of Slovakia between 1990 and 2018. *Acta Geographica Slovenica*.
- Tolrá, J., et al. (2020). Mapping of urban environmentally sensitive areas in Bratislava city. *Journal of Soils and Sediments*.
- Vanderhaegen, S., & Canters, F. (2021). Modelling urban sprawl and assessing its costs in the planning process. *Land Use Policy*.

E. Housing, Demography & Social Infrastructure

Challenges

1. Lack of affordable housing in growing cities and degradation in shrinking areas.
2. Demographic ageing and migration flows create uneven service demands.
3. Spatial inequalities between urban cores, suburban areas, and rural hinterlands.

Risks

1. Increased segregation, gentrification, pressure on public services.

2. Vacant housing in peripheral towns while metropolitan centres face shortages.

Actions Needed

- Strengthen integrated housing strategies aligned with mobility, land-use, and social policy.
- Use inclusionary zoning, public–private partnerships, and community land trusts.
- Align school, healthcare, and social service infrastructure with demographic projections.
- Support regeneration of shrinking towns through place-based revitalization strategies.

Proofs: see chapter 1.4.

F. Infrastructure, Mobility & Regional Accessibility

Challenges

1. Overreliance on car-based mobility; insufficient integration between land-use and public transport.
2. Regional disparities in accessibility, especially for rural areas and small towns.
3. Smart mobility systems (ITS, shared mobility, AV readiness) not aligned with spatial plans.

Risks

4. Increased congestion, emissions, and mobility poverty.
5. Fragmented mobility networks undermine regional cohesion.

Actions Needed

- Develop integrated regional mobility plans including rail, buses, cycling, pedestrian networks.
- Support multimodal hubs and transit-oriented corridors.
- Embed smart mobility solutions (real-time data, intelligent signalling, shared mobility platforms) into spatial strategies.
- Ensure accessibility standards for vulnerable groups.

Proofs:

Challenge F.1 “*Overreliance on car-based mobility; insufficient integration between land-use and public transport.*”

- Eurostat and DG MOVE data show that in the EU-27, passenger cars account for around four-fifths of inland passenger transport (about 82 % of passenger-km in 2017), while buses/coaches and rail together account for less than one fifth (ERF, 2020; Eurostat, 2024). For Slovakia, the same dataset reports a still car-dominant but slightly less extreme structure: 73.8 % passenger-km by car, 15.6 % by bus/coach and 7.0 % by rail in 2017 (ERF, 2020). These figures confirm a strong reliance on car-based mobility at both EU and Slovak level.
- A recent analysis of public passenger transport in rural Slovakia notes that over past decades the modal share has shifted away from buses and trains towards individual car use, driven by service cuts, ageing infrastructure and affordability issues, and that rail and bus networks struggle to offer competitive alternatives outside major corridors (Focus, 2025).

- OECD and ITF work on decarbonising urban mobility stresses that reducing congestion and emissions requires co-ordinated land-use and transport planning, with compact development and high-capacity public transport rather than dispersed, car-dependent growth (OECD, 2024a; OECD/ITF, 2024).

Challenge F.2 *“Regional disparities in accessibility, especially for rural areas and small towns.”*

- OECD’s Regions and Cities at a Glance and the working paper Spurring Growth in Lagging Regions in Slovak Republic show that regional inequality in Slovakia is among the highest in the OECD: GDP per capita in the Bratislava region is more than double that of Prešov, and insufficient labour mobility and transport infrastructure are highlighted as key causes of persistent gaps (OECD, 2015; OECD, 2022).
- The same OECD work explicitly identifies completion of the national transport network as crucial for easing bottlenecks in Bratislava and improving access to jobs in central and eastern regions (OECD, 2015).
- European and Slovak studies underline that rural areas and small towns are particularly affected. The ITF/OECD report Innovations for Better Rural Mobility documents that limited transport options in rural and remote regions hinder access to basic services, jobs and social activities, and calls for region-level coordination to provide sustainable solutions (ITF/OECD, 2021).
- A dedicated analysis of rural public transport in Slovakia describes “transport poverty” in many villages due to inadequate service coverage, long travel times and high relative costs for vulnerable groups (FOCUS, 2025).
- Case studies of Banská Bystrica and Prešov regions show that eccentric locations of regional centres and weak direct public-transport links significantly reduce daily accessibility from surrounding rural districts (Kvizda et al., 2019; Némethová et al., 2020).

Challenge F.3 *“Smart mobility systems (ITS, shared mobility, AV readiness) not aligned with spatial plans.”*

- The EU’s Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy stresses that digitalisation (ITS, multimodal travel information, Mobility as a Service, automation) must go hand in hand with sustainable urban planning and clear investment priorities, integrated through Sustainable Urban Mobility Plans (SUMPs) and wider territorial strategies (EUROPEAN COMMISSION, 2020a).
- The revised ITS Directive (EU) 2023/2661 and its 2024–2028 work programme seek to accelerate deployment of intelligent transport systems and multimodal travel information across member states, but also highlight barriers such as fragmented data governance and uneven implementation between regions and cities (European Commission, 2023a).
- For Slovakia, the project Clean, Smart and Fair Urban Mobility notes that while there is strong interest in electrification, MaaS and new mobility services, institutional capacity and coordination between transport, spatial planning and environmental authorities remain limited, and urban mobility plans are not yet systematically aligned with land-use policies (TML, 2023).

- In rural mobility, responsibilities are explicitly split between the Ministry of Agriculture and the Ministry of Transport, creating sectoral fragmentation that complicates the integration of shared or demand-responsive services into regional development and spatial plans (SMARTA, 2019).

Risk F.1 *“Increased congestion, emissions, and mobility poverty.”*

- The EU transport pocketbook and Key Figures on European Transport show that transport accounts for roughly 25 % of total EU greenhouse-gas emissions, with road transport responsible for the vast majority; despite efficiency gains, emissions from transport have declined more slowly than in other sectors because of growth in traffic volumes (Eurostat, 2024; European Commission, 2024b).
- The Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy explicitly frames current trends as unsustainable, warning that without mode shift to sustainable modes and better system efficiency, congestion and emissions will continue to grow (EUROPEAN COMMISSION, 2020a).
- In a car-dependent context like Slovakia’s, where public transport outside main corridors is under pressure, this implies higher congestion and emissions risks, particularly around major cities.
- European institutions are increasingly treating “transport poverty” as a distinct social risk. A European Parliament briefing defines transport poverty as difficulty in accessing essential activities because of the cost, availability or adequacy of transport, and stresses that it disproportionately affects rural residents, low-income households, women, young and older people, and persons with disabilities (European Parliament, 2022).
- The European Commission’s 2024 study on transport poverty confirms three main dimensions – availability, accessibility and affordability – and identifies significant pockets of transport poverty across the EU (European Commission, 2024c).
- In Slovakia, the rural transport analysis cited above explicitly labels many rural communities as facing transport poverty due to declining services and high relative costs (Focus, 2025).

Risk F.2 *“Fragmented mobility networks undermine regional cohesion.”*

- OECD work on Slovakia shows that incomplete and uneven transport infrastructure acts as a structural brake on convergence. Spurring Growth in Lagging Regions in Slovak Republic concludes that completing the road and rail network is “important for removing expansion bottlenecks in the Bratislava region and reducing obstacles for job creation in the central and eastern regions” and explicitly links weak labour mobility and accessibility to persistent regional disparities (OECD, 2015).
- Regions and Cities at a Glance similarly documents large gaps in economic performance and well-being between Slovak regions and highlights that such inequalities can threaten national cohesion if not addressed through effective regional and transport policy (OECD, 2022; OECD, 2024a).
- EU analyses of rural transport emphasise that poorly connected rural areas suffer from shrinking populations, weaker access to education, health and jobs, and growing feelings of exclusion, which in turn undermine territorial cohesion goals set out in EU treaties (European Commission, 2025a; ITF/OECD, 2021).

- The SMARTA country profile for Slovakia notes that rural mobility responsibilities are split between sectors and that there is a need for stronger coordination and integrated solutions to avoid service gaps between regions (SMARTA, 2019).

References

- Focus Association for Sustainable Development. (2025). *Analysis of public passenger transport service in rural areas of Slovakia*. Focus Association for Sustainable Development.
- European Commission. (2020). *Sustainable and smart mobility strategy – Putting European transport on track for the future*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2023). *ITS Directive and Action Plan – Framework for the deployment of intelligent transport systems*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *EU transport in figures – Statistical pocketbook 2024*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2024). *Transport poverty: Definitions, indicators, determinants, and mitigation strategies – Final report*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2025). *Minding the gap: How rural transport inequality affects us all*. EU Urban Mobility Observatory.
- European Parliament. (2022). *Understanding transport poverty*. European Parliamentary Research Service.
- European Union Road Federation. (2020). *Passenger transport 2020: EU-27 statistics*. European Union Road Federation.
- Eurostat. (2024). *Key figures on European transport – 2024 edition*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- ITF/OECD. (2021). *Innovations for better rural mobility*. International Transport Forum.
- OECD. (2015). *Spurring growth in lagging regions in the Slovak Republic*. OECD Economics Department Working Papers, No. 1211. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2022). *OECD regions and cities at a glance 2022 – Slovak Republic: Country note*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *OECD regions and cities at a glance 2024*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD/ITF. (2024). *Accessibility and transport appraisal*. OECD Publishing.
- SMARTA. (2019). *Slovakia – Rural shared mobility country profile*. SMARTA – Rural Shared Mobility.
- Transport & Mobility Leuven. (2023). *Clean, smart and fair urban mobility in Slovakia – Final report*. Transport & Mobility Leuven.

G. Environmental Sustainability & Climate Resilience

Challenges

1. Planning insufficiently addresses climate adaptation (heat, flooding, drought).
2. Inadequate integration of green infrastructure, water management, and climate scenarios.
3. High carbon emissions from buildings, transport, and land-use patterns.

Risks

1. More frequent climate-induced disasters.
2. High economic costs due to unprotected assets and infrastructure.

Actions Needed

- Adopt climate-adaptive spatial planning, integrating risk maps, climate models, and resilience standards.
- Expand urban green and blue infrastructure networks.
- Use smart environmental monitoring (air quality, water levels, heat sensors).
- Promote low-carbon urban forms, energy-efficient buildings, and renewable energy spatial strategies.

Proofs:

Challenge G.1 *“Planning insufficiently addresses climate adaptation (heat, flooding, drought).”*

- Across Europe, the European Environment Agency (EEA) has identified 36 major climate risks for Europe, eight of which are already particularly urgent and mainly concern heat impacts on people, flood and wildfire risks for people and infrastructure, and the viability of EU solidarity mechanisms (EEA, 2025a).
- The EEA concludes that current adaptation efforts are not keeping pace with accelerating climate impacts and calls for “fast-tracking” adaptation in most sectors and regions, which directly supports the statement that planning systems still insufficiently address adaptation to heat, flooding and drought (EEA, 2025a).
- Evidence on impacts shows why this gap matters. Weather- and climate-related extremes caused estimated economic losses of EUR 822 billion in the EU between 1980 and 2024, with more than EUR 208 billion (25 %) of these losses occurring in just the last four years (EEA, 2025b).
- A separate EEA briefing reports that floods, droughts, heatwaves and wildfires in 2023 alone caused over EUR 45 billion in damages across 38 European countries (EEA, 2024a). (eea.europa.eu) These losses are concentrated in a few major hazard types – exactly those (heat, flooding, drought) that should be integrated into local and regional planning.
- For Slovakia, the OECD Environmental Performance Review: Slovak Republic 2024 notes that the country “is not on a net-zero pathway” and that climate change is already increasing drought risks in the southwest; it stresses the need to strengthen climate adaptation, especially water management and the use of EU funds for adaptation infrastructure (OECD, 2024a).
- A recent book on Slovak water resources documents increasing frequency of hydrological extremes, including floods and droughts, and calls for more systematic risk assessment and integrated water management (Pekárová et al., 2019). An EU-level review of droughts in Slovakia similarly finds that adaptation measures still focus mainly on floods, while drought and water-scarcity adaptation “do not yet seem to be widespread” (European Commission, 2019a).

Challenge G.2 *“Inadequate integration of green infrastructure, water management, and climate scenarios.”*

- The European Commission’s Green Infrastructure (GI) strategy stresses that GI must be integrated into spatial planning, Environmental Impact Assessment and Strategic Environmental Assessment, acknowledging that this integration is still incomplete across member states (European Commission, 2024a).

- The EEA work on nature-based solutions finds that projects such as urban green spaces, restored wetlands and green roofs are effective for flood protection and cooling, but concludes that they remain under-used and need to be “scaled up and expanded” to build climate resilience (EEA, 2023a).
- A 2025 Urban Agenda “Greening Cities” position paper adds that funding for urban GI is “inadequate, fragmented and difficult to access”, limiting systematic implementation even where cities are committed to expand it (Urban Agenda, 2025).
- In Slovakia, the OECD Environmental Performance Review highlights serious biodiversity degradation – around 75 % of species and 60 % of habitats in poor or bad status – and calls for more integrated landscape planning to improve water retention, carbon stocks and species habitats “through biological corridors, vegetation belts and other green/blue infrastructure” (OECD, 2024b). The same review states that Slovakia had a low absorption rate of EU funds for environmental infrastructure and climate adaptation in 2014–20 and urges better coordination and financing of water and nature-based solutions (OECD, 2024a).
- At EU level, water-scarcity policy underlines that at least 11 % of Europe’s population and 17 % of its territory have already been affected by water scarcity, with the cost of droughts over the last 30 years estimated at around EUR 100 billion, and calls for “water-efficient and water-saving” planning and investment (European Commission, 2019b)

Challenge G.3 “High carbon emissions from buildings, transport, and land-use patterns.”

- Buildings are the single largest final energy user in the EU, accounting for around 40 % of final energy consumption and a significant share of CO₂ emissions (Korytářová et al., 2019; Vourdoubas, 2022).
- The EEA data show that greenhouse gas emissions from buildings in the EU fell by 43 % between 2005 and 2023, with further modest reductions expected in 2024, but emphasise that substantial additional reductions are needed to reach climate neutrality (EEA, 2025c).
- The transport sector is now the largest source of greenhouse gas emissions in the EU, and unlike other sectors its emissions have barely fallen: between 1990 and 2022, transport emissions increased by about 26 %, while emissions from all other sectors dropped by 42 % (World Bank, 2024; EEA, 2025d). Recent EEA data confirm that, even with EU Green Deal policies, transport is on track to remain a dominant share of total emissions without much stronger measures (EEA, 2025d).
- For Slovakia, the EU Climate Action Progress Report 2024 states that net greenhouse gas emissions per capita in 2023 were 6.8 tCO₂-eq, roughly equal to the EU average, but that greenhouse-gas intensity of GDP (392 gCO₂-eq/EUR) is significantly above the EU average of 225 gCO₂-eq/EUR, indicating a more emission-intensive economic and land-use structure (European Commission, 2024b).
- The OECD Environmental Performance Review notes that national projections show increasing emissions in several non-ETS sectors, “especially transport,” and a decline in net removals from forests, which threatens achievement of 2030 targets and the net-zero goal (OECD, 2024a).

Risk G.1 “*More frequent climate-induced disasters.*”

- The EEA’s assessment of climate hazards concludes that Europe is the world’s fastest-warming continent and faces increasing frequency and intensity of heatwaves, floods, droughts and wildfires (EEA, 2021). As noted, cumulative economic losses from weather- and climate-related extremes in the EU reached about EUR 822 billion between 1980 and 2024, with a clear upward trend and exceptionally high losses in 2021–24 (EEA, 2025b).
- The EEA warns that without accelerated adaptation and emission reduction, Europe will experience “catastrophic” levels of risk to ecosystems, health, infrastructure and the economy (EEA, 2025a).
- Recent analyses underline the macroeconomic dimension: the European Central Bank has estimated that a plausible extreme drought scenario could wipe out up to 15 % of the euro-area’s economic output, with some EUR 1.3 trillion of bank loans exposed to water-scarcity risks (ECB, 2025). Studies for 2024–25 suggest that summers of combined heatwaves, droughts and floods already lead to annual losses of EUR 40–45 billion in the EU, projected to rise to around EUR 120–126 billion by 2029 if current trends continue (Mannheim University/ECB, 2025).

Risk G.2 “*High economic costs due to unprotected assets and infrastructure.*”

- EEA data show that a large share of Europe’s physical assets and infrastructure is located in hazard-prone areas: for example, nearly 15 % of industrial assets are on floodplains and many transport corridors are exposed to river and coastal flooding (EEA, 2021). The same assessments note that much of this infrastructure was designed for historical climate conditions and remains insufficiently protected against future extremes, increasing expected damage costs (EEA, 2025a).
- Economic modelling reinforces this. An Allianz Research study finds that recurring heatwaves in 2025 alone could reduce European GDP growth by up to 0.5 percentage points, primarily through productivity losses and disruptions to infrastructure and supply chains (Allianz, 2025).
- The ECB drought scenario and EU-level water-scarcity estimates both stress that inadequate adaptation of water, energy and transport systems magnifies systemic risks and long-term economic losses (ECB, 2025; European Commission, 2019b).
- For Slovakia, the OECD Environmental Performance Review underlines that expanding wastewater treatment, improving flood protection and investing in green/blue infrastructure will require substantial additional investment, and warns that low absorption of EU funds and weak cost recovery in water tariffs currently delay these investments (OECD, 2024a).

References

Allianz. (2025). *Heatwaves – Global economic losses from extreme heat in 2025*. Allianz Research Briefing. Allianz.

European Central Bank. (2025). *Droughts and the euro area economy*. European Central Bank.

European Commission. (2019). *Water scarcity and droughts in the EU*. Directorate-General for Environment.

European Commission. (2024). *Climate action progress report 2024 – Slovakia factsheet*. Directorate-General for Climate Action.

European Commission. (2024). *Green infrastructure*. Directorate-General for Environment.

European Environment Agency. (2021). *Europe's changing climate hazards — An index-based interactive report*. Publications Office of the European Union.

European Environment Agency. (2023). *Nature-based solutions play a crucial role in building Europe's climate resilience* (Press release, 16 November 2023). European Environment Agency.

European Environment Agency. (2024). *Extreme weather: Floods, droughts and heatwaves*. European Environment Agency.

European Environment Agency. (2025). *Climate change impacts, risks and adaptation in Europe*. European Environment Agency.

European Environment Agency. (2025). *Economic losses from weather- and climate-related extremes in Europe* (Indicator assessment). European Environment Agency.

European Environment Agency. (2025). *Greenhouse gas emissions from energy use in buildings in Europe* (Indicator assessment). European Environment Agency.

European Environment Agency. (2025). *Greenhouse gas emissions from transport in Europe* (Indicator assessment). European Environment Agency.

Korytárová, K., et al. (2019). *Energy efficiency in buildings – Insights from Slovakia*. Ministry of Transport and Construction of the Slovak Republic.

Mannheim University & European Central Bank. (2025). *Economic impacts of Europe's 2024–2025 extreme summer*. Mannheim University; European Central Bank.

OECD. (2024). *OECD environmental performance reviews: Slovak Republic 2024*. OECD Publishing.

OECD & Ministry of Environment of the Slovak Republic. (2024). *OECD environmental performance review of the Slovak Republic – Highlights*. OECD Publishing.

Pekárová, P., et al. (2019). *Water resources in Slovakia: Part II – Climate change, drought and floods*. Springer.

Urban Agenda for the EU. (2025). *Greening cities partnership – Position paper*. Urban Agenda for the EU.

H. Digitalisation of Spatial Planning & Data Governance

Challenges

1. Insufficient digital capacity in planning institutions.
2. Risky dependence on private technology providers.
3. Limited interoperability between digital planning tools across municipalities.

Risks

1. Cybersecurity threats to critical urban systems.
2. Inequitable outcomes if data-driven decisions ignore marginalized populations.
3. Poor-quality data leading to poor planning decisions.

Actions Needed

- Deploy GIS, digital twins, edge computing, real-time data analytics for planning (highlighted in many files).
- Establish ethical and transparent data governance frameworks.

- Provide training to planners on data analytics, modelling, and digital participatory methods.
- Ensure open-data principles to support transparency and innovation.

Proofs:

Challenge H.1 “*Insufficient digital capacity in planning institutions*”

- Across the EU, digital capacity gaps are a structural constraint for public administrations. Eurostat’s Digitalisation in Europe 2025 shows that in 2023, 44 % of EU citizens still lacked basic digital skills, and only 22 % of EU businesses provided ICT training to staff (Eurostat, 2025). This skills deficit limits the pool of digitally competent staff available to planning authorities and consultancies.
- The ESPON DIGIPLAN analysis of digital plans in European countries finds that planners must now handle highly detailed digital plan data and that “new skills for plan making and an adaptation of technology in planning authorities” are required (ESPON, 2022). Where such skills and resources are lacking, systems become “dysfunctional” and transition periods are prolonged, especially when generic e-government platforms are imposed from higher levels of government.
- In Slovakia, DESI-based assessments show the country ranked 23rd of 27 EU Member States in the 2022 Digital Economy and Society Index. Only 55 % of Slovaks have basic digital skills, and the country is “below the EU average across the indicators for digital public services”; usage of e-government services among internet users has declined to 62 % compared with an EU average of 64 % (U.S. Department of Commerce, 2024, based on DESI). This indicates that many Slovak public bodies, including municipal planning departments, operate from a relatively weak digital baseline, constraining the effective adoption of advanced GIS, plan registers and data-driven planning tools.

Challenge H2 “*Risky dependence on private technology providers*”

- The OECD stresses that digital public infrastructure (DPI) should be built on public governance of key components such as digital identity, data-sharing systems and base registries, supported by interoperability and open-source frameworks (OECD, 2024a). While 88 % of OECD countries have an interoperability framework, only 52 % have an open-source framework as a DPI enabler, and just 61 % have metadata standards (OECD, 2024a). Where public, open frameworks are missing, governments tend to rely more heavily on proprietary platforms and vendor-specific standards, which increases the risk of lock-in to private providers.
- DIGIPLAN shows that, in many European countries, digital planning systems were developed as generic e-government solutions driven by national IT agendas, not by planners’ needs, leading in some cases to “dysfunctional systems” at local level (Espon, 2022). Smaller municipalities often lack in-house capacity to configure or migrate these systems, further reinforcing dependence on external software suppliers and cloud providers for critical planning data. For Slovakia, where digital public services lag behind the EU average and SMEs show lower use of advanced digital technologies, this combination of weak internal capacity and fragmented standards heightens the risk that key spatial-planning functions (plan registers, geoportals, 3D models) will be controlled by a limited set of private vendors.

Challenge H3 “*Limited interoperability between digital planning tools across municipalities*”

- DIGIPLAN documents “great diversity regarding the level of digitisation in the field of spatial planning in Europe” and a wide variety of formats (raster, vector, PDFs) and legal statuses of digital plans, from purely informative to fully binding (ESPON, 2022). Although INSPIRE has fostered open geodata and metadata, it “has not necessarily driven digitisation in the cases” and has revealed strong differences between countries and regions. These differences, combined with separate national and regional portals, limit seamless data exchange between municipalities and cross-border regions.
- Even within the OECD area, only 64 % of countries have implemented base registries and just over half have digital notifications or payments as part of DPI (OECD, 2024a). This means that core reference datasets (addresses, land parcels, population registers) are not yet universally interoperable, undermining integrated spatial-planning analytics. In Slovakia, low use of e-invoicing (16 % of enterprises vs 32 % in the EU) and weaker digital public services signal that standardised, interoperable back-office processes are still developing, (trade.gov) making it harder to link municipal plan data with fiscal, infrastructure and demographic databases at national and EU scales.

Risk H1 “*Cybersecurity threats to critical urban systems*”

- Digitalisation of spatial planning, utilities and mobility management exposes cities to cyber risks. ENISA’s Threat Landscape 2025 analyses 4 875 cyber incidents affecting EU digital infrastructure between July 2024 and June 2025, with DDoS and ransomware ranked among the top threats and public administrations increasingly targeted. An accompanying sectoral analysis confirms that European public administrations face rising waves of politically motivated and hacktivist DDoS attacks, affecting the availability of online public services.
- The EU’s annual NISD security-incident report, summarised in a 2025 assessment, records 1 276 security incidents across Europe in 2024—an 18 % increase on the previous year—with healthcare, energy and transport as the most affected sectors, followed by digital infrastructure and banking (EU NIS CO-OPERATION Group, 2024, cited in Alvarez & Marsal, 2025). These sectors correspond directly to critical urban systems that increasingly rely on spatial-data platforms (e.g. SCADA-linked network maps, digital twins). Case-based evidence from attacks on hospitals and a major city water system in Poland underlines how cyber incidents can disrupt essential urban infrastructure and compromise sensitive spatial data.
- For Slovakia and other EU Member States that are still implementing the NIS2 Directive, limited in-house cybersecurity expertise in local governments, combined with dependence on external cloud and GIS providers, raises the probability that spatial-planning platforms, sensor networks and urban-operations dashboards become entry points for cyber-attacks on critical infrastructure.

Risk H2 “*Inequitable outcomes if data-driven decisions ignore marginalized populations*”

- Digital spatial-planning and smart-city tools depend on citizens’ ability to access and use online services. Eurostat shows that in 2023, only 56 % of EU residents had at least basic digital skills (Eurostat, 2025).

- A recent study of 27 European cities on smart-city governance concludes that the digital divide—covering access, skills and ability to benefit—disproportionately impacts elderly people, persons with disabilities, low-income groups and residents of remote areas, and that without specific interventions, smart-city digitalisation risks deepening exclusion (KRUHLOV; DVORAK, 2025).
- Complementary work on data bias in smart-city initiatives shows how algorithmic redlining and under-representation of certain neighbourhoods in datasets can “exacerbate environmental injustices and erode social cohesion” if uncorrected (PRISM, 2025). A systematic review of just and equitable smart-city projects finds that marginalised communities—low-income residents, women, people with disabilities—often bear the brunt of exclusion and inequity when digital tools are deployed without participatory governance (VARIOUS AUTHORS, 2025).
- In Slovakia, where e-government usage is slightly below the EU average and digital skills remain uneven, digital-first planning processes or online consultations risk excluding precisely those groups most affected by housing, transport and environmental decisions. Unless digital plan portals and decision-support tools are explicitly designed with universal accessibility, participatory mechanisms and data-ethics safeguards, spatial-planning digitalisation may reproduce or reinforce existing territorial and social inequalities.

Risk H1 “*Poor-quality data leading to poor planning decisions*”

- DIGIPLAN highlights substantial variation in the quality, completeness and legal status of digital plan data across Europe. In many jurisdictions, digital geodata are merely an information copy of binding analogue plans, often accompanied by disclaimers, while only a few countries (e.g. the Netherlands, Portugal) treat digital plan data as legally binding (ESPON, 2022). The report notes that digital plan data can be “disaggregated, divided and split without limitations”, which makes it easy to take regulations out of context, and warns of risks when plan data are used beyond the scale or purpose for which they were produced.
- At the same time, digitalisation raises expectations for precision: planners must provide much more detailed geometries and attributes than in analogue plans, but planning laws often lack explicit standards on accuracy, scale and fuzziness (ESPON, 2022). Combined with limited skills and resources in smaller municipalities, this can lead to inconsistent datasets, misaligned zoning layers and unreliable analyses.
- From a broader governance view, OECD indicators show that while data-sharing systems exist in 85 % of surveyed countries, only 52 % offer open-source frameworks and 61 % metadata standards for digital public infrastructure (OECD, 2024a). Without robust standards and quality-assurance mechanisms, the expansion of high-value public datasets—including planned land use—can entrench low-quality or biased inputs into analytical models and digital twins. For Slovakia and other EU countries where digital public services and advanced data infrastructures are still catching up, (trade.gov) this creates a direct risk that strategic planning, investment prioritisation and climate-risk assessments rest on incomplete or erroneous spatial information.

References

- Alvarez, Marsal. (2025, September 8). *Rise in critical infrastructure cyber risks across the EU requires strategic oversight*. Alvarez & Marsal.
- ESPON. (2022). *DIGIPLAN – Digitalisation of spatial planning and construction services in Europe: Final report*. ESPON EGTC.
- EU NIS Co-operation Group. (2024). *Annual report on NISD security incidents 2024*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *Digital Decade 2024: eGovernment benchmark*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2024). *eGovernment and digital public services*. European Commission.
- Eurostat. (2025). *Digitalisation in Europe – 2025 edition*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Kruhlov, V., & Dvorak, J. (2025). Social inclusivity in smart city governance: Overcoming the digital divide. *Sustainability*, 17(13), 5735.
- OECD. (2024). *2023 OECD digital government index: Results and key findings*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Government at a glance 2025* (Chapter 7: Digital government and innovation – Digital public infrastructure). OECD Publishing.
- PRISM. (2025). Data bias in smart city initiatives. In *PRISM urban futures scenarios*. PRISM.
- U.S. Department of Commerce. (2024). *Slovakia – Digital economy* (Country Commercial Guide). International Trade Administration.
- Various authors. (2025). A systematic review of research on just, equitable, responsible and sustainable smart cities. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* (in press).

I. Economic Development & Regional Competitiveness

Challenges

1. Uneven development between metropolitan regions and lagging areas.
2. Low innovation capacity in smaller towns and rural regions.
3. Land-use conflicts linked to logistics expansion, industrial areas, and energy transition sites.

Risks

1. Territorial disparities leading to depopulation and economic stagnation.
2. Competition rather than cooperation between municipalities.

Actions Needed

- Develop regional economic strategies linked to spatial planning.
- Support innovation districts, university–industry clusters, and smart specialization approaches.
- Foster intermunicipal cooperation on economic corridors and labour market areas.

Proofs:

Challenge I.1 “*Uneven development between metropolitan regions and lagging areas.*”

- Across the EU, regional gaps in GDP per capita and productivity remain large and persistent. The OECD Regional Outlook 2023 shows that inequalities between regions

within countries have changed little over the last twenty years and remain a key concern for competitiveness and cohesion (OECD, 2023).

- Regions and Cities at a Glance 2024 confirms that capital-city and large metropolitan regions systematically outperform rural and remote areas in income, productivity and access to services (OECD, 2024a).
- For Slovakia, multiple sources point to one of the highest regional disparities in the EU. The OECD review *Spurring Growth in Lagging Regions in Slovak Republic* concludes that regional inequality “is among the highest in the OECD and increasing,” with weak job creation and low technological capacity in central and eastern parts of the country (OECD, 2019).
- The IMF’s 2024 Selected Issues paper on *Regional Inequality in Slovakia* shows that GDP per capita in Bratislava significantly exceeds that in the rest of the country and that eastern regions host a large share of disadvantaged households (IMF, 2024).
- A World Bank–European Commission analysis similarly stresses that Slovakia has “one of the highest regional economic disparities among EU countries” and that narrowing these gaps is essential for long-term growth (World Bank; European Commission, 2019).

Challenge I.2 “*Low innovation capacity in smaller towns and rural regions.*”

- At European level, innovation is strongly concentrated in metropolitan regions. The European Commission’s Regional Innovation Scoreboard (RIS) 2025 finds that the highest-performing “Innovation Leaders” and “Strong Innovators” are mostly capital and large-city regions; many rural and peripheral territories are classified as Moderate or Emerging Innovators (European Commission, 2025a).
- A recent JRC policy brief on startup geography reports that in 2024, 76 % of EU startups were based in cities, 18 % in towns/suburbs and only 6 % in rural areas, confirming a pronounced urban–rural innovation divide (European Commission–JRC, 2025).
- Slovak evidence fits this pattern. According to the Regional Innovation Scoreboard 2025: Slovakia Regional Profile, Bratislavský kraj (the capital region) is a Moderate Innovator+ and clearly outperforms the rest of the country in human capital, research capacity and digitalisation, while the three non-metropolitan regions (Western, Central and Eastern Slovakia) are classified only as Emerging Innovators+ (European Commission, 2025b).
- Earlier RIS 2023 results show the same configuration: all Slovak regions are “emerging innovators” except Bratislava, which is a “moderate innovator,” and overall performance remains below the EU average (Es-Sadki; Hollanders, 2023).
- OECD’s Rural Innovation Pathways further documents that rural regions across OECD countries face structural barriers to innovation – thinner ecosystems, lower critical mass, and weaker access to finance and skills – and calls for targeted place-based support (OECD, 2024b)

Challenge I.3 “*Land-use conflicts linked to logistics expansion, industrial areas, and energy transition sites.*”

- Logistics and industrial expansion. The OECD/ITF report *Urban Logistics Hubs* stresses that freight transport accounts for around half of local air pollutants in cities and

generates major congestion and emissions, while new forms of warehousing and distribution (e-commerce, dark stores, reverse logistics) intensify pressure on scarce urban and peri-urban land (ITF–OECD, 2023).

- A systematic review of conflicts in European urban peripheries finds that land-use conflicts are the most frequently reported category, often linked to residential and commercial construction, transport infrastructure and logistics platforms (Kleemann et al., 2023). These studies show that the expansion of logistics and industrial functions frequently collides with housing, environmental and quality-of-life objectives.
- Energy transition land needs. Recent European research on renewable energy siting calculates that meeting EU wind and solar targets could require up to 445 000 km² of land by 2050, roughly the area of Sweden, and that business-as-usual deployment patterns disproportionately target “high-conflict” land covers (Rosslowe et al., 2024).
- A Nature Conservancy practitioners’ guide for Europe warns that scaling up renewables will create significant land-use and biodiversity impacts, especially where solar and wind farms compete with agricultural land and sensitive habitats (The Nature Conservancy, 2023).
- The same concern is reflected in EU debates around the REPowerEU package, which calls on Member States to map “Renewables Acceleration Areas” and to identify low-conflict sites through robust spatial planning (European Commission, 2022).
- Together with OECD work on managing environmental and energy transitions for regions and cities – which highlights land-use trade-offs between energy, housing, industry and nature – this provides strong evidence that logistics, industrial expansion and energy transition investments are already a major source of land-use conflict in European territories (OECD, 2021).

Risk I.1 “Territorial disparities leading to depopulation and economic stagnation.”

- Eurostat’s Rural Europe 2024 shows that many predominantly rural regions, especially in the north, south and east of the EU, have experienced net population losses due to out-migration towards cities and other Member States, while many cities continue to grow (Eurostat, 2024a).
- An OECD synthesis on regional inequalities reports that nearly 40 % of remote regions and 22 % of functional urban areas in the OECD shrank between 2001 and 2021, undermining local revenues and raising per-capita service costs (OECD, 2023). (latintrade.com) Recent media and policy analyses describe rural depopulation as a vicious cycle: declining population leads to weaker services, which in turn accelerates out-migration (Financial Times, 2025; OECD, 2023).
- For Slovakia, demographic studies highlight strong internal migration from eastern and central regions towards the Bratislava area and abroad, exacerbating east–west disparities and reducing labour supply in lagging territories (Káčerová, 2025).
- IMF and OECD analyses underline that poorer regions in central and eastern Slovakia combine lower productivity with weaker job creation, contributing both to out-migration and to the risk of long-term stagnation if convergence fails (IMF, 2024; OECD, 2019)

Risk I.2 “Competition rather than cooperation between municipalities.”

- In the EU and OECD, the Regions and Cities at a Glance 2024 report calls for stronger multi-level and inter-municipal cooperation to tackle regional inequalities and manage megatrends such as ageing and climate change, stressing that fragmented local decision-making can weaken investment and productivity (OECD, 2024a).
- Slovakia provides a clear case of structural fragmentation. The OECD–UCLG SNG-WOFI profile notes that municipal fragmentation in the Slovak Republic is “one of the highest in the OECD”: on average municipalities have about 1 900 inhabitants, with 84 % below 2 000 residents and 95 % below 5 000 (OECD; UCLG, 2022).
- The Council of Europe’s Delivering Good Governance in Slovakia project concludes that this high fragmentation “creates high overheads and harms the effectiveness of local government,” and cites EU country reports pointing to insufficient cooperation between national, regional and local levels (Council of Europe, 2021).
- Empirical work on municipal finance finds that very small Slovak municipalities struggle to provide quality services on their own and recommends cooperation or consolidation to gain economies of scale (Vámošová, 2018).
- In this context, municipalities often compete for investment, tax base and EU funds, instead of building joint functional-area strategies, especially around metropolitan regions such as Bratislava and Košice. OECD and World Bank analyses of lagging Slovak regions highlight that fragmented governance and weak horizontal coordination constrain the development of integrated labour markets and infrastructure corridors (OECD, 2019; World Bank; European Commission, 2019). This is robust evidence for the risk that competition rather than cooperation between municipalities undermines regional competitiveness and the functioning of wider economic territories.

References

- Es-Sadki, N., & Hollanders, H. (2023). *Regional innovation scoreboard 2023*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission. (2022). *REPowerEU plan – Guidance on renewables acceleration areas*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2025). *Regional innovation scoreboard 2025 – Main report and Slovakia regional profile*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- European Commission – Joint Research Centre. (2025). *Europe’s rural regions that bridge the innovation gap* (JRC Policy Brief). European Commission.
- Eurostat. (2024). *Rural Europe – Demographic developments in rural regions. Statistics Explained*. Eurostat.
- International Monetary Fund. (2024). *Slovak Republic: Selected issues – Regional inequality in Slovakia* (IMF Country Report No. 24/76). International Monetary Fund.
- ITF/OECD. (2023). *Urban logistics hubs*. OECD Publishing.
- Káčerová, M. (2025). Population imbalances in Europe: Urban concentration versus rural shrinkage – Slovak case study. *Geografický časopis*.
- Kleemann, J., et al. (2023). Conflicts in urban peripheries in Europe. *Land Use Policy*.
- OECD. (2019). *Spurring growth in lagging regions in the Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2021). *Managing environmental and energy transitions for regions and cities*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2023). *OECD regional outlook 2023: The long-standing geography of inequalities*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Regions and cities at a glance 2024*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Rural innovation pathways*. OECD Publishing.

OECD & UCLG. (2022). *World observatory on subnational government finance and investment – Country profile: Slovak Republic*. OECD; United Cities and Local Governments.

The Nature Conservancy. (2023). *Mapping a sustainable renewable energy transition for Europe* (Practitioner guide). The Nature Conservancy.

World Bank & European Commission. (2019). *Narrowing economic disparities between Slovakia's regions*. World Bank; European Commission.

J. Financial, Human Resource & Implementation Capacity

Challenges

1. Many municipalities lack stable long-term financing for infrastructure and planning.
2. Shortage of planners with expertise in digital, environmental, and participatory methods.
3. Implementation gaps between plans and actual development projects.

Risks

1. Overdependence on private developers and external consultants.
2. Plans losing credibility due to lack of implementation.

Actions Needed

- Strengthen municipal and regional planning capacities, training, and knowledge exchange.
- Secure multilevel funding mechanisms (EU funds, national programs, green finance).
- Create implementation-oriented planning processes with clear delivery pathways, monitoring, and evaluation indicators.

Proofs:

Challenge J.1 “*Many municipalities lack stable long-term financing for infrastructure and planning.*”

- OECD/UCLG SNG-WOFI data show that Slovak subnational governments remain among the most centralised in the OECD: subnational expenditure is only 7.8 % of GDP and 17.2 % of public spending, compared with EU-27 averages around 18.3 % of GDP and 34.3 % of public expenditure (OECD; UCLG, 2023). Grants and subsidies account for over 80 % of subnational revenue, while tax income represents just 0.6 % of GDP and 2.9 % of public tax revenue—far below EU-27 averages (OECD; UCLG, 2023). This strong dependence on central transfers and EU funds, combined with low local tax autonomy, constrains predictable multi-annual investment planning, especially for small municipalities that spend more than half of their budgets on administrative costs (OECD; UCLG, 2023). Similar patterns of underfunded local investment and reliance on upper-level grants and EU cohesion policy are identified for many EU countries in the SNG-WOFI synthesis report (OECD; UCLG, 2022).

Challenge J.2 “*Shortage of planners with expertise in digital, environmental, and participatory methods.*”

- Across OECD and EU public administrations, digital and green transitions have created new skills requirements which many administrations struggle to meet. The OECD Framework for Digital Talent and Skills in the Public Sector highlights persistent gaps in digital, data, user-centred design and change-management skills, and warns that recruitment and retention of suitably skilled professionals is a systemic challenge for governments at all levels (OECD, 2021).
- A recent OECD working paper on “Developing Skills for Digital Government” shows that many EU administrations still rely on ad-hoc training and lack strategic workforce planning for digital skills, which slows down the uptake of modern participation and co-creation methods (Burtscher; Piano; Welby, 2024).
- In Slovakia, the European Public Administration Country Report and the 2023 White Paper “Closer to the citizens” diagnose highly fragmented local government and the need for shared service centres precisely because many small municipalities cannot afford or attract specialised planners for environmental, digital and participatory tasks (European Commission, 2024).

Challenge J.3 “*Implementation gaps between plans and actual development projects.*”

- The 2024 OECD Economic Survey of the Slovak Republic stresses that growth could be boosted by improving the efficiency of public investment and the absorption of EU funds, pointing to complex procedures and weaknesses in project preparation and procurement as key bottlenecks (OECD, 2024a).
- The OECD study on demographic change in the Banská Bystrica region shows how ageing, out-migration and limited fiscal space strain local budgets and institutional capacity, making it difficult to move from strategic plans to concrete infrastructure and service projects (OECD, 2024b).
- For cohesion policy, Výrostová and Nyikos demonstrate, using Hungary and Slovakia, that higher administrative capacity and institutional stability significantly reduce financial corrections and are associated with better EU funds performance—empirical evidence that weak capacity translates into implementation gaps and under-execution of planned investments (Výrostová; Nyikos, 2024).
- The European Commission’s recent technical-support projects to “boost administrative capacity for efficient management of EU funds in Slovakia” and to “increase EU funds’ absorption and provide result-oriented investments in 2021–2027” further confirm that implementation deficits are recognised as a structural issue requiring targeted reforms in strategic programming, human-resource management and public procurement (European Commission, 2023; 2025).

Risk J.1 “*Overdependence on private developers and external consultants.*”

- Limited fiscal autonomy and thin in-house expertise encourage local governments to rely on private developers for urban projects and on external consultants for feasibility studies, EU-fund applications and specialised analyses. In Slovakia, municipalities’ capacity constraints are reflected in their heavy reliance on earmarked transfers,

development fees and PPP arrangements for infrastructure, while strategic regulation of PPPs remains centralised (OECD; UCLG, 2023).

- At EU level, the European Court of Auditors’ Special Report 17/2022 shows that the European Commission alone committed almost €1 billion annually to external consultants between 2017 and 2020, raising concerns about transparency and the risk of “hollowing out” internal capacities (European Court of Auditors, 2022).
- Research on consultancy use in government similarly warns that extensive outsourcing of core analytical and planning tasks can weaken long-term institutional knowledge and policy capability (Rethinking the commissioning of consultants, 2022).
- Given the much smaller staff and fiscal base of municipalities in Slovakia and many EU regions, these dynamics can easily translate into structural dependence on private developers and consultants, rather than a balanced partnership, when implementing local development strategies.
- Risk “Plans losing credibility due to lack of implementation.” Implementation gaps and under-absorption of EU and national investment funds undermine the credibility of local and regional development plans. The OECD SNG-WOFI synthesis underlines that subnational governments perform over half of public investment in the EU, but fiscal and capacity constraints often delay or scale down projects, creating persistent infrastructure backlogs (OECD; UCLG, 2022).
- In Slovakia, repeated technical-support initiatives by the European Commission to simplify procedures and strengthen administrative capacity for cohesion policy are a response to long-standing difficulties in turning programming documents into completed projects on the ground (European Commission, 2023; 2025). When citizens see strategic plans and spatial concepts repeatedly revised while flagship projects are postponed or cancelled, trust in public institutions and in participatory planning processes erodes, and investors may discount municipal strategies as non-credible guidance for their own decisions—precisely the risk identified in this thematic block.

References

- Burtscher, M., Piano, S., & Welby, B. (2024). Developing skills for digital government: A review of good practices across OECD governments. *OECD Social, Employment and Migration Working Papers*, No. 303. OECD Publishing.
- European Commission. (2023). *Commission supports Slovakia to make better use of cohesion funds* (Press release, 19 September 2023). European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *European public administration country report – Slovakia (EUPACK 2024) and White Paper: Closer to the citizens*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2025). *Boosting administrative capacity for efficient management of EU funds in Slovakia* (Technical Support Instrument project brief). European Commission.
- European Court of Auditors. (2022). *External consultants at the European Commission – Scope for reform* (Special Report No. 17/2022). Publications Office of the European Union.
- OECD. (2021). *The OECD framework for digital talent and skills in the public sector*. *OECD Working Papers on Public Governance*, No. 45. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *OECD economic surveys: Slovak Republic 2024*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Preparing for demographic change in the Banská Bystrica region, Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.

- OECD & UCLG. (2022). *2022 synthesis report – World observatory on subnational government finance and investment (SNG-WOFI)*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD & UCLG. (2023). *Country and territory profile: Slovak Republic – Europe (SNG-WOFI)*. OECD Publishing.
- Výrostová, E., & Nyikos, G. (2024). Administrative capacity and EU funds management systems performance: The cases of Hungary and Slovakia. *Regional Studies*, 58(4), 704–718.

1.6. Challenges, Problems, Risks, and Required Actions in the Legal Environment for Planning in Cities & Regions

Effective spatial development depends fundamentally on coherent governance structures and clear legal frameworks. Yet across Europe, fragmented institutional arrangements and inconsistent legislation remain among the most significant obstacles to integrated, future-oriented planning. Spatial, environmental, mobility, housing, water, digital, and economic policies are often governed by separate legal regimes, administered by multiple institutions with overlapping or unclear responsibilities. This complexity creates substantial coordination challenges and undermines the ability of cities and regions to plan coherently across functional urban areas where people actually live, work, commute, and interact with the environment.

This chapter examines how legal fragmentation, institutional path dependency, and misaligned governance structures weaken spatial planning systems and limit their capacity to address current societal needs. With administrative boundaries rarely matching functional territories, municipalities often lack the legal instruments needed for joint planning, shared service provision, or coordinated land-use decisions. Vertical coordination is equally problematic: the distribution of powers between national, regional, and municipal levels is frequently ambiguous, reflecting ongoing tensions between decentralization and recentralization. These inconsistencies reduce policy integration, delay key investments, and weaken the credibility of strategic plans.

The rigidity and outdated nature of many planning laws further exacerbate these challenges. Traditional zoning systems built on assumptions of stability struggle to respond to rapid demographic change, climate pressures, economic volatility, and technological innovation. When legal frameworks are slow, burdensome, or unable to accommodate experimentation, planning decisions risk being bypassed altogether—leading to informal development, ad hoc approvals, and reduced public trust.

Legal barriers also impede cross-sectoral coordination. Strong sectoral legislation in fields such as transport, environment, water management, and heritage protection often overrides strategic spatial plans, resulting in misaligned investments and contradictory land-use outcomes. Meanwhile, spatial planning remains legally disconnected from emerging sectors like digitalization, health, ageing, and housing affordability—limiting the system’s overall capacity to manage complex, interdependent challenges.

Citizen participation is another area where legal frameworks remain insufficient. Despite growing recognition of participatory rights, engagement is often formalistic and inconsistent, especially at metropolitan and regional levels where decision-making structures are more diffuse. This “illusion of inclusion” undermines trust and contributes to conflict, litigation, and delays in project implementation.

Finally, legal uncertainty and ongoing path dependency create further obstacles. Frequent amendments to planning laws, inconsistent judicial interpretations, and entrenched institutional practices create instability that affects both public authorities and private investors. Without a clear hierarchy of plans, defined competences, and professionalized planning institutions, the effectiveness of spatial governance remains limited.

By exploring these interconnected challenges, risks, and reforms, this chapter provides a comprehensive understanding of how governance and legal fragmentation shape the performance of spatial planning systems. It highlights the urgent need for integrated legal frameworks, adaptive legislation, clearer coordination mechanisms, stronger participatory rights, and stable multilevel governance structures that reflect the realities of functional urban regions. These reforms are essential for building coherent, resilient, and equitable spatial development systems capable of addressing the complex challenges of the 21st century.

A. Governance & Legal Framework Fragmentation

Challenges

1. Evidence from European spatial-planning research shows that fragmented governance and inconsistent legal frameworks are major obstacles to effective planning.
2. Fragmentation of governance structures increases the number of actors, creates “greater distance between them”, and produces inconsistent goals across sectors, hindering coordination.
3. Legal responsibilities are split between state, regional, and municipal levels, leading to poor vertical and horizontal coordination.
4. Administrative boundaries rarely match functional urban areas, making coordinated planning across municipalities legally difficult (Slovak Urban Policy).
5. Many countries face tension between decentralization and recentralization of planning powers, producing unclear legal mandates and overlapping competences.

Risks

1. Conflicting legal mandates delay or block major spatial, housing, environmental, and infrastructure investments.
2. Weak coordination leads to territorial fragmentation and unequal development performance.
3. Important environmental goals may be diluted in favour of dominant economic interests when integration mechanisms are weak.

Actions Needed

- Strengthen legal mechanisms for horizontal and vertical coordination, especially across functional urban areas.
- Align sectoral legislation (transport, environment, water, housing) within a common territorial governance framework.
- Introduce joint planning bodies or inter-municipal legal agreements to harmonize land-use decisions.

Proofs:

Challenge A.1 “*Evidence from European spatial-planning research shows that fragmented governance and inconsistent legal frameworks are major obstacles to effective planning.*”

- OECD work on regions and cities stresses that achieving competitiveness, net-zero transition and territorial cohesion requires integrated place-based strategies; weak multi-level governance and fragmented competences are explicitly associated with more persistent regional gaps in productivity and well-being in the EU and OECD (OECD, 2023a). European evidence from the World Observatory on Subnational Government Finance and Investment likewise concludes that unclear and overlapping responsibilities between tiers of government are among the main obstacles to coherent spatial, housing and infrastructure planning (OECD/UCLG, 2022).

Challenge A.2 *“Fragmentation of governance structures increases the number of actors, creates “greater distance between them”, and produces inconsistent goals across sectors, hindering coordination.”*

- The SNG-WOFI country profile for Slovakia underlines that the country has almost 3 000 municipalities, many with fewer than 2 000 inhabitants; despite their small size, these municipalities have extensive responsibilities in urban planning, housing, environment and social services, which strains their administrative and technical capacity (OECD/UCLG, 2023).
- Comparative SNG-WOFI analysis for Europe finds that a high number of very small municipalities often “cannot cope with their responsibilities due to insufficient financial, human and technical capacity”, which increases the number of actors and makes cross-sector coordination more difficult (OECD/UCLG, 2022). Similar concerns are echoed by the Council of Europe, which notes that municipal fragmentation in Slovakia creates high overheads and harms the effectiveness of local government (Council of Europe, 2021; Council of Europe, 2023).

Challenge A.3 *“Legal responsibilities are split between state, regional, and municipal levels, leading to poor vertical and horizontal coordination.”*

- In Slovakia, more than 400 tasks have been transferred to municipal and regional levels in successive decentralisation waves, but the central state retains strong legal and financial steering powers, creating complex shared competences in fields such as planning, transport, education and social policy (OECD/UCLG, 2023).
- The EU’s 2019 Country Report and the 2024 public-administration country brief both highlight that implementation of cross-cutting reforms is often limited, partly due to weak coordination between ministries, regions and municipalities (European Commission, 2019; European Commission, 2025). The SGI 2024 report ranks Slovakia last among OECD/EU countries in the category “coordination”, noting that the government office has limited capacity to align line-ministry proposals with overall priorities, which further weakens vertical and horizontal policy coherence (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024).

Challenge A.4 *“Administrative boundaries rarely match functional urban areas, making coordinated planning across municipalities legally difficult”*

- The EU–OECD definition of Functional Urban Areas (FUAs) describes them as a “city and its commuting zone”, built from contiguous local administrative units where at least

15 % of employed residents commute to the core city, thus explicitly recognising that the economic city extends beyond municipal borders (Poelman & Veneri, 2019; Eurostat, 2023).

- In the GHSL–OECD FUA dataset, FUAs in Slovakia such as Bratislava or Košice consist of multiple municipalities across several districts, confirming that functional labour-market areas cut across administrative boundaries (European Commission–JRC/OECD, 2019).
- The OECD territorial analysis for the Banská Bystrica region stresses the need to strengthen multi-level governance and adapt spatial and land-use planning to overcome “fragmentation in territories”, which includes better coordination at functional-area scale (OECD, 2024b). In this context, Slovak urban policy operates in a legal framework still largely organised by municipalities and self-governing regions, which complicates binding FUA-wide planning.

Challenge A.5 *“Many countries face tension between decentralization and recentralization of planning powers, producing unclear legal mandates and overlapping competences.”*

- The 2022 SNG-WOFI synthesis report documents that in many European states decentralisation reforms have been followed by partial recentralisation or tighter central oversight, particularly in strategic planning, infrastructure and environmental regulation, leading to complex shared competences (OECD/UCLG, 2022).
- In Slovakia, the Council of Europe notes that the system of public administration – composed of the central level, de-concentrated state administration, self-governing regions and municipalities – “faces challenges in its proper functioning” and that the government is considering reforms to rebalance responsibilities between levels (Council of Europe, 2021; Council of Europe, 2023). Policy advice prepared under the “Delivering Good Governance in Slovakia” project explicitly highlights overlapping competences and recommends clarifying mandates and diversifying the scope of services by municipal size (Allio, 2023).

Risk A.1 *“Conflicting legal mandates delay or block major spatial, housing, environmental, and infrastructure investments.”*

- The European Commission’s 2019 Country Report and the 2024 public-administration country brief for Slovakia underline that complex procedures, limited administrative capacity and weak coordination have slowed absorption of EU funds and delayed implementation of infrastructure and reform projects (European Commission, 2019; European Commission, 2025). OECD analysis for the Banská Bystrica region similarly argues that strengthening multi-level governance and clarifying roles is necessary to adapt public finances and infrastructure investment to demographic change, implying that current arrangements risk under-investment or delays (OECD, 2024b). The SGI 2024 assessment links Slovakia’s poor coordination record to “frequent inconsistencies” between strategies and implementation across sectors (Bertelsmann Stiftung, 2024).

Risk A.2 *“Weak coordination leads to territorial fragmentation and unequal development performance.”*

- The OECD Regional Outlook 2023 – The Longstanding Geography of Inequalities provides comparative evidence that regions in countries with weaker multi-level governance and coordination tend to display more persistent inequalities in GDP per capita, access to services and well-being (OECD, 2023a).
- The OECD country note for Slovakia shows that regional income disparities have widened over 2000–2020, with increased polarisation between the most and least prosperous regions (OECD, 2023b). IMF analysis finds that regional income inequality in Slovakia is among the highest in Europe; GDP per capita in Bratislava significantly exceeds that in eastern regions, reflecting differences in productivity and labour-market performance (IMF, 2024). SNG-WOFI and Council of Europe documents link these disparities to municipal fragmentation and limited capacity for coordinated regional development (OECD/UCLG, 2023; Council of Europe, 2021). (oecd-cfe-eds.github.io)

Risk A.3 *“Important environmental goals may be diluted in favour of dominant economic interests when integration mechanisms are weak.”*

- The SNG-WOFI 2022 synthesis emphasises that subnational governments are central to delivering the Sustainable Development Goals, but that fragmented responsibilities and insufficient coordination mechanisms hinder the integration of climate and environmental objectives into sectoral policies and investment decisions (OECD/UCLG, 2022).
- OECD work on Banská Bystrica stresses that integrated approaches across spatial planning, transport, environment and public finance are needed to adapt to demographic and climate pressures; without such integration, short-term economic or fiscal considerations are likely to dominate land-use and infrastructure choices (OECD, 2024b). At EU level, the Regional Outlook 2023 warns that if regional inequalities and governance gaps persist, the green transition may proceed unevenly, with lagging regions under-investing in environmental goals relative to more prosperous areas (OECD, 2023a).

References

- Allio, L. (2023). *Regional policy advice on strengthening the status of cities and municipalities in Slovakia*. Council of Europe.
- Bertelsmann Stiftung. (2024). *SGI 2024: Slovakia report*. Bertelsmann Stiftung.
- Council of Europe. (2021). *Delivering good governance in Slovakia*. Council of Europe.
- Council of Europe. (2023). *Strengthening the status of cities and municipalities in Slovakia: A peer review*. Council of Europe.
- European Commission. (2019). *Country report Slovakia 2019*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2025). *Country brief 2024 – Slovakia (EUPACK)*. European Commission.
- European Commission, Joint Research Centre, & OECD. (2019). *GHSL–OECD functional urban areas (GHSL_FUA 2019)*. Publications Office of the European Union.
- Eurostat. (2023). *Territorial typologies manual – Cities, commuting zones and functional urban areas. Statistics Explained*. Eurostat.

International Monetary Fund. (2024). Regional inequality in Slovakia. In *Slovak Republic: Selected issues* (IMF Country Report No. 24/76). International Monetary Fund.

OECD. (2023). *OECD regional outlook 2023: The longstanding geography of inequalities*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2023). *OECD regional outlook 2023 – Country note: Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.

OECD. (2024). *Preparing for demographic change in the Banská Bystrica region, Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.

OECD & UCLG. (2022). *2022 synthesis report of the World Observatory on Subnational Government Finance and Investment – Highlights*. OECD; United Cities and Local Governments.

OECD & UCLG. (2023). *Subnational government structure and finance: Country profile – Slovak Republic (SNG-WOFI)*. OECD; United Cities and Local Governments.

Poelman, H., & Veneri, P. (2019). The EU-OECD definition of a functional urban area. *OECD Regional Development Working Papers*, No. 2019/11. OECD Publishing.

B. Rigid and Outdated Planning Legislation

Challenges

1. Many countries still rely on rigid zoning systems with limited ability to adapt policies to new issues.
2. Traditional planning laws assumed stability and predictability—yet planners now face uncertainty, disruptive technologies, and complex socio-economic change.
3. Legal procedures tend to be slow and burdensome, unable to respond to dynamic urban development needs.

Risks

1. When laws are too rigid, decisions bypass formal planning, resulting in informal development or contradictory ad-hoc decisions.
2. Outdated requirements reduce planning credibility and hinder sustainable spatial development.

Actions Needed

- Modernize planning legislation to include adaptive tools, scenario-based planning, and iterative updates.
- Introduce legally supported experimental zones, pilot areas, and flexible instruments enabling learning and innovation.
- Preserve accountability and transparency to prevent misuse of discretion.

Proofs:

Challenge B.1 “*Many countries still rely on rigid zoning systems with limited ability to adapt policies to new issues.*”

- Across the OECD, land-use planning is still dominated by statutory zoning and detailed, legally binding plans. The OECD overview of land-use planning systems notes that in most member countries local authorities adopt strategic plans plus detailed plans that contain zoning regulations and ordinances, embedded in laws that define a fixed hierarchy of plans (OECD, 2017a; OECD, 2017b; KRAWCHENKO, 2021).

- These systems were designed for stability and legal certainty rather than rapid policy adjustment. The companion report *The Governance of Land Use in OECD Countries* concludes that existing land-use policies often lack flexibility and explicitly recommends making them “more flexible and more effective” to cope with new economic, environmental and social pressures (OECD, 2017b).
- For Slovakia, this rigidity is visible in the long-standing Building Act No. 50/1976 Coll., which governed spatial planning and building regulation for almost 50 years before the recent reform. Legal analyses emphasise that the 2024 reform will end the validity of a nearly 50-year-old act and introduce more flexible, up-to-date instruments (POLÁČEK & PARTNERS, 2023; SPECTATOR, 2023).
- OECD work on Slovak housing policy similarly stresses that barriers to expanding housing supply stem from land-use regulation and calls for reforming land-use policy to reduce constraints and make building permits more responsive (DE PACE, 2024).

Challenge B.2 *“Traditional planning laws assumed stability and predictability—yet planners now face uncertainty, disruptive technologies, and complex socio-economic change.”*

- The OECD highlights that land use today is shaped by powerful new drivers—climate change, demographic decline or ageing, housing affordability crises and the green and digital transitions—while many planning frameworks were built for an era of steady urban growth and relatively predictable trends (OECD, 2017b; OECD, 2023a).
- In its regional studies on demographic change (including for Banská Bystrica in central Slovakia), the OECD notes that current spatial planning instruments remain largely oriented towards expansion and do “not yet sufficiently integrate scenarios of long-term population decline,” making it difficult to adapt to shrinking labour markets and ageing communities (OECD, 2024a).
- At EU level, recent in-depth reviews for Slovakia and other member states stress that planning and permitting systems must adjust to new investment needs linked to climate neutrality, energy transition and digital infrastructure; otherwise, they risk becoming bottlenecks for both private and public investment (European Commission, 2025).

Challenge B.3 *“Legal procedures tend to be slow and burdensome, unable to respond to dynamic urban development needs.”*

- The OECD Economic Survey of the Slovak Republic 2024 finds that complex administrative procedures for granting building permits slow down construction projects and recommends adopting more efficient, digitalised processes to make housing supply more responsive (OECD, 2024b).
- The 2024 OECD working paper on housing notes again that there is “scope for eliminating barriers to expand housing supply by reforming land use policy and streamlining the administration of building permits” (De Pace, 2024).
- Complementing these OECD assessments, a European legal briefing reports that permitting of any projects is a long-standing problem in the Slovak Republic, with international surveys placing Slovakia near the bottom: on average, it takes around 300 days to permit even a simple building such as a family house, and delays are worse for complex projects involving multiple authorities (Ceelm, 2023). The fact that the 2024 Building Act reform explicitly aims to simplify and accelerate procedures, merge

separate zoning and construction procedures, and introduce statutory deadlines for opinions and decisions confirms that the previous system was widely seen as too slow and burdensome to support dynamic urban development (Poláček & partners, 2023; KPMG Slovensko, 2023).

Risk B.1 *“When laws are too rigid, decisions bypass formal planning, resulting in informal development or contradictory ad-hoc decisions.”*

- The OECD’s land-use governance report warns that poorly coordinated and rigid planning frameworks can generate unintended consequences, including incentives for developers to circumvent formal procedures and inconsistent decisions across sectors and levels of government (OECD, 2017b).
- (library.unccd.int) In Slovakia, the new Building Act strengthens sanctions for unauthorised building and simplifies permitting partly to tackle a legacy of informal or non-compliant construction, which had flourished under slow and opaque procedures (SPECTATOR, 2023; KPMG SLOVENSKO, 2023).
- Moreover, OECD case studies on land-use adaptation in shrinking regions show that where statutory plans are difficult to revise, authorities often rely on ad hoc exceptions or project-specific negotiations rather than systematic plan updates, undermining transparency and predictability (OECD, 2024a; OECD, 2023b).

Risk B.2 *“Outdated requirements reduce planning credibility and hinder sustainable spatial development.”*

- The OECD stresses that outdated land-use regulations and fragmented planning frameworks can lock in unsustainable spatial patterns, such as urban sprawl, high infrastructure costs and environmental degradation, and calls for integrated, flexible planning that considers climate, housing, transport and fiscal impacts together (OECD, 2017b; OECD, 2023a).
- In central and eastern European regions facing demographic decline, including Slovakia’s Banská Bystrica, OECD analysis shows that current planning rules often fail to support compact settlement patterns, brownfield reuse and adaptation of oversized infrastructure, thereby hindering long-term fiscal and environmental sustainability (OECD, 2024a).
- For Slovakia specifically, EU and OECD documents link slow, complex permitting and rigid land-use rules to constrained housing supply, rising prices and difficulties in directing development towards more sustainable forms (DE PACE, 2024; OECD, 2024b; European Commission, 2025).
- As procedures lose credibility with investors and citizens, informal practices and legal disputes increase, further weakening the ability of planning institutions to steer development towards compact, climate-resilient and socially inclusive spatial structures—exactly the risk your text identifies.

References

CEE Legal Matters. (2023). *Slovakia: The problem with building permits*. CEE Legal Matters.

- De Pace, F. (2024). *Enhancing the efficiency, inclusiveness, and environmental sustainability of housing in the Slovak Republic*. OECD Economics Department Working Papers, No. 1806. OECD Publishing.
- European Commission. (2025). *In-depth review 2025 – Slovakia* (Institutional Paper No. 315). European Commission.
- KPMG Slovensko. (2023). *Changes brought by the new building act*. KPMG Slovensko.
- Krawchenko, T. (2021). Land use planning systems in OECD countries: Trends, practices, innovations and reforms. In *Encyclopedia of the UN Sustainable Development Goals*. Springer.
- OECD. (2017). *Land-use planning systems in the OECD: Country fact sheets*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2017). *The governance of land use in OECD countries: Policy analysis and recommendations*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Preparing for demographic change in Castilla y León, Spain / Campania, Italy: Chapters on adapting land use and spatial planning to shrinkage*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *OECD economic surveys: Slovak Republic 2024*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Preparing for demographic change in the Banská Bystrica region, Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Regions and cities at a glance 2024*. OECD Publishing.
- Poláček & Partners. (2023). *Fundamental changes brought by the new building legislation*. Poláček & Partners.
- The Slovak Spectator. (2023). *Slovakia gets new legislation governing construction after almost 50 years*. The Slovak Spectator.

C. Legal Barriers to Integrated, Cross-Sectoral Planning

Challenges

1. Strong sectoral laws (transport, environment, water, heritage) often override strategic spatial plans, making integration legally weak.
2. Unequal power between sectors and differences in their legal timeframes make coordination difficult.
3. Spatial planning remains legally disconnected from key emerging sectors such as digitalization, health, and housing.

Risks

1. Misaligned investment decisions and contradictory land-use outcomes.
2. Overlapping assessments and procedures increase administrative burden and create legal uncertainty for local authorities and investors.

Actions Needed

- Introduce binding cross-sector obligations to consider spatial impacts in all sectoral legislation.
- Ensure spatial plans have strengthened legal weight in decision-making.
- Harmonize environmental, infrastructure, and urban-development procedures to reduce conflicts.

Proofs:

Challenge C.1 *“Strong sectoral laws (transport, environment, water, heritage) often override strategic spatial plans, making integration legally weak.”*

- Comparative OECD work on land-use governance shows that in most OECD and EU countries, framework planning laws coexist with powerful sectoral laws on transport, environment, water and heritage. These sectoral regimes frequently have directly applicable permitting or project-approval powers that “constrain or override” strategic spatial plans when conflicts arise, making integration legally fragile (OECD, 2017).
- The companion survey of land-use planning systems documents 229 different types of spatial and land-use plans, but notes that key decisions on infrastructure, water management or nature protection are often taken under separate sector statutes with their own procedures and appeal regimes (OECD, 2017; OECD, 2017a).
- In Slovakia, the “Concept of Territorial Development of Slovakia” is formally the top-level spatial planning document, binding for regional and local plans (Úrad pre územné plánovanie a výstavbu, 2024).
- However, the planning system operates alongside strong sectoral legislation on transport, environment, water and cultural heritage, which retains autonomous permitting powers. Recent legal analyses of the new Office for Spatial Planning and Construction stress that, despite modernisation, many sectoral procedures (for example environmental impact assessment, water and nature protection permits) continue to run in parallel and can block or reshape projects even when they comply with spatial plans (Mazúr, 2023).

Challenge C.2 *“Unequal power between sectors and differences in their legal timeframes make coordination difficult.”*

- OECD analysis of land-use governance emphasises that sectoral ministries and agencies (notably transport and environment) often command more financial resources, technical expertise and legal instruments than planning authorities, leading to “asymmetric bargaining power” and making integrated decisions difficult (OECD, 2017).
- Sectoral laws also operate with distinct planning cycles (e.g. multi-annual river-basin management plans under the EU Water Framework Directive, transport investment programmes, Natura 2000 management plans) that do not align with statutory spatial plan review periods, reinforcing fragmentation (Krawchenko, 2020).
- In Slovakia, the Council of Europe’s Delivering Good Governance in Slovakia project notes that local and regional self-government is highly fragmented and fiscally weak compared with central ministries, which reduces its influence over sectoral investment decisions (Council of Europe, 2021; Trutkowski, 2023).
- Policy advice prepared under the same programme highlights that key strategic sectors remain centrally driven, while municipalities mainly implement measures within a limited legal and financial space, making horizontal and vertical coordination structurally difficult (Allio, 2023).
- The OECD Regulatory Policy Outlook 2025 shows that Slovakia still struggles to coordinate impact assessments and stakeholder processes across ministries, recommending stronger whole-of-government mechanisms to avoid inconsistent regulations and overlapping procedures (OECD, 2025).

Challenge C.3 “*Spatial planning remains legally disconnected from key emerging sectors such as digitalization, health, and housing.*”

- The OECD land-use programme underlines that effective land-use governance must coordinate “a broader set of public policies affecting land use beyond traditional planning systems,” explicitly naming housing, climate, transport, fiscal and innovation policies as areas where integration is often weak (OECD 2024).
- However, trends in spatial planning across OECD countries show that statutory plans still focus primarily on physical land use and zoning, while fast-moving policy agendas—digital connectivity, health systems, green infrastructure—are typically regulated by sector strategies with limited formal linkage to planning law (Krawchenko 2020; OECD 2017).
- In Slovakia, the official description of the planning system confirms that national and regional spatial plans define land use, transport corridors and technical infrastructure, but sectoral strategies for digitalisation, health-care facilities or social housing are developed under separate frameworks and only indirectly reflected in plans (Úrad pre územné plánovanie a výstavbu 2024; Mazúr 2023).
- Recent EU country reporting also notes that fragmented governance and unpredictable regulation hinder Slovakia’s capacity to implement investment projects in areas such as digital infrastructure, health and housing, suggesting that spatial planning is not yet a fully integrated platform for these emerging sectors (European Commission 2025).

Risk C.1 “*Misaligned investment decisions and contradictory land-use outcomes.*”

- The OECD’s Governance of Land Use in OECD Countries shows that when transport, housing, environmental protection and fiscal policies are decided in silos, the result is often inconsistent land-use outcomes: infrastructure located without regard to settlement patterns, sprawl in some regions and undersupply of housing in others, and rising congestion and emissions (OECD 2017). These misalignments translate into higher public costs and lower productivity in functional urban areas.
- For Slovakia and other EU members, the European Court of Auditors’ landscape review on transport infrastructure finds that reduced and poorly prioritised investment has “held back the modernisation of the EU’s transport network,” noting weaknesses in strategic coordination between EU, national and regional investment choices (European Court of Auditors 2023).
- The 2025 Country Report Slovakia further states that fragmented governance and administrative burdens “heavily impact Slovakia’s capacity to effectively implement investment projects,” which contributes to bottlenecks in transport and other infrastructure (European Commission 2025).
- Evidence from multi-level governance assessments in Slovakia shows that many municipalities and regions develop their own strategies with limited coordination, leading to inconsistent approaches to land development and service provision across functional areas (Council of Europe 2021; OECD/UCLG 2023).
- Together, these findings substantiate the risk that legally fragmented, sector-driven decisions will produce misaligned investments and contradictory land-use patterns, undermining both competitiveness and territorial cohesion in Slovakia and the wider EU.

Risk C.2 “*Overlapping assessments and procedures increase administrative burden and create legal uncertainty for local authorities and investors.*”

- The OECD has repeatedly stressed that complex, overlapping regulatory procedures and documentation requirements generate substantial administrative burden, discouraging investment and innovation; simplifying and streamlining such procedures is therefore a core recommendation of its administrative-simplification agenda (OECD 2024b).
- In the EU, the Commission has set a target to reduce administrative burden for businesses by at least 25 % by 2030, explicitly acknowledging that cumulative reporting and permitting obligations in areas such as environment and transport have become too heavy and unpredictable (European Commission 2024a).
- Environmental permitting provides a concrete example. A CERRE study on renewable-energy permitting notes that “lengthy, complex and multiple parallel permitting procedures” for generation assets, grid connections and related infrastructure are a major barrier to deployment, delaying projects for years and increasing costs (CERRE 2024).
- In response, Commission Recommendation (EU) 2024/1343 on speeding up permit-granting for renewable energy explicitly calls on Member States to streamline and integrate administrative authorisations, environmental assessments and spatial-planning steps, recognising that current fragmentation creates uncertainty for investors and overloads authorities (European Commission 2024b).
- These EU-wide findings are mirrored in Slovakia. Country analyses highlight that an “unpredictable regulatory environment, administrative burdens and fragmented governance structure” hamper investment implementation (European Commission 2025).
- Council of Europe advice on Slovak regional and local government reform stresses that complex, overlapping competences and procedures between central and local levels generate high overheads and weaken local effectiveness (Council of Europe 2021; Allio 2023). In fields such as construction and spatial planning, the coexistence of planning permission, environmental impact assessment, sectoral consents (water, nature, cultural heritage) and public-procurement rules creates multiple potential litigation and appeal points, which investors perceive as legal risk, even when environmental standards are not in question (Mazúr 2023; OECD 2025).

References

- Allio, L. (2023). Policy Advice on Regional Decentralisation in Slovakia. Strasbourg: *Weak Legal Basis for Citizen Participation* Council of Europe.
- CERRE (2024). Speeding Up Renewable Energy Permitting in Europe: Overcoming Implementation Challenges. Brussels: Centre on Regulation in Europe.
- Council of Europe (2021). Delivering Good Governance in Slovakia. Strasbourg: Council of Europe, Centre of Expertise for Good Governance.
- European Commission (2024a). Simplification and Implementation – Better Regulation: Simplification. Brussels: European Commission.
- European Commission (2024b). Commission Recommendation (EU) 2024/1343 on Speeding Up Permit-Granting Procedures for Renewable Energy and Related Infrastructure Projects. Official Journal of the European Union L 1343.

European Commission (2025). Country Report Slovakia 2025. European Semester Country Report. Brussels: European Commission.

European Court of Auditors (2023). Landscape Review on EU Transport Infrastructure Investment. Luxembourg: European Court of Auditors.

Krawchenko, T. (2020). “Trends in Spatial Planning in OECD Countries.” In: Trends in Spatial Planning. Paris: OECD.

Mazúr, J. (2023). “The Current and New Legal Regulations of Spatial Planning in the Legal Order of the Slovak Republic.” Štát a právo, Special issue.

OECD (2017). The Governance of Land Use in OECD Countries: Policy Analysis and Recommendations. Paris: OECD Publishing.

OECD (2024a). Governance of Land Use – Project Overview. Paris: OECD. (OECD)

OECD (2024b). Administrative Simplification – Topic Page. Paris: OECD. (OECD)

OECD (2025). OECD Regulatory Policy Outlook 2025: Slovak Republic Country Chapter. Paris: OECD Publishing.

Úrad pre územné plánovanie a výstavbu Slovenskej republiky (2024). Spatial Planning System of the Slovak Republic. Bratislava: UÚPV SR.

D. Weak Legal Basis for Citizen Participation

Challenges

1. Although participation rights have increased, legal provisions often remain weak or unevenly applied.
2. Many countries still operate with weak engagement or mere information sharing, not meaningful involvement.
3. At metropolitan/regional scales, citizen engagement is particularly difficult due to unclear legal responsibilities and lack of participatory procedures.

Risks

1. “Illusion of inclusion”: participation tools appear in law but do not influence decisions, reducing trust.
2. Legal challenges and public opposition delay projects when engagement is insufficient.

Actions Needed

- Strengthen legal requirements for early and continuous participation, including digital platforms.
- Mandate transparent feedback loops showing how public input influenced decisions.
- Harmonize participation rights across regions and sectors.

Proofs:

Challenge D.1 “*Although participation rights have increased, legal provisions often remain weak or unevenly applied.*”

- Across the EU and OECD, the formal right of citizens to participate has expanded, but implementation remains partial. The OECD’s work on open government notes that many countries have adopted access-to-information laws and consultation requirements, yet often lack clear standards on the quality and impact of participation and on how input must be taken into account in decisions (OECD, 2016; OECD, 2017a; OECD, 2023a). (OECD, 2017b) stresses that open government reforms need to move from

scattered transparency measures towards robust participation frameworks embedded in law and practice.

- For Slovakia and the EU, the Aarhus Convention provides a binding legal basis in environmental matters, yet several compliance cases show uneven application. In the Mochovce nuclear power plant case, the Aarhus Convention Compliance Committee found that Slovakia had failed to ensure timely and effective public participation, and recommended changes in national procedures (UNECE, 2011). A later communication on Slovak forestry legislation again concluded that Slovakia did not fully comply with obligations on public participation in preparing regulations (UNECE, 2021). These decisions show that even where rights are formally recognised, they are not consistently implemented.
- The 2024 Rule of Law Report for Slovakia and civil-society shadow reports further highlight the frequent use of accelerated legislative procedures and short consultation periods, which limit meaningful involvement of stakeholders (European Commission, 2024; Liberties, 2024; Central European Times, 2024). This confirms the challenge that participation rights exist but remain legally and practically weak or unevenly applied.

Challenge D.2 *“Many countries still operate with weak engagement or mere information sharing, not meaningful involvement.”*

- OECD analyses distinguish between simple information provision and deeper forms of consultation and active participation in decision-making. The Open Government: The Global Context and the Way Forward report, based on a survey in over 50 countries (including EU members), concludes that many participation practices stop at “informing” or one-off consultations and that only a minority systematically involve citizens in co-creating policies or evaluating results (OECD, 2016). The more recent OECD Guidelines for Citizen Participation Processes stress that participation is often ad hoc, with unclear objectives and little feedback on how citizen input influenced outcomes (OECD, 2023b).
- At EU level, the Better Regulation Guidelines require stakeholder consultations, but evaluations of their application highlight that consultations can be highly technical and dominated by better-organised interests, and that citizens often experience them as a top-down information exercise rather than genuine dialogue (European Commission, 2019; European Commission, 2020).
- A joint civil-society submission to the 2024 Rule of Law cycle explicitly describes public consultations in several member states, including Slovakia, as “tick-the-box exercises”, with short deadlines and limited possibilities for civil-society organisations to influence draft laws (Civil Society Europe, 2024). This directly supports the statement that in practice engagement often means information sharing or symbolic consultation, not meaningful involvement.

Challenge D.3 *“At metropolitan/regional scales, citizen engagement is particularly difficult due to unclear legal responsibilities and lack of participatory procedures.”*

- OECD and EU work on functional areas and cohesion policy stresses that metropolitan and regional scales are crucial for managing transport, environment and economic development, but that legal responsibilities are often fragmented between levels of

government. Open Government: The Global Context and the Way Forward concludes that subnational participation frameworks are usually less developed than national ones, and that coordination across levels of government is a key challenge for citizen participation (OECD, 2016).

- An OECD case study on implementing citizen participation in EU cohesion policy across 11 pilot territories notes that regional and metropolitan authorities frequently lack clear procedural rules, stable funding and dedicated capacities for involving citizens throughout the investment cycle; responsibilities are split between managing authorities, line ministries and municipalities, which makes it hard for citizens to know who is accountable and where to engage (OECD, 2023c).
- In Slovakia, the Open Government Partnership National Action Plan acknowledges that participation is stronger around central-government initiatives than at regional or local level and that systematic frameworks for citizen engagement across territories are still being built (Government Office of the Slovak Republic, 2024).

Risk D.1 “Illusion of inclusion’: participation tools appear in law but do not influence decisions, reducing trust.”

- OECD surveys show that citizens’ sense of “having a say” in government decisions is limited. Government at a Glance 2023 reports that, on average across OECD countries, around half of respondents score low on the belief that the political system lets them influence what government does (OECD, 2023a). The OECD Survey on the Drivers of Trust also finds that people who feel their views are taken into account show significantly higher trust in public institutions than those who feel ignored (OECD, 2022). A Slovak analysis of participatory democracy summarises these findings and shows that both OECD and Eurobarometer data link meaningful participation to higher trust and democratic stability (GLOBSEC, 2024).
- At EU level, research on institutional trust finds persistent concern about decreasing trust in several member states and identifies limited political voice as a key factor (TRUEDEM, 2023). Civil-society reports to the 2024 Rule of Law cycle warn that when consultations are formalistic or rushed, they create an “illusion of participation” that can actually undermine legitimacy (Civil Society Europe, 2024). Justice & Environment’s synthesis of Court of Justice and Aarhus case law similarly emphasises that decisions adopted without effective public participation risk being seen as illegitimate and provoke stronger opposition (Justice & Environment, 2023).
- For Slovakia, the combination of formal commitments under the Open Government Partnership and repeated criticism of fast-tracked laws and symbolic consultations (European Commission, 2024; Liberties, 2024) illustrates the risk that legal participation tools do not translate into real influence, thereby weakening trust and democratic resilience.

Risk D.2 “Legal challenges and public opposition delay projects when engagement is insufficient.”

- The Aarhus Convention explicitly links effective public participation to smoother implementation of environmentally significant projects and policies (Aarhus Convention, 1998). Where participation is inadequate, affected communities and NGOs

can—and do—resort to legal remedies. The Mochovce nuclear power plant case before the Aarhus Compliance Committee shows how perceived deficiencies in access to information and participation in Slovakia generated lengthy international review and additional procedural steps (UNECE, 2011).

- Another case on Slovak forestry legislation similarly reflects how insufficient involvement of the public in drafting legislation led to a finding of non-compliance and the need to revise legal provisions (UNECE, 2021).
- The EU-wide analysis by Justice & Environment on effective participation under the Aarhus Convention concludes that lack of early and meaningful engagement often results in court challenges, annulment of permits and project delays, while good-quality participation can reduce conflict and litigation (Justice & Environment, 2023).
- OECD work on stakeholder engagement in regulation and infrastructure also notes that insufficient consultation increases the risk of legal disputes and public opposition, particularly for large infrastructure projects (OECD, 2023a).

References

- Aarhus Convention. (1998). *Convention on access to information, public participation in decision-making and access to justice in environmental matters*. UNECE.
- Central European Times. (2024). *New EC report assesses rule of law across CEE*. Central European Times.
- Civil Society Europe. (2024). *Joint civil society contribution on civic space to the 2024 annual rule of law report*. Civil Society Europe.
- European Commission. (2019–2020). *Better regulation guidelines and toolbox*. European Commission.
- European Commission. (2024). *2024 rule of law report – Country chapter on Slovakia*. European Commission.
- Globsec. (2024). *Participatory democracy in Slovakia*. GLOBSEC.
- Government Office of the Slovak Republic. (2024). *Open Government Partnership national action plan of the Slovak Republic 2024–2026*. Úrad splnomocnenca vlády SR pre rozvoj občianskej spoločnosti.
- Justice & Environment. (2023). *The practice of the Court of Justice of the European Union regarding effective participation under the Aarhus Convention*. Justice & Environment.
- Liberties (Civil Liberties Union for Europe). (2024). *Liberties rule of law report 2024 – Slovakia chapter*. Civil Liberties Union for Europe.
- OECD. (2016). *Open government: The global context and the way forward*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2017). *Recommendation of the Council on open government (OECD/LEGAL/0438)*. OECD.
- OECD. (2023). *Government at a glance 2023*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *Implementing citizen participation at all stages of the EU cohesion policy cycle*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *OECD guidelines for citizen participation processes*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2025). Citizen participation and deliberation. In *Government at a glance 2025*. OECD Publishing.
- TruEDEM Project. (2023). *Institutional trust in Europe: Dimensions, levels and dynamics (Deliverable D4.2)*. TruEDEM.

UNECE. (2011). *Progress report on the findings and recommendations of the Aarhus Convention Compliance Committee in Case ACCC/2009/41 (Slovakia – Mochovce NPP)*. UNECE.

UNECE. (2021). *Findings and recommendations of the Compliance Committee with regard to Communication ACCC/2014/101 (Slovakia – Forestry legislation)*. UNECE.

E. Legal Uncertainty and Path Dependency

Challenges

1. Many planning systems, especially in post-socialist countries, suffer from path dependency, with old legal structures persisting despite new societal needs.
2. Frequent amendments to planning laws create instability and confusion for municipalities and investors.
3. Inconsistent judicial interpretations undermine legal certainty.

Risks

1. Reduced investor confidence and increased litigation.
2. Weak enforcement of plans due to contradictory or unstable legal requirements.

Actions Needed

- Comprehensive reforms rather than piecemeal amendments.
- Clear hierarchy of plans and legally defined competences.
- Professionalization and training for planning authorities to ensure consistent interpretation of laws.

Proofs:

Challenge E.1 “Path dependency of planning systems in post-socialist countries”

- In Slovakia, spatial planning was governed for decades by Act No. 50/1976 Coll. (the Building Act), adopted in a socialist context and only gradually modified, so that the core hierarchy of spatial plans and instruments from 1976 and the Concept of Territorial Development of Slovakia 2001/2011 still formed the backbone of the system up to the recent reforms (Jakušová; Michalovič 2023).
- This confirms strong legal path dependency: old concepts and tools persisted even as societal needs shifted towards climate adaptation, digitalisation and new forms of development. OECD work on land-use planning similarly notes that many OECD countries, including in Central and Eastern Europe, still rely on rigid, zoning-based frameworks inherited from earlier periods, and that reforms often seek to modernise these legacy systems while preserving their basic structure (OECD 2017).

Challenge E.2 “Frequent amendments and unstable legal environment”

- The Slovak construction and planning framework is currently undergoing major reform: Acts No. 200/2022 Coll. on Spatial Planning and 201/2022 Coll. on Construction are intended to replace the old Building Act, but their entry into force has been phased and repeatedly adjusted. As HKV Law Firm summarises, the legislature had to adopt Act No. 205/2023 Coll. to harmonise “complex procedural changes, new institutes and a different way of permitting construction” across many sectoral laws, while the new

Construction Act was postponed to 2025 and the old Building Act remains applicable for building permits until the end of 2024 (HKV Law Firm 2024).

- At the same time, new regional planning and construction offices and the URBION information system were introduced, but the latter was not fully operational when the legislation entered into force, which “may reduce the clarity of the application process for claimants” (HKV Law Firm 2024).
- Academic analysis by Jakušová and Michalovič highlights that spatial planning rules are now partly in a stand-alone Spatial Planning Act and partly in transitional provisions, adding layers of complexity to an already dense hierarchy of plans and documents (Jakušová; Michalovič 2023).

Challenge E.3 “Inconsistent judicial and regulatory practice undermining legal certainty”

- While detailed statistics on planning case-law consistency are scarce, broader governance assessments show that Slovakia’s legal and regulatory framework is perceived as unpredictable. The Sustainable Governance Indicators (SGI) 2024 report notes that the judiciary is formally autonomous but that “recent decisions have indicated a lack of independence,” corruption in the judiciary is a “significant concern,” and implementation of regulatory impact assessments and ex-post evaluations is “erratic” (Bertelsmann Stiftung 2024).
- At EU level, the Commission underlines that threats to the rule of law “challenge the legal, political and economic basis of how the EU works” and that the rule of law is essential for “predictable and equitable rules and a system of effective judicial remedies” (European Commission 2019a; 2020).
- The EU “Effective justice systems” thematic factsheet stresses that quality, independence and efficiency of courts are prerequisites for an investment- and business-friendly environment (European Commission 2017). (European Commission) In a context where judicial independence is questioned and implementation of laws is uneven, investors and municipalities can reasonably anticipate divergent interpretations and outcomes, which supports your challenge about inconsistent application undermining legal certainty in planning and related fields.

Risk E.1 “Reduced investor confidence and increased litigation”

- EU institutions explicitly link legal certainty and effective justice systems to investment. The Commission’s rule-of-law communications and the EU Justice Scoreboard emphasise that respect for the rule of law and effective courts are essential for a “citizen-, business- and investment-friendly environment” (European Commission 2019a; 2025).
- A European Semester factsheet similarly notes that effective justice systems “instil confidence throughout the entire business cycle” and are crucial for implementing economic law (European Commission 2017).
- Empirically, an EIB working paper using EU-wide EIB Investment Survey data shows that higher uncertainty raises borrowing costs, leads firms to “spend less on new projects” and to cancel or delay investments, including climate-related investments (Lucalli et al. 2025).

- In Slovakia, the combination of major but staggered legislative reforms, overlapping old and new regimes, and concerns about judicial independence and corruption (Bertelsmann Stiftung 2024) plausibly heightens perceived legal risk in construction and real-estate projects. Under these conditions, investors are more likely to rely on litigation to clarify rules, or to avoid complex projects altogether, substantiating your risk of reduced investor confidence and more disputes.

Risk E.2 “Weak enforcement of plans due to contradictory or unstable legal requirements”

- The new Slovak Spatial Planning Act reinforces the binding nature of spatial planning documentation and sets up a complex hierarchy from national concepts down to municipal and zone-level plans (Jakušová; Michalovič 2023).
- At the same time, transitional provisions mean that proceedings started before 1 April 2024 continue under the old Building Act, while new proceedings follow the new framework; numerous sectoral laws were simultaneously amended to reflect the reform (HKV Law Firm 2024).
- HKV also highlight that the planned digitalisation (URBION system) lagged behind the legal changes, reducing transparency for users. In practice, this coexistence of legal regimes, the high volume of cross-referencing amendments, and partial implementation of digital tools create a high risk that authorities, courts and investors will apply rules inconsistently across territories and time. SGI 2024 further notes that monitoring of compliance with standards for land-use and related local services in Slovakia is “fragmented,” and that horizontal coordination across ministries is weak (Bertelsmann Stiftung 2024).
- EU-wide, the Commission warns that deficiencies in the rule of law and justice systems can undermine uniform application of EU law and the effective functioning of internal-market rules (European Commission 2019a; 2020).

References

- Bertelsmann Stiftung. (2024). *SGI 2024: Slovakia report*. Bertelsmann Stiftung.
- European Commission. (n.d.). *Effective justice systems* (European Semester thematic factsheet). European Commission.
- European Commission. (2019). *Communication: Further strengthening the rule of law within the Union* (COM(2019) 343 final). European Commission.
- European Commission. (2025). *2025 EU justice scoreboard – Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the ECB, the EESC and the CoR*. European Commission.
- HKV Law Firm. (2024, April 30). Reform of construction legislation. *HKV Law & Business Blog*.
- Jakušová, V., & Michalovič, M. (2023). The current and new legal regulations of spatial planning in the legal conditions of the Slovak Republic. In *Právny priestor pre geoinformatiku a územné plánovanie*.
- Lucalli, E., et al. (2025). *How do energy prices and uncertainty affect climate investment by European firms?* (EIB Working Paper No. 2025/05). European Investment Bank.
- OECD. (2017). *Land-use planning systems in the OECD*. OECD Publishing.

F. Legal Barriers to Multilevel Governance

Challenges

1. Cities often lack legal authority to coordinate with surrounding municipalities despite functioning as functional urban areas (as noted in the Slovak Urban Policy).
2. National legislation often recentralizes key sectors (water, environment, housing), limiting regional or municipal influence.
3. Legal fragmentation between local, regional, and national levels complicates strategic planning.

Risks

1. Metropolitan areas underperform due to missing frameworks for joint planning.
2. Regional inequalities and incoherent spatial development patterns.

Actions Needed

- Create legal frameworks for metropolitan governance structures.
- Strengthen inter-municipal cooperation through binding agreements.
- Clarify division of powers in national legislation.

Proofs:

Challenge F.1 “*Cities often lack legal authority to coordinate with surrounding municipalities despite functioning as functional urban areas (as noted in the Slovak Urban Policy).*”

- The joint EU–OECD definition of Functional Urban Areas (FUAs) explicitly recognises that cities operate as labour-market regions extending far beyond their administrative borders: a FUA is defined as a city plus all local units where at least 15 % of employed residents commute to that city (OECD, 2019; Eurostat, 2023).
- Recent EU FUA toolkits underline that such functional areas “have one thing in common: cooperation beyond administrative borders” and require specific governance arrangements (EC–World Bank–OECD–UN–Habitat, 2025).
- OECD/UCLG SNG-WOFI country profile shows that Slovakia has 2 927 municipalities, most of them very small, and that cooperation between them is predominantly voluntary and project-based rather than grounded in binding metropolitan law (OECD; UCLG, 2023).
- The Council of Europe’s Delivering Good Governance in Slovakia project similarly notes that high municipal fragmentation and limited formalised cooperation mechanisms “harm the effectiveness of local government” (Council of Europe, 2021). Taken together, this is strong evidence that, although Bratislava, Košice and other Slovak FUAs function as integrated economic territories, cities often lack clear legal mandates and instruments to coordinate with their surrounding municipalities, confirming the challenge identified in the Slovak Urban Policy and in internal project analyses. (EMINUK, 2025).

Challenge F.2 “*National legislation often recentralizes key sectors (water, environment, housing), limiting regional or municipal influence.*”

- Comparative OECD and Council of Europe assessments describe Slovakia as a unitary state with formally decentralised self-governing regions and municipalities, but with

key competences and financing rules tightly framed by national legislation (OECD; UCLG, 2023).

- Policy advice prepared under Delivering Good Governance in Slovakia – II phase concludes that the legal framework for local self-government is complex and unstable, with frequent legislative changes and a persistent tendency to recentralise decision-making in sensitive sectors such as environment and utilities (Council of Europe, 2023). (Mesa10) EU country reports also criticise “insufficient cooperation between the national, regional and local levels” and note that municipal financing capacities are often restricted to basic services and infrastructure, leaving little room for proactive housing and environmental policies (European Commission, 2019). (Portal) These findings support the claim that national legislation and funding rules frequently limit the effective influence of regions and municipalities over water management, environmental protection and housing – sectors that are central to sustainable local development.

Challenge F.3 *“Legal fragmentation between local, regional, and national levels complicates strategic planning.”*

- The OECD Regional Outlook 2023 stresses that effective regional development in EU/OECD countries requires coherent multi-level governance frameworks; fragmented legal responsibilities and poorly coordinated sectoral laws are identified as key causes of inconsistent regional strategies (OECD, 2023).
- In Slovakia, Council of Europe policy advice on strengthening the status of cities and municipalities points to “fragmented and overlapping competences” across levels of government and recommends simplifying the territorial and regulatory framework to enable more strategic, long-term planning (Council of Europe, 2023).
- The SNG-WOFI country profile further documents that subnational governments rely heavily on shared and delegated responsibilities, governed by multiple sectoral laws, which complicates integrated territorial strategies and joint investment programming (OECD; UCLG, 2023).

Risk F.1 *“Metropolitan areas underperform due to missing frameworks for joint planning.”*

- OECD work on FUAs shows that metropolitan areas are the main growth engines in Europe, but that their performance depends crucially on appropriate governance arrangements and joint planning across municipal boundaries (OECD, 2019; OECD, 2020).
- An URBACT review of functional territories highlights that many European metropolitan areas are administratively fragmented and that where no formal metropolitan governance framework exists, urban sprawl, congestion and inefficient infrastructure investments are more common, undermining competitiveness (URBACT, 2025).
- For Slovakia, OECD regional country notes and the Banská Bystrica case study argue that strengthening multi-level governance and functional-area cooperation is necessary to attract investment and respond to demographic change, implying that current arrangements are not fully exploiting metropolitan potential (OECD, 2023; OECD, 2024).

- The Committee of the Regions has likewise called for stronger metropolitan and functional-area frameworks in EU cohesion policy, warning that without them metropolitan regions underperform relative to their socio-economic role (CoR, 2024).

Risk F.2 “*Regional inequalities and incoherent spatial development patterns.*”

- The OECD Regional Outlook 2023 shows that regional disparities in GDP per capita within Slovakia have widened since 2000, with a rising Theil index and increasing polarisation between the most and least prosperous regions (OECD, 2023). It links such persistent inequalities in EU countries to shortcomings in multi-level governance and the lack of coherent, place-based development strategies. At the EU scale, functional-territory analyses note that where administrative boundaries and sectoral laws are not aligned with FUA or other functional areas, land-use and infrastructure decisions are often taken in isolation, leading to incoherent settlement patterns, urban sprawl and inefficient public service provision (EC–JRC; OECD, 2019; URBACT, 2025).
- In Slovakia, the EU’s 2019 Country Report and the Council of Europe’s good-governance projects emphasise that high municipal fragmentation and weak cross-level coordination “create high overheads and harm the effectiveness of local government”, diverting resources from strategic functions such as spatial planning, transport and housing (European Commission, 2019; Council of Europe, 2021).

References

- Committee of the Regions. (2024). *Metropolitan regions and functional urban areas as socio-economic engines*. European Committee of the Regions.
- Council of Europe. (2021). *Delivering good governance in Slovakia*. Council of Europe.
- Council of Europe. (2023). *Policy advice on strengthening the status of cities and municipalities in Slovakia*. Council of Europe.
- EMINUK. (2025). *D2.1 Internal project document on multilevel governance*. EMINUK.
- European Commission. (2019). *Country report Slovakia 2019*. European Commission.
- OECD. (2019). *The EU-OECD definition of a functional urban area*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2023). *OECD regional outlook 2023: Country note – Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD. (2024). *Preparing for demographic change in the Banská Bystrica region, Slovak Republic*. OECD Publishing.
- OECD & UCLG. (2023). *Subnational government structure and finance: Country profile – Slovak Republic (SNG-WOFI)*. OECD; United Cities and Local Governments.
- URBACT. (2025). *Functional territories for better integrated governance*. URBACT Secretariat.

2. Challenges, Problems, Risks, and Required Actions in the Development of Cities & Region in the Slovak Republic

Slovakia is currently divided into 8 regions, 79 districts, including 5 in Bratislava and 4 in Košice, and 2,890 municipalities (Hamalová, 2022). In terms of statistical territorial units, there are 3 regional levels - NUTS 1 - Slovakia, NUTS 2 – 4 areas, NUTS 3- 8 regions. At the

local level, there are 2 levels of statistical territorial units – LAU 1 – 79 districts and LAU 2 – 2 890 municipalities.

The local level of governance in Slovakia was established in 1990 by no. 369/1990 Coll. on municipalities amended and its importance was confirmed also by the Constitution of the Slovak Republic in 1993 (Act of NRSR no. 90/2001 Coll. on the Constitution of the Slovak Republic amended). Gradually, the self-governing bodies were established, as well as the practical implementation of their competences, rights and responsibilities for public governance - there was constituted an important and legitimate system of the country (Krnáč et al, 2018).

By the act no. 369/1990 Coll. on municipalities amended, municipality is an independent self-governing territorial unit of the Slovak Republic, associating citizens who have there a permanent residence. The role of the municipality is to care about the comprehensive development of its territory and the population living in it. The municipality takes its name, cadastral area, the right to own symbols (coat of arms, flag, seal, and anthem); the right to associate with other municipalities.

In Slovakia, a one-tiered municipal government was established beside the cities of Bratislava and Košice (cities over 100 thousand inhabitants) with two-layers of self-government - city and city district. In Bratislava and Košice, only 2 cities with more as 100 000 inhabitants, the division of tasks, responsibilities and duties is defined by Act on the capital city Bratislava and the Act on the city of Kosice. The total number of Slovak municipalities is 2 890, including 141 cities. 84,81 % of municipalities have less than 1999 inhabitants. The structure of the Slovak cities by the number of citizens presents table 1.

Table 1 Structure of the Slovak municipalities and cities by the number of citizens.

Municipalities by number of inhabitants	Number	Share
Municipalities with less as 1 999 inhabitants	2451	84,81%
Municipalities with 2 000 - 4 999 inhabitants	301	10,42%
Municipalities with 5 000 - 9 999 inhabitants	67	2,32%
Municipalities with 10 000 - 19 999 inhabitants	33	1,14%
Municipalities with 20 000 - 49 999 inhabitants	28	0,97%
Municipalities with 50 000 - 99 999 inhabitants	8	0,28%
Municipalities with more as 100 000	2	0,07%
Total	2890	100,00%
Towns by number of inhabitants	Number	%
0-4999	23	16,31%
5000-9999	46	32,62%
10000-19 999	34	24,11%
20000-49 999	28	19,86%
50-99 999	8	5,67%
100 000 and more	2	1,42%
Total	141	100%

The regional level the governance is presented by higher territorial units, territorial self-governing and administrative unit of the Slovak Republic. It defined by the Act No. 302/2001 Coll. of the National Council of the Slovak Republic on the self-government of higher territorial units, as amended. A self-governing region is a legal entity which, under conditions laid down

by law, independently manages its own property and revenues, and secures and protects the rights and interests of its inhabitants. The map of all 8 regions in the Slovakia presents figure 1.

Figure 1 Map of Slovak Regions

While Slovakia shares many of the development challenges seen across European regions, several structural and institutional characteristics intensify their impact and shape a distinct national context. The country’s governance environment is marked by fragmentation, a high degree of centralization, and limited capacity at regional and municipal levels — factors that hinder coherent economic, social, environmental, and spatial development. Persistent regional disparities, demographic decline, brain drain, and dependence on low-value industrial structures further complicate long-term development trajectories. Slovakia also struggles with weak innovation ecosystems, outdated infrastructure, insufficient social and affordable housing, and growing climate vulnerabilities. These issues are magnified by misalignment between national, regional, and local strategies and by limited cooperation across functional urban areas. As a result, Slovakia faces heightened risks of territorial polarization, reduced competitiveness, and slow adaptation to technological and environmental change. Overcoming these challenges requires systemic improvements in governance, stronger metropolitan and regional cooperation, investment in human capital and innovation, and more integrated, forward-looking policies across sectors.

2.1. Challenges, Problems, Risks, and Required Actions in the Economic Development of Slovakia

Slovakia’s economic development is increasingly constrained by a deeply fragmented governance system. OECD and EU assessments repeatedly point to one systemic barrier: the

country lacks coherent, well-coordinated economic governance capable of driving long-term transformation. National ministries responsible for the economy, education, transport, finance, and innovation operate in parallel, producing contradictory policies and weak strategic alignment.

Regional self-governments remain among the weakest in the EU, with limited competencies, scarce resources, and minimal influence over regional development. Most decisions—funding allocations, strategic planning, sectoral reforms—are centralized, leaving regions unable to shape industrial policy, transport networks, workforce development, or innovation ecosystems. At the same time, municipalities rarely cooperate across functional urban areas. This results in fragmented management of housing, labour mobility, industrial zones, and public transport.

These governance weaknesses have direct economic consequences: delayed infrastructure projects, inefficient use of EU funds, stalled innovation capacity, and widening regional disparities between western and eastern Slovakia. Short political cycles further undermine continuity, making it difficult to implement long-term reforms in education, research, energy transition, or transport corridors.

The chapter demonstrates that governance fragmentation interacts with structural vulnerabilities—overdependence on automotive production, weak R&D performance, skills mismatches, and brain drain. Without stronger cross-ministerial coordination, empowered regions, metropolitan governance, and long-term national development frameworks, Slovakia risks falling behind neighbouring Central European economies.

As the proofs related to Slovakia situation across addressed domains are to big extend identic with the proofs identified in previous chapter, the authors decided to integrate the proofs there with listing the specifics for Slovakia. In this context, pls. refer for proofs for challenges and risks in this chapter there.

Fragmented Economic Governance & Weak Strategic Coordination

Challenges

- Evidence from OECD and EU regional development assessments shows that fragmented governance is one of Slovakia’s core economic bottlenecks.
- Strategic fragmentation among national ministries (economy, education, finance, transport) produces contradictory policies, especially in innovation, regional development, labour markets, and infrastructure.
- Weak regional self-government (VÚC) limits the ability to design and implement territorial strategies; most competencies and resources remain centralized.
- Misalignment between national strategies (e.g., RIS3, Recovery Plan) and local/regional needs leads to ineffective targeting of investment support.
- Insufficient cooperation among municipalities reduces capacity to manage industrial zones, labour mobility, housing, and transport across functional regions.
- Short political cycles undermine continuity of long-term economic policies.

Risks

- Inconsistent priorities delay major economic investments, including transport corridors, R&D centres, and energy transition projects.

- Persistent regional disparities, with Western Slovakia advancing but Central and Eastern regions stagnating.
- Inefficient use of EU funds due to fragmented responsibilities and lack of coordination.

Actions Needed

- Strengthen cross-ministerial economic policy coordination, especially for innovation, education, and infrastructure.
- Provide greater fiscal and strategic autonomy to regional governments to implement place-based development strategies.
- Institutionalize metropolitan cooperation mechanisms for transport, housing, innovation, and industrial development (Bratislava, Košice, Žilina).
- Establish long-term national development frameworks beyond 4-year political cycles.

Economic Structure Dependence & Low Value-Added Production

Challenges

- Slovakia's economy is over-dependent on automotive and assembly-based industries, with limited domestic value capture.
- Low-level diversification makes the economy vulnerable to global supply-chain shocks and technological disruption.
- Weak domestic supplier base results in high import dependency for intermediate goods.
- Limited high-tech exports and insufficient transformation of applied research into commercial innovation.

Risks

- Automation and electrification of cars may reduce employment in dominant industrial sectors.
- Volatility in global supply chains exposes Slovakia to production downturns.
- Technological lag threatens competitiveness as neighbouring countries (CZ, PL, HU) accelerate tech-industry support.

Actions Needed

- Support industrial diversification into AI, robotics, advanced materials, defence tech, and green technologies.
- Strengthen domestic supplier upgrading programs to move SMEs into higher-value segments.
- Boost technology transfer mechanisms, including innovation vouchers, R&D tax incentives, and university–industry partnerships.

Skills Mismatch, Brain Drain & Weak Education–Economy Linkages

Challenges

- Chronic mismatch between education outputs and labour-market needs (ICT, engineering, green skills).
- Brain drain—thousands of young people leave annually due to wage gaps and perceived lack of opportunities.
- Vocational training is outdated, misaligned with digitization and Industry 4.0 requirements.
- Insufficient cooperation between universities, research institutions, and employers.

- Low investment in lifelong learning and adult reskilling.

Risks

- Workforce shortages in key sectors (IT, healthcare, R&D, engineering) limiting investment attraction.
- Aging population increases dependency ratios and fiscal pressure.
- Loss of talent reduces innovation potential and slows transition to a knowledge-based economy.

Actions Needed

- Modernize curricula for digital, technical, and green skills at all levels.
- Introduce dual education reforms linked to regional industry needs.
- Create incentives for high-skilled return migration (tax benefits, grants).
- Invest in lifelong learning and reskilling programs tied to economic transitions (EV, robotics, AI).

Infrastructure Gaps & Territorial Disparities

Challenges

- Incomplete highway and rail networks, especially in Central and Eastern Slovakia, limit mobility and investment.
- Insufficient multimodal transport and logistics capacity, reducing export competitiveness.
- Uneven quality of digital infrastructure outside main urban centres.
- Housing shortages in growing metropolitan areas (Bratislava, Košice) limit labour mobility.

Risks

- Investors avoid poorly connected regions, reinforcing economic duality between West and East.
- Logistics inefficiencies, exacerbated by outdated rail freight infrastructure, raise business costs.
- Housing constraints accelerate outward migration, especially among youth.

Actions Needed

- Prioritize completion of key TEN-T corridors and rail modernization.
- Develop regional logistics hubs integrating rail–road–air transport.
- Expand digital connectivity, especially high-speed internet in rural areas.
- Implement affordable housing strategies in metropolitan growth areas.

Weak Innovation Ecosystem & Low R&D Investment

Challenges

- Slovakia's R&D spending (as % of GDP) remains among the lowest in the EU.
- Fragmented research institutions, low collaboration, and administrative barriers hinder innovation output.
- Insufficient commercialization, with few spin-offs and patent applications.
- Public R&D funding is unstable, often concentrated in EU-program cycles.

Risks

- Low productivity growth threatens long-term competitiveness.

- Investors shift R&D-intensive activities elsewhere in Central Europe.
- Difficulty adopting AI, automation, and green technologies across industry sectors.

Actions Needed

- Increase public and private R&D investment, targeting applied sectors.
- Support creation of innovation districts and university-based research centres.
- Simplify grant administration and reduce bureaucracy in R&D funding.
- Strengthen intellectual property support services for researchers and SMEs.

Environmental Pressures, Energy Transition Challenges & Climate Risks

Challenges

- High dependency on fossil fuels and imported energy sources.
- Slow adoption of renewables, restrictions in spatial planning, and weak grid capacity.
- Air quality and environmental degradation, especially in industrial regions.
- Vulnerability to climate change impacts (heatwaves, droughts, flooding).

Risks

- Energy insecurity and vulnerability to geopolitical shocks.
- Failure to meet EU climate obligations, risking penalties.
- Reduced competitiveness if Slovak firms fall behind green standards.

Actions Needed

- Modernize energy infrastructure and increase RES integration.
- Implement green industrial transformation programs for high-emission sectors.
- Strengthen climate adaptation strategies at regional and municipal levels.
- Promote circular economy models in manufacturing and construction.

2.2. Challenges, Problems, Risks, and Required Actions in the Social Development of Slovakia

Slovakia faces with the demographic and social transformation that will shape its economic resilience, territorial cohesion, and long-term development trajectory. The country faces one of the fastest-ageing populations in the EU, combined with persistently low fertility rates and continued outmigration of young and skilled workers—especially from eastern, southern, and rural regions. These trends accelerate demographic imbalance, weaken labour supply, and increase pressure on social and healthcare systems already struggling with limited capacity and underinvestment. Rising dependency ratios further threaten the sustainability of pensions and long-term care.

At the same time, Slovakia continues to experience some of the most significant regional disparities in Central Europe. Prosperous metropolitan centres contrast sharply with declining peripheral areas, where weak labour markets, limited transport accessibility, and shrinking populations undermine local development. Social exclusion, particularly among marginalised Roma communities, remains a persistent challenge, driven by segregation in housing and education and insufficient integration of social, health, and employment services.

Education quality and skills formation represent a critical bottleneck. Persistent underfunding, outdated curricula, and low attractiveness of the teaching profession contribute to weak learning outcomes and a growing mismatch between education and labour-market needs. This reinforces brain drain and reduces Slovakia’s ability to adapt to technological transformation. Fragmented social-protection systems and slow progress in community-based services further limit support for vulnerable groups, increasing long-term costs and eroding trust in institutions.

Labour-market pressures are amplified by industrial transition, automation, and low productivity in key sectors. Without strong reskilling systems, better childcare provision, and inclusive activation policies, structural unemployment may rise. Housing affordability presents an additional challenge: Slovakia has one of the lowest shares of social housing in the EU, with rising prices pushing young families and low-income households into insecurity or outmigration.

This chapter analyses these interconnected demographic, social, and territorial dynamics, highlighting the risks they pose to Slovakia’s future and identifying the strategic actions necessary to strengthen resilience, inclusion, and sustainable development across all regions.

Demographic Decline & Ageing Population

Challenges

- Slovakia faces one of the fastest-ageing populations in the EU, with fertility rates persistently below replacement levels.
- Outmigration of young and skilled workers (especially from eastern and southern regions) accelerates demographic imbalance.
- Insufficient capacity of social and healthcare systems to accommodate rapid ageing.
- Dependency ratios are increasing, putting pressure on pensions, long-term care, and public finances.

Risks

- Labour shortages, reduced economic productivity, and slower innovation.
- Unsustainable pension and health-care costs.
- Deepening regional disparities as shrinking towns lose skilled youth.

Actions Needed

- Develop a long-term demographic strategy linking family policy, migration policy, and labour-market incentives.
- Invest in long-term care infrastructure, geriatric facilities, and community-based social services.
- Support return migration programs and attract skilled migrants.
- Introduce pension system reforms ensuring long-term sustainability.

Persistent Regional Inequalities

Challenges

- Strong East–West divide in income, employment, education, and access to services.
- Peripheral rural areas experience population decline, weak labour markets, and limited public transport.
- Concentration of opportunities in Bratislava and selected urban centres.
- Fragmented territorial governance weakens strategic regional development.

Risks

- Continuation of “two-speed Slovakia”—prosperous urban cores vs. declining peripheries.
- Social tensions, increased poverty, and reduced social cohesion. Higher pressure on urban centres due to rural depopulation.

Actions Needed

- Targeted regional development programs tied to measurable outcomes.
- Integrated transport, digital, and service infrastructure investments in poorer regions.
- Strengthen inter-municipal cooperation to pool resources and coordinate services.
- Support local economic ecosystems (SMEs, social enterprises, innovation hubs).

Social Exclusion & Poverty (Especially Among Roma Communities)

Challenges

- Slovakia has one of the highest rates of severe material deprivation among marginalised.
- Roma communities in the EU.
- Persistent segregation in housing and education.
- Low educational attainment and barriers to labour-market participation.
- Insufficient integration of social, education, health, and employment services.

Risks

- Perpetuation of intergenerational poverty.
- Limited labour-market participation reduces national economic potential.
- Social tensions and higher public spending on crisis interventions.

Actions Needed

- Implement coordinated, place-based inclusion programs linking housing, education, health, and employment.
- Strengthen anti-discrimination enforcement and desegregation measures.
- Invest in early childhood education, community centres, and health mediators.
- Support social housing and integrated municipal services.

Education Quality & Skills Mismatch

Challenges

- Slovakia’s education outcomes (PISA) consistently fall below EU/OECD averages.
- Under-financed school system and lack of teacher support (low salaries, low attractiveness of teaching career).
- Skills mismatch between education output and labour-market needs.
- Insufficient focus on digital skills, critical thinking, and STEM competencies.

Risks

- Reduced human capital and long-term economic competitiveness.
- More young people seeking education abroad and not returning.
- Failure to adapt to digital and technological transformation.

Actions Needed

- Increase long-term investment in education, teacher training, and school infrastructure.
- Modernize curricula with emphasis on digital and critical-thinking competencies.
- Expand dual education links with employers.

- Support inclusive education and reduce early school leaving.

Inefficient Social Protection & Fragmented Services

Challenges

- Social services system is fragmented between state, regions, and municipalities, resulting in uneven access.
- Lack of integrated case management for vulnerable groups (elderly, disabled, long-term unemployed, children at risk).
- Underdeveloped community-based and preventive services; overreliance on institutional care.
- Administrative burden and complexity in accessing benefits.

Risks

- High long-term costs due to underinvestment in prevention.
- Increased poverty and inequality.
- Diminished trust in public institutions.

Actions Needed

- Develop an integrated social-services coordination framework with clear competences.
- Shift from institutional care to community-based and preventive services.
- Simplify benefit systems and improve accessibility through digitalization.
- Strengthen workforce capacity in social work and care professions.

Labour Market Challenges & Technological Transformation

Challenges

- High share of low-productivity jobs and slow industrial modernization.
- Automation threatens manufacturing jobs, especially in automotive sector.
- Insufficient lifelong learning and reskilling opportunities.
- Low employment among women with young children and long-term unemployed.

Risks

- Structural unemployment if workers cannot adapt to technological change.
- Compounded regional inequalities where industrial jobs concentrate.
- Loss of competitiveness in key sectors.

Actions Needed

- Introduce national reskilling and upskilling programs aligned with industrial transformation.
- Support diversification of regional economies and innovation activities.
- Expand childcare services and flexible work options to increase women's employment.
- Strengthen labour-market activation and tailored counselling.

Housing Affordability & Social Housing Deficit

Challenges

- Severe shortage of affordable rental housing, with one of the lowest shares of public/social housing in the EU.
- High housing prices relative to incomes, especially in Bratislava and regional capitals.

- Insufficient regulatory tools for municipalities to shape markets (e.g., inclusionary zoning).
- Poor housing conditions in marginalised settlements.

Risks

- Young families excluded from housing markets, encouraging outmigration.
- Growing homelessness and housing insecurity.
- Informal or substandard housing proliferation.

Actions Needed

- Develop a national affordable housing strategy, including large-scale rental construction.
- Expand municipal capacities for housing planning and management.
- Modernize building regulations to support affordable, energy-efficient construction.
- Integrate housing solutions with social inclusion programs

2.3. Challenges, Problems, Risks, and Required Actions in Environmental Development of Slovakia

Slovakia’s environmental performance and climate resilience are increasingly limited by a fragmented governance system that divides responsibilities across multiple ministries, regional administrations, and more than 2,900 municipalities. This institutional complexity weakens coordination, slows decision-making, and undermines the integration of key environmental agendas—water management, biodiversity protection, climate adaptation, waste policy, and energy transition—into spatial planning and sectoral strategies. Ecological systems operate across river basins, mountain ranges, and protected landscapes, yet administrative boundaries rarely match these natural units, resulting in inconsistent management and contradictory policy choices.

The country faces rising climate risks, including floods, droughts, heatwaves, and forest disturbances, while many municipalities still lack mandatory adaptation plans or the financial and analytical capacity to prepare them. Biodiversity loss and landscape fragmentation continue as development, transport networks, and intensive land use erode ecological corridors and degrade habitats. Air quality remains one of the most pressing public-health challenges in Slovak cities, driven by outdated heating, industrial emissions, and insufficient sustainable mobility.

Water-management systems show similar weaknesses: aging infrastructure, insufficient wastewater treatment, and limited stormwater retention make settlements vulnerable to hydrological extremes. Energy transition efforts progress slowly due to administrative barriers, grid constraints, and high dependence on fossil fuels, particularly in heating and industry. Waste management and circular-economy development lag behind EU standards, while soil degradation continues to threaten agricultural productivity.

Collectively, these environmental and governance challenges expose Slovakia to increasing ecological, economic, and social risks. This chapter examines the roots of institutional fragmentation, identifies the consequences for environmental policy outcomes, and outlines the reforms needed to strengthen coordination, integrate ecological principles into

territorial development, and build a more resilient and sustainable environmental governance system.

Fragmented Governance & Weak Environmental Policy Integration

Challenges

- Environmental governance in Slovakia is spread across several ministries (Environment, Agriculture, Economy, Transport), regional administrations, and 2,900+ municipalities—resulting in weak cross-sector alignment and inconsistent environmental decision-making.
- Environmental agendas (water, biodiversity, climate adaptation, waste, energy) are insufficiently integrated into spatial planning and sectoral policies.
- Administrative boundaries do not match ecological boundaries (river basins, protected areas, emission zones), making coordinated environmental management difficult.
- Municipalities have limited analytical capacity and often depend on short-term project funding rather than stable environmental planning frameworks.

Risks

- Conflicting policies (e.g., forestry vs. biodiversity; transport vs. air quality) undermine national environmental objectives.
- Slow implementation of EU environmental directives may result in infringement procedures and financial penalties.
- Fragmented governance reduces adaptive capacity to climate change impacts (floods, droughts, erosion).

Actions Needed

- Establish stronger mechanisms for inter-ministerial environmental coordination.
- Integrate ecological boundaries (river basins, Natura 2000 areas) into planning frameworks and regional development strategies.
- Strengthen environmental planning capacity at regional and municipal levels through shared services, joint authorities, or ecological planning centres.

Climate Change Vulnerabilities & Insufficient Adaptation Measures

Challenges

- Slovakia faces increasing climate risks: extreme floods (northern regions), heatwaves (cities), drought (southern lowlands), and forest disturbances (Tatra region).
- Urban areas lack long-term adaptation plans: green infrastructure, urban cooling, water retention, and heat-resilient design are insufficiently applied.
- Climate adaptation measures are not legally mandatory for municipalities or developers.
- Hydrological extremes are increasing, yet water management remains rigid, relying mainly on grey infrastructure.

Risks

- Higher frequency of natural hazards causing damage to property, ecosystems, and infrastructure.
- Escalating costs for municipalities and the state due to reactive rather than proactive management.
- Increased vulnerability of energy, water, and food systems to climate shocks.

Actions Needed

- Introduce legal obligations for climate-risk assessments and adaptation measures at municipal and regional levels.
- Mainstream nature-based solutions (floodplains, rain gardens, wetlands, urban forests) into planning and investment frameworks.
- Modernize water management with integrated, basin-level approaches and promote retention rather than reliance on large infrastructure.

Biodiversity Loss, Landscape Fragmentation & Habitat Degradation

Challenges

- Slovakia's biodiversity-rich landscapes face pressures from development, forestry intensification, agriculture, and infrastructure expansion.
- Habitat fragmentation due to roads, urban growth, and industrial sites reduces ecological connectivity.
- Natura 2000 obligations are often weakly enforced, and management plans for protected areas are outdated or insufficiently implemented.
- Agricultural subsidies historically favoured intensification rather than biodiversity-friendly practices.

Risks

- Continued decline of ecologically important species and habitats, especially in lowlands.
- Ecosystem services deterioration (pollination, water retention, soil fertility), affecting long-term economic resilience.
- EU sanctions for failing to protect Natura 2000 sites or manage protected areas adequately.

Actions Needed

- Introduce ecological connectivity corridors into the planning system with legal protection.
- Strengthen enforcement of Natura 2000 regulations and update management plans with binding measures.
- Shift agricultural and forestry incentives toward biodiversity-positive measures (hedgerows, extensive grazing, mixed forests).

Persistent Air Pollution & Urban Environmental Quality Issues

Challenges

- Slovakia ranks among the EU's worst performers in PM2.5 due to domestic solid-fuel heating, industrial emissions, and traffic.
- Urban areas lack systematic low-emission strategies: weak public transport integration, limited cycling infrastructure, slow electrification.
- Many municipalities have outdated or incomplete Air Quality Management Plans.
- Urban green infrastructure is unevenly distributed and often undervalued in planning.

Risks

- Continued public health impacts and higher healthcare costs.

- Infringement procedures from the European Commission for exceeding air-quality limits.
- Reduced attractiveness of cities for investment and population retention.

Actions Needed

- Introduce stronger local emission-control regulations and financial incentives to replace outdated heating systems.
- Integrate air quality goals into transport planning and municipal zoning decisions.
- Create robust urban greening standards (tree planting requirements, permeable surfaces, heat mitigation zones).

Water Management Challenges: Floods, Droughts & Infrastructure Gaps

Challenges

- Aging water infrastructure leads to high leakage, insufficient stormwater management, and limited capacity during extreme rainfall.
- Water scarcity is growing in the southern and eastern parts of Slovakia, yet irrigation systems are outdated or unused.
- Many settlements still lack modern wastewater treatment facilities, especially small villages.
- River regulation, channelization, and hydropower expansions reduce natural river dynamics and degrade habitats.

Risks

- Repeated flood events causing major municipal and agricultural damage.
- Drought impacts reducing agricultural productivity and stressing drinking-water supplies.
- Penalties for failing to meet EU Water Framework Directive objectives.

Actions Needed

- Implement integrated water retention strategies (wetlands, floodplains, soil improvement) at regional scales.
- Modernize water-supply and wastewater infrastructure, prioritizing vulnerable rural regions.
- Expand adaptive river restoration projects to increase resilience and ecological quality.

Energy Transition, Decarbonization & Dependence on Fossil Fuels

Challenges

- Despite progress, Slovakia is still significantly dependent on fossil fuels in heating, industry, and transport.
- Renewable energy deployment is slowed by administrative complexity, grid-capacity limits, and public resistance to infrastructure.
- Energy poverty remains a major issue, especially in rural areas using solid fuels.
- Industrial decarbonization is slow, with limited incentives for clean technologies.

Risks

- Failure to meet EU 2030 and 2050 climate targets.
- Increased energy vulnerability due to dependence on imported fossil fuels.
- Slow economic modernization and reduced competitiveness.

Actions Needed

- Simplify permitting and grid connection for renewable sources.
- Expand support for community energy, rooftop solar, and green heating technologies.
- Create strategic incentives for industrial decarbonization and circular-economy innovations.

Waste Management, Circular Economy & Soil Degradation

Challenges

- High material consumption and low recycling rates persist despite EU obligations.
- Illegal landfills remain widespread, especially near small municipalities.
- Soil degradation from erosion, contamination, and unsustainable land management threatens food security.
- Circular-economy mechanisms are underdeveloped and lack strong legal support.

Risks

- Increased land contamination and environmental remediation costs.
- Financial penalties for non-compliance with EU waste directives.
- Loss of agricultural productivity due to declining soil quality.

Actions Needed

- Strengthen enforcement against illegal dumping and accelerate landfill remediation.
- Develop national circular-economy legislation supporting reuse, repair, and industrial symbiosis.
- Implement soil protection standards and incentives for regenerative agricultural practices

2.4. Challenges, Problems, Risks, and Required Actions in the Digital Development of Slovakia

Slovakia’s digital transformation is significantly constrained by fragmented governance structures, unclear institutional mandates, and inconsistent coordination across government levels. Multiple ministries—Informatization and Regional Development (MIRRI), Economy, Education, Interior—share responsibility for digital development, yet their priorities often diverge, resulting in duplicated projects, incompatible systems, and slow progress in modernizing public administration. Regional and municipal authorities also lack coherent digital strategies and sufficient technical capacity, which widens the gap between better-prepared urban centres and digitally weaker rural areas.

Digital systems in public administration, healthcare, education, justice, and transport operate in isolated technological silos, preventing interoperability and limiting the efficiency of public services. Frequent institutional reorganisations, including changes in MIRRI’s mandate, further disrupt long-term planning and undermine continuity of national digital strategies. Outdated legislation, rigid procurement rules, and slow regulatory adaptation to emerging technologies (AI, IoT, cloud services) create additional barriers to innovation.

Weak data governance, fragmented datasets, and limited availability of high-quality open data reduce Slovakia’s potential to develop digital services, support research, and stimulate

private-sector innovation. At the same time, insufficient broadband coverage in rural areas reinforces regional inequalities and restricts economic opportunities. Low digital skills across much of the population, combined with shortages of IT professionals and underprepared schools, further slow progress in digitalisation.

Cybersecurity vulnerabilities add another layer of risk: municipalities, public institutions, and critical infrastructure operators often lack adequate protection, increasing exposure to cyberattacks and eroding public trust in digital government. Finally, Slovakia's digital innovation ecosystem remains underdeveloped, with weak university–industry cooperation, fragmented funding, and bureaucratic hurdles limiting the growth of startups and tech enterprises.

This chapter analyses these structural barriers, showing how fragmented governance, outdated legislation, weak data systems, and limited innovation capacity collectively slow Slovakia's digital transformation. It highlights the reforms needed to build a coordinated, secure, inclusive, and innovation-driven digital governance framework.

Fragmented Digital Governance & Institutional Coordination

Challenges

Evidence from European digital-transformation assessments shows that fragmented digital governance and unclear mandates significantly slow down national digitalization. Slovakia faces similar structural barriers:

- Multiple ministries (MIRRI, Economy, Education, Interior) share digital-development responsibilities, often with overlapping mandates and inconsistent priorities.
- Central government, regional self-governments (VÚC), and municipalities lack coordinated digital agendas; many local authorities have weak digital capacities.
- Digital systems (public administration, health, education, justice) operate in isolated silos, preventing interoperability.
- Frequent institutional reorganizations (e.g., changes in MIRRI's mandate) disrupt continuity of long-term digital strategies.

Risks

- Slower implementation of e-government, delayed public digital services.
- Risks of duplicated IT investments and incompatible systems across ministries.
- Incoherent digital transformation between urban and rural regions, widening territorial inequalities.

Actions Needed

- Establish a stable national coordination authority with clear digital-competence mandates.
- Develop a single National Interoperability Framework binding for all public institutions.
- Strengthen regional and municipal digital-governance capacities through funding and guidelines.

Inefficient and Outdated Digital Legislation

Challenges

- Key digitalization laws, including data governance, cybersecurity, and digital identity, remain incomplete, outdated, or inconsistently enforced.

- Legislation does not keep pace with emerging technologies (AI, IoT, cloud), and regulatory adaptation is slow.
- Complex procurement laws limit innovation in public IT projects, often prioritizing low price over value and quality.
- Inflexible legal requirements hinder pilot projects or experimental digital solutions.

Risks

- Slow uptake of modern technologies in public services and business.
- Increased legal uncertainty for digital startups and tech investors.
- Public IT projects become outdated by completion, wasting public resources.

Actions Needed

- Update digital legislation with adaptive and technology-neutral principles.
- Introduce regulatory sandboxes for AI, data-driven services, and digital innovations.
- Reform public procurement to allow innovation partnerships, pilot testing, and value-based criteria.

Data Governance, Interoperability, and Digital Infrastructure Integration

Challenges

- Public administration lacks unified data standards, causing data fragmentation.
- Many systems are not interoperable across ministries, municipalities, or EU digital infrastructures.
Limited availability of high-quality open data reduces innovation potential in research and business.
- Rural areas face weaker digital infrastructure & broadband coverage, limiting regional competitiveness.

Risks

- Poor-quality data leads to inefficient policymaking and delays in digital public services.
- Reduced private-sector innovation due to lack of reliable open datasets.
- Digital divide between regions reduces economic opportunities and social inclusion.

Actions Needed

- Create a National Data Governance Act covering data standards, sharing, and responsibilities.
Accelerate cross-sector interoperability and integrate Slovak systems into EU Digital Single Market infrastructure.
- Expand high-speed broadband and 5G infrastructure, prioritizing underserved regions.
- Release open data in machine-readable formats with clear licensing.

Low Digital Skills, Workforce Shortages & Education System Gaps

Challenges

- Slovakia ranks below the EU average in digital skills, especially in older and rural populations.
- Severe shortage of IT professionals due to brain drain and insufficient STEM graduate output.
- Schools lack modern equipment and teachers lack digital competencies.

- Adult education and reskilling systems are fragmented and rarely aligned with labor-market needs.

Risks

- Slower digital transformation in public and private sectors.
- Limited ability of Slovakia to compete for high-value digital investments.
- Widening inequality for populations excluded from digital services and labor markets.

Actions Needed

- Integrate digital skills systematically into all levels of education, including teacher training.
- Support workforce reskilling programs, especially in AI, cybersecurity, cloud, and data analytics.
- Fund regional digital-skills centers for adult learning and digital inclusion.

Cybersecurity Vulnerabilities and Insufficient Resilience

Challenges

- Slovakia experiences rising cyber threats, but many institutions still lack adequate cybersecurity frameworks.
- Municipalities and smaller institutions are highly vulnerable due to outdated systems and limited budgets.
- Critical infrastructure sectors (health, energy, transport) face inconsistent implementation of cybersecurity measures.
- Public awareness and cyber hygiene remain low.

Risks

- Increased probability of cyberattacks affecting state systems, critical services, or businesses.
- Costly incidents, data breaches, or disruptions of public services.
- Erosion of citizen trust in digital government.

Actions Needed

- Strengthen national cybersecurity incident response capabilities and mandatory standards.
- Introduce financial incentives and training for municipalities to upgrade security.
- Invest in cyber literacy campaigns and mandatory training for public employees.

Weak Innovation Ecosystem & Limited Support for Digital Entrepreneurship

Challenges

- Insufficient connection between universities, research institutions, and private companies.
- Fragmented innovation funding and weak support for scaling digital startups.
- Business environment burdened by bureaucracy, slow permitting, and legal complexity.
- Limited cross-border cooperation in digital research & development.

Risks

- Slovakia risks lagging behind Central European competitors in digital innovation (CZ, PL, EE).

- Lower attractiveness for high-tech investors and researchers.
- Digital startups relocate abroad, weakening the domestic ecosystem.

Actions Needed

- Create incentives for university–industry collaboration (joint AI labs, tech transfer, research partnerships).
- Streamline regulation for startups and digital-business operations.
- Increase funding for applied research and scale-up programs.
- Engage in EU-level digital innovation networks.

2.5. Challenges, Problems, Risks, and Required Actions in spatial planning, land-use planning, urban planning and regional planning in Cities & Regions of Slovakia

Slovakia’s spatial-planning and territorial-governance system is significantly constrained by fragmented institutions, inconsistent legal frameworks, and weak coordination across government levels. European research and Slovak policy documents repeatedly confirm that fragmentation between national ministries, regional self-governments and almost 3000 municipalities is one of the most serious barriers to coherent territorial development. As a result, key sectors—transport, housing, environment, water, and economic development—operate largely in silos, often ignoring spatial or cross-sectoral impacts.

Administrative boundaries rarely match functional urban areas such as Bratislava, Košice, Žilina, Nitra, Prešov, and Banská Bystrica. This misalignment produces uncoordinated suburbanization, inefficient logistics patterns, and costly infrastructure duplication. Regions hold limited statutory planning powers, while many municipalities lack the analytical capacity to manage complex development processes. Legal mandates frequently conflict, slowing approvals for housing, roads, railways, industrial parks, or green-infrastructure projects and reinforcing territorial disparities.

Planning legislation remains rigid and outdated, relying on slow zoning procedures that cannot keep pace with demographic decline, climate change, energy transition, or new mobility patterns. Sectoral laws regularly override spatial plans, and weak legal integration results in duplicated assessments, unclear responsibilities, and delays for strategic investments. Participation rights are uneven, often symbolic, and rarely mandated at metropolitan or regional scales, contributing to public mistrust and project opposition.

Frequent amendments, unclear judicial interpretations, and entrenched path dependencies create legal uncertainty for municipalities, planners, and investors. At the same time, Slovakia lacks effective metropolitan governance frameworks, limiting cooperation across functional regions and weakening the country’s competitiveness. This chapter examines these structural barriers and highlights the legal and institutional reforms needed to build a more coherent, coordinated, and future-ready territorial-governance system.

Governance & Legal Framework Fragmentation

Challenges

Evidence from European spatial-planning research and Slovak policy documents (e.g., *Slovak Urban Policy*) consistently shows that fragmented governance is one of the biggest obstacles.

- Fragmentation across national–regional–municipal levels leads to inconsistent objectives and inability to coordinate complex development (transport, housing, climate adaptation).
- Self-governing regions (VÚCs) have limited statutory planning powers and weak influence over state infrastructure and economic development.
- Municipalities (2,900+) are extremely fragmented, many too small to handle complex planning tasks, producing unequal planning capacities.
- Administrative boundaries do not match functional urban areas (Bratislava, Košice, Žilina, Nitra, Prešov, Banská Bystrica), resulting in:
 - uncoordinated suburbanization,
 - chaotic logistics and transport patterns,
 - infrastructure inefficiencies.
- State sectoral ministries (environment, transport, economy) operate in silos, frequently ignoring territorial impacts.

Risks

- Contradictory legal mandates prolong approvals of roads, railways, housing zones, industrial parks, and green infrastructure.
- Fragmentation leads to uneven territorial development—especially around Bratislava and in declining eastern regions.
- Environmental objectives (water retention, biodiversity, climate adaptation) are overridden by stronger economic and infrastructure sectors.

Actions Needed

- Strengthen legal mechanisms for horizontal and vertical coordination, especially linking municipalities around metropolitan regions.
- Legally align sectoral legislation (transport, water, housing, environment) under a unified territorial-governance framework.
- Create joint planning bodies and enable inter-municipal legally binding agreements for land-use and infrastructure decisions.

Rigid and Outdated Planning Legislation

Challenges

Although Slovakia is undergoing reform (new Construction Act and Spatial Planning Act), long-standing issues remain:

- Rigid, zoning-oriented system with slow updates of Územné Plány Obcí (UPO) and ÚPN VÚC.
- Zoning changes take years, creating legal uncertainty and hindering urban revitalization.
- Traditional legislation assumed static growth, but Slovakia now faces:
 - demographic decline,
 - climate impacts,
 - energy transformation,
 - rapid suburbanization,
 - new mobility and logistics patterns.
- Procedures are highly bureaucratic, making strategic adaptation extremely slow.

Risks

- Developers and municipalities bypass formal planning through exceptions, producing uncoordinated development.
- Rigid planning reduces the system's ability to respond to affordable-housing needs and climate adaptation.
- Outdated regulations discourage innovation (brownfield regeneration, temporary uses, mixed-use zoning).

Actions Needed

- Fully modernize planning laws with adaptive, scenario-based, and iterative planning tools.
- Allow pilot areas, innovation districts, and experimental zones with special rules.
- Maintain accountability and transparent decision-making to prevent discretionary abuses.

Legal Barriers to Integrated, Cross-Sectoral Planning

Challenges

- Slovakia experiences strong silos between sectoral laws and insufficient integration.
- Sectoral legislation (transport, rail, nature protection, water, heritage) often overrides territorial plans.
- Lengthy Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) procedures operate independently from urban plans, leading to duplicated processes.
- No legal requirement for sectoral ministries to consider spatial impacts in strategic decisions.
- Weak integration with new sectors:
 - digital infrastructure & data,
 - public health & ageing,
 - energy transition & climate adaptation.

Risks

- Misaligned investments (roads vs. public transport, industry vs. environment, housing vs. utilities) produce contradictory land-use outcomes.
- Overlapping assessments increase administrative burden and delay projects.
- Local authorities face legal uncertainty when sectoral and spatial frameworks conflict.

Actions Needed

- Legally require all sectoral policies to evaluate territorial impacts.
- Strengthen legal weight of spatial plans in permitting decisions.
- Harmonize EIAs, infrastructure laws, and permitting procedures with spatial planning.

Weak Legal Basis for Citizen Participation

Challenges

- Participation practices in Slovakia remain procedural rather than meaningful.
- Participation provisions vary strongly across municipalities, lacking minimum standards.
- Public hearings often occur too late to influence planning content.
- Digital engagement tools are rarely mandated.

- Participation at regional or metropolitan level is almost absent due to unclear competencies and no legal framework for cross-municipal consultations.

Risks

- Growing mistrust and public opposition to infrastructure, housing, and energy projects.
- Legal challenges by citizens or civic groups may delay or block projects.
- “Consultation fatigue” results when participation is symbolic rather than substantive.

Actions Needed

- Introduce early-stage and continuous participation requirements in law.
- Mandate digital participation tools and transparent reporting on public feedback.
- Harmonize participation rights across regions, municipalities, and sectoral procedures.

Legal Uncertainty & Path Dependency

Challenges

- Frequent small amendments to the Building Act and related regulations generate unpredictability.
- Long-term path dependency reinforces outdated zoning concepts and rigid technocratic planning.
- Inconsistent judicial decisions (especially in permitting disputes) increase uncertainty.
- Municipalities with low capacity struggle to interpret complex legal changes.

Risks

- Lower investor confidence, encouraging speculative rather than strategic development.
- Litigation and delays in major projects, including industrial parks or transport corridors.
- Poor enforcement of spatial plans when legal requirements contradict or change frequently.

Actions Needed

- Undertake comprehensive legal reforms, avoiding piecemeal amendments.
- Establish a clear hierarchy of plans and well-defined competences of each level.
- Ensure professional training and capacity building for municipal and regional planners.

Legal Barriers to Multilevel Governance

Challenges

- Slovakia lacks functioning metropolitan governance structures, despite strong functional ties.
- No legal framework for metropolitan or micro-regional planning bodies.
- Regions (VÚCs) have limited planning authority, while key competences remain at the state level.
- Strong recentralization trends (water management, housing finance, national transport plans) limit the ability of cities to coordinate across territories.
- Suburban municipalities often act independently, competing instead of cooperating.

Risks

- Underperforming metropolitan regions (especially Bratislava), losing competitiveness.
- Increasing regional inequalities between western and eastern Slovakia.
- Inefficient infrastructure spending due to fragmented decision-making.

Actions Needed

- Introduce metropolitan legal frameworks for Bratislava, Košice, and other functional regions.
- Encourage binding inter-municipal cooperation.
- Clarify division of powers between state, region, and municipal levels for strategic planning

2.6. Challenges, Problems, Risks, and Required Actions in the Legal Environment for Planning in Cities & Regions of Slovakia

Slovakia’s ability to steer spatial development is fundamentally constrained by a governance system that is both highly fragmented and legally inconsistent. The country’s territorial architecture is marked by an unusual combination of extensive municipal fragmentation, limited regional authority, and dominant sectoral ministries whose decisions often bypass spatial considerations. With almost 2,900 municipalities—many lacking technical staff or planning expertise—Slovakia faces one of the weakest local planning capacities in Europe, creating major differences in the quality and coherence of development decisions.

This fragmentation is intensified by a legal environment in which responsibilities are scattered across state, regional, and municipal levels without clear coordination mechanisms. Functional urban areas such as Bratislava, Košice, Žilina, and Prešov extend far beyond their administrative borders, yet Slovak law provides virtually no tools for metropolitan planning. As a result, suburbanization unfolds chaotically, transport systems remain uncoordinated, and infrastructure investments are often planned in isolation rather than as part of an integrated territorial strategy.

Sectoral ministries—including transport, environment, culture, and regional development—operate under separate legislative frameworks that frequently conflict. These inconsistencies slow permitting procedures, create regulatory confusion, and weaken the ability of spatial planning to guide land use, environmental protection, and infrastructure development. Planning legislation itself remains rigid and procedurally heavy, unable to respond to climate risks, shrinking populations, or changing mobility patterns. Many municipalities and regions rely on outdated zoning plans and lack the flexibility required for revitalization, brownfield redevelopment, or mixed-use innovation districts.

Public participation provisions, although formally present, are applied unevenly and often come too late to influence outcomes. Together with frequent legal amendments and unclear judicial interpretations, this contributes to declining trust in planning institutions and increases the likelihood of appeals and litigation. Slovakia also lacks a legal basis for multilevel governance, leaving metropolitan areas without the ability to coordinate transport, housing, utilities, and economic development across municipal borders.

This chapter explores how these structural and legal weaknesses shape territorial outcomes in Slovakia and highlights the reforms necessary to create a more coherent, coordinated, and adaptable governance framework capable of guiding sustainable development.

Governance & Legal Framework Fragmentation **Challenges**

European research and Slovak policy documents consistently identify fragmentation and unclear division of competences as a core structural weakness.

- Slovakia has highly fragmented municipal structure (2,890 municipalities), many of which lack the capacity to manage complex planning tasks.
- Legal responsibilities are split among the state, self-governing regions (VÚC), and municipalities, with weak vertical coordination in spatial planning.
- Administrative boundaries rarely correspond to functional urban areas (Bratislava, Košice, Žilina, Prešov), complicating metropolitan-scale planning.
- Overlapping competences between ministries—especially transport, environment, regional development, culture/heritage—create legal inconsistencies.
- Tensions persist between decentralization (municipal autonomy) and recentralization trends (e.g., environmental permitting, infrastructure planning), generating unclear mandates.

Risks

- Conflicting legal responsibilities can delay or block infrastructure, housing, and environmental projects.
- Weak coordination contributes to territorial fragmentation and uneven regional development.
- Environmental priorities may be weakened by sectoral dominance, especially in transport or economic development.

Actions Needed

- Strengthen legal tools for horizontal and vertical coordination, especially for functional urban areas.
- Align planning-related legislation (transport, environment, housing, water management) under a coherent territorial governance framework.
- Legally support joint planning bodies, metropolitan authorities, and inter-municipal agreements.

Rigid and Outdated Planning Legislation

Challenges

- The system is based on rigid zoning and outdated categories, limiting flexibility in rapidly changing urban contexts.
- Complex and lengthy procedures hinder timely responses to economic, demographic, and climate-related pressures.
- Traditional uniform planning tools do not account for uncertainty, innovation, disruptive technologies, or climate adaptation.

Risks

- Investors and municipalities circumvent formal planning procedures → ad-hoc development, poor-quality urban form, and legal disputes.
- Reduced trust in planning as a tool for managing development.
- Inconsistent land-use outcomes and spatial conflicts.

Actions Needed

- Modernize Slovakia's planning legislation with flexible, adaptive tools and scenario-based approaches.

- Introduce experimental zones, pilot territories, and responsive planning instruments for innovation.
- Ensure transparency and public accountability to avoid misuse of discretion or corruption risks.

Legal Barriers to Integrated, Cross-Sectoral Planning

Challenges

Slovakia's spatial planning framework is only weakly integrated with sectoral laws.

- Sectoral legislation (transport, nature protection, water, heritage) often overrides municipal or regional plans.
- Differences in legal timeframes and procedures make harmonization difficult.
- Spatial planning is poorly linked to emerging policy areas such as digital infrastructure, climate adaptation, public health, or housing affordability.
- Environmental impact assessment (EIA) and planning procedures run in parallel instead of being coordinated, increasing administrative burden.

Risks

- Contradictory development decisions and inconsistent land use.
- Long and complex permitting processes, increasing uncertainty for municipalities and investors.
- Increased possibility of legal conflicts and appeals.

Actions Needed

- Introduce binding cross-sector coordination obligations.
- Increase the legal weight and enforceability of spatial plans at municipal and regional levels.
- Harmonize spatial planning with EIA, infrastructure planning, water management, and environmental protection procedures.

Weak Legal Basis for Citizen Participation

Challenges

Although Slovak law provides basic participation rights, they are often formalistic and insufficient.

- Participation often occurs too late (e.g., during formal comments rather than early-stage co-creation).
- Uneven application across municipalities and regions due to capacity differences.
- Lack of clear legal provisions for participation at metropolitan or inter-municipal scales.
- Limited digital engagement tools and absence of structured feedback obligations.

Risks

- The “illusion of inclusion”: citizens can comment but rarely influence outcomes → low trust.
- Increased legal challenges, objections, and appeals.
- Social opposition delaying strategic or infrastructure projects.

Actions Needed

- Strengthen and standardize legal requirements for early and continuous participation.
- Mandate transparent feedback loops showing how public input was used.

- Encourage use of digital participation platforms and minimum national standards.

Legal Uncertainty and Path Dependency

Challenges

Slovakia exhibits strong legal path dependency rooted in historical structures.

- Spatial planning and construction law reforms have been attempted for decades but remain fragmented and unfinished.
- Frequent amendments of the existing building code create instability and interpretation challenges.
- Contradictory judicial decisions and unclear hierarchy of plans undermine legal certainty.
- Many municipalities lack capacity and rely on legacy practices, not modern planning approaches.

Risks

- Lower investor confidence and increased litigation.
- Weak enforcement of spatial plans.
- Policy instability that discourages long-term strategic planning.

Actions Needed

- Implement comprehensive reform, not isolated amendments, of planning and construction legislation.
- Clarify the hierarchy of plans, competences, and the legal force of strategies.
- Invest in capacity-building and professional training for planning authorities.

Legal Barriers to Multilevel Governance

Challenges

Slovakia lacks clear legal foundations for metropolitan governance and inter-municipal planning.

- Key metropolitan areas (Bratislava, Košice) lack legal entities enabling coordinated planning across municipal borders.
- National legislation centralizes many decisions (transport, environment), limiting planning influence of regions (VÚC) and municipalities.
- Fragmentation between state, regional, and local levels complicates strategic planning and investment coordination.

Risks

- Underperforming metropolitan areas due to missing joint frameworks.
- Territorial inequalities between regions worsen.
- Infrastructure and services (transport, housing, utilities) develop incoherently.

Actions Needed

- Create legal frameworks for metropolitan governance and functional urban area planning.
- Support binding inter-municipal cooperation mechanisms.
- Clearly define roles and responsibilities of state, regions, and municipalities in planning processes.

Conclusions

The strategic assessment demonstrates that cities and regions across Slovakia are exposed to a complex, interlinked set of economic, social, environmental, digital, spatial-planning, and governance challenges. The analysis confirms that these pressures do not occur in isolation; rather, they reinforce one another and demand integrated, multi-level responses. Fragmented governance emerges as one of the most significant systemic barriers, limiting the country's ability to deliver coherent development policies, coordinate investments, and respond to rapid societal and technological change.

The assessment highlights that weak vertical and horizontal coordination hinders functional-region planning, contributes to regional disparities, and restricts the capacity of municipalities and regions to participate meaningfully in long-term strategic development. Economic vulnerabilities, including dependence on low value-added industries, skills mismatches, and demographic decline, further compound territorial inequalities. Social challenges—especially persistent poverty, segregation, and limited access to quality services—reinforce cycles of exclusion that require coordinated, place-based interventions.

Environmental risks such as climate change impacts, water scarcity, and soil degradation reveal the urgent need for adaptive and resilient planning frameworks. At the same time, digital transformation offers opportunities for innovation and improved governance, yet its potential remains constrained by institutional fragmentation, low digital skills, and uneven infrastructure.

Spatial and land-use planning systems are characterized by outdated legislation, slow procedures, and weak integration with sectoral policies, resulting in inconsistent development outcomes, delays in key projects, and reduced ability to implement strategic territorial visions. Legal inconsistencies undermine enforcement, create uncertainty for investors, and perpetuate outdated planning practices.

Across all thematic areas, the assessment underscores that incremental or isolated reforms will be insufficient. The challenges identified require systemic, coordinated, and forward-looking approaches that combine legislative reform, strengthened metropolitan and regional governance, improved planning capacities, enhanced data-driven decision-making, and long-term investment in human capital and innovation.

The findings clearly indicate that Slovakia's future development depends on its ability to build more resilient, inclusive, and well-coordinated territorial governance structures. Strengthening cooperation across municipalities, aligning sectoral and spatial policies, and empowering regions with adequate competences and resources are essential to address the transformation demands identified in this assessment. Ultimately, the transition toward sustainable, smart, and innovative socio-ecosystems will require coherent strategies, stable institutions, and a shared commitment to long-term territorial development across all levels of government.

References (additional to the “proofs”)

- Act no. 369/1990 Coll. on municipalities amended
- Act no. 377/1990 Coll. on capital city of Slovak Republic Bratislava amended.
- Act no. 401/1990 Coll. on city Košice amended.
- Act no. 90/2001 Coll. on the Constitution of the Slovak Republic amended
- Act No. 302/2001 Coll. of the National Council of the Slovak Republic on the self-government of higher territorial units, as amended
- Aufrichtová, Z., & Hanus, J. (2014). *Kvalita sídelného prostredia: Vymedzenie problému hodnotenia kvality urbánneho prostredia pomocou Systému na podporu priestorového rozhodovania*. ALFA 3.
- Austrian Environmental Protection Agency. (2024). *Monitoring der Flächeninanspruchnahme und Versiegelung: Tätigkeitsbericht 2022 + 2023*.
https://www.oerok.gv.at/fileadmin/user_upload/Bilder/2.Reiter-Raum_u_Region/6_OEREK_Umsetzungspakte/Bodenstrategie/Baseline_2022/5_UBA_Taetigkeitsbericht_Monitoring_2022-2023.pdf
- Bizoň, M. (2025, October 30). *Proces tvorby územného plánu*. LinkedIn.
<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7386296737176469504/>
- Bizoň, M. (2025, October 31). *Ktoré mesto má najviac pozemkov?* LinkedIn.
<https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7373712155881340928/>
- Brothaler, J., Dillinger, T., Getzner, M., Kanonier, A., Grinzinger, E., & Chamraci, M. (2023). *Klimaorientierte und ressourcenschonende Raumentwicklung und Finanzausgleich*. TU Wien.
- Carayannis, E. G., Barth, T. D., & Campbell, D. F. (2012). The quintuple helix innovation model: Global warming as a challenge and driver for innovation. *Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship*, 1(2). <https://doi.org/10.1186/2192-5372-1-2>
- Cestná databanka. (2025, October 30). *Novinky*. Slovenská správa ciest.
<https://www.cdb.sk/sk/Novinky.alej>
- Club of Rome Carnuntum. (2019). *Was ich über den Zukunftsrat wissen wollte...*
<https://www.clubofrome-carnuntum.at/zukunftsrat-start-2/>
- Council of Europe. (2023). *Local and regional democracy in the Slovak Republic*. Council of Europe Publishing.
<https://www.coe.int>
- Dotácie na územné plánovanie. (2025, October 30). Úrad pre územné plánovanie a výstavbu SR. <https://uupv.sk/uzemne-planovanie/dotacie-na-uzemne-planovanie>
- Energieinstitut Linz. (2024). *Smart Region Upper Austria Report*. <https://www.energieinstitut-linz.at>
- ESPN. (2023). *Climate territorial foresight report*. <https://www.espon.eu/climate>
- ESPN. (2023). *Territorial governance and spatial planning systems in Europe*.
<https://www.espon.eu/territorial-governance>
- ESPN. (2023). *Territorial governance and innovation ecosystems in Central Europe*.
<https://www.espon.eu/territorial-governance>
- European Commission. (2023). *Harnessing talent in Europe's regions*. <https://ec.europa.eu>
- European Commission. (2024). *9th Cohesion Report*.
<https://cohesiondata.ec.europa.eu/stories/s/Cohesion-Report-2024/y7vb-9h8f>
- European Commission. (2024). *Biodiversity Strategy 2030 and Green Infrastructure Review*.
https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/biodiversity-strategy-2030_en
- European Commission. (2024). *Digital Economy and Society Index (DESI) 2024*. <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/digital-economy-and-society-index-desi-2024>
- European Commission. (2024). *European Innovation Scoreboard 2024*.

<https://ec.europa.eu/research-and-innovation/en/statistics/performance-indicators/european-innovation-scoreboard> European Commission. (2024). *European Transport Outlook 2050*.
<https://transport.ec.europa.eu> European Commission. (2025). *A modernised cohesion policy: Mid-term review*. https://ec.europa.eu/regional_policy European Committee of the Regions. (2023). *Empowering local authorities for innovation*. <https://cor.europa.eu/en> European Court of Auditors. (2023). *Special Report No. 14/2023: Smart Specialisation Strategies*.
<https://www.eca.europa.eu/en/publications> European Court of Auditors. (2024). *Recovery and Resilience Facility implementation review*. <https://www.eca.europa.eu> European Environment Agency. (2024). *Resource productivity and domestic material consumption*.
<https://www.eea.europa.eu/en/analysis/indicators/resource-productivity-and-domestic-material-consumption/resource-productivity-and-domestic-material-consumption-5> European Investment Bank. (2024). *European Investment Report – Climate investment*.
<https://www.eib.org/en/publications/2024-european-investment-report-climate-investment> Eurobarometer. (2024). *Perceived inequalities in Europe*.
<https://europa.eu/eurobarometer/surveys/detail/2986> Eurofound. (2023). *European quality of life survey 2023*. <https://www.eurofound.europa.eu/en/publications> Eurostat. (2024). *Population projections (proj_19np)*.
https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/proj_19np/default/table Eurostat. (2024). *Quality of life indicators*. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Quality_of_life_indicators Eurostat. (2024). *Structural business statistics*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat> Eurostat. (2024). *Urban audit and regional accounts*.
<https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat> Fischer, C. (2022). *Ergebnisse aus Römerland Carnuntum 2040*. <https://rlc2040.at/ergebnisse-aus-roemerland-carnuntum-2040/>
 Geoportál Slovenskej republiky. (2025, October 30). Ministerstvo životného prostredia SR. <https://geoportal.gov.sk/> Grinzinger, E., Steinbrunner, B., Schartmüller, L., Weiss-Eizinger, S., Zech, S., Hochradl, H., Birli, B., Huber, S., Schellner, K., Weiss, M., Wallenberger, J., & Sillipp, N. (2025). *How2SoilWalk: Handbuch zur Durchführung bewusstseinsbildender Spaziergänge zum Bodenschutz*. TU Wien. <https://doi.org/10.34726/9781>
 Hanus, J., Macák, L., & Polonský, F. (2025, October 30). *Výsledky hodnotenia kvality sídelného prostredia všetkých obcí na Slovensku za rok 2022 v novej aplikácii*. LinkedIn. <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7371089026545651712/>
 Inštitút priestorového plánovania. (2025, October 30). *Kvalita sídelného prostredia*. <https://ipp-oz.sk/kvalita-sidelneho-prostredia/> IOM Slovakia. (2024). *Labour mobility and migration trends in the Slovak Republic*. <https://iom.sk>
 Komora architektov SR. (2025, October 30). *Zoznam architektov*. <https://komarch.sk/zoznamy-architektov>
 Krnáč, J., Liptáková, K., Vitálišová, K., Borseková, K. (2018) Transformation of territorial self-government in the Slovakia. In Economic problems of Visegrad Group countries and Ukraine, 7-38, Ternopil, Osadtsa U. V.
 Metodika tvorby a implementácie PHRS. (2025, October 30). MIRRI SR. <https://mirri.gov.sk/sekcie/regionalny-rozvoj-2/metodika-tvorby-implementacie-phrs/> Mesto Košice. (2025, October 30). *Plán pre Košice*. <https://planprekosice.sk/> MuMAP. (2025, October 30). Najvyšší kontrolný úrad SR. <https://mumap.nku.gov.sk/>

Národná banka Slovenska. (2024). *Economic and monetary developments report*.
<https://www.nbs.sk>Národný geoportál. (2025, October 30). Ministerstvo životného prostredia SR. <https://geoportal.gov.sk/>

OECD. (2023). *Innovation policy review of Slovakia*. <https://www.oecd.org/sti/>

OECD. (2023). *Regional outlook 2023*. <https://www.oecd.org/regional/regional-outlook/>

OECD. (2024). *Better life index*. <https://www.oecd.org/better-life-index/>OECD. (2024). *Economic survey of the Slovak Republic 2024*. <https://www.oecd.org/economy/slovak-republic-economic-snapshot/>OECD. (2024). *Public governance review of Slovakia*.
<https://www.oecd.org/gov/public-governance-review-slovakia-2024.htm>OECD. (2024). *Regional governance monitor 2024*. <https://www.oecd.org/regional/>OECD. (2024). *Skills outlook 2024*. <https://www.oecd.org/skills/>

OECD. (2024). *Strategic foresight report 2024*. <https://www.oecd.org/strategic-foresight/>

OECD. (2024). *Regional outlook 2024*. <https://www.oecd.org/regional/regional-outlook/>OECD. (2025). *Preparing for demographic change in the Banská Bystrica Region*.
<https://doi.org/10.1787/62ab1acb-en>Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development. (2024). *Regional outlook 2024: Strengthening resilience and cohesion*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264898762-en>

Otvorené údaje Štatistického úradu SR. (2025, October 30). <https://data.statistics.sk/api/>

ÖROK. (2023). *Flächeninanspruchnahme und Versiegelung in Österreich: Kontextinformationen und Beschreibung der Daten für 2022*.
[https://www.oerok.gv.at/fileadmin/user_upload/Bilder/2.Reiter-Raum u. Region/6. OEREK Umsetzungspakte/Bodenstrategie/Baseline_2022/0 OEROK Bericht Flaecheninanspruchnahme und Versiegelung_2022.pdf](https://www.oerok.gv.at/fileadmin/user_upload/Bilder/2.Reiter-Raum_u_Region/6_OEREK_Umsetzungspakte/Bodenstrategie/Baseline_2022/0_OEROK_Bericht_Flaecheninanspruchnahme_und_Versiegelung_2022.pdf)

Regionálna vodárenská spoločnosť Vlára–Váh, s. r. o. (2025, October 30). *O nás*.
https://rvsvv.sk/?page_id=19

SIEA. (2023). *Smart specialisation strategy of the Slovak Republic 2021–2027*.
<https://s3platform.jrc.ec.europa.eu/slovakia>Slovenská komora architektov. (2025, October 30). <https://komarch.sk/zoznamy-architektov>Slovenský úrad geodézie, kartografie a katastra SR. (2025, October 30). [https://www.skgeodesy.sk/sk/Soil Walks Dashboard](https://www.skgeodesy.sk/sk/Soil_Walks_Dashboard). (2025). *Dashboard zur Flächeninanspruchnahme und Versiegelung*.
https://secure.umweltbundesamt.at/powerbi-embed/start?reportName=soilwalks_oeffentlich&settings.navContentPaneEnabled=false

Statistical Office of the Slovak Republic. (2024). *Regional indicators database*.
<https://slovak.statistics.sk>

Úrad pre územné plánovanie a výstavbu SR. (2025, October 30). *Odborná spôsobilosť na obstarávanie ÚPP a ÚPD*. <https://uupv.sk/uzemne-planovanie/odborna-sposobilost>

Úrad pre územné plánovanie a výstavbu SR. Vyhláška č. 392/2023 Z. z. o obsahu a spôsobe spracovania územnoplánovacej dokumentácie.

Úrad pre územné plánovanie a výstavbu SR. Vyhláška č. 69/2024 Z. z. o územnotechnických požiadavkách na výstavbu.

Úrad pre územné plánovanie a výstavbu SR. Vyhláška č. 153/2024 Z. z. o štandardoch a metodike spracovania ÚPD.

Zákon č. 24/2006 Z. z. o posudzovaní vplyvov na životné prostredie v znení neskorších právnych predpisov.

Zákon č. 200/2022 Z. z. o územnom plánovaní v znení neskorších právnych predpisov.

Zákon č. 271/2025 Z. z. o podpore prioritných okresov v znení neskorších právnych predpisov.

Zákon č. 539/2008 Z. z. o podpore regionálneho rozvoja v znení neskorších právnych predpisov.

UN-Habitat. (2023). *World cities report 2023: Envisioning the future of cities.*

<https://unhabitat.org>

Vak Stupava. (2025, October 30). [https://www.vak-stupava.sk/Vizia 2050](https://www.vak-stupava.sk/Vizia_2050). (2024). *Podklad T2-1: Sociálny rozvoj miest a regiónov.* Ústav manažmentu STU.

World Bank. (2020). *Community-based social service centres as a tool of multilevel partnership.* <https://www.worldbank.org>